

Permutable Power Minimum Length Representations of Natural Numbers from 0 to 20000

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Abstract

*This paper works with representations of natural numbers from 0 to 20000 written in terms of expressions with addition, subtraction and exponents. Digits from 0 to 9 and 1 to 9 are used in such a way that for each number represents with same digits in bases and exponents with different permutations. Some numbers can be written in more than one way, but we have chosen with less possible expression, calling as **minimum length**. This work extends the author's previous work [6] from 1 to 9 to 0 to 9.*

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1 Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers

In this section, we shall write different ways of writing natural numbers. These representations are divided in four different types.

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1.1 First Type: Increasing and Decreasing

In 2014, author [1] wrote natural numbers in increasing and decreasing orders of 1 to 9 and 9 to 1. See examples below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{100} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 \times 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{101} &:= 1 + 2 + 34 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 \times 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{102} &:= 12 + 3 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 6 + 5 + 4^3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{103} &:= 1 \times 2 \times 34 + 5 + 6 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 \times 6 + 5 \times 4 + 3 + 21 \\
 \mathbf{104} &:= 1 + 23 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 65 + 4 \times 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{105} &:= 1 + 2 \times 3 \times 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{106} &:= 12 + 3 + 4 \times 5 + 6 + 7 \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times 7 + 6 \times 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{107} &:= 1 \times 23 + 4 + 56 + 7 + 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{108} &:= 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 + 5 + 6 + 78 + 9 = 9 + 8 + 76 + 5 + 4 + 3 + 2 + 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

See more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{999} &:= 12 \times 3 \times (4 + 5) + (67 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 8 + 7 + 654 + 321. \\
 \mathbf{2535} &:= 1 + 2345 + (6 + 7 + 8) \times 9 = 9 + 87 \times (6 + 5 \times 4 + 3) + 2 + 1. \\
 \mathbf{2607} &:= 123 \times 4 \times 5 + 6 + (7 + 8) \times 9 = 987 + 6 \times 54 \times (3 + 2) \times 1. \\
 \mathbf{10958} &:= 12 \times 3 + \sqrt{4} + 5! \times (67 + 8 \times \sqrt{9}) = (9 + 8 \times 7 \times 65 + 4) \times 3 - 2 + 1. \\
 \mathbf{11807} &:= 1 \times 234 \times (5 + 6 \times 7) + 89 = -9 + 8 + 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 \times 3)^2 \times 1.
 \end{aligned}$$

We observe that the number 10958 is the only number among 0 to 11111, where we need extra operations, such as **square-root**, **factorial**, etc. to write in increasing case. For more details refer author's web-site link [5]. Extension of numbers from 11112 to 30000 refer [2, 3, 4].

1.2 Second Type: Flexible Power Representations

Let us consider two numbers, 1 and 2. Using the idea of power and the operations of *addition* and *subtraction*, we can write following 3 numbers in terms of 1 and 2, as $1 = -1^2 + 2^1$, $3 = 1^2 + 2^1$ and $5 = 1^1 + 2^2$. In this situation, we observe that *bases* and *exponents* are of same digits. Permutations of exponent values helps in bringing different numbers. In case of repeated values, for example, $3 = 1^2 + 2^1 = -1^1 + 2^2$, only possibilities is considered. There is only one number having single digit, i.e., $1 = 1^1$. For simplicity, let us represent the above procedure as $(1, 2)^{(1, 2)}$, resulting in three possible values. The above procedure is with two digits. Instead having two digits, we can work with two letters, such as,

$$(a, b)^{(a, b)}, \dots, (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)^{(a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)},$$

where $a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, all distinct.

1.2.1 Unequal String Lengths

$$100 := 2^6 + 6^2$$

$$101 := 1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$$

$$102 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$103 := 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$104 := -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$$

$$105 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$$

$$106 := 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$$

$$107 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$$

$$108 := 1^7 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$$

$$109 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$$

$$110 := 1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$$

$$111 := -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$$

$$112 := 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$$

$$113 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$114 := -2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$$

$$115 := 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$$

$$116 := 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$$

$$117 := -1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$$

$$118 := 3^5 - 5^3$$

$$119 := 1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3.$$

See more examples,

$$638 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4$$

$$666 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4$$

$$786 := -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$$

$$1933 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 7^1$$

$$1934 := 2^9 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 9^3$$

$$3098 := -3^3 + 5^5$$

$$2280 := -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4$$

$$6922 := -3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5$$

$$9711 := 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^1$$

$$9777 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$$

$$11110 := 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3$$

$$11111 := -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4.$$

The whole work is from 1 to 11111. For details refer [6]. This work extend this work to 20000.

1.2.2 Equal String Lengths

Based on second type still we can write natural numbers in a sequential way with uniform representations. Instead working with unequal strings as of previous section, here we worked with equal string using the digits 0 to 9, i.e., using all the 10 digits, {0,1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9}. The results obtained are symmetric, i.e., writing in 0 to 9 or 9 to 0, the resulting number is same. See some examples below,

$$201 := 0^3 + 1^9 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 9^0$$

$$202 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^4$$

$$203 := 0^3 - 1^9 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 9^1$$

$$204 := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^0 + 9^3$$

$$205 := 0^3 + 1^9 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 8^2 + 9^1$$

$$206 := 0^7 - 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 9^2$$

$$207 := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^1 + 9^3$$

$$208 := 0^7 + 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 9^2$$

$$209 := 0^7 - 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^2$$

$$210 := 0^5 - 1^7 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$211 := 0^7 + 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^2$$

$$212 := 0^5 + 1^7 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$213 := 0^5 + 1^8 - 2^7 - 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$214 := 0^5 + 1^7 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$$

$$215 := 0^5 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 + 9^1$$

$$216 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 9^2$$

$$217 := 0^7 - 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^0$$

$$218 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 + 9^2$$

$$219 := 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 + 9^0$$

$$220 := 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 + 9^1.$$

Below are more examples,

$$\mathbf{11080} := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^1 + 8^3 + 9^4$$

$$\mathbf{11081} := 0^8 - 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^3$$

$$\mathbf{11082} := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 8^0 + 9^2$$

$$\mathbf{11083} := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^2 + 9^3$$

$$\mathbf{11084} := 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 9^4$$

$$\mathbf{11085} := 0^8 + 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 8^2 + 9^3$$

$$\mathbf{11086} := 0^7 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^2 + 9^4$$

$$\mathbf{11087} := 0^6 + 1^9 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^1 + 9^3.$$

The whole work is from 1 to 11111. For details refer [7].

Analysing the procedures given in sections 1.1 and 1.2, we observe that in section 1.1, all the 9 digits are used in increasing and decreasing ways to bring natural numbers, where each digit appears only once. In this case, the operations used are, **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, potentiation, factorial** and **square-root**. The section 1.2 works with representations of natural numbers written in a way that we use each digit twice, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits with different permutations. Subsection 1.2.1 choose the digits from 1 to 9, according to necessity, while subsection 1.2.2 works with all the 10 digits, i.e., 0 to 9, along with the operations of **addition** and **subtraction**.

1.3 Third Way: Single Digit Representations

In [1], author wrote natural numbers 1 to 1000 using single digit in each case. For example,

$$\mathbf{717} := (1 + 1)^{11} - 11^{(1+1+1)}$$

$$:= 22^2 + 222 + 22/2$$

$$:= 3^{(3+3)} - 3 - 3 \times 3$$

$$:= 4 \times (4 \times 44 + 4) - 4 + 4/4$$

$$:= (55 \times (55 + 5 + 5) + 5 + 5)/5$$

$$:= (6 \times 6 / (6 + 6))^6 - 6 - 6$$

$$:= 777 - 7 \times 7 - 77/7$$

$$:= 8 \times 88 + (88 + 8 + 8)/8$$

$$:= 9 \times 9 \times 9 - (99 + 9)/9.$$

$$\mathbf{786} := ((1 + 1 + 1)^{(1+1+1)} + 1)^{(1+1)} + 1 + 1$$

$$:= (22 + 2 + 2 + 2)^2 + 2$$

$$:= 33 \times (3^3 - 3) - 3 - 3$$

$$:= 4 \times (4 \times (44 + 4) + 4) + (4 + 4)/4$$

$$:= 5 + (5^5 - 5/5)/(5 - 5/5)$$

$$:= 66 \times (6 + 6) - 6$$

$$:= 777 + 7 + (7 + 7)/7$$

$$:= 8 \times (88 + 8) + 8 + (88 - 8)/8$$

$$:= 9 \times 99 - 99 - 9 + (9 + 9 + 9)/9$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{995} &:= (11-1)^{(1+1+1)} - (11-1)/(1+1) \\
&:= 22 + 2 \times (22^2 + 2) + 2/2 \\
&:= 3 \times 333 - 3 - 3/3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4 - 4) + 4 - 4/4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5+5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) - 5 \\
&:= 666 + 6 \times 66 - 66 - 6/6 \\
&:= (7+7) \times (77-7) + 7 + 7 + 7/7 \\
&:= 888 + 88 + 8 + 88/8 \\
&:= 999 - (9+9+9+9)/9.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{1000} &:= (11-1)^{(1+1+1)} \\
&:= 2 \times (22^2 + 2^{(2+2)}) \\
&:= (3 \times 3 + 3/3)^3 \\
&:= 4 \times (4^4 - 4) - 4 - 4 \\
&:= 5 \times (5+5) \times (5 \times 5 - 5) \\
&:= ((66-6)/6)^{(6 \times 6 / (6+6))} \\
&:= (7+7+7-7/7) \times (7 \times 7 + 7/7) \\
&:= 888 + 88 + 8 + 8 + 8 \\
&:= 999 + 9/9.
\end{aligned}$$

Values are calculated up to 1.000.000 (.txt file), but the work is written only from 0 to 1000. For details, refer Taneja [9]. For recent extension to 20000 in four parts refer Taneja [10, 11, 12]. This is a forth part from 15001-20000.

1.4 Forth Way: Single Letter Representations

We observe that the numbers written in previous section 1.3 are in terms of each digit, not necessarily symmetric. But there are numbers, that can be written in a symmetric way, see examples below:

$$\mathbf{5} = \frac{11-1}{1+1} = \frac{22-2}{2+2} = \frac{33-3}{3+3} = \frac{44-4}{4+4} = \frac{55-5}{5+5} = \frac{66-6}{6+6} = \frac{77-7}{7+7} = \frac{88-8}{8+8} = \frac{99-9}{9+9}.$$

$$\mathbf{6} = \frac{11+1}{1+1} = \frac{22+2}{2+2} = \frac{33+3}{3+3} = \frac{44+4}{4+4} = \frac{55+5}{5+5} = \frac{66+6}{6+6} = \frac{77+7}{7+7} = \frac{88+8}{8+8} = \frac{99+9}{9+9}.$$

$$\mathbf{55} = \frac{111-1}{1+1} = \frac{222-2}{2+2} = \frac{333-3}{3+3} = \frac{444-4}{4+4} = \frac{555-5}{5+5} = \frac{666-6}{6+6} = \frac{777-7}{7+7} = \frac{888-8}{8+8} = \frac{999-9}{9+9}.$$

$$\mathbf{56} = \frac{111+1}{1+1} = \frac{222+2}{2+2} = \frac{333+3}{3+3} = \frac{444+4}{4+4} = \frac{555+5}{5+5} = \frac{666+6}{6+6} = \frac{777+7}{7+7} = \frac{888+8}{8+8} = \frac{999+9}{9+9}.$$

Motivated by this idea, instead working for each digit separately, we can work with a **single letter "a"**, for example,

• Running-Type

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{5} &:= (aa - a)/(a + a) & \mathbf{925} &:= (aaaaa - aa)/(aa + a) \\
\mathbf{6} &:= (aa + a)/(a + a) & \mathbf{1089} &:= (aaaa - aa - aa)/a \\
\mathbf{55} &:= (aaa - a)/(a + a) & \mathbf{1991} &:= (aaaaaa/aaa \times (a + a) - aa)/a \\
\mathbf{56} &:= (aaa + a)/(a + a) & \mathbf{2020} &:= (aaaaa - a)/aa \times (a + a)/a \\
\mathbf{561} &:= (aaaa + aa)/(a + a) & \mathbf{2035} &:= (aaaa - a)/(a + a + a) \times aa/(a + a) \\
\mathbf{666} &:= aaa \times (aa + a)/((a + a) \times a) & \mathbf{4477} &:= (aaa/(a + a + a) \times aa \times aa)/(a \times a)
\end{aligned}$$

$$4999 := (aaaaa - aaaa - a - a)/(a + a)$$

$$5000 := (aaaaa - aaaa)/(a + a).$$

• Fraction-Type

$$\begin{aligned} 5 &:= \frac{aa - a}{a + a} & 1991 &:= \frac{\frac{aaaaaa}{aaa} \times (a + a) - aa}{aaa} \\ 6 &:= \frac{aa + a}{a + a} & 2020 &:= \frac{\frac{aaaaa - a^a}{aa} \times (a + a)}{aa} \\ 55 &:= \frac{aaa - a}{a + a} & 2035 &:= \frac{\frac{aaaa - a^a}{a + a + a} \times aa}{a + a} \\ 56 &:= \frac{aaa + a}{aaa + a} & 4477 &:= \frac{\frac{a + a}{aaa} \times aa \times aa}{a \times a} \\ 561 &:= \frac{a + a}{aaaa + aa} & 4999 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa - a - a)}{(a + a)} \\ 666 &:= \frac{aaa \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} & 5000 &:= \frac{(aaaaa - aaaa)}{(a + a)} \\ 786 &:= \frac{(\frac{(aa + a) \times aa}{a} - a) \times (aa + a)}{(a + a) \times a} & 122988 &:= \frac{(aaaa - a - a - a) \times aaa}{a \times a} \\ 925 &:= \frac{aaaaa - aa}{aa + a} \\ 1089 &:= \frac{aaaa - aa - aa}{a} \end{aligned}$$

where $a \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, and $aa = 10 \times a + a$, $aaa = 10^2 \times a + 10 \times a + a$, etc.

The full work is from 1 to 11111 numbers, written in two different ways. One running type [16] and another in fraction-type way [17]. For previous work refer [13, 14]. The summary of author's work on recreation of numbers in different situations refer [23].

1.5 Running Expressions

Previous subsections, works with natural numbers in different situations using 9 or 10 digits. In this section also we shall do similar kind of work, but in little different way. It is based on the idea of subsection 1.1. We divide the numbers in equal parts, two or three in such a way that the results are increasing and decreasing orders 1 to 9 or 9 to 1 or 9 to 0 separated by equalities, for example,

$$\begin{aligned} 1^{234} &= (5 + 67)/(8 \times 9) \\ 98/7 + 6 &= 54/3 + 2 \times 1. \end{aligned}$$

Below are more examples, written in increasing and decreasing ways:

- **Increasing Order**

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{12} &= 3 + 4 + (5 \times 6 + 7 + 8)/9 & (1) \\ \mathbf{123} &= 4 + 5 + 6 \times 7 + 8 \times 9 \\ \mathbf{1234} &= -5 + 6! + 7 + 8^{\sqrt{9}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12 + 3 \times 4 + 5 \times (6 + 7) &= \mathbf{89} \\ 1 + 23 + 45 + 6! &= \mathbf{789} \end{aligned}$$

- **Decreasing Order**

$$\begin{aligned} 98 - 7 \times (6 + 5) \times (4 - 3) &= \mathbf{21} & (2) \\ \sqrt{9} \times 87 + 6 + 54 &= \mathbf{321} \\ 9 - 8 + 7! - 6 \times 5! &= \mathbf{4321} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9 - 8 + 7 - 6 + 5 + 4 - 3 + 2 &= \mathbf{10} \\ 9 \times (8 + 7) + 6 + 5 + 4^3 &= \mathbf{210} \\ (9 - 87 + 6!) \times 5! / 4! &= \mathbf{3210} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98} &= (7 + 6) \times 5 + 4 \times 3 + 21 \\ \mathbf{987} &= 6! + 5! + (4 + 3) \times 21 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{98} &= 7 + 65 + 4 + 32 - 10 \\ \mathbf{987} &= 6! + 54 + 3 + 210 \end{aligned}$$

Above examples give representations separated by equality sign having the digits in either increasing and/or decreasing orders. There are numbers that can be written in increasing as well as decreasing orders at the same time with single or double equality signs, such as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{16} &:= 12/3 \times 4 = 5 + 6 + (7 + 8)/\sqrt{9} \\ &:= (9 + 87)/6 = 5 + 4 + 3 \times 2 + 1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18} &= 12 + 3! = \sqrt{4 + 5} \times 6 = 7 + 8 + \sqrt{9} \\ &= \sqrt{9} + 8 + 7 = \sqrt{6 \times 54} = -3 + 21 = 3! + 2 + 10 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{120} &:= (1 \times 2 + 3)! = 4 \times 5 \times 6 = ((7 + 8) / \sqrt{9})! & (3) \\
 &:= ((\sqrt{9})! - 8 + 7)! = 6 \times 5 \times 4 = (3 \times 2 - 1)! = 3! \times 2 \times 10
 \end{aligned}$$

The above three examples divide the numbers in two and three parts respectively with equality signs using the numbers in increasing as well as decreasing orders. From the examples (1), (2) and (3), we observe that the operations used are **addition, subtraction, multiplication, division, potentiation, factorial** and **square-root**. More details can be seen in [23, 19, 20]. In this work, our interest is to found examples similar to (1), (2) and (3), using **Fibonacci sequence** values.

1.5.1 Running Expressions with Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Similar to (1) and (2), given above, below are examples of running expressions using **Fibonacci sequence** numbers. Most of the results uses basic operations, except numbers 21 and 9876, where extra operation, such as factorial is used.

• Increasing Order

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12} &= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) + 6 - 7 - 8 - 9 & (4) \\
 \mathbf{123} &= -4 \times 5 \times (6 - F(7)) - 8 - 9 \\
 \mathbf{1234} &= 5 \times F(6) \times F(7) + F(8) \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 + F(2^3 + F(4)) + (5 - 6)^7 &= \mathbf{89} \\
 1 \times 2 \times 3^4 \times 5 - F(F(6)) &= \mathbf{789} \\
 1 + 23 + F(4 \times 5) &= \mathbf{6789}.
 \end{aligned}$$

• Decreasing Order

$$\begin{aligned}
 9 + (-F(8)/7 + 6) \times 5 - F(4)! + 3 &= \mathbf{21} & (5) \\
 -98 - F(7) + F(6) \times 54 &= \mathbf{321} \\
 (F(9) \times F(8) + 7) \times 6 - 5 &= \mathbf{4321}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{98} &= (7 - 6) \times 5 + F(4) \times (32 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{987} &= (6 - 5) \times F(4 \times (3 + 2 - 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98 &= -5 - 4 - 3 + 2 \times F(10) \\
 987 &= (6 - 5)^4 \times F(3 \times 2 + 10) \\
 9876 &= (\sqrt{5 + 4})! + F(F(3!) \times 2) \times 10
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in Taneja [21].

1.5.2 Running Expressions with Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. These are given by

$$1, 3, 6, 10, 15, 21, \dots$$

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

The letter "*C*" represents as "**binomial coefficient**".

In this paper our aim is to bring **running expressions** by use of **triangle numbers**. This we have done in subsequent sections. Due to high quantity of numbers, we the work is limited to 3 digits in case of single equality. As a part of results, see below some interesting examples,

- **Increasing Order**

$$\begin{aligned}
 12 &= T(3) - 4 - 5 + 6 - (7 - 8) \times 9 & (6) \\
 123 &= (-4 + 5) \times 6 + T(7) + 89 \\
 1234 &= T(56 \times 7/8) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 + 2 + T(3) \times 4 - 5 + 67 &= 89 \\
 1 + 2 + T(3) + T(45 - 6) &= 789 \\
 -1 - 2 + T(3) + T(-4 + T(T(5))) &= 6789.
 \end{aligned}$$

- **Decreasing Order**

$$\begin{aligned}
 9 \times 8 - T(7) - T(6) + 5 - 4 - 3 &= \mathbf{21} \\
 T(9 + 8) - 7 \times 6 + T(5 \times 4) &= \mathbf{321} \\
 (-T(9) + T(T(8))) \times 7 - T(6) - 5 &= \mathbf{4321}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{98} &= (7 - 6) \times 5^4 - T(32) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{987} &= T(6) \times (5 \times T(4) - 3) \times (2 - 1) \\
 \mathbf{9876} &= T(5 \times T(4 + 3)) + T(2 + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{98} &= (7 - 6) \times T(5) - 4 + 32 + T(10) \\
 \mathbf{987} &= (6 - 5) \times 4 \times (T(T(T(3))) + 2) + T(10) \\
 \mathbf{9876} &= (-5 + T(T(T(4)))) \times T(3) + T(T(-2 + 10))
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9 \times 8 - T(7) - T(6) - T(5) - 4 + 3 \times 2 &= \mathbf{10} \\
 T(9) + 87 \times (6 - 5) + T(4 \times 3) &= \mathbf{210} \\
 T(9) + 8 + 7 + T(6) \times T(5) \times T(4) &= \mathbf{3210}
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in Taneja [22].

2 Minimum Length Flexible Power Representations

Let's see the procedure applied

2.1 Procedure

Let us consider, $(a, b)^{(a, b)}$, where $a, b \in 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9$. Extending it for more number of digits, i.e., for 3, 4, 5, etc., we have a general procedure:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (a, b)^{(a,b)}; \\
& (a, b, c)^{(a,b,c)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d)^{(a,b,c,d)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d, e)^{(a,b,c,d,e)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i)}; \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j)}.
\end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where, $a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, with no repetition of number in each case. Each line of (9) represents the length, for example, the first line is of length 2, second line is of length 3, etc. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
& (a, b)^{(a,b)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 2} \\
& (a, b, c)^{(a,b,c)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 3} \\
& (a, b, c, d)^{(a,b,c,d)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 4} \\
& (a, b, c, d, e)^{(a,b,c,d,e)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 5} \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 6} \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 7} \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 8} \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 9} \\
& (a, b, c, d, e, f, g, h, i, j)^{(a,b,c,d,e,f,g,h,i,j)} \longrightarrow \text{Length 10.}
\end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Remark 2.1. The procedure is for the digits 0 to 9, 1 to 9, etc. The previous work of author [6] is for the digits 1 to 9. This work brings both situations, i.e., 0 to 9 and 1 to 9.

2.2 Differences Choice of Sets

Below are some numbers where we have difference among the choice of digits sets from $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$ or $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$. The first value in **blue** is with the choice of from the set $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$, and the second value in **red** is for the choice from the set $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{25} & := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 & \mathbf{217} & := 0^6 + 3^0 + 6^3 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2 \\
\mathbf{215} & := 0^6 - 3^0 + 6^3 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2 & \mathbf{242} & := 0^3 + 3^5 - 5^0 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 9^1
\end{aligned}$$

$244 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^4$	$1031 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$= 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$256 := -0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4$	$1039 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$342 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$1041 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$344 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 7^3$	$= -1^9 + 2^8 + 8^1 + 9^2$	$1071 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 7^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$380 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2$	$1073 := 0^7 + 3^6 + 6^0 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$472 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3$	$1104 := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^1$
$487 := 0^9 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$	$1148 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^9 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 - 9^2$
$511 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^1$	$1150 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^7 - 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5$
$515 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2$	$1152 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^2$
$605 := 0^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	$1181 := 0^7 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^8 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 8^2 + 9^3$
$626 := 0^5 + 4^0 + 5^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4$	$1182 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^1$
$656 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1$	$1183 := 0^7 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^1$
$664 := 0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1$	$1199 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1$
$730 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1$	$1240 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4$
$754 := 0^8 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 8^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2$	$1242 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 9^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 6^4$
$767 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 8^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1$	$1270 := 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4$
$792 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1$	$1290 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^1 + 6^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 6^4$
$794 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1$	$1292 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 6^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4$
$809 := 0^9 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4$	$1294 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4$
$811 := 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3$	$1295 := 0^6 - 4^0 + 6^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 6^4$
$853 := 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	$1296 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^0 + 6^4$	$= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 8^1$
$855 := 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4$	$1297 := 0^6 + 4^0 + 6^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 6^4$
$867 := 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4$	$1298 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^0 + 6^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4$
$894 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4$	$1300 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4$
$898 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2$	$1302 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 + 6^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 6^4$
$900 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3$	$= -2^6 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^4$	$1341 := 0^6 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^4$
$943 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1359 := 0^2 + 2^6 - 4^0 + 6^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4$
$970 := 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$1361 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 6^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^2$
$971 := 0^9 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$1378 := 0^7 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 6^4$
$972 := 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$1418 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 7^0 - 8^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^3$
$1007 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1440 := 0^9 + 2^6 - 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$1009 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$1520 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1$
$1017 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1674 := 0^8 + 3^7 - 7^0 - 8^3$	$= 1^9 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 9^3$
$1019 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1689 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^2$
$1023 := 0^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^2 + 9^3$	$1691 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^4$
$1025 := 0^4 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$= -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3$	$1693 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^4$
$1027 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1694 := 0^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 7^4$

$$\begin{aligned}
1735 &:= 0^7 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 + 7^4 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 6^1 & 2272 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 7^4 = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 \\
1737 &:= 0^7 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 + 7^4 = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^2 & 2309 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
1757 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^0 + 9^2 = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 6^1 & 2311 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^0 = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
1778 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^0 = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^1 & 2313 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 = -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
1791 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 9^0 = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 & 2319 &:= 0^6 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 6^4 = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
1793 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 9^0 = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 & 2336 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 7^4 = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
1828 &:= 0^6 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 & 2373 &:= 0^7 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 7^4 = -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^4 \\
1830 &:= 0^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 & 2375 &:= 0^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 7^4 = 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^4 \\
1842 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3 & 2399 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 7^4 \\
1846 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 - 7^3 & 2400 &:= 0^7 - 4^0 + 7^4 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 7^4 \\
1864 &:= 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 - 7^3 & 2442 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 7^0 = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^4 \\
1906 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^3 - 7^0 = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^3 & 2444 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^0 = 1^7 + 2^6 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
1932 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 7^0 = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^1 & 2464 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 7^4 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^4 \\
1940 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^3 & 2466 &:= 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 7^4 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^4 \\
1970 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 - 6^3 - 7^0 = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^2 & 2579 &:= 0^7 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^4 = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
2024 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^4 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 & 2628 &:= 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^0 = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
2025 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 = 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 2698 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 - 7^0 + 8^3 = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^5 + 9^2 \\
2026 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 & 2700 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 + 7^0 + 8^3 = -1^7 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
2031 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^4 & 2753 &:= 0^9 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
2061 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 - 5^3 - 7^0 = -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 2755 &:= 0^9 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
2063 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^0 = 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 2771 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
2065 &:= 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 - 7^0 = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^4 & 2775 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 \\
2087 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^4 & 2996 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 = 1^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
2116 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^3 & 3071 &:= 0^8 - 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 \\
2118 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^3 & 3100 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 5^5 = -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
2122 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^1 & 3342 &:= 0^6 + 3^0 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
2124 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^0 = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^1 & 3426 &:= 0^7 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^4 = 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
2178 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^1 = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^1 & 3435 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 - 5^5 - 8^0 = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 8^1 \\
2182 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^1 = -1^5 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^2 & 3567 &:= 0^8 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^0 = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 \\
2186 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 7^0 = -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 & 3679 &:= 0^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 = 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
2188 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 7^0 = 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 & 3681 &:= 0^4 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 = -1^6 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\
2190 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 7^0 = 1^9 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 9^1 & 3775 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 8^4 = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
2192 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 7^1 = -1^5 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^2 & 3777 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 8^4 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
2194 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 7^1 = -1^7 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 3839 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 \\
2196 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 7^1 = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 - 7^1 & 3840 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
2250 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^0 = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 & 3853 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
2252 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^0 = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 & 3879 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 6^3 = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
3881 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 6^3 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
3917 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^1 \\
3919 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
3936 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\
3950 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 8^3 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\
3977 &:= 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^2 \\
3979 &:= 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
3997 &:= 0^8 - 2^6 + 4^0 - 6^2 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4005 &:= 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^0 &= 1^5 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 \\
4007 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 &= 1^4 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^2 \\
4013 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 &= 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4014 &:= 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4015 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4016 &:= 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4029 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 8^4 &= -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4031 &:= 0^8 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 8^4 &= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4033 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 8^4 &= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
4068 &:= 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 &= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\
4088 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 &= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4090 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 &= -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4092 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 &= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4095 &:= 0^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\
4096 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4097 &:= 0^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4100 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 &= -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4102 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 &= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4104 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 &= 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4124 &:= 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4159 &:= 0^8 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 8^4 &= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 \\
4161 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 8^4 &= -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^2 \\
4163 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 \\
4165 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 &= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 \\
4173 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 &= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4177 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 \\
4178 &:= 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4185 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 &= -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 \\
4187 &:= 0^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 &= 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 \\
4195 &:= 0^8 + 2^6 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 8^4 &= -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 \\
4197 &:= 0^8 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 8^4 &= 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 \\
4213 &:= 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^0 &= -1^4 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^2 \\
4259 &:= 0^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 7^0 &= 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 \\
4275 &:= 0^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 9^0 &= -1^5 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4311 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^3 &= -1^6 + 2^8 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4313 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^3 &= 1^6 + 2^8 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4350 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 &= 1^4 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4351 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 &= -1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
4353 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 &= -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4437 &:= 0^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^0 + 9^4 &= -1^5 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4449 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4462 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4465 &:= 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4477 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4587 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 \\
4592 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4608 &:= 0^8 + 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4623 &:= 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^0 &= -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4664 &:= 0^9 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4715 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4720 &:= 0^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4721 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4727 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4745 &:= 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^3 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4786 &:= 0^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^3 &= 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4803 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 &= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4805 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4
\end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.2. By no means the above list is complete. It is just an idea. The other values can be seen in the **Complete List** given in subsection below.

2.3 Complete List: 0 to 10000

According to Procedure given in (9), below are representations of numbers from 0 to 10000. These representations are of minimum length according to (10). The numbers given in **blue** are for the choice of digits 0 to 9, and the numbers given in **red** are for the choice of digits from 1 to 9.

0 := $-0^0 + 1^1$	= $-2^4 + 4^2$	33 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 4^2$	= $1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2$
1 := $0^1 + 1^0$	= $-1^2 + 2^1$	34 := $1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$	= $1^6 + 3^3 + 6^1$
2 := $0^0 + 1^1$	= $-1^3 + 3^1$	35 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 6^2$	= $1^6 - 2^1 + 6^2$
3 := $-0^0 + 2^2$	= $1^2 + 2^1$	36 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$
4 := $1^3 + 3^1$	= $1^3 + 3^1$	37 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 6^2$	= $-1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$
5 := $0^0 + 2^2$	= $1^1 + 2^2$	38 := $1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$	= $1^2 + 2^5 + 5^1$
6 := $1^5 + 5^1$	= $1^5 + 5^1$	39 := $1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	= $1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$
7 := $1^6 + 6^1$	= $1^6 + 6^1$	40 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 6^2$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$
8 := $1^7 + 7^1$	= $1^7 + 7^1$	41 := $0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 - 6^3$	= $1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 9^1$
9 := $1^8 + 8^1$	= $1^8 + 8^1$	42 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2$	= $1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$
10 := $1^9 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 9^1$	43 := $0^6 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 6^2$	= $-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 7^2$
11 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 9^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1$	44 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^0$	= $-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2$
12 := $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	= $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1$	45 := $-0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$
13 := $-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	46 := $-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	= $-1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$
14 := $1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 2^2 + 9^1$	47 := $-0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$	= $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^1$
15 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 4^2$	= $1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2$	48 := $0^7 - 2^0 + 7^2$	= $1^7 - 2^1 + 7^2$
16 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	49 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 7^2$	= $-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$
17 := $2^3 + 3^2$	= $2^3 + 3^2$	50 := $0^7 + 2^0 + 7^2$	= $-1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$
18 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2$	= $1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2$	51 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 7^2$	= $1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$
19 := $1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	= $1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2$	52 := $1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	= $1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$
20 := $-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	= $-1^6 + 3^3 - 6^1$	53 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 7^2$	= $-1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2$
21 := $1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	= $1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1$	54 := $0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3$	= $1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3$
22 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	55 := $2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$	= $2^6 + 3^3 - 6^2$
23 := $-2^2 + 3^3$	= $-2^2 + 3^3$	56 := $-0^0 + 2^5 + 5^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$
24 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3$	57 := $2^5 + 5^2$	= $2^5 + 5^2$
25 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3$	= $-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1$	58 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 5^2$	= $1^1 + 2^5 + 5^2$
26 := $-0^0 + 3^3$	= $-1^1 + 3^3$	59 := $1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$	= $1^2 + 2^6 - 6^1$
27 := $-0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3$	= $-1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	60 := $-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	= $-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$
28 := $0^0 + 3^3$	= $1^1 + 3^3$	61 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$	= $-1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$
29 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3$	= $1^1 + 2^6 - 6^2$	62 := $1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$	= $1^4 - 3^1 + 4^3$
30 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3$	= $1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3$	63 := $0^2 + 2^6 - 6^0$	= $1^8 - 2^1 + 8^2$
31 := $2^2 + 3^3$	= $2^2 + 3^3$	64 := $-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$	= $-2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2$
32 := $2^4 + 4^2$	= $2^4 + 4^2$	65 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 6^0$	= $-1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$

$66 := -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$103 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$
$67 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 8^2$	$104 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$
$68 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$105 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2$
$69 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$106 := 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$
$70 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$107 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^2$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$
$71 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$108 := 1^7 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$
$72 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3$	$109 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^1$
$73 := 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^2$	$110 := 1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
$74 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$111 := 0^4 + 2^7 - 4^2 - 7^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 - 7^1$
$75 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$112 := 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$	$= 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$
$76 := -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^1$	$113 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$
$77 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 7^2$	$114 := -2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^5 - 5^3$
$78 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$115 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3$
$79 := 2^7 - 7^2$	$= 2^7 - 7^2$	$116 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^3$
$80 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$117 := -0^0 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$
$81 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2$	$118 := 3^5 - 5^3$	$= 3^5 - 5^3$
$82 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$119 := 0^0 + 3^5 - 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^5 - 5^3$
$83 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$120 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$
$84 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$121 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$
$85 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^2$	$122 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 7^1$
$86 := 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$123 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$
$87 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 9^2$	$124 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 5^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 7^1$
$88 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$125 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 5^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3$
$89 := 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$126 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 5^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 6^2$
$90 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3$	$127 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 7^0$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$
$91 := 0^6 + 2^7 - 6^2 - 7^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	$128 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 6^2$
$92 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 5^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$129 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$
$93 := 0^6 + 2^7 - 6^2 + 7^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 7^1$	$130 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^0$	$= -1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 6^3$
$94 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^0 + 5^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^1$	$131 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3$
$95 := 0^8 + 2^5 - 5^0 + 8^2$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$132 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^4 - 5^3$	$= 1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 6^3$
$96 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$133 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3$
$97 := 0^8 + 2^5 + 5^0 + 8^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	$134 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$
$98 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2$	$135 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3$
$99 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$136 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$
$100 := 2^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^6 + 6^2$	$137 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 7^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3$
$101 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 6^2$	$138 := -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$
$102 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$= -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	$139 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3$

140 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	177 := $2^7 + 7^2$	= $2^7 + 7^2$
141 := $-2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $-2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	178 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 7^2$	= $1^1 + 2^7 + 7^2$
142 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	179 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 7^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2$
143 := $-2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	= $-2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	180 := $0^4 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^0$	= $-1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2$
144 := $-0^0 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $-1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3$	181 := $1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2$	= $1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^2$
145 := $3^4 + 4^3$	= $3^4 + 4^3$	182 := $1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2$	= $1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2$
146 := $0^0 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3$	183 := $1^5 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^2$	= $1^5 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^2$
147 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $-1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^3$	184 := $1^6 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 7^2$	= $1^6 + 2^7 + 6^1 + 7^2$
148 := $2^5 - 3^2 + 5^3$	= $2^5 - 3^2 + 5^3$	185 := $-1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	= $-1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
149 := $2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	= $2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3$	186 := $-1^5 + 2^8 - 5^1 - 8^2$	= $-1^5 + 2^8 - 5^1 - 8^2$
150 := $2^7 - 3^3 + 7^2$	= $2^7 - 3^3 + 7^2$	187 := $1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	= $1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
151 := $0^2 - 2^6 - 3^0 + 6^3$	= $1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 7^2$	188 := $-1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 8^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 8^2$
152 := $0^5 + 2^7 + 5^2 - 7^0$	= $1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^1$	189 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$	= $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$
153 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 6^3$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	190 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$	= $1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 8^2$
154 := $0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 7^0$	= $-1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	191 := $-0^0 + 2^8 - 8^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$
155 := $-0^0 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	= $1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^3$	192 := $2^8 - 8^2$	= $2^8 - 8^2$
156 := $-2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	= $-2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	193 := $0^0 + 2^8 - 8^2$	= $1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$
157 := $0^0 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	= $1^1 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	194 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 - 8^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 8^2$
158 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 5^3$	= $1^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 - 7^1$	195 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$	= $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 8^2$
159 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^3$	196 := $1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 8^2$	= $1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 8^2$
160 := $-0^0 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	= $-1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	197 := $-1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	= $-1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$
161 := $-2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	= $-2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	198 := $-0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$
162 := $0^0 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	= $1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3$	199 := $-2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$	= $-2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$
163 := $0^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 - 7^0$	= $1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^1$	200 := $0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$	= $1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 - 5^2$
164 := $-0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	201 := $-0^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$	= $-1^9 + 2^7 - 7^1 + 9^2$
165 := $2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	= $2^8 - 3^3 - 8^2$	202 := $4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$	= $4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5$
166 := $2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	= $2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	203 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$
167 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	= $1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^3$	204 := $2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$	= $2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$
168 := $-1^8 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$	= $-1^8 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$	205 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$	= $1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 7^2$
169 := $1^9 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 9^1$	= $1^9 + 2^7 + 7^2 - 9^1$	206 := $-2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	= $-2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$
170 := $-1^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^1$	= $-1^6 + 2^7 + 6^2 + 7^1$	207 := $0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$	= $1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3$
171 := $-1^5 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^2$	= $-1^5 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^2$	208 := $-2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3$	= $-2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3$
172 := $-1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2$	= $-1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2$	209 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$
173 := $-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2$	210 := $-2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	= $-2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$
174 := $0^9 - 2^0 + 4^4 - 9^2$	= $1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2$	211 := $-0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	= $1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$
175 := $2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	= $2^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	212 := $-1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	= $-1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$
176 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 7^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^7 + 7^2$	213 := $-0^0 + 1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	= $1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3$

214 := $1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^6 - 3^1 + 6^3$	251 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 4^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^4$
215 := $0^6 - 3^0 + 6^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$	252 := $-2^2 + 4^4$	$= -2^2 + 4^4$
216 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^0 + 6^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^3$	253 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^4$
217 := $0^6 + 3^0 + 6^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$	254 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^4$
218 := $-1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	255 := $-0^0 + 4^4$	$= -1^1 + 4^4$
219 := $2^8 + 3^3 - 8^2$	$= 2^8 + 3^3 - 8^2$	256 := $-0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4$
220 := $1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	257 := $0^0 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^4$
221 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 5^2$	258 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^4$
222 := $-1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^3$	259 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 4^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^4$
223 := $-0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	260 := $2^2 + 4^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^4$
224 := $-2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	$= -2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3$	261 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^4$
225 := $-2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	262 := $1^5 + 4^4 + 5^1$	$= 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^1$
226 := $2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	263 := $-1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$
227 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^2$	264 := $1^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 4^4 + 7^1$
228 := $-0^0 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	265 := $1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 + 8^1$
229 := $-3^3 + 4^4$	$= -3^3 + 4^4$	266 := $1^9 + 4^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^4 + 9^1$
230 := $0^0 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	267 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^2$
231 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	268 := $0^8 - 3^5 - 5^0 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^4$
232 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^4$	269 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^2$
233 := $2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	270 := $-0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$
234 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4$	271 := $2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$	$= 2^6 - 3^2 + 6^3$
235 := $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 5^1$	272 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$
236 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^1$	273 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$
237 := $-1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	274 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4$
238 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4$	275 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$
239 := $1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	276 := $2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$
240 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4$	277 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^2$
241 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 5^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^1$	278 := $-3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4$	$= -3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4$
242 := $0^3 + 3^5 - 5^0$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 9^1$	279 := $-2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$
243 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^1$	280 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$
244 := $0^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^4$	281 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1$
245 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^1$	282 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$
246 := $-1^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	283 := $3^3 + 4^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^4$
247 := $-1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$	284 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$
248 := $-1^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^7 + 4^4 - 7^1$	285 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$
249 := $1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 - 8^1$	286 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4$
250 := $-1^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$	$= -1^5 + 4^4 - 5^1$	287 := $2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
\mathbf{288} := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 \\
\mathbf{289} := 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 & = 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 \\
\mathbf{290} := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 6^3 \\
\mathbf{291} := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 6^2 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^2 \\
\mathbf{292} := -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 8^1 \\
\mathbf{293} := 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2 & = 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{294} := 0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{295} := 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^2 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 6^2 \\
\mathbf{296} := 0^6 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 6^3 & = -1^7 + 2^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
\mathbf{297} := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 \\
\mathbf{298} := 0^6 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 6^3 & = 1^7 + 2^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
\mathbf{299} := -1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
\mathbf{300} := -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^3 & = -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^3 \\
\mathbf{301} := 1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 2^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
\mathbf{302} := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{303} := 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 & = 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 \\
\mathbf{304} := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{305} := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
\mathbf{306} := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{307} := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
\mathbf{308} := 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^0 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{309} := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
\mathbf{310} := -1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 - 9^1 \\
\mathbf{311} := -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 & = -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 \\
\mathbf{312} := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
\mathbf{313} := 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 & = 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
\mathbf{314} := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
\mathbf{315} := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 6^1 \\
\mathbf{316} := -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{317} := -0^0 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{318} := -3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = -3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
\mathbf{319} := -0^0 + 2^8 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{320} := 2^8 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{321} := 0^0 + 2^8 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{322} := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{323} := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{324} := -0^0 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{325} := -4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = -4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
\mathbf{326} := 0^0 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{327} := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^1 \\
\mathbf{328} := 1^7 + 2^8 + 7^1 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^8 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{329} := 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^2 & = 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^2 \\
\mathbf{330} := 1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 2^8 + 8^2 + 9^1 \\
\mathbf{331} := -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 7^3 & = -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{332} := 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 6^4 & = 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 6^4 \\
\mathbf{333} := 0^7 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 7^3 & = 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{334} := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{335} := 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{336} := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{337} := 2^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & = 2^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{338} := -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{339} := -1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 & = -1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{340} := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{341} := 1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 & = 1^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{342} := 0^7 - 3^0 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 6^1 \\
\mathbf{343} := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^0 + 7^3 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{344} := 0^7 + 3^0 + 7^3 & = -1^9 + 2^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{345} := -1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{346} := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{347} := 1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{348} := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{349} := -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{350} := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 8^2 \\
\mathbf{351} := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{352} := -2^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^2 \\
\mathbf{353} := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{354} := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^1 \\
\mathbf{355} := -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 7^3 \\
\mathbf{356} := 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2 & = 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2 \\
\mathbf{357} := 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 6^2 \\
\mathbf{358} := -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1 \\
\mathbf{359} := -1^8 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^8 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
\mathbf{360} := -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1 & = -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
\mathbf{361} := -1^6 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 6^1 & = -1^6 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 6^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
362 := 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1 & = 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
363 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
364 := -2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = -2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
365 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
366 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 6^3 \\
367 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
368 := 3^5 + 5^3 & = 3^5 + 5^3 \\
369 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
370 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3 \\
371 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
372 := 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
373 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^3 \\
374 := 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3 & = 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3 \\
375 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^3 \\
376 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1 \\
377 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
378 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^1 \\
379 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 & = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
380 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 & = -1^4 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
381 := 0^3 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^7 + 3^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
382 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 & = -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
383 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 7^0 & = -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
384 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^0 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^2 \\
385 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^0 & = 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
386 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^0 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
387 := 0^7 + 3^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 & = 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
388 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
389 := -1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 \\
390 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1 \\
391 := -1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
392 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^1 \\
393 := 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
394 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
395 := -2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
396 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
397 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
398 := -0^0 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
399 := 4^5 - 5^4 & = 4^5 - 5^4 \\
400 := 0^0 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
401 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
402 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
403 := 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
404 := 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2 & = 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2 \\
405 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^2 \\
406 := 1^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 6^1 & = 1^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 6^1 \\
407 := 1^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
408 := 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 & = 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
409 := 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 \\
410 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
411 := 0^8 - 2^6 - 3^0 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
412 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
413 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2 \\
414 := 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2 & = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 9^2 \\
415 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
416 := 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
417 := -1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
418 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
419 := -1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3 \\
420 := -2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3 & = -2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3 \\
421 := 1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 7^3 \\
422 := 0^4 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 2^9 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
423 := 0^7 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^1 - 9^2 \\
424 := 0^4 - 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
425 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -1^5 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 9^2 \\
426 := 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4 \\
427 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 9^2 \\
428 := 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 9^2 & = 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 9^2 \\
429 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 9^2 \\
430 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
431 := 2^9 - 9^2 & = 2^9 - 9^2 \\
432 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
433 := 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2 \\
434 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 7^2 \\
435 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 9^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
436 &:= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 9^2 &= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 9^2 & 473 &:= 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 6^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
437 &:= 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 9^2 &= 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 9^2 & 474 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^0 &= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
438 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^1 - 9^2 & 475 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^0 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 7^3 \\
439 &:= 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 - 9^2 &= 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 - 9^2 & 476 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 &= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
440 &:= 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 - 9^2 &= 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 - 9^2 & 477 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 + 9^0 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^1 \\
441 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 - 9^2 &= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 478 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^1 &= -1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^1 \\
442 &:= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 479 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3 \\
443 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 480 &:= 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3 &= 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3 \\
444 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 6^2 & 481 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 7^3 \\
445 &:= -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 482 &:= 1^9 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3 \\
446 &:= -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 483 &:= -2^7 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 7^3 &= -2^7 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 7^3 \\
447 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & 484 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 9^0 &= -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 + 9^1 \\
448 &:= 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & 485 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 9^3 \\
449 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & 486 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^0 &= -1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^1 \\
450 &:= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 487 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^3 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1 \\
451 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 & 488 &:= 0^5 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 9^0 &= 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^1 \\
452 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 &= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^4 - 8^2 & 489 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^1 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1 \\
453 &:= -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 &= -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & 490 &:= -1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3 \\
454 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3 & 491 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^1 \\
455 &:= 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 &= 1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & 492 &:= 1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3 \\
456 &:= -1^8 + 2^9 - 8^2 + 9^1 &= -1^8 + 2^9 - 8^2 + 9^1 & 493 &:= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1 &= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1 \\
457 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2 & 494 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 \\
458 &:= 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2 & 495 &:= 0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 9^0 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1 \\
459 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^2 & 496 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^1 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 - 6^3 \\
460 &:= 0^6 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 6^3 &= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 7^2 & 497 &:= 0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^0 &= 1^5 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 9^1 \\
461 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3 & 498 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^0 &= 2^6 + 3^5 - 5^2 + 6^3 \\
462 &:= 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3 &= 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3 & 499 &:= -2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4 &= -2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
463 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 7^3 & 500 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^0 &= -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 8^3 \\
464 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 + 9^0 &= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^3 & 501 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1 &= -2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^2 \\
465 &:= 1^6 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 6^3 &= 1^6 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 6^3 & 502 &:= -1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1 &= -1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1 \\
466 &:= -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1 &= -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1 & 503 &:= -3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4 &= -3^6 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
467 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 & 504 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1 \\
468 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 6^2 - 9^1 & 505 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 9^1 &= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
469 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 &= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^3 & 506 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 8^3 &= 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 8^3 \\
470 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 - 3^0 + 7^3 &= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 507 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3 &= -1^5 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 \\
471 &:= 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 6^3 &= -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^2 + 9^1 & 508 &:= -1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3 &= -1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3 \\
472 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^0 + 7^3 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 509 &:= -2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3 &= -2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
510 := 1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 8^3 \\
511 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^1 \\
512 := -0^0 + 3^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3 \\
513 := 3^6 - 6^3 & = 3^6 - 6^3 \\
514 := 0^0 + 3^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3 \\
515 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
516 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 8^3 \\
517 := 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3 & = 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3 \\
518 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^3 \\
519 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
520 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 \\
521 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
522 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 \\
523 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^6 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
524 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 8^3 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 8^3 \\
525 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
526 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 - 9^0 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
527 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 - 9^0 & = -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 9^1 \\
528 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
529 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1 \\
530 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^3 \\
531 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 9^1 \\
532 := 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 & = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
533 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 \\
534 := 0^8 + 2^5 - 3^2 - 5^0 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
535 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 7^3 \\
536 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 \\
537 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^0 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
538 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 \\
539 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^0 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
540 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\
541 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^0 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 \\
542 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
543 := -2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 & = -2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
544 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 6^3 \\
545 := -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 & = -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 \\
546 := 3^6 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 & = 3^6 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
547 := 0^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 - 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^1 \\
548 := 2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3 & = 2^6 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 6^3 \\
549 := 0^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^1 \\
550 := -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
551 := -1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 & = -1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 \\
552 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
553 := 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 \\
554 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
555 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
556 := -1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\
557 := -1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = -1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
558 := 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\
559 := 1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = 1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
560 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 - 9^0 & = 2^8 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 8^2 \\
561 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^0 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
562 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^0 & = -1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
563 := -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
564 := 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 & = 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
565 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2 \\
566 := 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2 & = 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2 \\
567 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 9^2 \\
568 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 - 9^1 \\
569 := -1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1 & = -1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1 \\
570 := -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
571 := 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^2 + 9^1 \\
572 := 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 & = 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
573 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
574 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
575 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 \\
576 := 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 \\
577 := -2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = -2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
578 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
579 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
580 := -1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3 \\
581 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
582 := 1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 7^3 \\
583 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 + 9^1 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
584 := -1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 8^2 + 9^1 \\
585 := 0^7 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 2^9 - 7^1 + 9^2 \\
586 := -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
587 := 0^7 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 7^3 & = -1^5 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 9^2 \\
588 := -1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
589 := -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^2 \\
590 := 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
591 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^2 \\
592 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 9^2 \\
593 := 2^9 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 9^2 \\
594 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 9^2 \\
595 := -3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
596 := 0^0 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
597 := 0^5 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^2 \\
598 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
599 := 0^5 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 \\
600 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 7^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
601 := 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 + 9^2 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
602 := 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 + 9^2 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
603 := 0^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^0 & = 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
604 := -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
605 := 0^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^0 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
606 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
607 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
608 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
609 := -2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = -2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
610 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
611 := 1^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 & = 1^5 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 \\
612 := 1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
613 := -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^2 & = -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^2 \\
614 := 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
615 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
616 := -1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
617 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
618 := 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
619 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^2 \\
620 := -1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
621 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 9^2 \\
622 := 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
623 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
624 := 0^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 & = 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
625 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^3 \\
626 := 0^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
627 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
628 := -1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
629 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = 3^4 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
630 := 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
631 := -3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 & = -3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
632 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
633 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
634 := 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
635 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
636 := -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
637 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
638 := -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
639 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
640 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
641 := 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 & = 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
642 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
643 := -1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 \\
644 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
645 := 1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 \\
646 := 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 & = 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
647 := 0^9 - 3^4 - 4^0 + 9^3 & = -1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
648 := -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 & = -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
649 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 & = 1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
650 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 \\
651 := 0^5 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4 & = -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
652 := -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
653 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
654 := 1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
655 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
656 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 \\
657 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
658 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 &= -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1 \\
659 &:= 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
660 &:= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
661 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
662 &:= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 &= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
663 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 &= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
664 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1 \\
665 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
666 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0 &= -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
667 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
668 &:= 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 &= 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
669 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 &= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
670 &:= -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 &= -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 \\
671 &:= 2^8 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 &= 2^8 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 \\
672 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 &= -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
673 &:= 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 &= 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
674 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
675 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 &= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
676 &:= 0^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^2 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 \\
677 &:= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 &= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
678 &:= 0^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 6^2 &= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 - 9^2 \\
679 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
680 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0 &= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2 \\
681 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
682 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0 &= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2 \\
683 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
684 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
685 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= -2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
686 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
687 &:= 2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2 \\
688 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^4 - 9^2 \\
689 &:= 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^3 &= 3^6 - 4^4 + 6^3 \\
690 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
691 &:= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
692 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
693 &:= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
694 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
695 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
696 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
697 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
698 &:= 0^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 \\
699 &:= -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 &= -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 \\
700 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
701 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
702 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^2 \\
703 &:= 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 8^3 &= 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
704 &:= -3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= -3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
705 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
706 &:= 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^0 &= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2 \\
707 &:= 0^9 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
708 &:= 3^7 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 &= 3^7 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
709 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 &= 1^9 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
710 &:= 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 6^2 &= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^1 \\
711 &:= 2^9 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 \\
712 &:= 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 &= 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
713 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
714 &:= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 \\
715 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 9^2 \\
716 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 \\
717 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
718 &:= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^1 \\
719 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
720 &:= 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^0 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 6^1 \\
721 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
722 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= -1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 \\
723 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
724 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 &= 1^3 + 3^6 - 6^1 \\
725 &:= -1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 \\
726 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
727 &:= 1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 \\
728 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 - 6^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
729 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^0 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 9^3 \\
730 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 6^0 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
731 &:= -1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
732 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
733 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 \\
734 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = -1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
735 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 9^3 \\
736 := 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
737 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 9^3 \\
738 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^0 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
739 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 9^3 \\
740 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
741 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 9^3 \\
742 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
743 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 \\
744 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 \\
745 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 & = -1^5 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 8^3 \\
746 := 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 \\
747 := 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^0 & = 1^5 + 2^8 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 8^3 \\
748 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^1 \\
749 := -1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 \\
750 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 8^3 \\
751 := 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 \\
752 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2 \\
753 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
754 := 0^8 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2 \\
755 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 \\
756 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
757 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
758 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
759 := 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3 & = 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3 \\
760 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 8^3 \\
761 := 1^8 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
762 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
763 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^9 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^3 \\
764 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
765 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 & = -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 \\
766 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
767 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1 \\
768 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
769 := 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 & = 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 \\
770 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^3 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 8^3 \\
771 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^5 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 8^3 \\
772 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
773 := 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
774 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 \\
775 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^2 & = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
776 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 \\
777 := 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 & = 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 \\
778 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 \\
779 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 8^3 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 \\
780 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
781 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 \\
782 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^2 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 \\
783 := 0^4 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^2 + 8^3 & = 1^5 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
784 := 0^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2 \\
785 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1 \\
786 := -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 & = -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 \\
787 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 9^1 \\
788 := 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 & = 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 \\
789 := 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^5 & = 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^5 \\
790 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 \\
791 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3 \\
792 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 \\
793 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3 \\
794 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 \\
795 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3 \\
796 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^0 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 \\
797 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 9^3 \\
798 := -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 & = -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 \\
799 := 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 \\
800 := 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 & = 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 \\
801 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
802 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 \\
803 := -0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
804 := 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 \\
805 := 0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
806 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 = -1^6 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 8^3 & 843 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
807 &:= 1^9 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 = 1^9 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 9^3 & 844 &:= -2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 = -2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
808 &:= 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 = 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & 845 &:= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 = 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 \\
809 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^4 & 846 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 \\
810 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 = -1^9 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 7^2 + 9^3 & 847 &:= -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 = -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 \\
811 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 & 848 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
812 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 & 849 &:= 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 = 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
813 &:= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 = -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 & 850 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 9^2 \\
814 &:= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 851 &:= -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
815 &:= 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 & 852 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
816 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 & 853 &:= 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
817 &:= -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 854 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
818 &:= -3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 855 &:= 0^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
819 &:= 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 856 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\
820 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^5 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 8^2 & 857 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
821 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 858 &:= -2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = -2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
822 &:= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 859 &:= -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 = -1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
823 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 860 &:= 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 = 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^4 \\
824 &:= 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^1 = 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^1 & 861 &:= 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 = 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
825 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 & 862 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^6 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
826 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 & 863 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
827 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 & 864 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
828 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 & 865 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^4 \\
829 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 & 866 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 = -2^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
830 &:= 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 = 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 & 867 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
831 &:= 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^2 = -1^9 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 6^2 + 9^3 & 868 &:= 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 = 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
832 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 & 869 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
833 &:= 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 = 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 & 870 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1 \\
834 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 8^3 & 871 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
835 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^2 = -1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 & 872 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^1 \\
836 &:= 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 = 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 & 873 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 = 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
837 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^2 = 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 & 874 &:= -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
838 &:= 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 7^3 - 9^1 = 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 7^3 - 9^1 & 875 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
839 &:= -2^8 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 = -2^8 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 876 &:= -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 \\
840 &:= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2 = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2 & 877 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 \\
841 &:= 0^7 + 3^5 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^3 = -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^2 & 878 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
842 &:= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2 = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^2 & 879 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 - 9^0 = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
880 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 917 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
881 &:= -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 918 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 \\
882 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 919 &:= -2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 = -2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 \\
883 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & 920 &:= 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^0 - 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 \\
884 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 & 921 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
885 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & 922 &:= 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 = 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
886 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 923 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
887 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & 924 &:= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
888 &:= -2^5 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 = -2^5 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 & 925 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 \\
889 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 926 &:= 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
890 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 927 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
891 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & 928 &:= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
892 &:= 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & 929 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
893 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^4 & 930 &:= -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
894 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^4 & 931 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
895 &:= -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 932 &:= 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
896 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 933 &:= 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 \\
897 &:= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 934 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^4 = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 \\
898 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 935 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 = -1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 \\
899 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 936 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
900 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -2^6 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^4 & 937 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 \\
901 &:= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 938 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 = 1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
902 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^9 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2 + 9^3 & 939 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 \\
903 &:= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 940 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
904 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^9 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 7^2 + 9^3 & 941 &:= -2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
905 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 942 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
906 &:= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 943 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 \\
907 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 944 &:= -0^0 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
908 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 = -2^7 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 & 945 &:= 3^6 + 6^3 = 3^6 + 6^3 \\
909 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 946 &:= 0^0 + 3^6 + 6^3 = 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
910 &:= -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & 947 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 \\
911 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 & 948 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
912 &:= 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 6^3 = 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 6^3 & 949 &:= 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
913 &:= -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 = -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 & 950 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 6^3 \\
914 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 & 951 &:= 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 = 1^5 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
915 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & 952 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
916 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 & 953 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 = 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 7^1
\end{aligned}$$

$954 := 1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$978 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$
$955 := 1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$979 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
$956 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$980 := 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	$= 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
$957 := 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	$981 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^3$
$958 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$	$982 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$959 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$983 := -2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$960 := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$= -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$984 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$961 := 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$985 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$962 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$	$986 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^0$	$= 2^8 + 3^5 - 5^2 + 8^3$
$963 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1$	$= -1^7 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 7^2$	$987 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$
$964 := -1^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1$	$988 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$965 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$989 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 9^3$
$966 := -1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$990 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$
$967 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$991 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1$
$968 := 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$992 := 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1$
$969 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$993 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1$
$970 := 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$994 := 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 9^3$	$= 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 9^3$
$971 := 0^9 + 3^5 - 5^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$995 := 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$= 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$
$972 := 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1$	$996 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$973 := 0^9 + 3^5 + 5^0 + 9^3$	$= 2^9 - 3^5 - 5^2 + 9^3$	$997 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$974 := -1^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4$	$= -1^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4$	$998 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$975 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$999 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$976 := -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	$1000 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$977 := 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3$		
$1001 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$= -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1013 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^2$
$1002 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$1014 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$1003 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$= 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1015 := 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$1004 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$1016 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^2$
$1005 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1017 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$1006 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$= -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2$	$1018 := -1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= -1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$
$1007 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1019 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1$
$1008 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$	$1020 := 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$
$1009 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$1021 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^1$	$= -2^8 + 3^6 + 6^2 + 8^3$
$1010 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2$	$1022 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1$
$1011 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1023 := 0^4 + 4^5 - 5^0$	$= 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^2 + 9^3$
$1012 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1$	$1024 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
1025 := 0^4 + 4^5 + 5^0 & = -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 & 1062 := 0^4 + 2^6 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 6^0 & = 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
1026 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^0 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1063 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1027 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1064 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1028 := -1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1065 := 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1029 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^2 & 1066 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1030 := 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1067 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1031 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1068 := -3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = -3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1032 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1069 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1033 := -2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1070 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 \\
1034 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1071 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 \\
1035 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1072 := 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1036 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 & 1073 := 0^7 + 3^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 \\
1037 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1074 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = 1^8 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^1 \\
1038 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1075 := 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
1039 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1076 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
1040 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^0 & = 1^6 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 & 1077 := -1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
1041 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^0 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1078 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
1042 := 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 & = 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 & 1079 := 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
1043 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1080 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 \\
1044 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1081 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
1045 := -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 & = -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 & 1082 := 1^6 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 & = 1^6 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^2 \\
1046 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1083 := 0^6 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
1047 := -0^0 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 & 1084 := 1^8 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & = 1^8 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
1048 := -4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 1085 := 0^6 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^3 & = 1^7 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^2 \\
1049 := 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 1086 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
1050 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1087 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
1051 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1088 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & = 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
1052 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^0 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1089 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 \\
1053 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1090 := -2^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -2^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
1054 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 1091 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1055 := -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1092 := 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1056 := -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^2 & 1093 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 \\
1057 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1094 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^1 \\
1058 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & = 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^2 & 1095 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 \\
1059 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1096 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^0 & = 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^2 \\
1060 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & 1097 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 \\
1061 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 & 1098 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 & = -1^8 + 2^4 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
1173 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 & 1210 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1174 := 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 & 1211 := 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 \\
1175 := -1^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 1212 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1176 := 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 & = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 & 1213 := -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 \\
1177 := 1^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 1214 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1178 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 6^4 & 1215 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1179 := 0^7 - 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 8^2 + 9^3 & 1216 := -2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 & = -2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1180 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 1217 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1181 := 0^7 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 8^2 + 9^3 & 1218 := -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2 \\
1182 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^1 & 1219 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2 \\
1183 := 0^7 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^1 & 1220 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1184 := 0^1 + 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 2^8 - 3^3 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 & 1221 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 & = -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1185 := 0^6 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 7^0 & = 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^1 & 1222 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1186 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 1223 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = 1^4 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^3 \\
1187 := -1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & 1224 := -2^7 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = -2^7 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
1188 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 6^4 & 1225 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1189 := 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & 1226 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1190 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 6^4 & 1227 := -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1191 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 3^0 - 7^2 + 9^3 & = -1^7 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & 1228 := -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 & = -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1192 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & 1229 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1193 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 3^0 - 7^2 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 1230 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 & = 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^3 \\
1194 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & 1231 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
1195 := 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 1232 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
1196 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1233 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 9^3 \\
1197 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1234 := -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 & = -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1198 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1235 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1199 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 & 1236 := 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 & = 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1200 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1237 := -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 \\
1201 := 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1238 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1202 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1239 := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 \\
1203 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 6^2 + 9^3 & 1240 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1204 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1241 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 9^3 & = 1^8 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
1205 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1242 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1206 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 & 1243 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 \\
1207 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 1244 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1208 := 0^5 - 2^6 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 & 1245 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 9^3 \\
1209 := 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 6^2 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 6^2 + 9^3 & 1246 := -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^6 + 6^1 + 8^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1321 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 6^4 &= -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
1322 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1323 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= 1^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
1324 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1325 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
1326 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1327 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 9^3 \\
1328 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1329 &:= -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^2 &= -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^2 \\
1330 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^2 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1331 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^0 &= -1^6 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
1332 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1333 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 + 9^0 &= -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
1334 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= -1^9 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
1335 &:= -1^8 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
1336 &:= 0^5 + 2^6 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1337 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 \\
1338 &:= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 \\
1339 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 9^3 \\
1340 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1341 &:= 0^6 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 &= -1^6 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
1342 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1343 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1344 &:= 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 &= 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1345 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1346 &:= 2^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 &= 2^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
1347 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
1348 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1349 &:= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1350 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1351 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
1352 &:= 0^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1353 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
1354 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1355 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1356 &:= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 &= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1357 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1358 &:= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1359 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 4^0 + 6^4 &= -2^2 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
1360 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1361 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
1362 &:= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1363 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1365 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1366 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1367 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1368 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1369 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
1370 &:= -2^8 + 3^7 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -2^8 + 3^7 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
1371 &:= -1^7 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1372 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 6^4 \\
1373 &:= 1^7 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1374 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1375 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1376 &:= 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1377 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1378 &:= 0^7 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1379 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1380 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 6^4 \\
1381 &:= -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1382 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1383 &:= 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1384 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1385 &:= -1^7 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1386 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^1 \\
1387 &:= 1^7 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^7 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
1388 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 6^4 &= -1^5 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
1389 &:= 2^7 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^3 &= 2^7 - 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^3 \\
1390 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1391 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
1392 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^0 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 6^4 \\
1393 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
1394 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 &= -1^7 - 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^5
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
1765 &:= 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 9^3 &1802 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 9^1 \\
1766 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^2 &1803 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^7 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
1767 &:= -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1804 &:= 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &= 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
1768 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1805 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 7^0 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
1769 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^1 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^1 &1806 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3 \\
1770 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1807 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
1771 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^1 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^1 &1808 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3 \\
1772 &:= 2^7 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= 2^7 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 7^4 &1809 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
1773 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 &1810 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1774 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 7^4 &= -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 7^4 &1811 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 \\
1775 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 &1812 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 &= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 \\
1776 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^0 &= 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^2 &1813 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 \\
1777 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^2 &= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^2 &1814 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1778 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^0 &= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 7^1 &1815 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
1779 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^0 - 7^3 &= 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^2 &1816 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 &= -2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
1780 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1817 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
1781 &:= -2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1818 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 - 7^3 \\
1782 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1819 &:= -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^3 &= -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^3 \\
1783 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^2 &= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^2 &1820 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 \\
1784 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 9^1 &1821 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &= 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1785 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 &1822 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 \\
1786 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &1823 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 \\
1787 &:= -2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &= -2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &1824 &:= -1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1788 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 &1825 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 \\
1789 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^0 &= 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 7^2 &1826 &:= 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1790 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 9^0 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 &1827 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 \\
1791 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 9^0 &= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 &1828 &:= 0^6 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1792 &:= -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 &1829 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 \\
1793 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 9^0 &= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^1 &1830 &:= 0^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
1794 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 &= -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 &1831 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 \\
1795 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1832 &:= -1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
1796 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 &= 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 7^1 &1833 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 \\
1797 &:= -1^6 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^6 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1834 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
1798 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 7^1 &= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 7^1 &1835 &:= -1^8 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
1799 &:= -0^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &= 1^6 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^4 &1836 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 &= 1^9 + 3^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
1800 &:= -3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &= -3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &1837 &:= -1^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 &= -1^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
1801 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &1838 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3 &= -1^5 + 3^7 - 5^1 - 7^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2281 &:= -2^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 &= -2^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2282 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
 2283 &:= 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2284 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 &= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2285 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2286 &:= 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 - 7^0 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
 2287 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 7^4 \\
 2288 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
 2289 &:= -2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
 2290 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
 2291 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
 2292 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2293 &:= -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
 2294 &:= 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 &= 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 \\
 2295 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 &= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 \\
 2296 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 \\
 2297 &:= 0^5 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^4 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2298 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2299 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2300 &:= 0^7 - 2^6 - 4^0 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2301 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2302 &:= 0^7 - 2^6 + 4^0 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2303 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2304 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 &= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2305 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^4 \\
 2306 &:= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 &= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2307 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
 2308 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2309 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2310 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^0 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2311 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^0 &= -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 2312 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
 2313 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 &= -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
 2314 &:= -1^6 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
 2315 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 \\
 2316 &:= 1^6 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
 2317 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2318 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 &= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
 2319 &:= 0^6 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2320 &:= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 &= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
 2321 &:= 0^6 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^3 \\
 2322 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
 2323 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= 3^6 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
 2324 &:= -1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
 2325 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2326 &:= 1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
 2327 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2328 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2329 &:= -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 &= -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
 2330 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
 2331 &:= 0^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2332 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^8 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 2333 &:= -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2334 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^8 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 2335 &:= 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2336 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
 2337 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2338 &:= 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -2^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 2339 &:= -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2340 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^8 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 2341 &:= 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2342 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2343 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 - 7^0 &= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2344 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
 2345 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2346 &:= -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2347 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2348 &:= -2^8 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 &= -2^8 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
 2349 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
 2350 &:= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
 2351 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 2352 &:= -2^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= -2^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 2353 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 2354 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 7^2 + 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 7^2 + 9^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$2503 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$	$2540 := 1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$
$2504 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$2541 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 7^4$
$2505 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^2$	$= -2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^2$	$2542 := -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$
$2506 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^3$	$2543 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 7^4$
$2507 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^4$	$2544 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2508 := 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^7 + 7^0 + 8^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^3$	$2545 := 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2509 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$2546 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2510 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$2547 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2511 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3$	$2548 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
$2512 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$2549 := -2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
$2513 := 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$2550 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
$2514 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$2551 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3$
$2515 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 7^4$	$2552 := -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$2516 := 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^3 + 7^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^3 + 7^2$	$2553 := 0^5 + 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 7^4$
$2517 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3$	$2554 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$2518 := 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$2555 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 7^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^1$
$2519 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3$	$2556 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$2520 := -1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 9^1$	$2557 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$
$2521 := -1^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$2558 := 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$
$2522 := 1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 - 9^1$	$2559 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^2$	$= -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^2$
$2523 := -1^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$	$2560 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^2$
$2524 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^4$	$2561 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 7^4$
$2525 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2562 := 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3$
$2526 := -2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2563 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3$
$2527 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2564 := 0^6 + 2^7 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^3$
$2528 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 8^4$	$2565 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$
$2529 := -0^0 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2566 := 0^6 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$
$2530 := 3^7 + 7^3$	$= 3^7 + 7^3$	$2567 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$
$2531 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2568 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$
$2532 := -2^9 + 5^5 - 9^2$	$= -2^9 + 5^5 - 9^2$	$2569 := 0^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$
$2533 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2570 := 1^6 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^4$
$2534 := 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2571 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2535 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 7^3$	$2572 := 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2536 := 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$2573 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 7^4$
$2537 := 1^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$2574 := 1^7 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^7 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^1$
$2538 := -1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$	$2575 := -2^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3$	$= -2^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3$
$2539 := 1^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^1$	$2576 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
2577 := -2^9 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^3 & = -2^9 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^3 & 2614 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2578 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^1 & 2615 := -1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
2579 := 0^7 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 2616 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
2580 := 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 2617 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
2581 := 0^7 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^4 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & 2618 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
2582 := 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^4 & 2619 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^0 - 9^2 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
2583 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2620 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
2584 := 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2621 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2585 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2622 := 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^4 & = 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
2586 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & 2623 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2587 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & 2624 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
2588 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & 2625 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
2589 := 0^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^3 - 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2626 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^1 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
2590 := 1^8 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 2627 := -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^2 & = -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
2591 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^3 - 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2628 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^0 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
2592 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 2629 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
2593 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 6^0 + 7^3 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 & 2630 := 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
2594 := 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 & = 3^6 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 6^3 & 2631 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
2595 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2632 := 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2596 := 0^4 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 & 2633 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
2597 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2634 := 1^7 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^7 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
2598 := 0^4 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^0 & = 1^8 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 2635 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 \\
2599 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 2636 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
2600 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 2637 := -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 & = -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2601 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2638 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 - 8^4 & = 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 - 8^4 \\
2602 := 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 2639 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2603 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 & 2640 := 0^7 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 7^2 - 9^1 \\
2604 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 2641 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^0 & = 1^6 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\
2605 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 & 2642 := 0^7 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 7^2 - 9^1 \\
2606 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 2643 := 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^2 & = 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
2607 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 2644 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
2608 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 2645 := -2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
2609 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 2646 := 0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
2610 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 9^2 & 2647 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^2 + 8^3 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^2 + 8^3 \\
2611 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 2648 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\
2612 := -3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = -3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 2649 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 7^2 + 8^3 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 7^2 + 8^3 \\
2613 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = 1^1 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 2650 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2725 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2726 &:= 1^7 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 = 1^7 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
 2727 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2728 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^3 \\
 2729 &:= -2^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^3 = -2^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^3 \\
 2730 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^3 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
 2731 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 - 7^2 = 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
 2732 &:= -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 = -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
 2733 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^2 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
 2734 &:= 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 = 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
 2735 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 = 1^2 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
 2736 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
 2737 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
 2738 &:= 0^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 7^3 = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^2 - 9^1 \\
 2739 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
 2740 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^0 = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^2 - 9^1 \\
 2741 &:= -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 7^5 - 9^1 = -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 7^5 - 9^1 \\
 2742 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 \\
 2743 &:= -2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 = -2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 \\
 2744 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 \\
 2745 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 2746 &:= 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 = 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
 2747 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 2748 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
 2749 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 2750 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
 2751 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 2752 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
 2753 &:= 0^9 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2754 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
 2755 &:= 0^9 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^4 + 9^3 = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2756 &:= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 9^1 = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 9^1 \\
 2757 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 = -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
 2758 &:= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 9^1 = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 7^2 + 9^1 \\
 2759 &:= 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 = 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
 2760 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 9^3 = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^3 \\
 2761 &:= 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 7^5 + 9^1 = 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 7^5 + 9^1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2762 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2763 &:= -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
 2764 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2765 &:= -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
 2766 &:= 1^7 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 = 1^7 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
 2767 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^4 = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2768 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2769 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2770 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2771 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 2772 &:= -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2773 &:= -3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2774 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2775 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2776 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2777 &:= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2778 &:= -1^7 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -1^7 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
 2779 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
 2780 &:= 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
 2781 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 \\
 2782 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 = -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 \\
 2783 &:= 0^7 + 3^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2784 &:= -1^7 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -1^7 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
 2785 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 = -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 \\
 2786 &:= 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 = 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 \\
 2787 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 = 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 \\
 2788 &:= -2^9 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 9^2 = -2^9 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 9^2 \\
 2789 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 7^3 \\
 2790 &:= -1^9 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 = -1^9 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
 2791 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 = -1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
 2792 &:= -1^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
 2793 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
 2794 &:= -1^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 = -1^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 \\
 2795 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2796 &:= -2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 = -2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2797 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2798 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 = 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2799 &:= -0^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= -1^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2800 &:= 4^6 - 6^4 &= 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2801 &:= 0^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2802 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2803 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2804 &:= 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2805 &:= -2^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= -2^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
 2806 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
 2807 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
 2808 &:= 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
 2809 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
 2810 &:= 1^9 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
 2811 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 &= -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
 2812 &:= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2813 &:= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
 2814 &:= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
 2815 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 - 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 &= 1^9 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^1 \\
 2816 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2817 &:= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2818 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2819 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 &= 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 2820 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^2 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
 2821 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
 2822 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2823 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2824 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2825 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2826 &:= -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2827 &:= 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2828 &:= 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2829 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^7 + 2^9 - 4^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
 2830 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2831 &:= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 &= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^4 \\
 2832 &:= -2^8 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= -2^8 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
 2833 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
 2834 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
 2835 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2836 &:= -2^6 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= -2^6 - 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2837 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2838 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2839 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2840 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
 2841 &:= -0^0 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^1 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2842 &:= -3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2843 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^1 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2844 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^4 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
 2845 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2846 &:= 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2847 &:= 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^4 &= 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
 2848 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
 2849 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2850 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
 2851 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2852 &:= -2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2853 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2854 &:= -2^6 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= -2^6 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2855 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
 2856 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 \\
 2857 &:= 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 &= 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 \\
 2858 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 9^1 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 \\
 2859 &:= -1^9 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 9^1 &= -1^9 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\
 2860 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
 2861 &:= -1^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 &= -1^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
 2862 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
 2863 &:= 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 &= 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
 2864 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2865 &:= -2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2866 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^1 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2867 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^3 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2868 &:= -0^0 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2869 &:= -4^4 + 5^5 &= -4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2870 &:= 0^0 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2871 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= -1^3 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^5 \\
 2872 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^5 &= 1^2 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^5
 \end{aligned}$$

3093 := $-2^4 - 4^2 + 5^5$	= $-2^4 - 4^2 + 5^5$	3130 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 2^2 + 5^5$
3094 := $-2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3131 := $-1^7 + 5^5 + 7^1$	= $-1^7 + 5^5 + 7^1$
3095 := $0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3132 := $1^6 + 5^5 + 6^1$	= $1^6 + 5^5 + 6^1$
3096 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 - 2^6 + 5^5 + 6^2$	3133 := $1^7 + 5^5 + 7^1$	= $1^7 + 5^5 + 7^1$
3097 := $-0^0 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3134 := $1^8 + 5^5 + 8^1$	= $1^8 + 5^5 + 8^1$
3098 := $-3^3 + 5^5$	= $-3^3 + 5^5$	3135 := $1^9 + 5^5 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 5^5 + 9^1$
3099 := $0^0 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^1 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3136 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 5^5 + 9^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^5$
3100 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 7^1$	3137 := $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^5$	= $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^5$
3101 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3138 := $-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3102 := $2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3139 := $1^9 + 2^2 + 5^5 + 9^1$	= $1^9 + 2^2 + 5^5 + 9^1$
3103 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^5$	3140 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^5$	= $1^4 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3104 := $-1^2 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^5$	= $-1^2 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^5$	3141 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5$
3105 := $1^6 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 6^1$	= $1^6 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 6^1$	3142 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5$	= $2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5$
3106 := $1^2 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^5$	= $1^2 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^5$	3143 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5$
3107 := $-0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^5$	3144 := $1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5$	= $1^4 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3108 := $-2^3 - 3^2 + 5^5$	= $-2^3 - 3^2 + 5^5$	3145 := $-1^6 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 6^1$	= $-1^6 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 6^1$
3109 := $0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^5$	= $1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^5$	3146 := $1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^5$	= $1^2 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^5$
3110 := $0^2 - 2^4 + 4^0 + 5^5$	= $-1^4 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5$	3147 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3111 := $-1^9 - 2^2 + 5^5 - 9^1$	= $-1^9 - 2^2 + 5^5 - 9^1$	3148 := $-2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3112 := $-1^2 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^5$	= $-1^2 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^5$	3149 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3113 := $-1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^5$	= $-1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^5$	3150 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^7 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 7^1$
3114 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 5^5 - 9^1$	= $1^2 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^5$	3151 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3115 := $-1^9 + 5^5 - 9^1$	= $-1^9 + 5^5 - 9^1$	3152 := $3^3 + 5^5$	= $3^3 + 5^5$
3116 := $-1^8 + 5^5 - 8^1$	= $-1^8 + 5^5 - 8^1$	3153 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3117 := $-1^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$	= $-1^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$	3154 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 2^6 + 5^5 - 6^2$
3118 := $-1^6 + 5^5 - 6^1$	= $-1^6 + 5^5 - 6^1$	3155 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3119 := $1^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$	= $1^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$	3156 := $2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$	= $2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5$
3120 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 - 2^2 + 5^5$	3157 := $2^4 + 4^2 + 5^5$	= $2^4 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3121 := $-2^2 + 5^5$	= $-2^2 + 5^5$	3158 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3122 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 5^5$	= $1^1 - 2^2 + 5^5$	3159 := $1^6 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 6^1$	= $1^6 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 6^1$
3123 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 5^5$	= $1^3 - 3^1 + 5^5$	3160 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 5^5 + 6^2$	= $1^6 - 2^1 + 5^5 + 6^2$
3124 := $-0^0 + 5^5$	= $-1^1 + 5^5$	3161 := $1^8 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 8^1$	= $1^8 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 8^1$
3125 := $-0^0 + 1^1 + 5^5$	= $-2^4 + 4^2 + 5^5$	3162 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 5^5 + 6^2$	= $-1^6 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 6^2$
3126 := $0^0 + 5^5$	= $1^1 + 5^5$	3163 := $0^1 + 1^6 + 2^0 + 5^5 + 6^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5$
3127 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 5^5$	= $-1^3 + 3^1 + 5^5$	3164 := $1^6 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 6^2$	= $1^6 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 6^2$
3128 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 5^5$	= $1^2 + 2^1 + 5^5$	3165 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 5^5 + 6^2$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5$
3129 := $2^2 + 5^5$	= $2^2 + 5^5$	3166 := $0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^3$	= $1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1$

$$\begin{array}{l} 3611 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^0 = -1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\ 3612 := 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 = 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\ 3613 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^4 = 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\ 3614 := 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^4 = 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^4 \\ 3615 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^4 = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^4 \\ 3616 := -2^3 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 = -2^3 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3617 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3618 := -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3619 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^0 = 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\ 3620 := 0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^0 = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3621 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^0 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3622 := 0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^0 = -2^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\ 3623 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^0 = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3624 := -2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\ 3625 := -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 = -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 3626 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 = -2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\ 3627 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\ 3628 := -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\ 3629 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 \\ 3630 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^1 = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\ 3631 := 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 = 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 3632 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^1 \\ 3633 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 = -1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 3634 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = -2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\ 3635 := 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 = 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 3636 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 - 9^0 = 3^4 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\ 3637 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = -1^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\ 3638 := 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\ 3639 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\ 3640 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3641 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 = 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 3642 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\ 3643 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\ 3644 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 3645 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3646 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\ 3647 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3648 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 9^1 = 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\ 3649 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^4 - 8^3 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\ 3650 := -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^1 = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\ 3651 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^0 = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\ 3652 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^0 = -1^4 - 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3653 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^0 = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\ 3654 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3655 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3656 := 0^4 + 2^0 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3657 := -1^4 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 = -1^4 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3658 := 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 = 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3659 := 1^4 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 = 1^4 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3660 := 1^2 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 = 1^2 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3661 := -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 = -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3662 := 1^8 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 = 1^8 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\ 3663 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 - 9^0 = 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3664 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 = -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 \\ 3665 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^0 = 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\ 3666 := 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 = 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\ 3667 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 = 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\ 3668 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 = -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3669 := 1^8 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^5 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^5 + 8^4 \\ 3670 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 = 1^2 - 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3671 := 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 = 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\ 3672 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^5 + 9^1 \\ 3673 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 = 2^9 - 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\ 3674 := -1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 = -1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3675 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 = 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\ 3676 := 1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 = 1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3677 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 = -1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\ 3678 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 = -1^4 + 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3679 := 0^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 = 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\ 3680 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 = -1^4 - 2^2 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3681 := 0^4 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 = -1^6 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\ 3682 := 0^1 + 1^4 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 = 1^4 - 2^2 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\ 3683 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 = 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\ 3684 := -1^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 = -1^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
4053 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 4090 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4054 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 & 4091 := 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\
4055 := 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 4092 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4056 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4093 := 1^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4057 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4094 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = -3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4058 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 & 4095 := 0^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\
4059 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4096 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4060 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 & 4097 := 0^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4061 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4098 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
4062 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & 4099 := -1^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4063 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4100 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4064 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & 4101 := -1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4065 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 4102 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4066 := 1^8 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 8^4 & 4103 := 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4067 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 4104 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4068 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & 4105 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4069 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 4106 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4070 := 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 4107 := 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4071 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 & 4108 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4072 := -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 & 4109 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4073 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & 4110 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4074 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4111 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4075 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4112 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4076 := 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4113 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4077 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & 4114 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4078 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4115 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4079 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 4116 := -2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 & = -2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4080 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4117 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4081 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 4118 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 \\
4082 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 & 4119 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4083 := 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 4120 := 1^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4084 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4121 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 & = 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4085 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4122 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 & = 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 \\
4086 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4123 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
4087 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 & 4124 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 \\
4088 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 & 4125 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
4089 := -1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & = -1^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 & 4126 := -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
4349 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4350 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4351 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
4352 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4353 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4354 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4355 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4356 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4357 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4358 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4359 := 0^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4360 := 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4361 := -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4362 := 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4363 := 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4364 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4365 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 5^5 + 9^3 & = 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
4366 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4367 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4368 := 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4369 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4370 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4371 := 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^8 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4372 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4373 := -2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = -2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4374 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4375 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\
4376 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4377 := 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4378 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 8^4 & = 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
4379 := -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
4380 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4381 := 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
4382 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4383 := -1^6 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4384 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
4385 := 1^6 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4386 := 1^8 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^8 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
4387 := 0^6 + 2^8 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4388 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4389 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4390 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4391 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4392 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4393 := 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4394 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4395 := 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
4396 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4397 := 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4398 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 \\
4399 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 & = 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4400 := 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 & = 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 \\
4401 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 \\
4402 := 0^7 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4403 := 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^1 \\
4404 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4405 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4406 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4407 := 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4408 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4409 := -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
4410 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4411 := 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
4412 := -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4413 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4414 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4415 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = -2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4416 := -1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = -1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4417 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 \\
4418 := 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4419 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 \\
4420 := 0^6 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4421 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
4422 := 0^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4423 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
4424 &:= -1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4425 &:= 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 8^4 \\
4426 &:= 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4427 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4428 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4429 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4430 &:= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4431 &:= 2^9 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\
4432 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^2 &= 1^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
4433 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4434 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^2 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4435 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4436 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4437 &:= 0^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^0 + 9^4 &= -1^5 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4438 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4439 &:= 0^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^0 + 9^4 &= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4440 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4441 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4442 &:= 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4443 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4444 &:= -1^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
4445 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4446 &:= -0^0 - 3^9 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
4447 &:= -3^9 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -3^9 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
4448 &:= 0^0 - 3^9 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^1 - 3^9 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
4449 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4450 &:= 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 &= 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 \\
4451 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4452 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 7^4 &= 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4453 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4454 &:= 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4455 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4456 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4457 &:= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 &= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 \\
4458 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4459 &:= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 &= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4460 &:= 1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= 1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4461 &:= 1^8 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4462 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4463 &:= 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 &= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\
4464 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4465 &:= 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4466 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4467 &:= -1^8 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4468 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4469 &:= 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4470 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4471 &:= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 &= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
4472 &:= 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 &= 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
4473 &:= 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4474 &:= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4475 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 \\
4476 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 &= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4477 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4478 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 &= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4479 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 &= 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4480 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4481 &:= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4482 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4483 &:= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4484 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 \\
4485 &:= 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4486 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4487 &:= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4488 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4489 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4490 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4491 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4492 &:= 0^5 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4493 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4494 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
4495 &:= -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
4496 &:= 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4497 &:= 2^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= 2^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
4498 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^4 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4499 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4500 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4501 &:= 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4502 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4503 &:= 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4504 &:= 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
4505 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4506 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4507 &:= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4508 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= 1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
4509 &:= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4510 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 &= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4511 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4512 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4513 &:= -1^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= -1^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
4514 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
4515 &:= 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
4516 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 &= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
4517 &:= -1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 &= -1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
4518 &:= 0^8 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 &= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4519 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4520 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4521 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4522 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
4523 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4524 &:= 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4525 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4526 &:= -3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 &= -3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4527 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4528 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4529 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 \\
4530 &:= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 &= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 \\
4531 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
4532 &:= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
4533 &:= 1^8 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4534 &:= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
4535 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4536 &:= 3^8 - 4^9 - 6^4 + 8^6 - 9^3 &= 3^8 - 4^9 - 6^4 + 8^6 - 9^3 \\
4537 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^2 &= 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4538 &:= -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^2 \\
4539 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4540 &:= 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4541 &:= -2^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 &= -2^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4542 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4543 &:= 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4544 &:= 0^4 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^0 &= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4545 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4546 &:= 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 &= 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 \\
4547 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 &= 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4548 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 &= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4549 &:= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 &= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4550 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4551 &:= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 &= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4552 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= -2^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
4553 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^3 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4554 &:= 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^3 &= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
4555 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 &= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4556 &:= 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 &= 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4557 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4558 &:= 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
4559 &:= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 &= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4560 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
4561 &:= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 &= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4562 &:= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 &= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 \\
4563 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4564 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4565 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4566 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4567 &:= 0^9 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 \\
4568 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4569 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4570 &:= 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 &= 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4571 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &4608 &:= 0^8 + 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4572 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^6 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 &4609 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= 1^4 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 \\
4573 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &4610 &:= 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4574 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^4 &4611 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4575 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &4612 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4576 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^3 &4613 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 \\
4577 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &4614 &:= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 &= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 \\
4578 &:= 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^3 &4615 &:= -0^0 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= -1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
4579 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &4616 &:= -4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= -4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
4580 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &= 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &4617 &:= 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
4581 &:= 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 &4618 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^4 \\
4582 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 &4619 &:= 0^2 + 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
4583 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &4620 &:= 2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
4584 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^8 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 &4621 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^4 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
4585 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &4622 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^0 &= 1^8 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4586 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 &= 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3 &4623 &:= 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^0 &= -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4587 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4624 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -2^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
4588 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 &= -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^3 &4625 &:= 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^0 &= 2^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
4589 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4626 &:= -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4590 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 &= 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^3 &4627 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4591 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4628 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4592 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^4 &4629 &:= 0^8 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
4593 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4630 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 9^3 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4594 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^4 &4631 &:= 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 9^3 \\
4595 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4632 &:= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 &= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
4596 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &4633 &:= -2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= -2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4597 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4634 &:= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 &= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\
4598 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^4 &4635 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4599 &:= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4636 &:= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 &= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\
4600 &:= -1^8 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 &= -1^8 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 &4637 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
4601 &:= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 &4638 &:= 0^8 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= -1^8 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4602 &:= 1^8 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 &= 1^8 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 &4639 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
4603 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &4640 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
4604 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 &4641 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 &= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
4605 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &4642 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
4606 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 &4643 &:= 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^0 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
4607 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 &4644 &:= 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 &= 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4645 &:= 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^0 &= -1^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 4682 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4646 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^4 & 4683 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4647 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4684 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4648 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4685 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4649 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4686 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4650 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 4687 &:= -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4651 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4688 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4652 &:= 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4689 &:= 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4653 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4690 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 &= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4654 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 & 4691 &:= 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 &= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4655 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4692 &:= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 &= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
4656 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4693 &:= -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4657 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 & 4694 &:= -3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= -3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4658 &:= 1^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 4695 &:= 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4659 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 7^4 & 4696 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4660 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^1 & 4697 &:= -2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 &= -2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4661 &:= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 & 4698 &:= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4662 &:= 0^9 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^1 & 4699 &:= -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4663 &:= 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 9^2 & 4700 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4664 &:= 0^9 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 & 4701 &:= 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4665 &:= -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 & 4702 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 &= -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
4666 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 & 4703 &:= -3^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -3^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
4667 &:= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 & 4704 &:= 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4668 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 4705 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4669 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 4706 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4670 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 4707 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 &= 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4671 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3 & 4708 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4672 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 & 4709 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 &= 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
4673 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 & 4710 &:= -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4674 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 4711 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4675 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 4712 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 7^4 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4676 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 4713 &:= 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4677 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 4714 &:= -1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4678 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 4715 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4679 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 & 4716 &:= 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4680 &:= -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 & 4717 &:= 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 &= 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4681 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 & 4718 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
4719 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 & = -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4720 := 0^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4721 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4722 := 0^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4723 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4724 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4725 := -2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = -2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4726 := -1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = -1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4727 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4728 := 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4729 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4730 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4731 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4732 := 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4733 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4734 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4735 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4736 := 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4737 := -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4738 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4739 := 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4740 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4741 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4742 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4743 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^3 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4744 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 & = 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4745 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^3 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4746 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4747 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4748 := 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 & = 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4749 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 \\
4750 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4751 := 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4752 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 & = -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4753 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4754 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4755 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4756 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4757 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4758 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4759 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4760 := 0^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4761 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
4762 := 0^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4763 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4764 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4765 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
4766 := -1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4767 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4768 := 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4769 := -2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
4770 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4771 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4772 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
4773 := 2^9 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
4774 := -2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
4775 := -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4776 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4777 := -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
4778 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4779 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4780 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4781 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4782 := 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4783 := 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 & = 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4784 := 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
4785 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4786 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^3 & = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4787 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4788 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4789 := 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4790 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4791 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 & = -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4792 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4793 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4794 &:= 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 = 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4795 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4796 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4797 &:= 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
4798 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
4799 &:= -2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 = -2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
4800 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
4801 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 8^3 = 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4802 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
4803 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4804 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
4805 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4806 &:= -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 = -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
4807 &:= -1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 = -1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4808 &:= 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 = 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
4809 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4810 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4811 &:= 3^4 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^3 = 3^4 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
4812 &:= -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4813 &:= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4 = -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
4814 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4815 &:= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4 = 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
4816 &:= 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 = 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4817 &:= 0^3 - 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4818 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 - 7^4 = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
4819 &:= 0^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 - 7^4 = 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
4820 &:= 0^4 - 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
4821 &:= 0^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 - 7^4 = -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\
4822 &:= 0^4 - 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^3 = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4823 &:= 0^3 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4824 &:= 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^2 = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^2 \\
4825 &:= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 = -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 \\
4826 &:= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 = -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
4827 &:= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 = 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 \\
4828 &:= -2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 = -2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
4829 &:= 0^3 - 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4830 &:= 0^4 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^3 = -1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
4831 &:= 0^3 + 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^0 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4832 &:= 0^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^4 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
4833 &:= 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 = 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4834 &:= 0^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4835 &:= 0^9 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 9^2 = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4836 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 = -2^5 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
4837 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4838 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4839 &:= -2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4840 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4841 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4842 &:= -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4843 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4844 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 = 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
4845 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
4846 &:= 0^9 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
4847 &:= -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4848 &:= 0^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^0 + 8^4 = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4849 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 = 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
4850 &:= 0^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4851 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4852 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4853 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4854 &:= 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4855 &:= 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 = 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4856 &:= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^2 = 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
4857 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
4858 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4859 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4860 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4861 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4862 &:= -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4863 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4864 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4865 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4866 &:= -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4867 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4868 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4869 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^3 = -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
4870 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4871 &:= 2^9 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 = 2^9 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 \\
4872 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
4873 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4874 &:= 0^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4875 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 = 1^9 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
4876 &:= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 = -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4877 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4878 &:= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
4879 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^0 = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
4880 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^0 = 1^4 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
4881 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^0 = 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
4882 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4883 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
4884 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4885 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4886 &:= 0^8 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^0 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4887 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4888 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4889 &:= -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4890 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4891 &:= -2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4892 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4893 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4894 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4895 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4896 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4897 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4898 &:= 2^9 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 = 2^9 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
4899 &:= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 = -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4900 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
4901 &:= 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4902 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^1 = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4903 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^1 = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4904 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^1 = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4905 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^3 = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^1 \\
4906 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^1 = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
4907 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^3 = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4908 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4909 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 = -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4910 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^0 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
4911 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^0 = -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4912 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
4913 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^0 = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^3 \\
4914 &:= -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4915 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4916 &:= -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4917 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
4918 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 = -1^5 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 - 8^2 \\
4919 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
4920 &:= -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 = -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4921 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
4922 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4923 &:= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
4924 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4925 &:= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4926 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4927 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4928 &:= 0^7 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 - 9^0 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
4929 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4930 &:= -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
4931 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4932 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 \\
4933 &:= -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4934 &:= -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
4935 &:= 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4936 &:= 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 \\
4937 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4938 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4939 &:= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4940 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4941 &:= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4942 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
4943 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4944 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
4945 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4946 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
4947 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4948 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^0 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4949 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^0 + 9^4 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
4950 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^0 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4951 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^0 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4952 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4953 &:= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4954 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4955 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
4956 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4957 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4958 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4959 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 &= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 \\
4960 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
4961 &:= -2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
4962 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
4963 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 \\
4964 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4965 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4966 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4967 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
4968 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4969 &:= 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4970 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4971 &:= 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 &= 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5001 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5002 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5003 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
5004 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^3 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5005 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
5006 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
4972 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4973 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4974 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4975 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 &= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
4976 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
4977 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
4978 &:= 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
4979 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
4980 &:= -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4981 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
4982 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4983 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^2 &= -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
4984 &:= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^2 &= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
4985 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^0 &= -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4986 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 7^0 &= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^2 \\
4987 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^0 &= 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4988 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^0 &= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
4989 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^0 &= 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4990 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
4991 &:= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4992 &:= -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 &= -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
4993 &:= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4994 &:= 0^8 - 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
4995 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
4996 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
4997 &:= -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4998 &:= -2^8 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= -2^8 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
4999 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5000 &:= -2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= -2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5007 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
5008 &:= 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 &= 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
5009 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 \\
5010 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 8^3 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5011 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
5012 &:= 0^5 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 - 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5013 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5014 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5015 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5016 &:= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 8^3 = 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 8^3 \\
5017 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 8^3 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 8^3 \\
5018 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^7 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
5019 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5020 &:= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5021 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5022 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5023 &:= -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5024 &:= -3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = -3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5025 &:= 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5026 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5027 &:= -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5028 &:= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5029 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5030 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5031 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5032 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
5033 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 8^3 = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5034 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 8^3 = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
5035 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5036 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
5037 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5038 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
5039 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5040 &:= 0^8 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5041 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5042 &:= 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -2^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
5043 &:= 0^1 + 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5044 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
5045 &:= -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5046 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
5047 &:= 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5048 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5049 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5050 &:= -2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5051 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5052 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5053 &:= 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5054 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^0 = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5055 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^0 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5056 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^0 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5057 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^0 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5058 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5059 &:= 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^3 = 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
5060 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
5061 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5062 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 = -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5063 &:= -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 = -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5064 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 = 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5065 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 = -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5066 &:= 0^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 = 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
5067 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^8 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5068 &:= 0^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5069 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^3 = 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
5070 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5071 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5072 &:= -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 = -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5073 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5074 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
5075 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 = -1^9 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 \\
5076 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5077 &:= -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5078 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5079 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 9^4 = 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5080 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
5081 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 = -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
5082 &:= -2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5083 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^2 = 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
5084 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
5085 &:= -0^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5086 &:= 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5087 &:= 0^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5088 &:= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^1 &= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
5089 &:= 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5090 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^1 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
5091 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5092 &:= 0^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5093 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5094 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5095 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^0 &= -1^8 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
5096 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5097 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^0 &= -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5098 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5099 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5100 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5101 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5102 &:= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^1 &= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
5103 &:= -1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
5104 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^1 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
5105 &:= 1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
5106 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5107 &:= -1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5108 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5109 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
5110 &:= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5111 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^2 &= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
5112 &:= 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5113 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5114 &:= -1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5115 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5116 &:= 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5117 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\
5118 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5119 &:= 0^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5120 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5121 &:= 0^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5122 &:= 0^1 + 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5123 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5124 &:= -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5125 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5126 &:= 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5127 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5128 &:= -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5129 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5130 &:= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5131 &:= 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
5132 &:= 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 &= 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5133 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5134 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^0 &= -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5135 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^0 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5136 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5137 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5138 &:= 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 &= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
5139 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5140 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5141 &:= -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5142 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5143 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5144 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5145 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5146 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5147 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5148 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5149 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5150 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
5151 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5152 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5153 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5154 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5155 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5156 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5157 &:= -2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5158 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5159 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5160 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5161 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 = 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
5162 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^0 = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
5163 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 9^0 = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5164 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 = -1^8 + 2^6 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
5165 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5166 &:= -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 = -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5167 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5168 &:= 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5169 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5170 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5171 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5172 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5173 &:= -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5174 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5175 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5176 &:= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5177 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5178 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5179 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5180 &:= 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5181 &:= 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5182 &:= 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 = 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5183 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5184 &:= 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5185 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 \\
5186 &:= 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5187 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
5188 &:= -2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5189 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5190 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5191 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
5192 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5193 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 = -1^8 + 2^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
5194 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5195 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^8 + 2^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
5196 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^0 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5197 &:= -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 = -1^1 - 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5198 &:= -3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 = -3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
5199 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5200 &:= -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5201 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5202 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^0 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5203 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^0 = -1^8 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
5204 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^0 = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5205 &:= 0^7 - 2^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 - 8^2 = -1^5 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 9^1 \\
5206 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^0 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5207 &:= -2^6 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 = -2^6 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5208 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5209 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 = 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
5210 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5211 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5212 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5213 &:= -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5214 &:= 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5215 &:= -2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5216 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5217 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5218 &:= 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5219 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
5220 &:= 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
5221 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5222 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5223 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^2 \\
5224 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5225 &:= 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5226 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5227 &:= -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5228 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5229 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5230 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
5231 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^0 = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5232 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^4 = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5233 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^0 = 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5234 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5235 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 = 1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5272 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5236 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 & 5273 &:= -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5237 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5274 &:= -3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = -3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5238 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 5275 &:= 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5239 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5276 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5240 &:= -1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 & 5277 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5241 &:= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 = -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5278 &:= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5242 &:= 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 & 5279 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5243 &:= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5280 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5244 &:= 0^8 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 = -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5281 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 = -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5245 &:= 0^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 = 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 9^2 & 5282 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5246 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 = -3^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 + 9^4 & 5283 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 - 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^2 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5247 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^0 = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5284 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
5248 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^0 = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^1 & 5285 &:= 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 = 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5249 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^0 = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5286 &:= -2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5250 &:= -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 = -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 5287 &:= 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 = 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
5251 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5288 &:= 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 8^0 = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5252 &:= 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 = 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 5289 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 = 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
5253 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 5290 &:= 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5254 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5291 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5255 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5292 &:= 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
5256 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 & 5293 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
5257 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 & 5294 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^0 - 9^3 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5258 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 5295 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5259 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5296 &:= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5260 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5297 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5261 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5298 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5262 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5299 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
5263 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5300 &:= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5264 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5301 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5265 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5302 &:= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5266 &:= 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5303 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5267 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5304 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5268 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5305 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
5269 &:= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 & 5306 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5270 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5307 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
5271 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 = 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 5308 &:= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
5309 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5310 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5311 := 0^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5312 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5313 := 0^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = -2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5314 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5315 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
5316 := 0^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 9^3 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5317 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
5318 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5319 := -3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 & = -3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5320 := 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5321 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
5322 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5323 := 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 & = 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5324 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5325 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5326 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5327 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5328 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5329 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5330 := 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
5331 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5332 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
5333 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5334 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5335 := -2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 & = -2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5336 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5337 := 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
5338 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5339 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5340 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5341 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5342 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5343 := -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5344 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5345 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5346 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5347 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5348 := -2^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
5349 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5350 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5351 := 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
5352 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5353 := -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5354 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5355 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
5356 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5357 := -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5358 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5359 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5360 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5361 := -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5362 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5363 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5364 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5365 := -3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5366 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5367 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5368 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5369 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5370 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5371 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 & = 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5372 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
5373 := 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
5374 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5375 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5376 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5377 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5378 := -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
5379 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5380 := -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5381 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5382 := -1^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5383 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5384 &:= -1^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5385 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5386 &:= -1^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5387 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5388 &:= -2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5389 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5390 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5391 &:= -0^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5392 &:= 4^6 + 6^4 &= 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5393 &:= 0^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5394 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5395 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5396 &:= 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5397 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5398 &:= 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5399 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5400 &:= 1^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
5401 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5402 &:= 1^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 \\
5403 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5404 &:= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5405 &:= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5406 &:= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 \\
5407 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5408 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5409 &:= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5410 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5411 &:= 0^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^0 &= -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5412 &:= 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5413 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5414 &:= -2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5415 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5416 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5417 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5418 &:= -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5419 &:= 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5420 &:= 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5421 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
5422 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5423 &:= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 &= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 \\
5424 &:= 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &= 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 \\
5425 &:= 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5426 &:= -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5427 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^3 &= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^3 \\
5428 &:= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5429 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^3 &= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^3 \\
5430 &:= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5431 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^3 \\
5432 &:= 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5433 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^3 \\
5434 &:= 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
5435 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
5436 &:= 0^9 - 2^6 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 6^2 + 9^4 &= 1^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
5437 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5438 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5439 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 \\
5440 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5441 &:= 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 &= 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
5442 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5443 &:= -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 &= -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
5444 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5445 &:= 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
5446 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^8 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5447 &:= 0^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5448 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5449 &:= 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 &= 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5450 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5451 &:= -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 &= -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
5452 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5453 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 &= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5454 &:= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
5455 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
5456 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5457 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
5458 &:= -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5459 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 &= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5460 &:= 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5461 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
5462 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5463 &:= 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
5464 &:= -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5465 &:= 0^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5466 &:= 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5467 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5468 &:= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5469 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 8^2 \\
5470 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5471 &:= 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 &= 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5472 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5473 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
5474 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
5475 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5476 &:= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
5477 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5478 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^2 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
5479 &:= 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
5480 &:= -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^3 \\
5481 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^3 &= -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5482 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5483 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5484 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5485 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 8^2 \\
5486 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5487 &:= 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5488 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5489 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5490 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5491 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 &= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5492 &:= 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
5493 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5494 &:= -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5495 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5496 &:= 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5497 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
5498 &:= 0^7 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5499 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
5500 &:= 0^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5501 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
5502 &:= -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5503 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
5504 &:= 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5505 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5506 &:= 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5507 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5508 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5509 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5510 &:= 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 &= 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5511 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5512 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5513 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5514 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5515 &:= 1^9 + 2^1 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 2^1 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5516 &:= 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 &= 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5517 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5518 &:= 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 &= 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5519 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^0 &= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5520 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
5521 &:= -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5522 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
5523 &:= 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5524 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5525 &:= 0^7 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5526 &:= 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^4 &= 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5527 &:= 0^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
5528 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
5529 &:= -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5530 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
5531 := 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5532 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5533 := 1^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5534 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
5535 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5536 := 0^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
5537 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5538 := 0^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5539 := 0^1 + 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5540 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5541 := -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5542 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5543 := 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5544 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5545 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
5546 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5547 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
5548 := -1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5549 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^8 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
5550 := 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5551 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5552 := 0^7 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -2^9 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
5553 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5554 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5555 := -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 & = -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
5556 := -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5557 := 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5558 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5559 := -1^9 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5560 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5561 := 0^9 - 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5562 := 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5563 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5564 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
5565 := 0^9 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5566 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5567 := 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5568 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5569 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5570 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5571 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 8^1 \\
5572 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5573 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5574 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5575 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^0 - 9^3 & = -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
5576 := 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5577 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^0 - 9^3 & = 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
5578 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 9^3 \\
5579 := -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
5580 := 0^3 - 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
5581 := 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5582 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5583 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5584 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5585 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
5586 := -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5587 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5588 := 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5589 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
5590 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5591 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
5592 := -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5593 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5594 := 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5595 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5596 := 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
5597 := 1^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5598 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5599 := 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5600 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 & = -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
5601 := -2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
5602 := -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 & = -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5603 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
5604 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5605 &:= -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 &= -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 & 5642 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5606 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 & 5643 &:= 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5607 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 & 5644 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^1 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
5608 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 7^4 & 5645 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^1 \\
5609 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 &= -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 & 5646 &:= -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
5610 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 & 5647 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^0 &= 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^1 \\
5611 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 7^4 &= -1^9 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 5648 &:= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
5612 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 5649 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 &= -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5613 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^4 &= 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 5650 &:= 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^3 &= 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^3 \\
5614 &:= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 &= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^4 & 5651 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5615 &:= 0^9 - 3^6 - 4^0 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^2 & 5652 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5616 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 5653 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^4 \\
5617 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 & 5654 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5618 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 & 5655 &:= 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5619 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 & 5656 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5620 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 & 5657 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5621 &:= 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 5658 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5622 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 5659 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5623 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 & 5660 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5624 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 & 5661 &:= 0^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^0 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5625 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 &= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 & 5662 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
5626 &:= 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^2 & 5663 &:= 0^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^0 &= -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\
5627 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 &= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 5664 &:= -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5628 &:= 3^9 - 4^8 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 9^3 &= 3^9 - 4^8 + 6^6 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 5665 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\
5629 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 & 5666 &:= 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5630 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 5667 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 \\
5631 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 & 5668 &:= -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 &= -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
5632 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 & 5669 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5633 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 & 5670 &:= 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5634 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 5671 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5635 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^4 & 5672 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5636 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 5673 &:= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^1 &= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
5637 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= -1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 & 5674 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5638 &:= 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 & 5675 &:= 0^6 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
5639 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 & 5676 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^0 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5640 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^3 & 5677 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
5641 &:= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 & 5678 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5679 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^0 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
5680 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 = -1^5 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5681 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
5682 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 7^4 = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5683 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 = 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
5684 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5685 &:= 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5686 &:= 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 = 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
5687 &:= 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 = 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5688 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5689 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
5690 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
5691 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 = 3^9 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^5 - 9^3 \\
5692 &:= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
5693 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 = -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5694 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5695 &:= 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^0 = 1^6 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
5696 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5697 &:= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5698 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^0 = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5699 &:= 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^0 = -2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
5700 &:= -2^8 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 = -2^8 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
5701 &:= 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^0 = 3^8 + 5^3 - 6^7 + 7^5 + 8^6 \\
5702 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^0 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
5703 &:= -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 = -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
5704 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
5705 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
5706 &:= -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 = -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
5707 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 = -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
5708 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
5709 &:= 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 = 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5710 &:= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
5711 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5712 &:= 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5713 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
5714 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^2 - 8^3 = -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
5715 &:= 0^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^2 - 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5716 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5717 &:= -2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5718 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5719 &:= -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 = -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
5720 &:= -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 = -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
5721 &:= 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 = 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
5722 &:= 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
5723 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
5724 &:= 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 8^3 = 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
5725 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
5726 &:= 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5727 &:= 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 = 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5728 &:= 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
5729 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5730 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5731 &:= -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
5732 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5733 &:= 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
5734 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5735 &:= 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 = 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
5736 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 = -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5737 &:= 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 = 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5738 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 = 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5739 &:= 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
5740 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5741 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 = 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
5742 &:= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 = 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
5743 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
5744 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^2 = -1^9 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5745 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
5746 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5747 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
5748 &:= -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
5749 &:= -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 = -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
5750 &:= 3^9 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 9^3 = 3^9 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\
5751 &:= 0^9 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 8^2 - 9^3 = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
5752 &:= 0^9 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^0 - 9^3 = -1^7 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 - 7^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5753 &:= 0^9 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 8^2 - 9^3 = 1^8 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5754 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5755 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 = 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
5756 &:= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5757 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5758 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5759 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5760 &:= 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5761 &:= 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5762 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5763 &:= 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5764 &:= 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 = 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 \\
5765 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
5766 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5767 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
5768 &:= -2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 = -2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
5769 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
5770 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^3 - 8^2 = -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
5771 &:= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
5772 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5773 &:= -1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 = -1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5774 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5775 &:= 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5776 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 6^4 + 8^3 = -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
5777 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 6^4 + 8^3 = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
5778 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 6^4 + 8^3 = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5779 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 6^4 + 8^3 = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5780 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5781 &:= -2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 = -2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
5782 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5783 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
5784 &:= 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 = 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
5785 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^1 - 8^3 = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
5786 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 8^3 = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
5787 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 8^3 = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5788 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5789 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5790 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5791 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5792 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5793 &:= 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5794 &:= 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5795 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5796 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5797 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5798 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 \\
5799 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 8^3 = 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 8^3 \\
5800 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 8^3 = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
5801 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^1 - 8^3 = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
5802 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^1 - 8^3 = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
5803 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^1 = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
5804 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^1 = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
5805 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 9^4 = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
5806 &:= 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^2 - 9^3 = 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
5807 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
5808 &:= 0^9 - 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^4 = -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
5809 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
5810 &:= 0^9 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
5811 &:= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
5812 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\
5813 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 = 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\
5814 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\
5815 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3 = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
5816 &:= -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3 = -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
5817 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3 = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
5818 &:= 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3 = 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
5819 &:= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5820 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5821 &:= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5822 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
5823 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = -1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5824 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
5825 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
5826 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5827 &:= 0^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5828 &:= 4^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^4 &= 4^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^4 \\
 5829 &:= 0^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5830 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
 5831 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 - 8^0 - 9^3 &= -2^9 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
 5832 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
 5833 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 \\
 5834 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 5835 &:= 0^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5836 &:= 0^2 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 5837 &:= 0^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5838 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
 5839 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5840 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
 5841 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5842 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 5843 &:= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5844 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 5845 &:= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5846 &:= -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 &= -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
 5847 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
 5848 &:= 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^4 &= 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
 5849 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5850 &:= 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 &= 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
 5851 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
 5852 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^1 - 9^5 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
 5853 &:= -1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^1 - 9^5 &= -1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^1 - 9^5 \\
 5854 &:= 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
 5855 &:= 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^1 - 9^5 &= 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^1 - 9^5 \\
 5856 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^1 - 9^5 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
 5857 &:= 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 &= 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
 5858 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 8^3 \\
 5859 &:= 0^9 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 9^4 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 \\
 5860 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^0 - 9^5 &= 1^9 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
 5861 &:= 0^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^0 - 9^5 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 \\
 5862 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
 5863 &:= 0^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 8^0 - 9^5 &= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 \\
 5864 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
 5865 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 \\
 5866 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
 5867 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^0 &= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 8^2 \\
 5868 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 8^1 - 9^5 &= 1^5 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 5869 &:= -1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 8^1 - 9^5 &= -1^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 + 8^1 - 9^5 \\
 5870 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 5871 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 5872 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 5873 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 5874 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
 5875 &:= 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 8^0 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5876 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^0 &= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
 5877 &:= 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^0 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5878 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 5879 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5880 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= -1^9 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5881 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5882 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
 5883 &:= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5884 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 7^0 - 8^3 &= 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
 5885 &:= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 5886 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 7^0 - 8^3 &= 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^5 + 8^3 \\
 5887 &:= 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 - 8^0 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
 5888 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 &= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
 5889 &:= -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
 5890 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 &= 1^5 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
 5891 &:= 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
 5892 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
 5893 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
 5894 &:= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
 5895 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
 5896 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
 5897 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
 5898 &:= -3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
 5899 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
 5900 &:= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5901 &:= -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5902 &:= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5903 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^0 &= 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
5904 &:= -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^2 &= -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
5905 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^0 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
5906 &:= -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5907 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5908 &:= 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
5909 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5910 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5911 &:= 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 \\
5912 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^3 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 \\
5913 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
5914 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 \\
5915 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
5916 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5917 &:= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5918 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
5919 &:= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
5920 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^0 - 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5921 &:= -2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5922 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 - 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5923 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5924 &:= -0^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5925 &:= 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5926 &:= 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5927 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
5928 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5929 &:= 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5930 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5931 &:= 0^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
5932 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5933 &:= 0^6 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
5934 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
5935 &:= 1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
5936 &:= -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
5937 &:= 1^8 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
5938 &:= 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
5939 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
5940 &:= 0^3 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^0 &= 1^7 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
5941 &:= 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5942 &:= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5943 &:= -1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
5944 &:= 0^3 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5945 &:= -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
5946 &:= 0^3 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 8^1 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
5947 &:= 1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
5948 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5949 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5950 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5951 &:= -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5952 &:= 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5953 &:= 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5954 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^4 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
5955 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^3 - 8^1 &= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
5956 &:= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5957 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 \\
5958 &:= 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
5959 &:= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 &= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
5960 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 &= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
5961 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^3 - 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
5962 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5963 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 8^0 &= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
5964 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= 1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
5965 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
5966 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= 1^5 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
5967 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^0 - 9^2 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
5968 &:= 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^2 &= 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
5969 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
5970 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
5971 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
5972 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 &= 1^5 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
5973 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 &= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^2 \\
5974 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 &= -1^4 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^1 - 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5975 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5976 &:= -2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5977 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5978 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
 5979 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
 5980 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
 5981 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5982 &:= 1^8 - 2^9 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 = 1^8 - 2^9 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
 5983 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5984 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
 5985 &:= 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 = 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
 5986 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 9^4 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
 5987 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5988 &:= -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 = -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6001 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 6002 &:= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 = -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
 6003 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 6004 &:= -0^0 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 = -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 6005 &:= -3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 = -3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 6006 &:= -2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6007 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6008 &:= -1^6 - 2^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 9^4 = -1^6 - 2^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
 6009 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 8^1 \\
 6010 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
 6011 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3 = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
 6012 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
 6013 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3 = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
 6014 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
 6015 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
 6016 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 \\
 6017 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 \\
 6018 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^3 \\
 6019 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
 6020 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
 6021 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 = -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
 6022 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
 6023 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^4 = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5989 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5990 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3 = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
 5991 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^3 = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^3 \\
 5992 &:= -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^3 = -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^3 \\
 5993 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5994 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5995 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
 5996 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 5997 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 5998 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 = -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
 5999 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
 6000 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 = 1^5 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6024 &:= 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 = 2^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 6025 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^3 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
 6026 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 = -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
 6027 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
 6028 &:= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 \\
 6029 &:= -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6030 &:= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 \\
 6031 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6032 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6033 &:= -2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6034 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 = 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6035 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6036 &:= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 \\
 6037 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6038 &:= -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
 6039 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^1 = -1^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
 6040 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 \\
 6041 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 = -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
 6042 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 = -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
 6043 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3 = -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
 6044 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3 \\
 6045 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3 = -2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3 \\
 6046 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3
 \end{aligned}$$

$6047 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^3$	$6084 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3$
$6048 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$6085 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3$
$6049 := 3^8 - 8^3$	$= 3^8 - 8^3$	$6086 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3$
$6050 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$6087 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^0 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3$
$6051 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3$	$6088 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 - 8^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3$
$6052 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$6089 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^0$	$= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^2$
$6053 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$6090 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^6 - 2^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4$
$6054 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^3$	$6091 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$
$6055 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^3$	$6092 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$
$6056 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3$	$6093 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$
$6057 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3$	$6094 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^1$
$6058 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3$	$6095 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3$
$6059 := 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^1$	$6096 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^1$
$6060 := -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4$	$6097 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1$
$6061 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6098 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^1$
$6062 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$6099 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1$
$6063 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6100 := -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^2$
$6064 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6101 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3$
$6065 := -2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6102 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2$
$6066 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6103 := -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6067 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6104 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6068 := 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$6105 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6069 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6106 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^3$
$6070 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4$	$= -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4$	$6107 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^3$
$6071 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$6108 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^3$
$6072 := 1^6 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 9^4$	$6109 := -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6073 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$6110 := 1^8 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^8 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4$
$6074 := 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4$	$6111 := 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6075 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 9^4$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^3$	$6112 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 - 3^6 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 9^4$
$6076 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3$	$6113 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^2$
$6077 := 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3$	$6114 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4$
$6078 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^3$	$6115 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6079 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6116 := -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4$
$6080 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$6117 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6081 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$6118 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3$
$6082 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3$	$6119 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3$
$6083 := 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$6120 := 0^9 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^3$

$$\begin{aligned}
6121 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6122 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6123 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6124 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 &= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
6125 &:= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
6126 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6127 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
6128 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
6129 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
6130 &:= -2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= -2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6131 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^2 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
6132 &:= -1^9 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 \\
6133 &:= -0^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
6134 &:= 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6135 &:= 0^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6136 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 &= 1^5 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6137 &:= 0^9 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
6138 &:= 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 &= 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6139 &:= 0^9 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
6140 &:= -2^8 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 &= -2^8 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
6141 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6142 &:= -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 \\
6143 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6144 &:= 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 \\
6145 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^1 \\
6146 &:= 0^8 + 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
6147 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^1 \\
6148 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
6149 &:= 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
6150 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
6151 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
6152 &:= 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
6153 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6154 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6155 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6156 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^5 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6157 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6158 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 &= 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
6159 &:= 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^1 \\
6160 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^0 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6161 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^0 &= 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6162 &:= -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 &= -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6163 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1 \\
6164 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 &= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6165 &:= 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6166 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6167 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1 \\
6168 &:= -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 7^4 &= -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6169 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
6170 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 &= 1^5 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6171 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
6172 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6173 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6174 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^1 &= -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6175 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^0 - 8^3 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1 \\
6176 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^0 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6177 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1 \\
6178 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 - 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6179 &:= 0^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^0 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1 \\
6180 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
6181 &:= 0^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^0 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
6182 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6183 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
6184 &:= 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 &= 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
6185 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
6186 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 - 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6187 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 &= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6188 &:= -1^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6189 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6190 &:= 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6191 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6192 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6193 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6194 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6195 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 9^4 = 1^7 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6196 &:= -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 = -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6197 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 = -1^7 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6198 &:= 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6199 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
6200 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^4 = -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6201 &:= -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^4 = -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6202 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^4 = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6203 &:= 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^4 = 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^4 \\
6204 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6205 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6206 &:= 0^6 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 - 7^4 = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6207 &:= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6208 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = -3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
6209 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6210 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6211 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6212 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 = -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6213 &:= 0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^0 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6214 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6215 &:= 0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6216 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^0 = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6217 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^0 = -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6218 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6219 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^2 \\
6220 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = -1^4 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6221 &:= 0^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^0 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6222 &:= 0^2 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6223 &:= 0^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6224 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
6225 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6226 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 = 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
6227 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6228 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6229 &:= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6230 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6231 &:= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6232 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6233 &:= -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6234 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6235 &:= -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 = -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
6236 &:= -1^9 - 2^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 = -1^9 - 2^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
6237 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 8^2 \\
6238 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6239 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 8^2 \\
6240 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6241 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6242 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6243 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6244 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6245 &:= 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 8^2 = 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 8^2 \\
6246 &:= 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
6247 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6248 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6249 &:= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6250 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6251 &:= 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5 - 8^3 = 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5 - 8^3 \\
6252 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 9^4 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6253 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 9^4 = -2^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6254 &:= -2^8 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 = -2^8 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 \\
6255 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 9^4 = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6256 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6257 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6258 &:= -1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6259 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^6 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
6260 &:= 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6261 &:= -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 = -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
6262 &:= 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 = -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6263 &:= 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^2 - 8^0 = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 8^1 \\
6264 &:= 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6265 &:= 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^2 + 8^0 = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 8^1 \\
6266 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 9^4 = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
6267 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
6268 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 9^4 = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
6269 := -2^8 - 4^9 - 6^2 + 8^6 + 9^4 & = -2^8 - 4^9 - 6^2 + 8^6 + 9^4 \\
6270 := 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
6271 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
6272 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6273 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6274 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6275 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6276 := 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 & = 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6277 := -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6278 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6279 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6280 := 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
6281 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6282 := 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 & = 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
6283 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6284 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6285 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6286 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6287 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6288 := 0^9 - 2^8 - 4^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6289 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^1 \\
6290 := 0^9 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 8^0 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6291 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^1 \\
6292 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6293 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6294 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6295 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
6296 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6297 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
6298 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6299 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 8^1 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
6300 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6301 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6302 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6303 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 8^3 \\
6304 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6305 := 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6306 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^0 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6307 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6308 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6309 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 \\
6310 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6311 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 8^3 \\
6312 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6313 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
6314 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6315 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
6316 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6317 := 0^9 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
6318 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6319 := 0^9 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6320 := 0^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6321 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6322 := 0^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^0 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6323 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
6324 := 1^9 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
6325 := 0^3 + 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
6326 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 7^0 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
6327 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^3 \\
6328 := -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
6329 := -2^9 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -2^9 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
6330 := 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
6331 := -2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6332 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6333 := -2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6334 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6335 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
6336 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6337 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6338 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6339 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6340 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 & = -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6341 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6342 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6343 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
6344 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^0 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6345 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6346 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^0 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6347 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^0 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6348 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^0 &= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6349 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 &= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
6350 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^0 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6351 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
6352 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6353 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6354 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6355 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6356 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6357 &:= -0^0 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6358 &:= -3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6359 &:= 0^0 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6360 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6361 &:= -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6362 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6363 &:= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^2 &= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
6364 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
6365 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
6366 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6367 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
6368 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6369 &:= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 &= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6370 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6371 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 &= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6372 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6373 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6374 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
6375 &:= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6376 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6377 &:= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6378 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^2 \\
6379 &:= -1^9 - 2^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6380 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6381 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6382 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^0 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6383 &:= 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^0 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 \\
6384 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
6385 &:= 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^0 &= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6386 &:= -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6387 &:= -1^9 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6388 &:= 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6389 &:= 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6390 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^1 &= -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6391 &:= -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^1 &= -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
6392 &:= 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
6393 &:= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^1 &= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
6394 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6395 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6396 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 &= -1^6 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6397 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6398 &:= -2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6399 &:= -3^9 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 8^5 - 9^4 &= -3^9 + 4^8 - 5^3 - 8^5 - 9^4 \\
6400 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6401 &:= -2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6402 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6403 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6404 &:= 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 &= 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6405 &:= -2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6406 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6407 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
6408 &:= 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
6409 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6410 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6411 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6412 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6413 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6414 &:= 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6415 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 &= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6416 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
6417 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6454 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^1 \\
6418 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6455 := -1^9 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
6419 := 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 6456 := -1^9 - 2^6 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^6 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
6420 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 & 6457 := 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
6421 := 0^3 - 3^6 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^1 & 6458 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6422 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 & 6459 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6423 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & 6460 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^0 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6424 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 & 6461 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6425 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & 6462 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^0 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6426 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^2 & 6463 := -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
6427 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & 6464 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^0 - 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6428 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^2 & 6465 := 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
6429 := 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & 6466 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^0 - 8^2 & = 1^9 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
6430 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6467 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6431 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^0 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & 6468 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 & = -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6432 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6469 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6433 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^1 & 6470 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6434 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^0 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6471 := 0^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^0 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 - 8^2 \\
6435 := 0^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 6472 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 \\
6436 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6473 := 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6437 := 0^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 & 6474 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 \\
6438 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^2 & 6475 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^3 + 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6439 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 - 8^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & 6476 := -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 \\
6440 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^2 & 6477 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6441 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & 6478 := 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 \\
6442 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^9 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 & 6479 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
6443 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & 6480 := -2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
6444 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 & 6481 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^0 & = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
6445 := 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & 6482 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^0 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^1 - 8^2 \\
6446 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 & 6483 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^0 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^2 \\
6447 := 0^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 8^3 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^1 & 6484 := -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 \\
6448 := 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^3 & 6485 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6449 := 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & = 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6486 := -3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
6450 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 & 6487 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6451 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^3 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^3 & 6488 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6452 := -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^1 & 6489 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6453 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^3 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^3 & 6490 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
6491 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6492 := 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
6493 := -1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6494 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6495 := 1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6496 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6497 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6498 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6499 := -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6500 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6501 := 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6502 := -1^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
6503 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6504 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6505 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6506 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 \\
6507 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^2 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6508 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 \\
6509 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
6510 := 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 \\
6511 := -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6512 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^0 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^1 - 8^2 \\
6513 := 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6514 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^0 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6515 := -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6516 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^2 - 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 \\
6517 := 0^9 - 2^0 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6518 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 \\
6519 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6520 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 \\
6521 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^0 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6522 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 \\
6523 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 - 8^2 \\
6524 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^1 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6525 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6526 := 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^1 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6527 := 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 5^2 - 8^0 & = 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6528 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 \\
6529 := -1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6530 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 \\
6531 := 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6532 := 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 & = 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6533 := 0^9 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6534 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
6535 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6536 := 0^1 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^1 \\
6537 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6538 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^1 \\
6539 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6540 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6541 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6542 := -1^9 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6543 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6544 := 0^9 - 2^0 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 \\
6545 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6546 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 \\
6547 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6548 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 \\
6549 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6550 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 \\
6551 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6552 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 \\
6553 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6554 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 \\
6555 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 8^1 & = -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6556 := -1^9 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6557 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
6558 := 1^9 - 4^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6559 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 8^0 & = 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6560 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 \\
6561 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6562 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 \\
6563 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^0 & = -1^9 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
6564 := -1^9 + 4^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^1 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

$6565 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6602 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^1$
$6566 := 1^9 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6603 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$
$6567 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6604 := 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^2$
$6568 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$6605 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$
$6569 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4$	$6606 := 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^2$
$6570 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$6607 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$
$6571 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6608 := 0^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^2$	$= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^1$
$6572 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$6609 := -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 - 8^1$
$6573 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6610 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^2$
$6574 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$6611 := -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^2$
$6575 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4$	$6612 := -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2$
$6576 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$6613 := -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6577 := 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2$	$= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2$	$6614 := 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2$
$6578 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$6615 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6579 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$6616 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6580 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6617 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6581 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6618 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6582 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^1$	$6619 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6583 := -1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$6620 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2$
$6584 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^1$	$6621 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6585 := 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$6622 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6586 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^1$	$6623 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6587 := 0^9 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6624 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6588 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4$	$6625 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6589 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 9^4$	$= 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4$	$6626 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6590 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^2$	$= -2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^2$	$6627 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6591 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6628 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6592 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^1$	$6629 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6593 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6630 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1$
$6594 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^1$	$6631 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6595 := 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^0$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6632 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6596 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$6633 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6597 := 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4$	$6634 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$
$6598 := 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$6635 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6599 := 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^2$	$6636 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1$
$6600 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^3 - 8^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^1$	$6637 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4$
$6601 := 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^0$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4$	$6638 := 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
6639 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 - 8^0 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^2 & 6676 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6640 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^2 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 6677 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6641 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^0 & = 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^2 & 6678 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 \\
6642 := -2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & 6679 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6643 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^1 & 6680 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6644 := -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 & 6681 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^0 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6645 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & 6682 := -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
6646 := 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 & 6683 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6647 := 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^3 - 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & 6684 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
6648 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1 & 6685 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^0 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6649 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 & 6686 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6650 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1 & 6687 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 8^3 \\
6651 := 0^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^2 & 6688 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6652 := -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^1 & 6689 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6653 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^2 & 6690 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6654 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^2 & = 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^2 & 6691 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6655 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^2 & 6692 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6656 := 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 8^2 & = -1^9 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 6693 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6657 := -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 & = -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 & 6694 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
6658 := 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^0 + 8^2 & = 1^9 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 6695 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6659 := 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 & 6696 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
6660 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 - 8^0 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & 6697 := 0^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6661 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & 6698 := -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
6662 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^0 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & 6699 := 0^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6663 := 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^2 & 6700 := 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
6664 := -1^9 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 6701 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6665 := -0^0 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^9 + 2^7 - 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4 & 6702 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6666 := -3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 6703 := 0^7 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6667 := 0^0 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^9 + 2^7 - 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4 & 6704 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6668 := -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 & 6705 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6669 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 8^3 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 8^3 & 6706 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 \\
6670 := 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^1 & 6707 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6671 := 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 8^3 & = 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 8^3 & 6708 := -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
6672 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & 6709 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6673 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 & 6710 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6674 := 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 & = 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 & 6711 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6675 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 - 8^1 & 6712 := -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
6713 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
6714 := -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
6715 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
6716 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
6717 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6718 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = -2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6719 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6720 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6721 := 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6722 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6723 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^4 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6724 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 & = -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6725 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6726 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6727 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6728 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^1 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6729 := -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
6730 := -2^8 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
6731 := 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
6732 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6733 := -1^9 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6734 := -1^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6735 := 1^9 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6736 := 1^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6737 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 - 8^0 & = -1^5 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6738 := -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
6739 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^0 & = 1^5 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6740 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^0 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6741 := 0^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6742 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6743 := 1^9 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6744 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6745 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6746 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6747 := -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6748 := -1^9 + 2^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^8 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
6749 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6750 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6751 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6752 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6753 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6754 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6755 := 0^8 - 5^7 - 6^0 + 7^6 - 8^5 & = 3^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
6756 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6757 := 0^8 - 5^7 + 6^0 + 7^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6758 := 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
6759 := -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
6760 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6761 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6762 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^2 \\
6763 := 1^8 - 5^7 + 6^1 + 7^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 - 5^7 + 6^1 + 7^6 - 8^5 \\
6764 := -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6765 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6766 := 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6767 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6768 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6769 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6770 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6771 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
6772 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^0 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6773 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
6774 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
6775 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^0 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6776 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^0 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6777 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6778 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6779 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6780 := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 - 8^0 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6781 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6782 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 & = 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6783 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 8^2 \\
6784 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6785 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6786 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6787 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
6788 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6789 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
6790 &:= 0^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6791 &:= 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 &= 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6792 &:= 0^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^9 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
6793 &:= -4^9 + 5^4 - 6^7 + 7^5 + 9^6 &= -4^9 + 5^4 - 6^7 + 7^5 + 9^6 \\
6794 &:= 1^9 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
6795 &:= -1^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6796 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6797 &:= 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6798 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6799 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6800 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6801 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6802 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 8^0 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6803 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6804 &:= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6805 &:= 2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 &= 2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
6806 &:= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6807 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^1 \\
6808 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6809 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
6810 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 \\
6811 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 &= -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 8^3 \\
6812 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6813 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6814 &:= 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^0 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6815 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6816 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6817 &:= 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6818 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^0 &= 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6819 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6820 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6821 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 &= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 \\
6822 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6823 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6824 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6825 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
6826 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6827 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 + 9^1 \\
6828 &:= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6829 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
6830 &:= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6831 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6832 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6833 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6834 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 8^0 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 \\
6835 &:= 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
6836 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 &= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
6837 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
6838 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6839 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6840 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6841 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6842 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
6843 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
6844 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6845 &:= 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
6846 &:= -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^2 &= -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6847 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^2 \\
6848 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6849 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6850 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
6851 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
6852 &:= -2^8 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= -2^8 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
6853 &:= 2^8 - 4^9 + 6^2 + 8^6 + 9^4 &= 2^8 - 4^9 + 6^2 + 8^6 + 9^4 \\
6854 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
6855 &:= 2^9 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 &= 2^9 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
6856 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
6857 &:= 2^7 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= 2^7 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
6858 &:= 0^4 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^0 &= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6859 &:= 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^0 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1 \\
6860 &:= 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 - 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6861 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^9 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 6898 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 = 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
6862 &:= -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 & 6899 &:= 0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^0 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6863 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 6900 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6864 &:= 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 = 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 & 6901 &:= 0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
6865 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^2 - 8^1 & 6902 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^0 = 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6866 &:= 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 = 2^8 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 6903 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^0 = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6867 &:= 0^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 9^4 = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 8^2 & 6904 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6868 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 9^4 = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 & 6905 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6869 &:= 0^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 9^4 = 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 6906 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6870 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 9^4 = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 & 6907 &:= 0^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^0 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6871 &:= 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 = 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 6908 &:= 0^2 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = -1^4 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
6872 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6909 &:= 0^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6873 &:= -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6910 &:= -3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 = -3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\
6874 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6911 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 = -1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6875 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^3 & 6912 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 = -1^9 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
6876 &:= -1^9 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 = -1^9 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 & 6913 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 = 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6877 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 & 6914 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 = -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
6878 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6915 &:= -0^0 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
6879 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^2 & 6916 &:= -3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = -3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6880 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6917 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6881 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1 & 6918 &:= -2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6882 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6919 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6883 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 8^1 & 6920 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6884 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6921 &:= -0^0 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^1 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6885 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 8^2 & 6922 &:= -3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6886 &:= 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 = 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 & 6923 &:= 0^0 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^1 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6887 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^2 & 6924 &:= -3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 = -3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
6888 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6925 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6889 &:= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6926 &:= 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6890 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^2 & 6927 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6891 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 & 6928 &:= 0^9 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 9^4 = -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
6892 &:= -2^8 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 = -2^8 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 6929 &:= -1^8 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 = -1^8 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
6893 &:= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 & 6930 &:= 0^9 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 9^4 = 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
6894 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 6931 &:= 1^8 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 = 1^8 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
6895 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 = -1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 & 6932 &:= -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 = -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6896 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 = -2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 & 6933 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^1 = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6897 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 = 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^1 & 6934 &:= 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 = 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6935 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^1 \\
6936 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6937 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
6938 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6939 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
6940 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6941 &:= 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 - 8^0 &= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6942 &:= -2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6943 &:= 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 8^0 &= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6944 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^0 + 8^3 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6945 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 + 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6946 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 + 8^3 &= -3^8 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
6947 &:= 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^0 + 8^3 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 8^1 \\
6948 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6949 &:= -2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6950 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6951 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
6952 &:= -2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
6953 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
6954 &:= 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6955 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
6956 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6957 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6958 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^0 &= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6959 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 8^0 &= -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6960 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^2 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6961 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^0 &= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6962 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^2 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6963 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6964 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^7 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
6965 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6966 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^5 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
6967 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6968 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2 &= 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 - 8^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7001 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7002 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7003 &:= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
6969 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6970 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6971 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
6972 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
6973 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
6974 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
6975 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6976 &:= -2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -2^8 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6977 &:= -1^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6978 &:= -1^9 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 \\
6979 &:= 1^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6980 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6981 &:= -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6982 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
6983 &:= 0^9 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
6984 &:= 0^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
6985 &:= 0^9 - 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^4 &= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
6986 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 - 9^2 &= -1^5 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
6987 &:= -1^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
6988 &:= -1^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 \\
6989 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
6990 &:= 1^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^4 \\
6991 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
6992 &:= -2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^4 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
6993 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
6994 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
6995 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
6996 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= 1^5 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
6997 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
6998 &:= -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
6999 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7000 &:= 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 &= 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7004 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7005 &:= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7006 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 &= 1^8 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
7007 := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & 7044 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7008 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 7045 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7009 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 & = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 & 7046 := 0^3 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7010 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 7047 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7011 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & 7048 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -2^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7012 := -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 & 7049 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
7013 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 9^4 & 7050 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7014 := -2^3 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^3 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7051 := -1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7015 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7052 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^3 \\
7016 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 8^3 & = -2^5 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 8^3 & 7053 := 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7017 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & 7054 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^3 \\
7018 := 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & 7055 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7019 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 9^4 & 7056 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7020 := -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 7057 := 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7021 := 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7058 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7022 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^5 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^4 & 7059 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7023 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7060 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
7024 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^1 & 7061 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7025 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7062 := 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7026 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^1 & 7063 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^1 \\
7027 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 & 7064 := -2^3 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^3 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7028 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^1 & 7065 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7029 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & 7066 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7030 := 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & 7067 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^3 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7031 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & 7068 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7032 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 - 8^0 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 7069 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7033 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7070 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7034 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^3 + 8^0 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & 7071 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = -2^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7035 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7072 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7036 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & 7073 := 3^8 + 8^3 & = 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7037 := -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7074 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7038 := 0^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & 7075 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7039 := 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7076 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7040 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 & 7077 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7041 := -1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7078 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^3 \\
7042 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 & 7079 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^3 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7043 := 1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7080 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
7081 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7082 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
7083 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^1 \\
7084 := 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7085 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
7086 := 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 & = 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 \\
7087 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 9^4 \\
7088 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7089 := 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7090 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7091 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7092 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
7093 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7094 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 \\
7095 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
7096 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 & = 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
7097 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 9^4 \\
7098 := -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7099 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^3 \\
7100 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7101 := 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7102 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7103 := -2^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7104 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
7105 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
7106 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 \\
7107 := 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7108 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7109 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7110 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7111 := 0^9 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 8^0 - 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7112 := 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7113 := 0^9 + 4^8 + 5^4 + 8^0 - 9^5 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^4 - 8^1 \\
7114 := 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
7115 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7116 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7117 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 9^4 \\
7118 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
7119 := 0^9 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7120 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7121 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7122 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
7123 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7124 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
7125 := 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7126 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7127 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7128 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7129 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7130 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^3 & = 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^3 \\
7131 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 8^3 \\
7132 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7133 := -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7134 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7135 := 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7136 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7137 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7138 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7139 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7140 := -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
7141 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7142 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7143 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7144 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7145 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7146 := -1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7147 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7148 := 1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7149 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7150 := 0^6 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7151 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7152 := 0^6 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
7153 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7154 := -1^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 9^4 \\
& = 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 \\
& = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^2 + 8^3 \\
& = -1^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7155 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
7156 &:= 1^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7157 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
7158 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7159 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^3 - 8^0 &= -1^8 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7160 &:= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7161 &:= 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^3 + 8^0 &= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
7162 &:= -1^9 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= -1^9 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
7163 &:= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 &= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
7164 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7165 &:= 3^9 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 &= 3^9 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7166 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7167 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7168 &:= -2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7169 &:= -2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= -2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7170 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7171 &:= -0^0 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7172 &:= -3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7173 &:= 0^0 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7174 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7175 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7176 &:= 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7177 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7178 &:= -3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= -3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7179 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7180 &:= 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 &= 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7181 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7182 &:= 0^6 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7183 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7184 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7185 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7186 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7187 &:= -1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7188 &:= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7189 &:= 1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7190 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7191 &:= 1^8 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7192 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= -1^5 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7193 &:= 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7194 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^5 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7195 &:= 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7196 &:= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7197 &:= -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7198 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7199 &:= 2^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 2^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7200 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 7^0 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7201 &:= 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 &= 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 \\
7202 &:= -3^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= -3^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
7203 &:= 0^0 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 1^1 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
7204 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= 1^8 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7205 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7206 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= -1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7207 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7208 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7209 &:= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7210 &:= -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7211 &:= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7212 &:= 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7213 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 &= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7214 &:= -1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 &= -1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 \\
7215 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 &= -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7216 &:= 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 &= 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 \\
7217 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 &= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7218 &:= 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7219 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7220 &:= 0^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7221 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= 1^9 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7222 &:= 0^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7223 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7224 &:= -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7225 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7226 &:= -1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= -1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7227 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7228 &:= 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7229 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7230 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7231 &:= 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7232 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7233 &:= 1^9 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7234 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7235 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
7236 &:= 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 &= 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
7237 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 &= 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
7238 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7239 &:= -2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
7240 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7241 &:= -2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7242 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7243 &:= 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 &= 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 \\
7244 &:= 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7245 &:= 1^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^8 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7246 &:= 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7247 &:= 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= -1^6 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
7248 &:= 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
7249 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7250 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7251 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7252 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7253 &:= -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7254 &:= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7255 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7256 &:= -2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= -2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7257 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7258 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7259 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 8^1 \\
7260 &:= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7261 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7262 &:= 0^6 + 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^0 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7263 &:= 0^6 + 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^3 &= 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7264 &:= 0^4 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7265 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7266 &:= 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7267 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^0 &= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7268 &:= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7269 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7270 &:= 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7271 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7272 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7273 &:= 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7274 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7275 &:= 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5 + 8^3 &= 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5 + 8^3 \\
7276 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7277 &:= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7278 &:= -2^8 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 &= -2^8 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
7279 &:= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7280 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7281 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7282 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 8^2 \\
7283 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7284 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 &= -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7285 &:= 0^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^0 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7286 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7287 &:= 0^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7288 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 8^0 + 9^3 &= 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7289 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 - 8^0 + 9^3 &= 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7290 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^3 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7291 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^3 &= 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7292 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^3 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7293 &:= 0^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 8^0 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7294 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^5 &= -1^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7295 &:= 0^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^0 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7296 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 &= 1^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7297 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7298 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7299 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7300 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 &= 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7301 &:= 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7302 &:= 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7303 &:= 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
7304 &:= 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7305 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7306 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7307 &:= -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7308 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7309 &:= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 &= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7310 &:= 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
7311 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7312 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7313 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 8^2 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7314 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 3^0 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 &= 1^6 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7315 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 8^2 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7316 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 9^5 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
7317 &:= 0^9 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 \\
7318 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^1 &= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7319 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 - 9^1 \\
7320 &:= -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7321 &:= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^1 + 8^3 &= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7322 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7323 &:= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 8^3 &= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7324 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7325 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7326 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7327 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
7328 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7329 &:= 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7330 &:= 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7331 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= -1^3 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
7332 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7333 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7334 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^3 \\
7335 &:= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^3 &= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7336 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^0 &= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
7337 &:= 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 &= 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
7338 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^0 &= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7339 &:= -1^6 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -1^6 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7340 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7341 &:= 1^6 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 1^6 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7342 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7343 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7344 &:= 0^6 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -2^3 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
7345 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
7346 &:= 0^6 - 2^9 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 \\
7347 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
7348 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7349 &:= -1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -1^6 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7350 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
7351 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7352 &:= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7353 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7354 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7355 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7356 &:= -3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &= -3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7357 &:= 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7358 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7359 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7360 &:= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7361 &:= 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7362 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7363 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
7364 &:= 2^8 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= 2^8 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
7365 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7366 &:= 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 &= 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
7367 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 &= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 8^3 \\
7368 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
7369 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 &= -2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
7370 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
7371 &:= 0^9 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^2 + 9^3 &= -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
7372 &:= -1^7 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^7 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
7373 &:= 0^6 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -1^9 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
7374 &:= 0^9 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7375 &:= 0^9 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7376 &:= 0^9 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7377 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 7378 &:= 1^6 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 = 1^6 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
 7379 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
 7380 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
 7381 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^2 \\
 7382 &:= 0^9 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 7^3 + 9^4 = 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 7383 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7384 &:= -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 = -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 7385 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 = 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7386 &:= 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 = 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 7387 &:= -2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 = -2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
 7388 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
 7389 &:= 0^7 - 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7390 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 7391 &:= 0^7 - 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 = -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7392 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
 7393 &:= 1^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7394 &:= 0^6 - 3^0 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 7395 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^0 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7396 &:= 0^6 + 3^0 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
 7397 &:= -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7398 &:= 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 = 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
 7399 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7400 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
 7401 &:= -2^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 = -2^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
 7402 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 = -1^7 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
 7403 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7404 &:= -2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 = -2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
 7405 &:= 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 = 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 7406 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
 7407 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^2 + 8^3 = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7408 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^2 + 8^3 = 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 7^2 + 8^3 \\
 7409 &:= -3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 = -3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
 7410 &:= 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 + 9^2 = 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
 7411 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 = -2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
 7412 &:= -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7413 &:= -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 = -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7414 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 = -1^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
 7415 &:= 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 = 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
 7416 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 = 1^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
 7417 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
 7418 &:= -2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 = -2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
 7419 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 = 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
 7420 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 = -1^7 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
 7421 &:= 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 = 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^5 \\
 7422 &:= 2^8 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 = 2^8 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
 7423 &:= 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7424 &:= -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7425 &:= 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 = 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
 7426 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
 7427 &:= -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7428 &:= -3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = -3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7429 &:= 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
 7430 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 = -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
 7431 &:= -2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 = -2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
 7432 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 = 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
 7433 &:= -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7434 &:= 2^8 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 = 2^8 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
 7435 &:= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7436 &:= 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
 7437 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7438 &:= 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
 7439 &:= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7440 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = 1^8 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
 7441 &:= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7442 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
 7443 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7444 &:= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7445 &:= -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 = -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
 7446 &:= 0^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
 7447 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7448 &:= -2^2 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 = -2^2 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
 7449 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
 7450 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 = -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7451 &:= -0^0 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^1 &7488 &:= 1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= 1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7452 &:= -3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= -3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &7489 &:= 1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7453 &:= 0^0 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^1 &7490 &:= -2^6 - 3^4 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 3^4 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7454 &:= -2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7491 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7455 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &7492 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7456 &:= -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &7493 &:= 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
7457 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 2^9 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 9^4 &7494 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7458 &:= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &7495 &:= -2^8 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 &= -2^8 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
7459 &:= 0^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^0 &= -3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 7^4 - 9^3 &7496 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7460 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &7497 &:= -1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7461 &:= 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &7498 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7462 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &7499 &:= 1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7463 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &7500 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^7 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
7464 &:= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &7501 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
7465 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &= -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &7502 &:= -1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 &= -1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7466 &:= 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 &7503 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
7467 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^1 &7504 &:= 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
7468 &:= 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^5 + 8^4 &= 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^5 + 8^4 &7505 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
7469 &:= 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^1 &7506 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
7470 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^1 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 &7507 &:= 0^9 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7471 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &7508 &:= -1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
7472 &:= 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &= 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &7509 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
7473 &:= 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &7510 &:= -1^6 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7474 &:= 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &7511 &:= 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
7475 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &7512 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7476 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^4 + 8^3 &7513 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7477 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7514 &:= -1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7478 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 &= -2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 &7515 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 2^9 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7479 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7516 &:= 1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7480 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7517 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7481 &:= -2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7518 &:= 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 &= 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7482 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7519 &:= 0^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7483 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7520 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7484 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^7 + 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &7521 &:= 0^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 2^9 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^4 \\
7485 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &7522 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7486 &:= -1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= -1^6 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &7523 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 \\
7487 &:= -1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &7524 &:= -1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
7525 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 7562 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7526 := 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7563 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7527 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4 & 7564 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7528 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7565 := -0^0 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7529 := -2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & 7566 := -3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7530 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & = 1^6 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7567 := 0^0 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7531 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7568 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^4 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7532 := 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7569 := 0^6 - 3^4 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7533 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7570 := 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7534 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 7571 := 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
7535 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4 & 7572 := -2^6 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7536 := -1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 7573 := -1^6 - 3^4 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^4 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7537 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 8^4 & 7574 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^1 & = 1^9 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7538 := 1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 7575 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 - 9^1 \\
7539 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^1 + 9^3 & 7576 := -2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -2^3 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7540 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^2 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^2 & 7577 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7541 := -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7578 := -2^6 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7542 := -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7579 := -1^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7543 := 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7580 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7544 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7581 := 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7545 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 - 8^0 + 9^3 & = -2^8 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 7582 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7546 := 0^6 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7583 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7547 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = -3^8 - 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 + 8^5 & 7584 := 0^9 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7548 := 0^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7585 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7549 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7586 := 0^9 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7550 := 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 7587 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7551 := -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7588 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7552 := -1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 7589 := -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7553 := 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7590 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7554 := 1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 7591 := 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7555 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 8^1 + 9^3 & 7592 := -0^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7556 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^5 + 8^4 & 7593 := -4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7557 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 7594 := 0^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7558 := -0^0 + 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7595 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7559 := 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7596 := -2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7560 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7597 := 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7561 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 7598 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
7599 := -1^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7600 := 0^6 - 2^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7601 := 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7602 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7603 := -1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7604 := -2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7605 := 1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7606 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7607 := -0^0 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7608 := -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7609 := 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7610 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7611 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7612 := 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7613 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7614 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7615 := -1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = -1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
7616 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7617 := 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
7618 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7619 := -0^0 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7620 := 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7621 := 0^0 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7622 := 0^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
7623 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
7624 := 0^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7625 := -1^9 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7626 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
7627 := 1^9 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7628 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
7629 := -1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7630 := 0^9 - 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^2 \\
7631 := 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7632 := 0^9 - 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^7 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7633 := 0^1 + 1^9 - 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^6 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7634 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7635 := -1^9 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7636 := 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7637 := 1^9 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
7638 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7639 := -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7640 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 \\
7641 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7642 := -1^8 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^8 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
7643 := 0^6 + 2^0 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7644 := 0^6 - 3^0 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^8 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
7645 := 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7646 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
7647 := -1^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7648 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
7649 := 1^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7650 := 0^6 - 3^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
7651 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7652 := 0^6 + 3^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
7653 := -1^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7654 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^8 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
7655 := 1^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7656 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
7657 := -2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
7658 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
7659 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7660 := -2^6 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7661 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7662 := 0^7 - 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 8^2 \\
7663 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7664 := 0^7 - 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 2^3 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7665 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
7666 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
7667 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
7668 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = 1^7 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7669 := 1^7 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^7 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7670 := -2^6 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 3^4 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7671 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7672 := -2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 & = -2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
7673 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7674 := 0^6 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = -2^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7675 := -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7676 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^6 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7677 := -1^9 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 & = -1^9 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
7678 := -1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7679 := -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7680 := 1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7681 := 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7682 := -1^4 - 2^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7683 := -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7684 := 0^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7685 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7686 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7687 := -2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7688 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7689 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7690 := -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7691 := 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7692 := 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7693 := 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7694 := -1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7695 := 0^4 - 2^6 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^7 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7696 := 0^6 - 2^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^8 - 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7697 := 0^4 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7698 := 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^3 \\
7699 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7700 := -1^4 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7701 := -1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7702 := 0^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7703 := -0^0 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7704 := -3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7705 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7706 := -1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7707 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7708 := 1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7709 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7710 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7711 := 0^2 - 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7712 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7713 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7714 := -2^6 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7715 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7716 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7717 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7718 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7719 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7720 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -2^6 - 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7721 := -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7722 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7723 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7724 := 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7725 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7726 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 7^4 \\
7727 := 0^4 - 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7728 := -1^8 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7729 := 0^4 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7730 := -1^6 - 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7731 := 0^6 + 3^4 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^7 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
7732 := -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7733 := 0^6 + 3^4 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7734 := 0^6 - 2^4 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7735 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7736 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7737 := -2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7738 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7739 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7740 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7741 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7742 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7743 := -1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7744 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7745 := 1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7746 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^8 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
7747 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7784 := -1^6 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7748 := 0^6 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7785 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^7 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
7749 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7786 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7750 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7787 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7751 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7788 := 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7752 := 0^6 + 2^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7789 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7753 := -1^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7790 := 0^7 + 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^6 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7754 := 1^6 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7791 := 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7755 := 1^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7792 := 0^6 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7756 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & 7793 := -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7757 := -1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7794 := 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
7758 := 0^6 + 2^3 - 3^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^2 & 7795 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7759 := 1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7796 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
7760 := 0^6 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 7797 := -1^6 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7761 := -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7798 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7762 := 0^7 - 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^6 + 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 7799 := 1^6 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7763 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7800 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7764 := -2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7801 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7765 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7802 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7766 := -1^6 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7803 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7767 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^7 - 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 7804 := 0^6 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7768 := 1^6 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7805 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7769 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7806 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^8 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7770 := -1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7807 := -1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7771 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7808 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^8 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7772 := 1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7809 := 1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7773 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7810 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7774 := 0^1 - 1^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 7811 := -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7775 := 0^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 7812 := 0^2 + 2^6 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7776 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7813 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7777 := 0^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 & 7814 := -0^0 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7778 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7815 := 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7779 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7816 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7780 := -1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7817 := -2^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -2^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7781 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7818 := -2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7782 := 1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7819 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7783 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 7820 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
7821 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7822 := -3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7823 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7824 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7825 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7826 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7827 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7828 := -2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7829 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7830 := 0^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 \\
7831 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7832 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7833 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7834 := -1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7835 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7836 := 1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7837 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7838 := 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7839 := 0^2 + 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 \\
7840 := -1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7841 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 \\
7842 := 1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7843 := 1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
7844 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7845 := -2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7846 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7847 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7848 := -0^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7849 := 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7850 := 0^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7851 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7852 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7853 := 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7854 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7855 := -1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7856 := -1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7857 := 1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7858 := 1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
7859 := 1^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
7860 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
7861 := -1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7862 := 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7863 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7864 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7865 := 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7866 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7867 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7868 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 \\
7869 := 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7870 := 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7871 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7872 := -2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7873 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7874 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7875 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7876 := 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7877 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7878 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7879 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7880 := 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7881 := 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7882 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7883 := -1^7 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7884 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7885 := 1^7 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7886 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
7887 := 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7888 := 0^7 + 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7889 := -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7890 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7891 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7892 := 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7893 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7894 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -1^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= -3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^8 + 2^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^4 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
= -1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= -1^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 1^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 2^6 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -1^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
= -1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= -1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
= 1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= 1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
= -1^2 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= -2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 1^3 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= -1^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= -1^3 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= -1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= -1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= 1^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= 1^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
= -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= -1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -1^1 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= -2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
= 1^8 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= -1^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
= -1^7 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^7 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
= 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
7895 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7932 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
7896 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 &7933 &:= -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7897 &:= -1^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7934 &:= -3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 &= -3^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
7898 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^8 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 &7935 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4 &= -1^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7899 &:= 1^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7936 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4 &= 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
7900 &:= 0^6 - 3^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 &7937 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4 &= 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7901 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7938 &:= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7902 &:= 0^6 + 3^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^6 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7939 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7903 &:= -1^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7940 &:= -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7904 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^5 &7941 &:= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 &= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
7905 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7942 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7906 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 &7943 &:= -2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7907 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7944 &:= 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7908 &:= 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^8 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 &7945 &:= 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7909 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7946 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
7910 &:= 1^8 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 &= 1^8 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 &7947 &:= -1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= -1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7911 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7948 &:= 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 &= 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
7912 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 &= 1^8 - 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 &7949 &:= 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7913 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &7950 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
7914 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 &= -1^8 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 &7951 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7915 &:= -1^9 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -1^9 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &7952 &:= 0^6 + 2^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
7916 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 &= 1^8 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 &7953 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7917 &:= 1^9 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 1^9 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &7954 &:= 0^6 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7918 &:= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &7955 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7919 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &7956 &:= 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7920 &:= 0^9 + 2^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 &7957 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7921 &:= -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= -1^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &7958 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
7922 &:= 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &7959 &:= 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
7923 &:= 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &7960 &:= 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7924 &:= -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^2 &= -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^2 &7961 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7925 &:= -1^9 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= -1^9 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 &7962 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7926 &:= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 &7963 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7927 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 &7964 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 3^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7928 &:= 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 &= 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 &7965 &:= 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
7929 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 &7966 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7930 &:= 0^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^1 &7967 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7931 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 &7968 &:= -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^2 &= -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
7969 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7970 := -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7971 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
7972 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
7973 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7974 := 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7975 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7976 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7977 := 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7978 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^0 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
7979 := 1^6 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7980 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
7981 := 0^6 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7982 := 0^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^4 \\
7983 := 0^6 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7984 := 0^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^0 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
7985 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
\\
8001 := 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8002 := 2^9 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
8003 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8004 := 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8005 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8006 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8007 := 2^8 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 2^8 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
8008 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8009 := -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8010 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8011 := 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8012 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^7 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8013 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8014 := -1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8015 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8016 := 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8017 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8018 := 0^7 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8019 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8020 := -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
\\
7986 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
7987 := 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
7988 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
7989 := 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 \\
7990 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7991 := 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
7992 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7993 := -2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
7994 := 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7995 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
7996 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
7997 := -1^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 \\
7998 := -1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
7999 := -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8000 := 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
\\
8021 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8022 := -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8023 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
8024 := 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8025 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8026 := -1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8027 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8028 := 1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8029 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8030 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8031 := 0^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8032 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8033 := 0^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
8034 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8035 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
8036 := -1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8037 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
8038 := 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8039 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8040 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8041 &:= 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & 8078 &:= -3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8042 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 8079 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8043 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8080 &:= 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^4 &= 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
8044 &:= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 8081 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8045 &:= -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 &= -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 8082 &:= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8046 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 8083 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8047 &:= 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 &= 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 8084 &:= -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8048 &:= -1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= -1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 8085 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8049 &:= 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 &= 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 & 8086 &:= -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
8050 &:= 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 8087 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8051 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8088 &:= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8052 &:= -4^8 - 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^6 + 8^5 &= -4^8 - 5^7 + 6^4 + 7^6 + 8^5 & 8089 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8053 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 8090 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8054 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8091 &:= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
8055 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 8092 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8056 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8093 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^4 \\
8057 &:= -2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 8094 &:= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8058 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8095 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
8059 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 8096 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
8060 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8097 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8061 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8098 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 \\
8062 &:= 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8099 &:= 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8063 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 8100 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8064 &:= -1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 &= -1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 8101 &:= -2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8065 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 8102 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8066 &:= 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 &= 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 8103 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 \\
8067 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 8104 &:= -0^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -1^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8068 &:= 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & 8105 &:= 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8069 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 8106 &:= 0^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8070 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 8107 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8071 &:= 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 8108 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8072 &:= 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 8109 &:= 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8073 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^4 & 8110 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 \\
8074 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8111 &:= -1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 &= -1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8075 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 8112 &:= -1^2 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8076 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & 8113 &:= 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8077 &:= -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 &= -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8114 &:= 1^2 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
8115 := 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 & 8152 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
8116 := 0^6 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & 8153 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
8117 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8154 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^2 \\
8118 := 0^6 + 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 8155 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
8119 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8156 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
8120 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8157 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
8121 := 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8158 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8122 := 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 8159 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
8123 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 8160 := 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8124 := 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 8161 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8125 := 0^0 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 8162 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
8126 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 8163 := 0^7 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8127 := -3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 8164 := 0^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8128 := 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 8165 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8129 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 8166 := 0^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
8130 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^4 & 8167 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8131 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8168 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8132 := 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8169 := 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8133 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8170 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8134 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 8171 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8135 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8172 := 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8136 := 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8173 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8137 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 & 8174 := 0^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8138 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 & 8175 := 0^7 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^6 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8139 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^3 & 8176 := 0^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8140 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 8177 := -1^6 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8141 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & 8178 := 0^9 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8142 := 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & 8179 := 0^6 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
8143 := -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & 8180 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8144 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & 8181 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8145 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8182 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8146 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^8 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 8183 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8147 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8184 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2 \\
8148 := 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8185 := -1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8149 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 8186 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
8150 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^4 & 8187 := 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
8151 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8188 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3
\end{array}$$

8189 := $0^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	8226 := $1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$
8190 := $0^1 - 1^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4$	= $1^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3$	8227 := $0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8191 := $0^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	8228 := $0^1 - 1^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$
8192 := $0^1 - 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4$	= $1^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4$	8229 := $0^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8193 := $0^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8230 := $2^6 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5$	= $2^6 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5$
8194 := $0^1 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4$	= $-1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3$	8231 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8195 := $0^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4$	= $1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8232 := $2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$	= $2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$
8196 := $-0^0 - 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3$	8233 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$	= $1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$
8197 := $-1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8234 := $-2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$	= $-2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$
8198 := $-0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8235 := $0^8 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $-1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$
8199 := $1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8236 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$	= $1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$
8200 := $0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8237 := $-0^0 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$	= $-1^1 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$
8201 := $-1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8238 := $4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$	= $4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$
8202 := $-0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	8239 := $0^0 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$	= $1^1 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$
8203 := $1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8240 := $-3^9 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^5$	= $-3^9 - 5^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^5$
8204 := $0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	8241 := $2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$	= $2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$
8205 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^1$	8242 := $2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$	= $2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6$
8206 := $0^6 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2$	= $1^7 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	8243 := $-1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$	= $-1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$
8207 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^1$	8244 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$	= $-1^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4$
8208 := $0^6 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2$	= $-1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	8245 := $1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$	= $1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$
8209 := $0^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^0$	= $-1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1$	8246 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5$	= $1^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4$
8210 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2$	= $1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	8247 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5$	= $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5$
8211 := $0^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0$	= $-1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2$	8248 := $0^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5$	= $1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2$
8212 := $-1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	8249 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5$	= $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5$
8213 := $1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2$	= $1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2$	8250 := $0^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5$	= $-1^1 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$
8214 := $1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	= $1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	8251 := $-2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$	= $-2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$
8215 := $0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$	8252 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$	= $-1^8 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8216 := $-2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$	= $-2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5$	8253 := $-1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$	= $-1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$
8217 := $-1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1$	= $-1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1$	8254 := $-0^0 + 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$	= $1^8 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8218 := $0^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4$	= $-1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4$	8255 := $1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$	= $1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$
8219 := $1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1$	= $1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^1$	8256 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1$	= $-1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8220 := $0^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4$	= $1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^4$	8257 := $0^6 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3$	= $-1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5$
8221 := $-2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	= $-2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	8258 := $0^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5$	= $1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
8222 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5$	= $1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8259 := $0^8 + 2^5 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5$
8223 := $2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$	= $2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$	8260 := $0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^0$	= $1^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4$
8224 := $-1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	8261 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^0$	= $-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5$
8225 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	= $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	8262 := $0^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^0$	= $1^6 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$

$$\begin{aligned}
8263 &:= 2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 2^9 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &8300 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
8264 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= -2^6 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 &8301 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= -2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8265 &:= 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &8302 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
8266 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8303 &:= -1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= -1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
8267 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8304 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
8268 &:= -1^6 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^6 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8305 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
8269 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^4 &= -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 &8306 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
8270 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8307 &:= 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
8271 &:= -1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= -1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8308 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
8272 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 &8309 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8273 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8310 &:= -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
8274 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 &= 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 &8311 &:= 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 &= 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8275 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8312 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^0 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8276 &:= 1^6 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 1^6 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8313 &:= -0^0 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 &= -1^1 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 \\
8277 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8314 &:= 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 &= 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 \\
8278 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 &8315 &:= 0^0 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 &= 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 \\
8279 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &8316 &:= 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 &= 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8280 &:= 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &8317 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8281 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 &8318 &:= 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 &= 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 \\
8282 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8319 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8283 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8320 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8284 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &8321 &:= -2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8285 &:= 0^2 + 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= 1^7 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 &8322 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8286 &:= 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &8323 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
8287 &:= -3^3 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 &= -3^3 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 + 8^4 &8324 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8288 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 &8325 &:= -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 &= -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
8289 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 &8326 &:= -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8290 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 &8327 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8291 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^0 &= -1^7 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 &8328 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8292 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 &8329 &:= 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 &= 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8293 &:= 0^2 - 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &8330 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8294 &:= -2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &8331 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8295 &:= 0^2 + 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &8332 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8296 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &8333 &:= -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8297 &:= 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 &8334 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8298 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^6 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8335 &:= 1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^6 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8299 &:= 0^2 + 1^6 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= -1^8 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 &8336 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^6 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
8337 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8374 := 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8338 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 & 8375 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8339 := -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8376 := -2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8340 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8377 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8341 := 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8378 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8342 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8379 := -0^0 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8343 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8380 := 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8344 := 0^8 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 & 8381 := 0^0 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8345 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8382 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8346 := 0^4 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 & 8383 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8347 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8384 := 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8348 := -2^6 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8385 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8349 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8386 := 0^6 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8350 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8387 := -1^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8351 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^1 & 8388 := 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8352 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8389 := 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
8353 := -2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8390 := 1^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
8354 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8391 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8355 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8392 := -1^6 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8356 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8393 := 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
8357 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & 8394 := 1^6 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8358 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 & 8395 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8359 := 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & 8396 := -1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8360 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^0 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8397 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8361 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8398 := 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8362 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8399 := 0^0 + 1^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8363 := -1^6 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 8400 := 0^6 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8364 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8401 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8365 := 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 8402 := 0^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8366 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8403 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8367 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 8404 := -1^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8368 := 0^6 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8405 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8369 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 & 8406 := 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8370 := 0^6 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 8407 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8371 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^1 & 8408 := -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8372 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 & 8409 := 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
8373 := -0^0 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 8410 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5
\end{array}$$

$8411 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$8448 := -0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8412 := 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$8449 := 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8413 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$8450 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8414 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8451 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 - 8^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5$
$8415 := 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2$	$8452 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$
$8416 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8453 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$
$8417 := 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$8454 := 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8418 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8455 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$
$8419 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8456 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
$8420 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8457 := 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
$8421 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8458 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$
$8422 := 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 2^6 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8459 := 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$
$8423 := -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8460 := -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8424 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4$	$8461 := -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8425 := 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8462 := 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8426 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$8463 := 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8427 := 0^6 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8464 := 0^2 + 2^6 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4$
$8428 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$8465 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8429 := 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8466 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1$
$8430 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$8467 := -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8431 := -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8468 := 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4$	$= 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4$
$8432 := 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$8469 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8433 := 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$8470 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8434 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	$8471 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$
$8435 := -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5$	$= -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5$	$8472 := -2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= -2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$
$8436 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$8473 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$
$8437 := 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5$	$8474 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= 1^8 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1$
$8438 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2$	$= -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2$	$8475 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8439 := 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$8476 := 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 2^6 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8440 := 0^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$8477 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$
$8441 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	$8478 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1$
$8442 := 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2$	$8479 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$
$8443 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	$8480 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8444 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$8481 := 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8445 := -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$= -1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$8482 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$8446 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	$8483 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5$
$8447 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4$	$= 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$8484 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$

$$\begin{aligned}
8485 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 &8522 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8486 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8523 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8487 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8524 &:= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
8488 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8525 &:= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
8489 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8526 &:= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
8490 &:= -3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8527 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8491 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8528 &:= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8492 &:= 0^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 &8529 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8493 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8530 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8494 &:= 0^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 &= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8531 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8495 &:= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8532 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8496 &:= 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 &8533 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8497 &:= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8534 &:= 0^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^0 &= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8498 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 &8535 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8499 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8536 &:= 0^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= 2^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
8500 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8537 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8501 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8538 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8502 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^2 &8539 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8503 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8540 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8504 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 &8541 &:= -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^1 &= -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8505 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8542 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8506 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 &8543 &:= -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8507 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8544 &:= 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8508 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 &8545 &:= 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8509 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8546 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8510 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 &8547 &:= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^3 &= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^3 \\
8511 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8548 &:= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8512 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8549 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 \\
8513 &:= -2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8550 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^3 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8514 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8551 &:= 0^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8515 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8552 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8516 &:= -0^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8553 &:= 0^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
8517 &:= 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8554 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^3 &= -1^9 + 2^6 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8518 &:= 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8555 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8519 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8556 &:= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
8520 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8557 &:= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 &= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
8521 &:= 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &= 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 &8558 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8559 &:= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 &= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 &8596 &:= 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 &= 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
8560 &:= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8597 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8561 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8598 &:= -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8562 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 &8599 &:= 0^4 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8563 &:= -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8600 &:= 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8564 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &8601 &:= 0^4 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8565 &:= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8602 &:= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8566 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 &8603 &:= 0^4 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^0 &= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
8567 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 &8604 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8568 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^2 &8605 &:= 0^4 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^0 &= -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8569 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8606 &:= 0^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8570 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &8607 &:= 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^0 &= -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
8571 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8608 &:= 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &= 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
8572 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 &8609 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8573 &:= -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8610 &:= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8574 &:= -1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &8611 &:= 0^4 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 7^0 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8575 &:= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8612 &:= -0^0 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^3 &= -1^9 + 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8576 &:= 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &8613 &:= -3^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^3 &= -3^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^3 \\
8577 &:= 0^9 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8614 &:= 0^0 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^3 &= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8578 &:= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 &8615 &:= 0^4 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^0 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8579 &:= 0^9 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8616 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
8580 &:= -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &8617 &:= 4^9 - 5^7 + 6^4 - 7^6 - 9^5 &= 4^9 - 5^7 + 6^4 - 7^6 - 9^5 \\
8581 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 - 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 - 9^2 &8618 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 &= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8582 &:= 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &8619 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8583 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 - 8^3 &8620 &:= -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
8584 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &8621 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= -1^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
8585 &:= 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3 &8622 &:= -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 &= -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8586 &:= 3^8 - 4^9 + 6^4 + 8^6 + 9^3 &= 3^8 - 4^9 + 6^4 + 8^6 + 9^3 &8623 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 &= 1^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
8587 &:= -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 - 8^3 &= -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 - 8^3 &8624 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8588 &:= 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 &8625 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8589 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8626 &:= -2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8590 &:= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 &8627 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8591 &:= 0^7 + 3^6 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 &8628 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
8592 &:= 0^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^9 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &8629 &:= -0^0 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8593 &:= -3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 &= -3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 &8630 &:= 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8594 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 &8631 &:= 0^0 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
8595 &:= -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &8632 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8633 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8670 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
8634 &:= 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8671 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8635 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8672 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
8636 &:= 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 &8673 &:= 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
8637 &:= 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 &8674 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
8638 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 &= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 &8675 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8639 &:= 1^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 &8676 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8640 &:= 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8677 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8641 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 &= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8678 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8642 &:= 0^6 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 &8679 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8643 &:= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8680 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8644 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^0 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8681 &:= 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8645 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8682 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8646 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^0 &= 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 7^1 &8683 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8647 &:= 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8684 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 &= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8648 &:= 0^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^0 &= -1^6 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 &8685 &:= 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8649 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8686 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8650 &:= 0^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^0 &= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &8687 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8651 &:= 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 7^0 &= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8688 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8652 &:= 0^8 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &8689 &:= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8653 &:= 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^0 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 &8690 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8654 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &8691 &:= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8655 &:= 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &8692 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8656 &:= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &8693 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8657 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &8694 &:= 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
8658 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 &8695 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8659 &:= 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 &8696 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8660 &:= 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &8697 &:= -2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8661 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8698 &:= 2^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 &= 2^9 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
8662 &:= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8699 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
8663 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 &8700 &:= 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 &= 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8664 &:= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 &= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 &8701 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8665 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 9^4 &8702 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
8666 &:= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &8703 &:= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
8667 &:= 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 - 9^0 &= -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^2 &8704 &:= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
8668 &:= 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 &8705 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
8669 &:= 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 + 9^0 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 &8706 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2 &= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8707 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2 &8744 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8708 &:= 0^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &8745 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8709 &:= 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &8746 &:= 0^3 + 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^0 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8710 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 &8747 &:= -2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8711 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &8748 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8712 &:= -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &8749 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8713 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 &8750 &:= 0^3 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^0 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8714 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8751 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8715 &:= -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^2 &= -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^2 &8752 &:= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 &= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
8716 &:= -0^0 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4 &8753 &:= 0^3 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8717 &:= -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 &8754 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8718 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8755 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8719 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8756 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8720 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1 &8757 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8721 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8758 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8722 &:= 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8759 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8723 &:= 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8760 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
8724 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8761 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8725 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8762 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8726 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^3 &8763 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8727 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8764 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8728 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8765 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8729 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8766 &:= -3^8 - 4^3 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6 &= -3^8 - 4^3 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6 \\
8730 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 &8767 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8731 &:= -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 &= -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 &8768 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= -1^6 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8732 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 &8769 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8733 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8770 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
8734 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 &8771 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8735 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8772 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^0 &= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
8736 &:= -2^8 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 &= -2^8 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 &8773 &:= 0^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8737 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8774 &:= 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^0 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
8738 &:= 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 9^4 &8775 &:= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
8739 &:= 0^3 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 7^1 + 9^4 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 &8776 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
8740 &:= 0^9 - 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= -2^5 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^3 &8777 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8741 &:= 0^3 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 7^1 + 9^4 &= -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 &8778 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8742 &:= 0^3 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^0 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^2 &8779 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
8743 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^2 &8780 &:= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
8781 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & 8818 := -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8782 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 & 8819 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8783 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8820 := 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
8784 := 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^4 + 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8821 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8785 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8822 := 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
8786 := -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 8823 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
8787 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8824 := -3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8788 := 0^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 8825 := 0^0 - 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8789 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8826 := 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8790 := 0^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 & 8827 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8791 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 & 8828 := 2^2 - 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = 2^2 - 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8792 := -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8829 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
8793 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8830 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8794 := 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8831 := 0^6 + 2^9 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
8795 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 8832 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8796 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8833 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
8797 := -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8834 := -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
8798 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8835 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
8799 := -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 & = -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 & 8836 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
8800 := -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8837 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
8801 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 & 8838 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8802 := 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8839 := -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
8803 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 & = 1^5 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^3 & 8840 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8804 := -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 & 8841 := 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
8805 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8842 := -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8806 := 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4 & 8843 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
8807 := 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 8844 := 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8808 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8845 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8809 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8846 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8810 := 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8847 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8811 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8848 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8812 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 8849 := 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8813 := 0^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^0 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8850 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8814 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8851 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
8815 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8852 := -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8816 := 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & 8853 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
8817 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & 8854 := 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
8855 := -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & 8892 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
8856 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8893 := 0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
8857 := 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & 8894 := -3^8 + 4^3 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6 & = -3^8 + 4^3 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6 \\
8858 := -2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^4 & 8895 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8859 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 8896 := -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8860 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8897 := 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8861 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^5 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & 8898 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
8862 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8899 := -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8863 := 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 - 8^1 & = 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 - 8^1 & 8900 := 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8864 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4 & 8901 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8865 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 + 9^3 & 8902 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
8866 := 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^3 & 8903 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8867 := 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 8904 := 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8868 := 0^1 - 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 8905 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8869 := 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 9^3 & 8906 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
8870 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8907 := 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8871 := 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & 8908 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
8872 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8909 := -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8873 := 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & 8910 := 0^6 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
8874 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8911 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8875 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 8912 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
8876 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 8913 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8877 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 8914 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8878 := -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 & 8915 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8879 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 8916 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
8880 := -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 8917 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8881 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8918 := 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8882 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8919 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8883 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8920 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
8884 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 8921 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8885 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8922 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8886 := 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8923 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
8887 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8924 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
8888 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^3 & 8925 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
8889 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & 8926 := 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
8890 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 8927 := 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^2 & = 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
8891 := 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & 8928 := 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^0 & = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
8929 &:= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 &= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 &8966 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
8930 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^0 &= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &8967 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
8931 &:= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 &8968 &:= 0^3 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
8932 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 &8969 &:= 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8933 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 &8970 &:= 0^3 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8934 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 9^4 &8971 &:= 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 \\
8935 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 &8972 &:= 0^3 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8936 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^4 &8973 &:= 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
8937 &:= 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -1^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8974 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
8938 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 - 8^0 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^3 &8975 &:= 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 &= 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^3 - 8^4 + 9^5 \\
8939 &:= 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 &8976 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8940 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^4 + 8^0 + 9^3 &= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &8977 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8941 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 &8978 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
8942 &:= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 &8979 &:= 0^9 + 3^6 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8943 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 &8980 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8944 &:= 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 &= 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 &8981 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8945 &:= 0^0 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 &= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 &8982 &:= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8946 &:= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &8983 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8947 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 &8984 &:= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 &= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
8948 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &8985 &:= 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -1^5 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 \\
8949 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 &8986 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
8950 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &8987 &:= 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8951 &:= 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8988 &:= -1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8952 &:= 0^3 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 7^4 - 8^1 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &8989 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8953 &:= 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 7^3 &8990 &:= 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8954 &:= 0^3 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 - 8^1 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 &8991 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8955 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 &8992 &:= 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
8956 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 - 9^3 &= -2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 &8993 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8957 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 &8994 &:= 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8958 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &8995 &:= 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^0 &= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
8959 &:= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &8996 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
8960 &:= 0^3 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 &8997 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
8961 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 &8998 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8962 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 &8999 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
8963 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 &9000 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
8964 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 & & & & \\
8965 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 - 9^3 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & & & &
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
9001 := 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 9038 := 0^9 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9002 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 9039 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
9003 := -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 & 9040 := 0^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9004 := 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9041 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
9005 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 - 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 & 9042 := 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
9006 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 & 9043 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
9007 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^2 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 9044 := -1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9008 := -2^5 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = -2^5 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & 9045 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^0 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
9009 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^2 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 9046 := 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9010 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^4 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^3 & 9047 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 8^3 & = 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
9011 := -1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 9048 := 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9012 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^6 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9049 := 0^9 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
9013 := 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 9050 := -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
9014 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9051 := -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 \\
9015 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 9052 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
9016 := 0^8 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 9053 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
9017 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 & 9054 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
9018 := 0^8 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 - 9^3 & 9055 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
9019 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 9056 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^1 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
9020 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9057 := 1^9 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
9021 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 9058 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^0 & = -1^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
9022 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9059 := 0^3 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
9023 := 1^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 9060 := 0^3 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^0 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
9024 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 - 9^3 & 9061 := 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
9025 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 9062 := -2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9026 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^3 & 9063 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9027 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 9064 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9028 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^3 & 9065 := -0^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9029 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 9066 := 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9030 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9067 := 0^0 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9031 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 9068 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
9032 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9069 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9033 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 9070 := 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9034 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 9071 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9035 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 9072 := 0^3 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^0 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9036 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^3 & 9073 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9037 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 9074 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9075 &:= 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 & 9112 &:= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9076 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9113 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9077 &:= 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 &= 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 & 9114 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9078 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9115 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9079 &:= 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 &= 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 9116 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9080 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 9117 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9081 &:= 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 9118 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9082 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9119 &:= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9083 &:= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 9120 &:= -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^2 &= -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^2 \\
9084 &:= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9121 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9085 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 & 9122 &:= 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9086 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9123 &:= 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9087 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 9124 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
9088 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9125 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9089 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 9126 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
9090 &:= 0^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 9127 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9091 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 9128 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3 \\
9092 &:= 0^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9129 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9093 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 9130 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9094 &:= -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9131 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9095 &:= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3 &= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3 & 9132 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9096 &:= 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9133 &:= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9097 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 - 8^1 & 9134 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
9098 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9135 &:= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9099 &:= 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 9136 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^5 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
9100 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9137 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9101 &:= -2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9138 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9102 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9139 &:= 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9103 &:= -3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 &= -3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 9140 &:= -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 - 8^2 &= -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
9104 &:= 3^8 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 &= 3^8 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 9141 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9105 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9142 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 &= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
9106 &:= -2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= -2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9143 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9107 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9144 &:= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9108 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9145 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9109 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 & 9146 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 &= -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9110 &:= 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 &= 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 9^2 & 9147 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 &= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9111 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9148 &:= 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
9149 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9186 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9150 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9187 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
9151 := -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 & = -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 & 9188 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9152 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9189 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9153 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9190 := -2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9154 := 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 & 9191 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9155 := -1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 9192 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9156 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9193 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9157 := -0^0 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9194 := 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9158 := -2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9195 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9159 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9196 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9160 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9197 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9161 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9198 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9162 := 0^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9199 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
9163 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9200 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
9164 := 0^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 - 9^1 & 9201 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9165 := 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 9202 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 & = 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9166 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^3 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^3 & 9203 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9167 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 8^3 & 9204 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9168 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^3 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^3 & 9205 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
9169 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9206 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
9170 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9207 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^3 \\
9171 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9208 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9172 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 8^3 & 9209 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9173 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9210 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9174 := 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9211 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9175 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9212 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9176 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & 9213 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9177 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9214 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9178 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9215 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
9179 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9216 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9180 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & 9217 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9181 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 8^3 & 9218 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
9182 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & 9219 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
9183 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^3 & 9220 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
9184 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 & 9221 := -0^0 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
9185 := -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9222 := -3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^5 & = -3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^5
\end{array}$$

$9223 := 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2$	$9260 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
$9224 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2$	$9261 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
$9225 := -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$9262 := -2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
$9226 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9263 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
$9227 := 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$9264 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
$9228 := -1^9 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9265 := 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$
$9229 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$9266 := 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
$9230 := 1^9 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9267 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3$
$9231 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 8^3$	$9268 := -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4$
$9232 := 0^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^0$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9269 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3$
$9233 := 0^9 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 8^3$	$9270 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 7^1 + 9^4$
$9234 := 0^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$9271 := -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$
$9235 := 0^9 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$9272 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1$
$9236 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$9273 := 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$
$9237 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$9274 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^3$
$9238 := -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9275 := 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$
$9239 := -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1$	$= -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1$	$9276 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 9^4$
$9240 := 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9277 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$
$9241 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$9278 := 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$
$9242 := 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$= 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$9279 := 0^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^0$	$= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$
$9243 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$9280 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$
$9244 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$9281 := 0^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^2$
$9245 := 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$9282 := -3^8 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= -3^8 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4$
$9246 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4$	$9283 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
$9247 := -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$9284 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4$
$9248 := 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$= 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$9285 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
$9249 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$9286 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
$9250 := -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$9287 := -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
$9251 := 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1 + 9^4$	$9288 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$
$9252 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$9289 := 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
$9253 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$9290 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$
$9254 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$9291 := 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
$9255 := -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$9292 := 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$
$9256 := 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$9293 := 1^5 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
$9257 := 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$9294 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$
$9258 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$9295 := 3^6 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 3^6 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 7^3 + 8^4$
$9259 := 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$9296 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$

9297 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	9334 := $-1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$
9298 := $2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$= 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	9335 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$
9299 := $0^0 + 2^8 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^3$	9336 := $1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$
9300 := $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$	9337 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4$
9301 := $0^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$	9338 := $0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^0$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1$
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9303 := $-1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9340 := $3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3$
9304 := $-3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	9341 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3$
9305 := $1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9342 := $0^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^0$	$= -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^2$
9306 := $0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^2$	9343 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3$
9307 := $-1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^3$	9344 := $0^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^0$	$= -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^3$
9308 := $0^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9345 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^3$
9309 := $0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^3$	9346 := $2^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^2$	$= 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^2$
9310 := $0^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9347 := $0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$
9311 := $0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$	9348 := $0^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$
9312 := $0^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$	9349 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3$
9313 := $0^1 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$	9350 := $-1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^1$
9314 := $0^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 9^4$	9351 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3$
9315 := $1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$	9352 := $-1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$
9316 := $-0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 9^4$	9353 := $-3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5$	$= -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5$
9317 := $-1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9354 := $1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$
9318 := $-2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4$	$= -2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4$	9355 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$	$= 1^6 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 - 9^4$
9319 := $1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9356 := $0^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^1$
9320 := $0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^7 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	9357 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9321 := $0^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$	9358 := $-2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9322 := $0^7 - 3^6 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	9359 := $-0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9323 := $0^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 7^0 + 9^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^3$	9360 := $-2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9324 := $0^7 - 3^6 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -2^5 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3$	9361 := $0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9325 := $0^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^0 + 9^4$	$= -1^5 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3$	9362 := $0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^0$	$= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$
9326 := $0^2 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9363 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9327 := $1^5 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3$	9364 := $0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 - 8^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$
9328 := $0^2 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9365 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9329 := $-0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$	9366 := $0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$
9330 := $-2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$	$= -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$	9367 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9331 := $0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3$	9368 := $-1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$
9332 := $-0^0 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 9^4$	9369 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9333 := $-2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	9370 := $1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$

$9371 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$9408 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$
$9372 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$9409 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^2$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^2$
$9373 := 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 9^4$	$9410 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$
$9374 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$9411 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3$
$9375 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$9412 := 0^9 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 + 9^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9376 := 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$9413 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$
$9377 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^3$	$9414 := -2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9378 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^1$	$9415 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$
$9379 := 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$= 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$9416 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2$
$9380 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^7 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9417 := -0^0 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9381 := -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 - 9^4$	$9418 := -4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9382 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2$	$9419 := 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9383 := 0^7 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 - 9^4$	$9420 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9384 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9421 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$
$9385 := 0^7 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2$	$9422 := 2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$9386 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$9423 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$
$9387 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$9424 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2$
$9388 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$9425 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9389 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$9426 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9390 := -0^0 - 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^7 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9427 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9391 := -3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9428 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2$
$9392 := 0^0 - 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9429 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9393 := 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$9430 := 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$	$= 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9394 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1$	$9431 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0$	$= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9395 := 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$9432 := 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$
$9396 := 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1$	$9433 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^2$
$9397 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1$	$9434 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^3$
$9398 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^2 - 7^5 + 9^4$	$= -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^2 - 7^5 + 9^4$	$9435 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$
$9399 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$9436 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$	$= -1^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3$
$9400 := -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$= -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$9437 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$
$9401 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$9438 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$	$= -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4$
$9402 := -0^0 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$9439 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$
$9403 := -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$9440 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$	$= 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4$
$9404 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$9441 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$
$9405 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 - 9^3$	$9442 := -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 - 9^4$
$9406 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$9443 := 0^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1$
$9407 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^2$	$9444 := -0^0 + 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$

$$\begin{array}{l}
9445 := 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9446 := 0^0 + 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9447 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9448 := -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9449 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9450 := 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9451 := 0^3 - 1^7 - 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9452 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9453 := -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
9454 := 0^9 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^0 - 9^4 \\
9455 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9456 := 0^9 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^0 - 9^4 \\
9457 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9458 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9459 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9460 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9461 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9462 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9463 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9464 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9465 := -1^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9466 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9467 := 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9468 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
9469 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^0 \\
9470 := 0^7 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9471 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^0 \\
9472 := 0^7 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9473 := 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9474 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9475 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9476 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9477 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9478 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9479 := 0^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^0 \\
9480 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9481 := 0^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^0 \\
9482 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9483 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9484 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9485 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9486 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9487 := -1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
9488 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
9489 := 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
9490 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
9491 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9492 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9493 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9494 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9495 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9496 := 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9497 := 0^2 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^0 \\
9498 := -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 \\
9499 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9500 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^0 - 7^5 + 9^4 \\
9501 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9502 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9503 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9504 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9505 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9506 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9507 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9508 := 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9509 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9510 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9511 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9512 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9513 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9514 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9515 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9516 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9517 := 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9518 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9445 := 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9446 := 1^1 + 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9447 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9448 := -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9449 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9450 := 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9451 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
9452 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9453 := -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
9454 := -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
9455 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9456 := 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
9457 := 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9458 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9459 := -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9460 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
9461 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9462 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
9463 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
9464 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
9465 := -1^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9466 := 1^8 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^4 \\
9467 := 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9468 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
9469 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9470 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
9471 := 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9472 := -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9473 := 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^1 \\
9474 := 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9475 := -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9476 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9477 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9478 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9479 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9480 := 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9481 := -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9482 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9483 := 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9484 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9485 := -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9486 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9487 := -1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
9488 := 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9489 := 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
9490 := -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9491 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9492 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9493 := 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9494 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
9495 := -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9496 := 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9497 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9498 := -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 \\
9499 := -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
9500 := -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
9501 := -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9502 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9503 := 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9504 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9505 := 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9506 := 1^9 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9507 := -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9508 := 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9509 := 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9510 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
9511 := 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9512 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
9513 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9514 := 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9515 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
9516 := -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9517 := 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9518 := 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9519 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 &9556 &:= 0^7 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^0 &= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^3 \\
9520 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &9557 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9521 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &9558 &:= 0^7 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^0 &= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^3 \\
9522 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^4 &9559 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9523 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^0 - 8^3 &= 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3 + 9^4 &9560 &:= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
9524 &:= 0^9 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 &= 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 + 9^4 &9561 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9525 &:= 0^8 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^0 - 8^3 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 8^1 &9562 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
9526 &:= -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 &9563 &:= 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^3 - 7^5 + 9^4 &= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 8^2 \\
9527 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9564 &:= -1^7 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^1 &= -1^7 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
9528 &:= -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9565 &:= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9529 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9566 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
9530 &:= -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 &9567 &:= 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^4 &= 3^9 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^4 \\
9531 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &9568 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
9532 &:= -3^8 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 &= -3^8 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 &9569 &:= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9533 &:= 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 - 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 - 9^3 &9570 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= 1^7 - 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9534 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9571 &:= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 &= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9535 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9572 &:= 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
9536 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9573 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9537 &:= 0^5 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^0 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^2 &9574 &:= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9538 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^2 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 &9575 &:= 0^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^3 &= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9539 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 &9576 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 &= -1^7 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9540 &:= -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &= -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 &9577 &:= 0^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 &= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9541 &:= -3^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3 + 8^5 &= -3^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3 + 8^5 &9578 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 &= 1^7 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
9542 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &9579 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 &= 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9543 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &9580 &:= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 &= -2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
9544 &:= -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 &= -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 &9581 &:= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9545 &:= 0^4 + 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9582 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
9546 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 &9583 &:= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &= 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
9547 &:= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 &9584 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
9548 &:= -1^9 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^4 &9585 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9549 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &9586 &:= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 &= 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
9550 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &9587 &:= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9551 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 &9588 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
9552 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 &9589 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9553 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^3 &= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 - 8^2 &9590 &:= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^2 &= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
9554 &:= 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^3 &= 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^3 &9591 &:= 0^5 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
9555 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^2 &9592 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
9593 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^1 & 9630 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9594 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 9631 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 \\
9595 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^1 & 9632 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9596 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 9633 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9597 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9634 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9598 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 9635 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9599 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 9636 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
9600 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 9637 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
9601 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 9638 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
9602 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 9639 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
9603 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^4 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9640 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9604 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^2 & 9641 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 - 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
9605 := -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^2 & 9642 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9606 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9643 := -0^0 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
9607 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 9644 := 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 & = 2^5 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
9608 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 9645 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9609 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 9646 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9610 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 8^3 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9647 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
9611 := -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 8^3 & = -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 8^3 & 9648 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
9612 := -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 & 9649 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9613 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9650 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9614 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9651 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9615 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9652 := 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9616 := 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 9653 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
9617 := 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 9654 := -1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9618 := -1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9655 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9619 := 0^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9656 := 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9620 := 1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9657 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9621 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9658 := 0^9 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9622 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9659 := 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
9623 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9660 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9624 := -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9661 := 0^1 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9625 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9662 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9626 := 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9663 := -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
9627 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 9664 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9628 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9665 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
9629 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 & 9666 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
9667 &:= -1^9 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9704 &:= -2^9 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^4 &= -2^9 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^4 \\
9668 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9705 &:= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9669 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9706 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9670 &:= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 &= -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9707 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
9671 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9708 &:= -1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9672 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9709 &:= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 &= 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
9673 &:= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9710 &:= 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9674 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9711 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
9675 &:= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9712 &:= 0^9 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9676 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9713 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9677 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9714 &:= 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9678 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9715 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9679 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 & 9716 &:= -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9680 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9717 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9681 &:= -1^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9718 &:= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9682 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9719 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9683 &:= 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9720 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9684 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 &= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9721 &:= 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
9685 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9722 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9686 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 9723 &:= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
9687 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9724 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
9688 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= -1^9 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9725 &:= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
9689 &:= -1^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9726 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9690 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9727 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9691 &:= 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9728 &:= -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\
9692 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 & 9729 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9693 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9730 &:= 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\
9694 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 & 9731 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9695 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9732 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
9696 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9733 &:= 0^7 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4 \\
9697 &:= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9734 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
9698 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9735 &:= 0^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
9699 &:= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9736 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
9700 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9737 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9701 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9738 &:= -1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= -1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\
9702 &:= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 &= 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9739 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9703 &:= 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9740 &:= 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 &= 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
9741 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9778 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
9742 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9779 := 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
9743 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9780 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
9744 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9781 := 0^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
9745 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9782 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
9746 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9783 := 0^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
9747 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9784 := -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
9748 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9785 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 - 8^0 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9749 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9786 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9750 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9787 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
9751 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9788 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9752 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9789 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
9753 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9790 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9754 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9791 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
9755 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9792 := -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9756 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9793 := 0^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
9757 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9794 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9758 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9795 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
9759 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9796 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
9760 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 9797 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
9761 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9798 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9762 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 9799 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^2 \\
9763 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^1 & 9800 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9764 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^0 & = 1^9 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9801 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9765 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 & 9802 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9766 := 0^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 & 9803 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9767 := -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 & 9804 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9768 := 0^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^2 & = -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9805 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^6 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
9769 := -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 & 9806 := -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9770 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9807 := 0^9 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
9771 := -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9808 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9772 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 9809 := 0^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
9773 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9810 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9774 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^2 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^2 & 9811 := -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9775 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9812 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
9776 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 9813 := 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
9777 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 9814 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

9815 := $-1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9852 := $-1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^4$
9816 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9853 := $2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$
9817 := $1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9854 := $1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^4$
9818 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4$	9855 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$
9819 := $-1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9856 := $-1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$
9820 := $0^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^4$	9857 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^4 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$
9821 := $0^1 - 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9858 := $1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$
9822 := $0^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2$	9859 := $0^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^0 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 - 9^4$
9823 := $0^1 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2$	9860 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9824 := $0^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2$	9861 := $0^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^4$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^4$
9825 := $0^1 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9862 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9826 := $0^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1$	9863 := $0^4 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$
9827 := $1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9864 := $0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9828 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9865 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$
9829 := $-1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9866 := $-1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9830 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1$	9867 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9831 := $1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9868 := $1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9832 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1$	9869 := $-1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9833 := $-1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9870 := $-2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9834 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9871 := $0^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9835 := $1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	9872 := $-0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9836 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1$	9873 := $3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9837 := $0^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^0$	$= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^2$	9874 := $0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9838 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9875 := $1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9839 := $0^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^3$	9876 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9840 := $0^1 + 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9877 := $2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9841 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^2$	9878 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^4 + 8^3$
9842 := $-1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9879 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9843 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 - 9^4$	9880 := $0^4 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 8^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1$
9844 := $1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	9881 := $0^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9845 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1$	9882 := $-1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9846 := $1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1$	9883 := $1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^4$
9847 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$	9884 := $1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4$
9848 := $-3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -3^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	9885 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9849 := $0^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1$	9886 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^2$
9850 := $0^1 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^4$	9887 := $2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3$	$= 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3$
9851 := $0^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^5 - 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3$	9888 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2$

$$\begin{aligned}
9889 &:= 0^3 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^0 &= 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 &9926 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
9890 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 &9927 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
9891 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &9928 &:= 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9892 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1 &9929 &:= 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9893 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &= -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &9930 &:= 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9894 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 &9931 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 \\
9895 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &= 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &9932 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 &= -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9896 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 &9933 &:= 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 &= 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9897 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^0 &= 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 &9934 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9898 &:= 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 &9935 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 \\
9899 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^0 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^1 &9936 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9900 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^0 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9937 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 &= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 \\
9901 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 8^0 &= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9938 &:= -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 &= -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
9902 &:= -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2 &= -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2 &9939 &:= 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
9903 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^0 &= 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 &9940 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
9904 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^0 &= -1^3 - 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 &9941 &:= -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 &= -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
9905 &:= 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &9942 &:= 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 &= 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
9906 &:= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9943 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
9907 &:= 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 &= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &9944 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9908 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9945 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 &= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9909 &:= -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &9946 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 &= 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
9910 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9947 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^0 &= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9911 &:= 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &9948 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^3 \\
9912 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9949 &:= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9913 &:= -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 &= -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 &9950 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9914 &:= 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 &= 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 &9951 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9915 &:= 4^9 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 &= 4^9 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 &9952 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9916 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9953 &:= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9917 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9954 &:= 0^3 - 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9918 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^4 &9955 &:= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9919 &:= 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 &= 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 &9956 &:= 0^3 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^1 &= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^1 \\
9920 &:= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 &9957 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^4 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9921 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 &9958 &:= 0^3 - 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
9922 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &9959 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^1 \\
9923 &:= -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &9960 &:= 0^3 + 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0 &= 1^6 + 2^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
9924 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1 &9961 &:= 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 7^0 &= -2^6 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
9925 &:= 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &= 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 &9962 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^2 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^2
\end{aligned}$$

9963 := $0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2$	9983 := $2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4$	$= 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4$
9964 := $-0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	9984 := $0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9965 := $-2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	$= -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	9985 := $2^3 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4$
9966 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	9986 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9967 := $-2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3$	$= -2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3$	9987 := $-2^4 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -2^4 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$
9968 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^2$	9988 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9969 := $1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2$	9989 := $2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9970 := $0^3 + 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^1$	9990 := $0^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9971 := $0^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^0$	$= 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$	9991 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9972 := $0^3 + 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	9992 := $-1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9973 := $-2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	9993 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 + 9^4$
9974 := $0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	9994 := $1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9975 := $-2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$	9995 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2$
9976 := $0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$	9996 := $0^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9977 := $0^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 + 9^4$	9997 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$
9978 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	9998 := $0^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$
9979 := $-2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^2$	9999 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$
9980 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10000 := $-1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$
9981 := $0^6 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= -2^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2$		
9982 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$		
10001 := $2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^4$	10018 := $1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1$
10002 := $1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10019 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^7 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10003 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	10020 := $-1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1$
10004 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10021 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$
10005 := $-2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10022 := $1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1$
10006 := $0^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10023 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 - 9^4$
10007 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	10024 := $0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^0$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2$
10008 := $-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10025 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0$	$= 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 7^3 + 8^5$
10009 := $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	10026 := $0^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2$
10010 := $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10027 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10011 := $1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^4$	10028 := $0^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^0$	$= -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1$
10012 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10029 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2$
10013 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	10030 := $0^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1$
10014 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	10031 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^2$
10015 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^2$	10032 := $-4^5 - 5^8 + 6^7 + 7^6 + 8^4$	$= -4^5 - 5^8 + 6^7 + 7^6 + 8^4$
10016 := $0^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 9^4$	10033 := $0^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^0$	$= 1^7 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^1$
10017 := $2^3 - 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	10034 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
\mathbf{10035} := 0^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^0 & = -3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^3 & \mathbf{10072} := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10036} := -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^1 & \mathbf{10073} := -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10037} := 0^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^0 & = -1^6 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & \mathbf{10074} := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10038} := 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^1 & \mathbf{10075} := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^1 + 8^4 - 9^5 \\
\mathbf{10039} := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = 1^6 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & \mathbf{10076} := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10040} := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & \mathbf{10077} := -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 & = -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10041} := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^8 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 & \mathbf{10078} := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10042} := -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & \mathbf{10079} := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = 1^6 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
\mathbf{10043} := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^8 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 & \mathbf{10080} := -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
\mathbf{10044} := 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & \mathbf{10081} := -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{10045} := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & \mathbf{10082} := 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
\mathbf{10046} := -2^9 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -2^9 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & \mathbf{10083} := 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{10047} := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & \mathbf{10084} := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10048} := -0^0 - 4^9 + 5^6 + 6^7 - 7^5 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & \mathbf{10085} := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{10049} := -4^9 + 5^6 + 6^7 - 7^5 - 9^4 & = -4^9 + 5^6 + 6^7 - 7^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10086} := -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{10050} := 0^0 - 4^9 + 5^6 + 6^7 - 7^5 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & \mathbf{10087} := 0^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{10051} := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10088} := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10052} := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^1 & \mathbf{10089} := 0^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
\mathbf{10053} := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10090} := 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{10054} := -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & \mathbf{10091} := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
\mathbf{10055} := 0^3 - 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10092} := -2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{10056} := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10093} := -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{10057} := -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10094} := -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{10058} := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10095} := 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{10059} := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & \mathbf{10096} := 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{10060} := -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10097} := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
\mathbf{10061} := 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10098} := -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
\mathbf{10062} := 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10099} := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{10063} := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = -2^9 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 9^4 & \mathbf{10100} := 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{10064} := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10101} := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{10065} := 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10102} := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10066} := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10103} := 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10067} := -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & \mathbf{10104} := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{10068} := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{10105} := -3^8 - 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3 + 8^5 & = -3^8 - 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3 + 8^5 \\
\mathbf{10069} := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^0 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & \mathbf{10106} := -2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
\mathbf{10070} := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 & \mathbf{10107} := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
\mathbf{10071} := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & \mathbf{10108} := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10109 := -2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10146 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
10110 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10147 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10111 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10148 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 - 8^3 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
10112 := -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10149 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10113 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10150 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10114 := 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10151 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 \\
10115 := -3^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 10152 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10116 := 0^7 - 2^2 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10153 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10117 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 & 10154 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10118 := 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 & = 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 & 10155 := 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
10119 := -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = -2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 & 10156 := 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
10120 := 0^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^3 & 10157 := -1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 & = -1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
10121 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 & 10158 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10122 := 0^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 8^3 & 10159 := 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 & = 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
10123 := 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & 10160 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10124 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10161 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10125 := 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10162 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10126 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10163 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
10127 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 10164 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10128 := -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & 10165 := 0^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^0 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^3 \\
10129 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 10166 := -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10130 := 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & 10167 := 0^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10131 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 10168 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10132 := 0^7 - 3^8 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10169 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
10133 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^7 - 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10170 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10134 := 0^7 - 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 & 10171 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
10135 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10172 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10136 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10173 := -1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = -1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
10137 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 10174 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
10138 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 10175 := 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 \\
10139 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 & 10176 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
10140 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 10177 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10141 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & 10178 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 \\
10142 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10179 := -1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 \\
10143 := 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10180 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10144 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4 & 10181 := -2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10145 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^3 & 10182 := 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

10183 := $0^0 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10220 := $-2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= -2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$
10184 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10221 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$
10185 := $2^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2$	$= 2^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2$	10222 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10186 := $0^1 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10223 := $1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2$
10187 := $0^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^0$	$= 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10224 := $0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^5 + 3^3 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^1$
10188 := $-1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^1$	10225 := $0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3$
10189 := $0^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10226 := $2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3$
10190 := $-1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3$	10227 := $0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^2$
10191 := $-1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^3$	10228 := $0^7 + 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10192 := $1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^3$	10229 := $-3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^4$	$= -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^4$
10193 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10230 := $2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3$
10194 := $-2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10231 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3$
10195 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10232 := $-1^7 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 + 8^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 + 8^5$
10196 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^3$	10233 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^2$
10197 := $-0^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10234 := $-0^0 - 1^9 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1$
10198 := $3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10235 := $-1^9 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$
10199 := $0^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10236 := $0^3 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10200 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	10237 := $1^9 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$
10201 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10238 := $0^3 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10202 := $2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10239 := $0^3 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^4$
10203 := $3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$= 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	10240 := $0^9 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10204 := $0^0 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	10241 := $2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10205 := $1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^3$	10242 := $0^9 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10206 := $1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^3$	10243 := $0^3 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^0$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10207 := $2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^4$	10244 := $-0^0 - 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^3$
10208 := $1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^1$	10245 := $-1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10209 := $2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10246 := $2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^2$
10210 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10247 := $1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10211 := $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10248 := $0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10212 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10249 := $0^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10213 := $-0^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10250 := $3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^4$	$= 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^4$
10214 := $2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10251 := $0^7 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10215 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10252 := $0^3 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10216 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10253 := $-1^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10217 := $-2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	10254 := $0^3 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$
10218 := $0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10255 := $1^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10219 := $-0^0 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^3$	10256 := $0^3 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1$

10257 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^3$	10294 := $-1^9 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 9^4$
10258 := $-0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10295 := $0^5 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^0$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10259 := $2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10296 := $-1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10260 := $0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10297 := $0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10261 := $0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$	10298 := $2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^3$
10262 := $0^7 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^0$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	10299 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10263 := $0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$	10300 := $-1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10264 := $0^7 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10301 := $-0^0 + 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$
10265 := $-2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$= -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2$	10302 := $1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10266 := $-0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10303 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$
10267 := $-2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	10304 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10268 := $0^0 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	10305 := $0^6 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^5 + 7^3$
10269 := $-0^0 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$	10306 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10270 := $-2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$	$= -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$	10307 := $0^6 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -2^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2$
10271 := $2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10308 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10272 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	10309 := $-1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10273 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	10310 := $-1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10274 := $1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	10311 := $1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10275 := $-1^6 + 2^7 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^7 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$	10312 := $1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10276 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^3$	10313 := $0^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$
10277 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^3$	10314 := $0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$
10278 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^3$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	10315 := $0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10279 := $0^6 + 2^7 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10316 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4$
10280 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	10317 := $-1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10281 := $0^6 + 2^7 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10318 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$
10282 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10319 := $1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10283 := $-0^0 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$	10320 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$
10284 := $2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	10321 := $-1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10285 := $-0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10322 := $0^6 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$
10286 := $2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10323 := $1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^3 + 8^4$
10287 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10324 := $1^7 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^7 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$
10288 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10325 := $0^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^3$
10289 := $-0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^3$	10326 := $-0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^4$
10290 := $-2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$	10327 := $-1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$
10291 := $0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2$	10328 := $-0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10292 := $0^7 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^2 - 9^4$	10329 := $1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$
10293 := $0^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^0$	$= -1^6 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$	10330 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10331 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 & 10368 := -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = -2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
10332 := 0^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 10369 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10333 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 & 10370 := 0^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10334 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 10371 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10335 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10372 := 0^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10336 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & 10373 := 0^1 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10337 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^3 & 10374 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10338 := 0^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^4 & 10375 := -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10339 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^3 & 10376 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 \\
10340 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10377 := 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^6 & = 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^6 \\
10341 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 10378 := -0^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10342 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10379 := 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10343 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 10380 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10344 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 10381 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
10345 := 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 10382 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10346 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 10383 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10347 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^3 & 10384 := 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10348 := 0^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^3 & 10385 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10349 := -1^4 - 4^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = -1^4 - 4^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & 10386 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10350 := 0^2 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 10387 := 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
10351 := -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 10388 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10352 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 10389 := 0^9 + 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10353 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 10390 := -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
10354 := 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 10391 := 0^9 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
10355 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 10392 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10356 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 10393 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10357 := 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 10394 := 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10358 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 10395 := 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10359 := 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^5 + 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^5 + 8^4 & 10396 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10360 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 10397 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^3 & = 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^3 \\
10361 := -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 10398 := 0^3 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10362 := -1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10399 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
10363 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 10400 := 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
10364 := 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 10401 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
10365 := -0^0 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^1 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^5 & 10402 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
10366 := -3^8 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^5 & = -3^8 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^5 & 10403 := -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10367 := 0^0 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^5 & = 1^1 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^5 & 10404 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10405 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 10442 := 0^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10406 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 & 10443 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10407 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 10444 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10408 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 & 10445 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10409 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 10446 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10410 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 10447 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10411 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 10448 := -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
10412 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 10449 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10413 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 10450 := 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
10414 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^3 & = -2^4 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 10451 := -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10415 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & 10452 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
10416 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & 10453 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10417 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & 10454 := 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10418 := 0^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & 10455 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10419 := -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 & 10456 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^3 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^3 \\
10420 := 0^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & 10457 := -3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = -3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
10421 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 10458 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10422 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & 10459 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 8^3 \\
10423 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^3 & 10460 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10424 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & 10461 := 0^8 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
10425 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 & 10462 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^3 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
10426 := 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^3 + 8^4 & 10463 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
10427 := -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 & 10464 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 7^0 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
10428 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 10465 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
10429 := -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10466 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
10430 := 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & 10467 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
10431 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10468 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
10432 := -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & 10469 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = 1^4 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
10433 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10470 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
10434 := 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 8^1 & 10471 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
10435 := 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & 10472 := 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
10436 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 10473 := 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
10437 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10474 := 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10438 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 10475 := -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10439 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10476 := -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
10440 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 10477 := 0^8 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10441 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^0 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10478 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10479 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10516 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10480 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & 10517 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10481 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^3 & 10518 := 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
10482 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & 10519 := 0^4 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10483 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10520 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
10484 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10521 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
10485 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10522 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 \\
10486 := 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 & 10523 := 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10487 := 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 + 9^4 & 10524 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10488 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10525 := 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10489 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10526 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
10490 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10527 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10491 := 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 10528 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
10492 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10529 := 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10493 := -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10530 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
10494 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10531 := 0^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10495 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10532 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
10496 := 1^8 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & 10533 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10497 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10534 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10498 := -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & 10535 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10499 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = -1^9 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 & 10536 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10500 := 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & 10537 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10501 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 & 10538 := -2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
10502 := 0^8 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10539 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10503 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10540 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
10504 := 0^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10541 := -0^0 - 3^8 - 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10505 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10542 := -3^8 - 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -3^8 - 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
10506 := 0^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10543 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10507 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^1 + 8^4 & 10544 := -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10508 := 0^8 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 10545 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10509 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 10546 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10510 := -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 10547 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10511 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 10548 := 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10512 := 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 10549 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10513 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10550 := 0^9 - 3^7 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^5 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10514 := -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 & = -2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 & 10551 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10515 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10552 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^4 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10553 := -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 8^4 & 10590 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10554 := 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & 10591 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10555 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10592 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10556 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10593 := 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10557 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10594 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10558 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10595 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10559 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^8 - 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10596 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10560 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10597 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10561 := 0^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10598 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 \\
10562 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 10599 := 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10563 := 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & 10600 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10564 := 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & 10601 := 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
10565 := -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 10602 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10566 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 10603 := 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
10567 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 10604 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10568 := 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 10605 := -2^7 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -2^7 - 3^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
10569 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10606 := 2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 9^6 & = 2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 9^6 \\
10570 := -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 10607 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
10571 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 10608 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10572 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 10609 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^9 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10573 := 0^2 - 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^2 + 8^4 & 10610 := -2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = -2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
10574 := -2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 9^6 & = -2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 9^6 & 10611 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^9 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10575 := -1^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & 10612 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
10576 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 10613 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 9^6 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10577 := 1^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & 10614 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10578 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 & 10615 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10579 := 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^1 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^1 + 8^4 - 9^5 & 10616 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10580 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & = 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10617 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10581 := 0^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 8^4 & 10618 := -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10582 := 0^9 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10619 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10583 := 0^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & 10620 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10584 := 0^9 + 4^8 + 5^0 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10621 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10585 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 & 10622 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10586 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 10623 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10587 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10624 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10588 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & 10625 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10589 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 & 10626 := 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = 2^3 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10627 := 0^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 10664 := 1^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10628 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 10665 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10629 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^2 & 10666 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
10630 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 10667 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10631 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 9^6 & 10668 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
10632 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10669 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10633 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10670 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 \\
10634 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10671 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10635 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & 10672 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10636 := 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 & 10673 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10637 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & 10674 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10638 := 0^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 9^6 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10675 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10639 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 10676 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10640 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10677 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10641 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^9 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & 10678 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
10642 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10679 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10643 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 10680 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10644 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10681 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10645 := -1^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^6 & = -1^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^6 & 10682 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 \\
10646 := 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & 10683 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10647 := 1^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^6 & = 1^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^6 & 10684 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
10648 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10685 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10649 := 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 & 10686 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10650 := -1^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 10687 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10651 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 & 10688 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
10652 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & 10689 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10653 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = -3^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 10690 := -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10654 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & 10691 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
10655 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 & = -2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 10692 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10656 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & 10693 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10657 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^1 + 8^4 & 10694 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10658 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & 10695 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10659 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10696 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
10660 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & 10697 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10661 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10698 := 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10662 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & 10699 := 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^2 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10663 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 10700 := 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10701 := 0^5 + 3^0 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10738 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^4 \\
10702 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 & 10739 := 0^4 - 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10703 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^6 & = -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 10740 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10704 := 2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^6 & = 2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^6 & 10741 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10705 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^6 & = 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 10742 := -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
10706 := 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 10743 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10707 := 0^9 - 3^0 + 4^8 + 5^3 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & 10744 := 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 \\
10708 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^0 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 & 10745 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10709 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 10746 := -1^7 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 \\
10710 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 & 10747 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
10711 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & 10748 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10712 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 10749 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10713 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 & 10750 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10714 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 10751 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
10715 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 10752 := -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
10716 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10753 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10717 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10754 := 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
10718 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10755 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10719 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 8^4 & 10756 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10720 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10757 := 0^7 - 3^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10721 := 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10758 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^4 & = -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
10722 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10759 := 0^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 \\
10723 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 10760 := 0^1 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10724 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10761 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^1 + 8^4 \\
10725 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10762 := -1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
10726 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 & 10763 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10727 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 10764 := 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
10728 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10765 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10729 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 & 10766 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10730 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10767 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10731 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 & 10768 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
10732 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10769 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10733 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10770 := 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 & = 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10734 := -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10771 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10735 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10772 := 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 7^5 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
10736 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^2 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 10773 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10737 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 10774 := -0^0 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10775 := -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 & = -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 & 10812 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10776 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 10813 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 + 9^4 \\
10777 := -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10814 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10778 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 8^4 & 10815 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
10779 := 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10816 := -2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
10780 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 10817 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10781 := 0^5 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10818 := 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
10782 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 10819 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10783 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10820 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10784 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 10821 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10785 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10822 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
10786 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 10823 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
10787 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10824 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10788 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^4 & 10825 := -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
10789 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10826 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10790 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10827 := -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10791 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 & 10828 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10792 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 10829 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
10793 := -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^6 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 8^4 & 10830 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10794 := -2^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -2^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & 10831 := -3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10795 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10832 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10796 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & 10833 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
10797 := -0^0 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^1 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & 10834 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10798 := -3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & 10835 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10799 := 0^0 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = 1^1 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & 10836 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10800 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & 10837 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10801 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10838 := 1^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10802 := 2^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = 2^2 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & 10839 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^2 + 8^4 \\
10803 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & 10840 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10804 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 & 10841 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10805 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & 10842 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10806 := 0^7 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 & 10843 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 \\
10807 := -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^1 + 8^4 & 10844 := -0^0 - 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
10808 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 & 10845 := -3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
10809 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10846 := 0^0 - 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 \\
10810 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 & 10847 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
10811 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 10848 := -1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1
\end{array}$$

10849 := $-1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^1$	10886 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$
10850 := $1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1$	10887 := $-0^0 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$	$= -1^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$
10851 := $-1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4$	10888 := $-3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$	$= -3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$
10852 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10889 := $0^0 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$	$= 1^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$
10853 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10890 := $-2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3$	$= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3$
10854 := $-2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10891 := $-3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3$
10855 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10892 := $2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$	$= 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$
10856 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10893 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6$
10857 := $-0^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10894 := $0^9 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^3 - 9^4$	$= 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^1$
10858 := $4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10895 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4$
10859 := $0^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10896 := $0^9 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$
10860 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10897 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4$
10861 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10898 := $2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4$	$= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4$
10862 := $2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10899 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 7^2 + 8^4$
10863 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10900 := $-0^0 - 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6$	$= -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$
10864 := $-1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	10901 := $-3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6$	$= -3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6$
10865 := $1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4$	10902 := $0^0 - 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6$	$= 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$
10866 := $1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 8^1$	10903 := $0^7 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$	$= 1^7 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^4$
10867 := $1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^1$	10904 := $2^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$= 2^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 + 8^2$
10868 := $-1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	10905 := $0^7 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$	$= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10869 := $-1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	10906 := $-1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3$
10870 := $1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	10907 := $0^2 - 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^0 + 9^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
10871 := $1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	10908 := $-0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10872 := $0^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 6^3 + 8^4$	$= -3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^3$	10909 := $-3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10873 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^0$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	10910 := $-0^0 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$
10874 := $0^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10911 := $2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$	$= 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$
10875 := $-1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	10912 := $0^0 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$
10876 := $-1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	$= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	10913 := $2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4$
10877 := $1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	10914 := $-0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3$
10878 := $1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	$= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4$	10915 := $-1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4$
10879 := $3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^3$	$= 3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^3$	10916 := $-1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3$
10880 := $-1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= -1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	10917 := $0^6 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^4$
10881 := $-2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10918 := $-1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3$
10882 := $1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^1$	10919 := $-0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10883 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4$	10920 := $-2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4$
10884 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10921 := $-2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$
10885 := $3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4$	10922 := $0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10923 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^2 & 10960 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10924 := 0^7 - 3^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 + 8^5 & = 1^4 - 3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 - 9^1 & 10961 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10925 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^2 & 10962 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
10926 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 - 8^0 + 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 & 10963 := 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10927 := -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 & 10964 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10928 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^0 + 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 & 10965 := 2^9 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 - 9^3 & = 2^9 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 - 9^3 \\
10929 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 10966 := 1^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10930 := 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^7 - 3^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 + 8^5 & 10967 := -1^3 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
10931 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10968 := 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
10932 := -2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10969 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10933 := -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 10970 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10934 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & 10971 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10935 := -0^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10972 := 0^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
10936 := 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10973 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 8^2 \\
10937 := 0^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10974 := 0^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10938 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & 10975 := -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 & = -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 \\
10939 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10976 := 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = 1^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10940 := 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10977 := -2^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = -2^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 \\
10941 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 10978 := 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10942 := -0^0 + 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 & 10979 := 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
10943 := 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 10980 := 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 \\
10944 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10981 := 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10945 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10982 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
10946 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 & 10983 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10947 := -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 10984 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
10948 := 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 - 9^3 & 10985 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10949 := -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10986 := -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10950 := 0^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^0 + 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 10987 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10951 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10988 := 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
10952 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & 10989 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 \\
10953 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & = 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & 10990 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
10954 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^2 & 10991 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
10955 := 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^4 & 10992 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
10956 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & 10993 := 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10957 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & 10994 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^5 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
10958 := 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & 10995 := -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
10959 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & 10996 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
10997 := 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11000 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
10998 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 & & \\
10999 := 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & & \\
\\
11001 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11035 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11002 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & 11036 := 1^7 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11003 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11037 := 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11004 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 11038 := -2^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
11005 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11039 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
11006 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 11040 := -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11007 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11041 := 2^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = 2^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 \\
11008 := 0^6 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 - 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 11042 := 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11009 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11043 := -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11010 := 0^6 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 - 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 11044 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11011 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11045 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 8^0 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
11012 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^9 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 & 11046 := -0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11013 := -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11047 := 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11014 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 2^8 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11048 := 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11015 := 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11049 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11016 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & 11050 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
11017 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11051 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
11018 := -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 11052 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11019 := 0^8 - 3^6 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 11053 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
11020 := 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 9^4 & 11054 := -3^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -3^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
11021 := -1^8 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 3^6 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11055 := -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
11022 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 11056 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
11023 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 11057 := 0^5 + 4^0 - 5^8 + 6^7 + 7^6 + 8^4 & = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 - 8^1 \\
11024 := 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 11058 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11025 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 11059 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 & = -3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
11026 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 11060 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
11027 := 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 11061 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 4^1 - 5^8 + 6^7 + 7^6 + 8^4 \\
11028 := 1^7 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 11062 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 \\
11029 := 2^4 - 3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^2 & = 2^4 - 3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^2 & 11063 := 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 & = 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 \\
11030 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11064 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^6 \\
11031 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11065 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 - 8^0 & = -1^8 - 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^4 \\
11032 := 0^7 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11066 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11033 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11067 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^3 + 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11034 := -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 11068 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11069 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11106 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11070 := -2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 11107 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11071 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 11108 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11072 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 11109 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11073 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^8 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11110 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11074 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^4 & 11111 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11075 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^8 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11112 := 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11076 := -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 11113 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11077 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11114 := 0^8 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
11078 := 0^8 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 11115 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
11079 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11116 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11080 := 0^8 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -3^9 - 4^4 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^3 & 11117 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11081 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 - 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11118 := -2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
11082 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 11119 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 \\
11083 := -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 11120 := 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 \\
11084 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^4 & 11121 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 + 5^2 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^1 \\
11085 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 11122 := 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
11086 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^4 & 11123 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11087 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 - 3^5 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 11124 := -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
11088 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & 11125 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11089 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & 11126 := 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
11090 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & 11127 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
11091 := -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 11128 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
11092 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 11129 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11093 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 - 9^2 & 11130 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11094 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 5^0 + 8^4 - 9^5 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 11131 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11095 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^1 & 11132 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11096 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 11133 := 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11097 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 11134 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11098 := 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11135 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11099 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11136 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11100 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & 11137 := -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11101 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & 11138 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11102 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & 11139 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11103 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 11140 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11104 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & 11141 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
11105 := 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & 11142 := 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
11143 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11144 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11145 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11146 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
11147 := -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11148 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11149 := 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11150 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11151 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 \\
11152 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 \\
11153 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 \\
11154 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 \\
11155 := 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11156 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11157 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
11158 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
11159 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11160 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11161 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11162 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11163 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11164 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11165 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11166 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^3 \\
11167 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11168 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11169 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11170 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11171 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11172 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11173 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11174 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11175 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11176 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11177 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11178 := 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11179 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
= 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
= -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 \\
= 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 - 9^2 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^8 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
= -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^3 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 - 9^1 \\
= 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
11180 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11181 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11182 := -1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11183 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11184 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11185 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11186 := 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
11187 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
11188 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11189 := -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
11190 := 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11191 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11192 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
11193 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11194 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11195 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11196 := -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
11197 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 \\
11198 := 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
11199 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
11200 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11201 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
11202 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11203 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11204 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11205 := 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11206 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11207 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11208 := 0^8 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11209 := 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11210 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11211 := 1^5 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
11212 := -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
11213 := 1^7 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
11214 := 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
11215 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11216 := -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
= -1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 \\
= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= -2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^3 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^1 \\
= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
= 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 \\
= 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
= 1^5 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 9^4 \\
= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^7 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11217 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & 11254 := -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11218 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & 11255 := 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
11219 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11256 := 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11220 := -3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11257 := 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11221 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11258 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11222 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^3 & 11259 := 0^6 + 3^3 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11223 := -1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & 11260 := 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11224 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11261 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11225 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & 11262 := -2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11226 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 & 11263 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11227 := -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & 11264 := 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11228 := 0^3 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 & 11265 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11229 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11266 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11230 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11267 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11231 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11268 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11232 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 11269 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11233 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^4 & 11270 := -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11234 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^0 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 11271 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11235 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11272 := -2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11236 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 & 11273 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11237 := -1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & 11274 := 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11238 := -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 11275 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11239 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & 11276 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
11240 := 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 11277 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11241 := 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 & = 1^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 & 11278 := 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11242 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11279 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 \\
11243 := -2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11280 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11244 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11281 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11245 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11282 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11246 := -0^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11283 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11247 := 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11284 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11248 := 0^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11285 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^2 & = 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11249 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11286 := 0^2 - 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11250 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11287 := -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11251 := 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11288 := 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 2^3 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
11252 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 & 11289 := 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
11253 := -1^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 & 11290 := 0^5 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11291 := 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11328 := 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11292 := -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11329 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11293 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11330 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
11294 := 0^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 11331 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11295 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11332 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11296 := 0^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^5 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 11333 := 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 & = 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 7^4 + 8^5 \\
11297 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11334 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^0 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11298 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11335 := -0^0 - 3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^3 & = -1^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
11299 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11336 := -3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^3 & = -3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^3 \\
11300 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^7 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11337 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11301 := -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 11338 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11302 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11339 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11303 := 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 11340 := 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^3 & = 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^3 \\
11304 := -1^5 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & 11341 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 \\
11305 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 11342 := 0^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
11306 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 11343 := -0^0 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11307 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = 1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 11344 := 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
11308 := 0^5 - 2^8 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 11345 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11309 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11346 := -1^5 - 3^3 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 \\
11310 := -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 11347 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11311 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11348 := -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^5 - 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
11312 := 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 11349 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11313 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & 11350 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11314 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & 11351 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 \\
11315 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^4 + 9^2 & 11352 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11316 := 0^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^2 & 11353 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 \\
11317 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^2 & 11354 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11318 := 0^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = -3^8 - 4^4 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 11355 := -1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & = -1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 \\
11319 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 3^8 - 4^4 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 11356 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11320 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 11357 := 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & = 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 \\
11321 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 11358 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
11322 := -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 11359 := 0^8 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 8^5 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 \\
11323 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & 11360 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
11324 := 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 11361 := 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 & = 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11325 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 11362 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
11326 := 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 11363 := 4^9 + 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6 & = 4^9 + 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6 \\
11327 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 11364 := 0^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11365 := -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 11402 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 \\
11366 := 0^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 11403 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 \\
11367 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11404 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11368 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 11405 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 \\
11369 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11406 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^4 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
11370 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 11407 := 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11371 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 11408 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11372 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 11409 := -1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11373 := -1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = -1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & 11410 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
11374 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 11411 := 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11375 := 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = 1^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & 11412 := 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11376 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 11413 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11377 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 11414 := 0^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
11378 := 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 11415 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11379 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11416 := 0^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11380 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 & 11417 := 0^1 + 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11381 := -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11418 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 - 8^2 \\
11382 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11419 := -1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11383 := 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11420 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
11384 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11421 := 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11385 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11422 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
11386 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^7 - 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 11423 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
11387 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 11424 := 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
11388 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^7 - 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 11425 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
11389 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11426 := -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
11390 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 3^3 + 4^9 + 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^6 & 11427 := 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
11391 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11428 := 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 \\
11392 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11429 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11393 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 11430 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
11394 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 11431 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
11395 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & 11432 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11396 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11433 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 - 8^3 \\
11397 := 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11434 := -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11398 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 - 8^4 & 11435 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^5 - 9^3 & = -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11399 := -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11436 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11400 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^1 & 11437 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11401 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^4 + 9^3 & 11438 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
11439 := 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
11440 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11441 := 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11442 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11443 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11444 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11445 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11446 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11447 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
11448 := 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11449 := 0^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
11450 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
11451 := 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
11452 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
11453 := -1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
11454 := 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
11455 := 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
11456 := -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11457 := -2^2 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11458 := 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11459 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11460 := 0^8 - 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11461 := -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11462 := 0^8 - 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11463 := 0^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 + 8^0 \\
11464 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11465 := 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11466 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11467 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11468 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11469 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11470 := -2^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
11471 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11472 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
11473 := -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
11474 := -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11475 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
\end{array}
\begin{array}{l}
= 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
= 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^5 + 2^1 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
= 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
= -1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
= 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
= 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 - 8^1 \\
= -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -2^2 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= -2^7 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
= -1^8 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= -2^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
= -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
= -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
\end{array}
\begin{array}{l}
11476 := 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11477 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
11478 := 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
11479 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
11480 := 0^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11481 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
11482 := 0^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11483 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
11484 := 0^3 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 - 9^1 \\
11485 := -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11486 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 \\
11487 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11488 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 \\
11489 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
11490 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^3 - 9^0 \\
11491 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
11492 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^3 + 9^0 \\
11493 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
11494 := 0^9 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 - 9^3 \\
11495 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
11496 := 0^9 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 - 9^3 \\
11497 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 - 8^0 \\
11498 := 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
11499 := 0^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^0 \\
11500 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
11501 := 0^8 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
11502 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^0 \\
11503 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
11504 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^0 \\
11505 := -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
11506 := -1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11507 := 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
11508 := 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11509 := -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11510 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11511 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11512 := 0^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 \\
\end{array}
\begin{array}{l}
= 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
= 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^2 \\
= 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
= -2^7 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
= -1^7 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
= -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
= -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
= -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^6 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
= -2^5 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^3 + 9^2 \\
= -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
= 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
= 1^7 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
= 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
= -1^9 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
= 1^9 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
= -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
= -1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
= 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 8^1 \\
= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
11513 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
11514 := 0^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11515 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11516 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11517 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11518 := 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11519 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11520 := 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11521 := 0^5 - 1^8 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11522 := 1^8 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11523 := 0^5 - 1^8 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11524 := 0^8 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11525 := 0^5 - 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11526 := 0^8 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11527 := 0^5 + 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11528 := -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11529 := 0^9 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
11530 := 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11531 := 0^5 - 1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11532 := 0^8 - 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11533 := 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
11534 := 0^8 - 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11535 := 0^5 + 1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11536 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11537 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11538 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
11539 := 0^7 - 3^0 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11540 := 1^8 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11541 := 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11542 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11543 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
11544 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11545 := 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11546 := 0^8 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
11547 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11548 := 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
11549 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 6^4 + 8^3 \\
= 2^8 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
= -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
= -1^1 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^8 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^2 - 8^5 \\
= 1^8 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^7 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
= -1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
= -1^7 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
= 1^9 + 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^4 \\
= -1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
= 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
= 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
= -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
= 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 8^4 \\
= 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^8 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
= 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
= -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
= 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11550 := -1^8 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11551 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11552 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11553 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11554 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11555 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11556 := 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11557 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11558 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11559 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11560 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11561 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11562 := -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
11563 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11564 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
11565 := -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
11566 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
11567 := 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
11568 := 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11569 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11570 := -2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11571 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11572 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11573 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11574 := -3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11575 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11576 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11577 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11578 := 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11579 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
11580 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11581 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
11582 := -1^8 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11583 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
11584 := 1^8 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
11585 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
11586 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^0 - 7^4 \\
= -1^8 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 2^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 8^4 \\
= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
= 1^6 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
= 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
= -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
= -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
= 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
= 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= -2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= 1^8 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= -3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= 1^1 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
= 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
= -1^8 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
= 1^8 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
= -1^6 - 2^8 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11587 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -2^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 11624 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
11588 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11625 := 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 + 8^3 & = 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 + 8^3 \\
11589 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 11626 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11590 := 0^6 - 2^8 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & 11627 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 & = -2^9 + 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11591 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 11628 := 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11592 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = -1^8 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & 11629 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11593 := 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 11630 := 0^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 \\
11594 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11631 := 0^6 - 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11595 := 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 11632 := -3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
11596 := 0^8 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11633 := 0^6 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11597 := 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 11634 := 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
11598 := 0^8 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 11635 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11599 := 0^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11636 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11600 := -2^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11637 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11601 := 0^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11638 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11602 := 1^8 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & 11639 := 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 & = 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
11603 := 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 - 8^1 & = 1^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 - 8^1 & 11640 := 0^6 - 2^8 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 2^7 - 4^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
11604 := -1^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11641 := 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4 & = 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
11605 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 11642 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = 2^8 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
11606 := 1^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 11643 := 0^1 + 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
11607 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 11644 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^4 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11608 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 11645 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11609 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 11646 := 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11610 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 11647 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11611 := 0^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = -1^5 + 4^4 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^1 & 11648 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11612 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11649 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11613 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11650 := -2^9 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11614 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 7^4 & 11651 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11615 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 - 7^4 & 11652 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
11616 := -0^0 + 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 11653 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11617 := 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 11654 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
11618 := 0^0 + 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 & 11655 := -2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
11619 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11656 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
11620 := 0^5 + 4^4 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 - 9^0 & = -3^9 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 7^4 + 9^5 & 11657 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11621 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11658 := -0^0 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
11622 := 0^5 + 4^4 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^0 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 & 11659 := 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
11623 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 11660 := 0^0 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11661 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11698 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11662 := -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11699 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11663 := 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 11700 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11664 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^2 + 8^4 & 11701 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
11665 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11702 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11666 := -3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11703 := 0^9 - 3^0 - 4^3 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11667 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11704 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^2 \\
11668 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^1 & 11705 := -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11669 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11706 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11670 := 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11707 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11671 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11708 := -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11672 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 11709 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11673 := -2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 11710 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11674 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 11711 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11675 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 11712 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11676 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 11713 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11677 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^1 + 8^4 & 11714 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11678 := 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11715 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 \\
11679 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11716 := 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11680 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 - 5^0 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 11717 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11681 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11718 := 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = 1^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
11682 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 11719 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 - 9^1 \\
11683 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11720 := 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = -1^9 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
11684 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 11721 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11685 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11722 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11686 := 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 11723 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11687 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11724 := -2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
11688 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -2^9 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^4 & 11725 := -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
11689 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11726 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11690 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^0 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 11727 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11691 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11728 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11692 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 11729 := 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11693 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^1 + 8^4 & 11730 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^3 \\
11694 := 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 11731 := -3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^3 & = -3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^3 \\
11695 := -3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 11732 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
11696 := 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 11733 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11697 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^2 + 8^4 & 11734 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 7^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11735 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11772 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11736 := -1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11773 := 1^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11737 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11774 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11738 := 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11775 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11739 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11776 := 0^9 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11740 := -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11777 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11741 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11778 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 \\
11742 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2 - 9^4 & 11779 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11743 := -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11780 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^0 & = 1^8 - 2^6 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11744 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11781 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11745 := 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11782 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
11746 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11783 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
11747 := -2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11784 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^4 \\
11748 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11785 := -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11749 := -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11786 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11750 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11787 := 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11751 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11788 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11752 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11789 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11753 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11790 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11754 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11791 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11755 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11792 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11756 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11793 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11757 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11794 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11758 := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11795 := -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11759 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11796 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 \\
11760 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11797 := 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11761 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11798 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11762 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11799 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11763 := -1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11800 := 0^2 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11764 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11801 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11765 := 1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11802 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11766 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11803 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
11767 := 0^9 - 4^0 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11804 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11768 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^2 & 11805 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11769 := 0^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11806 := 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11770 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 & 11807 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 \\
11771 := -1^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11808 := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11809 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11846 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11810 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 11847 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11811 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^5 + 5^3 + 8^4 & 11848 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11812 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^2 & 11849 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11813 := -0^0 - 3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11850 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11814 := -3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = -3^8 - 4^3 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 11851 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11815 := 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11852 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11816 := 0^8 - 2^9 - 5^0 - 6^6 - 8^2 + 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 11853 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11817 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11854 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11818 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 5^0 - 6^6 - 8^2 + 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 11855 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11819 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11856 := -2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11820 := 0^5 + 2^8 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 11857 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11821 := 0^4 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11858 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11822 := 0^5 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 11859 := 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
11823 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11860 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11824 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 11861 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11825 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11862 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11826 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^1 & 11863 := 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11827 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11864 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11828 := 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11865 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11829 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 & 11866 := -1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11830 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11867 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11831 := -2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11868 := 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11832 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11869 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11833 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11870 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11834 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^1 & 11871 := 0^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2 - 9^4 \\
11835 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11872 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11836 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11873 := 0^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11837 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11874 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11838 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^1 & 11875 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11839 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 11876 := -1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11840 := 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 11877 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11841 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 11878 := 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11842 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^1 & 11879 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11843 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11880 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11844 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11881 := -2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11845 := -3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 11882 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
11883 := -2^9 + 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 + 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11920 := 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
11884 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 11921 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11885 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11922 := -2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
11886 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11923 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11887 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11924 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11888 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & 11925 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11889 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11926 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11890 := 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & 11927 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11891 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11928 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11892 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11929 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11893 := -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 11930 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
11894 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11931 := 0^7 - 2^9 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11895 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & 11932 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11896 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11933 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11897 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & 11934 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
11898 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11935 := 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
11899 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11936 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11900 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11937 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11901 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11938 := 0^7 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
11902 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11939 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 \\
11903 := -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11940 := -1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11904 := -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 11941 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
11905 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11942 := 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11906 := -2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11943 := 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
11907 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11944 := 0^8 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
11908 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11945 := -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
11909 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11946 := 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
11910 := 0^3 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 - 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 11947 := -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11911 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11948 := -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11912 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11949 := 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11913 := 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11950 := 1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
11914 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 & 11951 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11915 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 11952 := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
11916 := -3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 11953 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 \\
11917 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & 11954 := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
11918 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 11955 := -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
11919 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 & 11956 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4
\end{array}$$

11957 := $-1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$= -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	11980 := $0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4$
11958 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	11981 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$
11959 := $1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	$= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	11982 := $-0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$
11960 := $-1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	11983 := $-2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= -2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$
11961 := $-3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$= -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	11984 := $0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$
11962 := $0^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0$	$= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	11985 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$
11963 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	11986 := $2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$	$= 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$
11964 := $0^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	11987 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$
11965 := $0^1 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	11988 := $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 - 9^1$
11966 := $0^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	11989 := $-0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
11967 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5$	11990 := $-2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
11968 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	11991 := $0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
11969 := $-1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1$	11992 := $-0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2$
11970 := $-2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$	$= -2^3 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$	11993 := $-1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
11971 := $1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1$	11994 := $-2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5$
11972 := $-0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	11995 := $1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
11973 := $3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	11996 := $0^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5$
11974 := $0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	11997 := $-2^9 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -2^9 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5$
11975 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$	11998 := $0^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5$
11976 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	11999 := $-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
11977 := $2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	12000 := $-0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2$
11978 := $2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2$	$= 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2$		
11979 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5$		
12001 := $1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	12015 := $-2^9 + 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -2^9 + 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5$
12002 := $0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2$	12016 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$
12003 := $-0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	12017 := $1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
12004 := $2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	12018 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$
12005 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	12019 := $0^7 - 3^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^5 - 9^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 7^1$
12006 := $0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^1$	12020 := $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$
12007 := $0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	12021 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
12008 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	12022 := $-1^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1$
12009 := $-2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	12023 := $-0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$
12010 := $-2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	12024 := $-1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4$
12011 := $0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	12025 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$
12012 := $0^2 + 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= 1^4 - 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^1$	12026 := $1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4$
12013 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4$	12027 := $0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4$	$= 1^7 - 3^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 - 9^3$
12014 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^2$	12028 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12029 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12066 := -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 \\
12030 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^1 & 12067 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12031 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12068 := -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
12032 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 12069 := 0^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^2 + 9^5 \\
12033 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12070 := 0^4 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12034 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3 + 9^2 & 12071 := 0^2 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 - 9^1 \\
12035 := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 - 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12072 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12036 := -2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4 & = -2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4 & 12073 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
12037 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4 & 12074 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
12038 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12075 := -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 & = -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12039 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 12076 := 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
12040 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12077 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
12041 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 12078 := 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
12042 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & 12079 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
12043 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 12080 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12044 := -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & 12081 := -2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12045 := 0^8 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^6 + 7^3 - 8^5 & = 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 & 12082 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12046 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^1 & 12083 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 \\
12047 := -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12084 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12048 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & 12085 := 0^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12049 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & 12086 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12050 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & 12087 := 0^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12051 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12088 := 0^1 + 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12052 := -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 12089 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^4 & = 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12053 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 12090 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12054 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 12091 := -1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12055 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 12092 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12056 := 0^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2 & 12093 := 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12057 := 1^3 - 3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 - 9^1 & 12094 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12058 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^2 & 12095 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12059 := 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^3 + 9^5 & = 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^3 + 9^5 & 12096 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12060 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^2 & 12097 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 2^2 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12061 := 2^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 & = 2^5 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 & 12098 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12062 := 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12099 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^4 & = -3^8 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 + 8^5 \\
12063 := 0^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12100 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12064 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 12101 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12065 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 12102 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
12103 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12104 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12105 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12106 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12107 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^4 \\
12108 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12109 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12110 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
12111 := 0^6 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12112 := -2^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12113 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12114 := -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12115 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12116 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12117 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^3 \\
12118 := 1^6 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12119 := -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12120 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12121 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12122 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12123 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12124 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
12125 := -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12126 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12127 := -1^9 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12128 := 0^5 - 3^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 + 7^3 - 9^0 \\
12129 := 1^9 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12130 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12131 := -1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12132 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12133 := 1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12134 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12135 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12136 := 0^9 - 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12137 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12138 := 0^9 - 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12139 := 0^1 + 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
= -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 + 9^2 \\
= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -2^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^3 \\
= 1^6 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= -1^9 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^7 - 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
= 1^9 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= -1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
= 1^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
= -1^9 + 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 2^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
= -1^9 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= 1^9 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12140 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12141 := -1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12142 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12143 := 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12144 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12145 := 0^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12146 := 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
12147 := 1^9 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12148 := -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12149 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
12150 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 - 9^4 \\
12151 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12152 := -2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12153 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12154 := -3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
12155 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
12156 := -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12157 := 0^5 + 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 8^3 \\
12158 := 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12159 := 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12160 := -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
12161 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12162 := -2^9 + 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12163 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
12164 := 0^5 - 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 8^0 \\
12165 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
12166 := 0^5 - 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^0 \\
12167 := -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12168 := 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12169 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
12170 := 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12171 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12172 := 0^7 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 \\
12173 := 0^9 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^0 - 9^5 \\
12174 := 0^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12175 := -2^5 + 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
12176 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 \\
= 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
= 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= -1^9 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= 1^9 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
= 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= -2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= -3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^9 - 2^8 + 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^1 + 9^5 \\
= -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= -2^9 + 4^4 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= -1^5 + 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^4 \\
= -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
= 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= 1^9 - 2^8 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 8^1 + 9^5 \\
= -1^5 - 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
= 1^5 - 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
= -2^5 + 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12177 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^2 & 12214 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
12178 := 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & 12215 := -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
12179 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & 12216 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12180 := -1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 & 12217 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
12181 := 1^9 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 - 9^5 & = 1^9 - 3^8 + 5^7 - 7^3 + 8^1 - 9^5 & 12218 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12182 := 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 & 12219 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12183 := -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 12220 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12184 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 12221 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
12185 := 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 12222 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12186 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 12223 := 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12187 := 0^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 & 12224 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12188 := 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^0 - 7^3 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 12225 := 0^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12189 := 0^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 12226 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12190 := -1^4 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^4 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & 12227 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12191 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12228 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12192 := 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12229 := 0^3 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12193 := -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 12230 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
12194 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12231 := -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12195 := 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 12232 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
12196 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 12233 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12197 := 0^7 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12234 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
12198 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 & 12235 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12199 := 0^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12236 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12200 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 12237 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12201 := 0^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 12238 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12202 := 0^1 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^7 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^3 & 12239 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12203 := 0^7 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12240 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12204 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 12241 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
12205 := -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 12242 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12206 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^4 & 12243 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12207 := 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 12244 := 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 \\
12208 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 12245 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = 1^8 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12209 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & 12246 := 0^8 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^9 - 2^7 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 7^1 + 9^5 \\
12210 := 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12247 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = -2^9 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^2 \\
12211 := -3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 12248 := 0^8 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
12212 := 0^0 - 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^9 - 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 & 12249 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12213 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & 12250 := 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12251 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 & 12288 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
12252 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12289 := 0^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
12253 := -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12290 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12254 := -3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^3 - 8^4 & 12291 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
12255 := 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12292 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12256 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12293 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12257 := -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12294 := -1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12258 := 0^8 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12295 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
12259 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12296 := 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12260 := 0^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12297 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
12261 := -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 & 12298 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12262 := 0^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12299 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12263 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12300 := 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12264 := -1^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12301 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12265 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^8 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12302 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 \\
12266 := 1^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12303 := 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12267 := 0^9 - 3^0 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12304 := 0^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
12268 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12305 := -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
12269 := 0^9 + 3^0 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12306 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
12270 := -1^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12307 := -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12271 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12308 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12272 := 1^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12309 := 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12273 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12310 := -1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12274 := 0^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12311 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 & = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12275 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12312 := 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12276 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12313 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12277 := -3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 12314 := 0^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12278 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12315 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -2^4 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12279 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 12316 := 0^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12280 := -1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12317 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12281 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 12318 := 0^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0 - 9^4 & = -1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^5 \\
12282 := 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12319 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0 - 9^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12283 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12320 := 0^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0 - 9^4 & = -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 \\
12284 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12321 := -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12285 := 0^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 12322 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12286 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12323 := 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12287 := 0^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 12324 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 - 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
12325 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12326 := -1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12327 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12328 := 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12329 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12330 := 0^8 - 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12331 := -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12332 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12333 := -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
12334 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12335 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12336 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12337 := 3^5 + 5^9 - 6^8 - 8^6 + 9^3 \\
12338 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12339 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12340 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12341 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12342 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12343 := 1^8 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12344 := 0^8 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12345 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0 - 9^4 \\
12346 := 0^8 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12347 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0 - 9^4 \\
12348 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
12349 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
12350 := -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12351 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12352 := 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12353 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12354 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12355 := 0^8 - 3^9 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12356 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12357 := 0^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12358 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12359 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12360 := -1^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12361 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12362 := 1^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12363 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12364 := 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 \\
12365 := 0^9 - 3^3 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12366 := -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12367 := 0^9 - 2^0 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12368 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 2^0 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12369 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12370 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12371 := 1^9 + 2^1 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12372 := 1^9 - 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12373 := 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4 \\
12374 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12375 := 0^9 + 2^3 - 3^0 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12376 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12377 := 0^9 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12378 := -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12379 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12380 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12381 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12382 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^2 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12383 := -1^9 - 2^2 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12384 := -2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12385 := 1^9 - 2^2 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12386 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12387 := -1^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12388 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12389 := 1^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12390 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12391 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12392 := 0^9 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12393 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12394 := 0^9 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12395 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12396 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12397 := -1^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12398 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
\end{array}$$

$12399 := 1^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12436 := 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2$
$12400 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12437 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$
$12401 := -1^9 + 2^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12438 := 0^7 - 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$12402 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 2^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$12439 := 0^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 - 8^0$	$= 1^9 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$
$12403 := 1^9 + 2^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12440 := 0^7 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 7^4$
$12404 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^3 + 3^2 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12441 := 0^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 + 8^0$	$= -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^3$
$12405 := 0^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^0 - 8^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12442 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 7^3 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$
$12406 := -1^9 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12443 := -1^7 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4$
$12407 := 0^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^0 - 8^4$	$= 1^9 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12444 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$
$12408 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 9^0$	$= 1^9 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12445 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$
$12409 := 0^9 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -2^6 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^4$	$12446 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$
$12410 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^0$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12447 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$
$12411 := 0^9 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 2^6 - 4^9 - 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$12448 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^3$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$
$12412 := -0^0 - 4^9 - 5^6 + 6^7 + 7^5 - 9^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12449 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$
$12413 := -4^9 - 5^6 + 6^7 + 7^5 - 9^4$	$= -4^9 - 5^6 + 6^7 + 7^5 - 9^4$	$12450 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^3 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^1$
$12414 := -1^9 + 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12451 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2$
$12415 := -1^9 - 2^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12452 := 1^3 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^1$
$12416 := 1^9 + 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12453 := 0^2 + 1^7 - 2^8 - 4^1 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4$
$12417 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12454 := -2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= -2^8 + 3^6 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4$
$12418 := -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2$	$= -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2$	$12455 := -1^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 - 9^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 - 9^2$
$12419 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12456 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 - 9^3$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4$
$12420 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12457 := 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 - 9^2$
$12421 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12458 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 - 9^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^4 - 6^5 - 9^1$
$12422 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12459 := 0^3 - 3^9 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 8^5 - 9^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^2$
$12423 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -2^7 + 3^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5$	$12460 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
$12424 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12461 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
$12425 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^8 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$12462 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
$12426 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12463 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1$
$12427 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^8 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$12464 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
$12428 := -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12465 := 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
$12429 := 0^7 - 2^8 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$= -1^9 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12466 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$
$12430 := 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12467 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^4 + 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$12431 := 0^7 - 2^8 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$12468 := 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$	$= 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4$
$12432 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2$	$12469 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$12433 := 0^9 + 2^4 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$12470 := -3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= -3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$12434 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2$	$12471 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$
$12435 := 0^9 + 2^4 + 4^0 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4$	$12472 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5$	$= 2^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 8^3$

$$\begin{array}{l}
12473 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12474 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12475 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12476 := -1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 \\
12477 := 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12478 := 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 \\
12479 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12480 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12481 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12482 := -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12483 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12484 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
12485 := -2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
12486 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
12487 := -1^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
12488 := -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
12489 := -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
12490 := 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
12491 := 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
12492 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12493 := -2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12494 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12495 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12496 := -0^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12497 := 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12498 := 0^0 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12499 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12500 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12501 := 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12502 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12503 := -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
12504 := -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
12505 := 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
12506 := 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
12507 := 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
12508 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
12509 := 0^4 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 8^0 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 \\
= 1^7 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 \\
= 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 \\
= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= -2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
= 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= -1^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^1 \\
= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^1 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
= 1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12510 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12511 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12512 := 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12513 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12514 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12515 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12516 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12517 := 0^9 - 3^0 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12518 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^0 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12519 := 0^9 + 3^0 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12520 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12521 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12522 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12523 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12524 := 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12525 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12526 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12527 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12528 := 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12529 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
12530 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12531 := -1^5 - 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
12532 := 0^7 - 3^9 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^5 - 9^0 \\
12533 := 1^5 - 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
12534 := 0^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12535 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12536 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12537 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12538 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12539 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12540 := 0^5 + 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 8^2 \\
12541 := -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
12542 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12543 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12544 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12545 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12546 := -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^9 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -1^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^4 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
= 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 \\
= 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= -1^5 - 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
= 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^5 - 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^1 \\
= 1^5 + 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
= 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^2 - 6^6 - 7^1 + 9^5 \\
= -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12547 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12584 := 0^4 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^1 + 8^0 & = -1^9 - 4^6 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 - 9^5 \\
12548 := 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 & 12585 := -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
12549 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 & 12586 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12550 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12587 := 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 & = 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12551 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^2 + 9^4 & 12588 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12552 := 0^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12589 := -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12553 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & 12590 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 \\
12554 := 0^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 12591 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12555 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & 12592 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12556 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 12593 := 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12557 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 - 7^1 + 9^3 & 12594 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12558 := -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 12595 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12559 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 12596 := 0^4 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 8^0 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12560 := 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^4 & 12597 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12561 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12598 := 0^4 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12562 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 12599 := 0^4 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 8^1 & = 1^5 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12563 := 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 12600 := 0^8 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12564 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 12601 := -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
12565 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 12602 := -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12566 := 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 12603 := 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
12567 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 12604 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12568 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 & 12605 := -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12569 := 0^9 + 2^7 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 7^2 + 9^5 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 7^1 + 9^3 & 12606 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12570 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^7 + 3^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 12607 := 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12571 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^8 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 & 12608 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12572 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12609 := 0^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12573 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^8 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 & 12610 := -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12574 := 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^5 - 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^5 - 9^4 & 12611 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12575 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 12612 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12576 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & 12613 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12577 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^2 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12614 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12578 := 0^9 - 4^6 + 5^7 - 6^0 - 7^4 - 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12615 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12579 := 0^4 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 & 12616 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12580 := 0^4 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 8^0 & = -1^7 + 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 12617 := -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^4 \\
12581 := 0^4 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 8^1 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 9^2 & 12618 := 0^4 - 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12582 := 0^4 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^1 + 8^0 & = 1^7 + 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 12619 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
12583 := 0^4 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 8^1 & = -1^9 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 - 9^1 & 12620 := 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12621 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 12658 := 0^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12622 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & 12659 := 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12623 := -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & = -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & 12660 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12624 := 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 2^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12661 := -1^5 + 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 & = -1^5 + 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
12625 := 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 - 8^0 + 9^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12662 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12626 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12663 := -1^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12627 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12664 := 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12628 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12665 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
12629 := 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12666 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12630 := 0^8 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12667 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12631 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12668 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12632 := 0^8 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12669 := 0^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12633 := -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12670 := 0^5 + 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 8^2 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12634 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 12671 := 0^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12635 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12672 := -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^2 & = -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
12636 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 12673 := 0^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
12637 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^3 & 12674 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 & = 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^2 \\
12638 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12675 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12639 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12676 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12640 := -1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12677 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12641 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12678 := 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12642 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12679 := -0^0 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12643 := -1^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12680 := -3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
12644 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & 12681 := 0^0 - 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
12645 := 1^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12682 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12646 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 12683 := 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 \\
12647 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12684 := 0^4 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^0 + 8^2 & = -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
12648 := 0^9 + 4^4 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 12685 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^8 + 5^0 - 8^3 + 9^5 & = -1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12649 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12686 := 0^4 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^0 + 8^2 & = 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
12650 := 0^9 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 12687 := 1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12651 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12688 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
12652 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^4 - 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 & 12689 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
12653 := -1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12690 := 0^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^2 \\
12654 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 12691 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = -1^4 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
12655 := 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12692 := 0^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
12656 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 & 12693 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = 1^4 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
12657 := 0^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 - 8^4 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12694 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
12695 := -1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12696 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12697 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^0 \\
12698 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^5 - 9^4 \\
12699 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12700 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^5 - 9^4 \\
12701 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12702 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12703 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12704 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12705 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12706 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12707 := 0^4 + 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12708 := 0^4 + 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12709 := 0^7 + 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4 \\
12710 := 2^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
12711 := -0^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
12712 := -2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
12713 := 0^7 - 1^8 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4 \\
12714 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 - 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12715 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12716 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12717 := 0^4 - 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12718 := 0^4 + 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12719 := 0^4 + 1^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12720 := 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 8^4 - 9^2 \\
12721 := 0^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12722 := 0^4 + 1^7 + 2^2 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12723 := 1^8 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12724 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12725 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12726 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12727 := 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12728 := 1^9 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 - 9^1 \\
12729 := -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
12730 := 0^7 - 2^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12731 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12732 := -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12733 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12734 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12735 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12736 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12737 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12738 := -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
12739 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12740 := 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12741 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
12742 := -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 - 9^2 \\
12743 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12744 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12745 := 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^0 \\
12746 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12747 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^2 \\
12748 := -1^7 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12749 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^2 \\
12750 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12751 := -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12752 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
12753 := 0^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12754 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^0 \\
12755 := -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
12756 := 0^7 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12757 := -1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12758 := 0^4 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 \\
12759 := 1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12760 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12761 := 1^8 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^4 + 9^1 \\
12762 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12763 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12764 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12765 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
12766 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
12767 := 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
12768 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
12769 := 1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12770 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12771 := 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12772 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12773 := 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
12774 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12775 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12776 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12777 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12778 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12779 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12780 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12781 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12782 := -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12783 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12784 := 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12785 := -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 \\
12786 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 \\
12787 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12788 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12789 := 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12790 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12791 := 1^8 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
12792 := 0^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^0 \\
12793 := -0^0 - 3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 9^3 \\
12794 := -3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 9^3 \\
12795 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^0 \\
12796 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12797 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 + 9^0 \\
12798 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
12799 := 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
12800 := 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^0 - 8^4 \\
12801 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^0 - 9^4 \\
12802 := 0^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12803 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^0 - 9^4 \\
12804 := 0^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
12805 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^0 \\
= 1^7 + 2^4 - 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^4 - 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
= 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^4 \\
= -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
= 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 \\
= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^2 - 5^3 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
= 1^8 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^3 \\
= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^1 - 9^4 \\
= -3^9 - 5^7 - 6^5 + 7^6 + 9^3 \\
= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^1 - 9^4 \\
= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
= 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
= -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= 1^2 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
= 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
= -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
12806 := 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 + 9^1 \\
12807 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
12808 := -3^8 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
12809 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
12810 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^4 \\
12811 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
12812 := -0^0 - 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12813 := -3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12814 := 0^0 - 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12815 := 0^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 \\
12816 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
12817 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
12818 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
12819 := 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12820 := 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
12821 := 1^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
12822 := 0^8 + 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4 \\
12823 := -3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
12824 := 3^9 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^5 - 9^4 \\
12825 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12826 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12827 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12828 := -1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
12829 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^2 \\
12830 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12831 := -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12832 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12833 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12834 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12835 := -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12836 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12837 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12838 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12839 := -0^0 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12840 := -4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12841 := 0^0 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
12842 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
= 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 + 9^1 \\
= 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^2 - 9^4 \\
= -3^8 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
= -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
= 2^3 - 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
= -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
= -3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
= 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
= -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
= -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
= 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
= 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^3 \\
= -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^2 \\
= 1^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
= 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^2 \\
= -3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
= 3^9 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^5 - 9^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
= 1^8 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= -1^7 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
= -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
= -1^1 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
= -4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
= 1^1 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
= -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12843 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^1 - 9^4 & 12880 := 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12844 := 2^2 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 2^2 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 12881 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12845 := 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & 12882 := 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 \\
12846 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^1 & 12883 := 0^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^0 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12847 := 0^7 - 3^4 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12884 := 0^3 - 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12848 := 0^8 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4 - 9^0 & = -1^9 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^1 & 12885 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12849 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12886 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 7^1 + 9^5 \\
12850 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12887 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12851 := 0^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^0 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12888 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 7^1 + 9^5 \\
12852 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12889 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12853 := 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12890 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12854 := 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12891 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12855 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = -2^7 + 3^4 - 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 12892 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12856 := 0^8 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^4 & = 2^9 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^4 & 12893 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 5^0 - 6^5 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12857 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12894 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2 - 9^4 \\
12858 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12895 := 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2 - 9^4 \\
12859 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12896 := 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
12860 := -1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 & = -1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 7^2 + 9^5 & 12897 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12861 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12898 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12862 := -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^1 & 12899 := -1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12863 := 0^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12900 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12864 := 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^1 & 12901 := 1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12865 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 12902 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12866 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 12903 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12867 := 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 12904 := 0^2 + 2^9 - 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12868 := 0^0 + 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 12905 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12869 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12906 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 5^0 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 3^8 - 4^9 - 6^3 + 8^6 + 9^4 \\
12870 := 1^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12907 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^3 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12871 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^4 & 12908 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12872 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12909 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12873 := -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & = -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & 12910 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12874 := -2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = -2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 12911 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12875 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^1 - 9^4 & 12912 := -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12876 := 0^4 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12913 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12877 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12914 := 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12878 := 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & 12915 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12879 := -0^0 + 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12916 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12917 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^2 - 5^1 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12954 := -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
12918 := -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12955 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12919 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12956 := 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
12920 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12957 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
12921 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12958 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
12922 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12959 := 0^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^0 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
12923 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12960 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12924 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12961 := 0^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
12925 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12962 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12926 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12963 := 0^8 + 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
12927 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 12964 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
12928 := 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 9^2 & 12965 := 0^8 + 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12929 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12966 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
12930 := 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12967 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12931 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12968 := -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
12932 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 12969 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
12933 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 12970 := 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
12934 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12971 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^3 \\
12935 := 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 12972 := 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
12936 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12973 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12937 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & 12974 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 \\
12938 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 12975 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12939 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & 12976 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^8 - 3^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 8^5 - 9^3 \\
12940 := -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 & 12977 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^4 \\
12941 := 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12978 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12942 := 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 & 12979 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 \\
12943 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 12980 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12944 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & 12981 := -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12945 := 0^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4 & 12982 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12946 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & 12983 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^4 \\
12947 := 0^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^4 & 12984 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12948 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 12985 := -2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 & = -2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
12949 := 0^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = -2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 12986 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12950 := -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & 12987 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
12951 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^5 - 8^4 + 9^3 & 12988 := -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12952 := 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & 12989 := 0^3 - 3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 7^4 - 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
12953 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^4 & 12990 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
12991 := -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 12997 := 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12992 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 12998 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 \\
12993 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 12999 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
12994 := 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13000 := -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
12995 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 & & \\
12996 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & & \\
\\
13001 := 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & = 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 & 13032 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13002 := 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13033 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13003 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13034 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13004 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13035 := -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 & = -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 \\
13005 := 1^9 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13036 := -2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 & = -2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 \\
13006 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13037 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13007 := 0^7 + 3^4 - 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 13038 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13008 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 13039 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13009 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^2 - 9^4 & 13040 := 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 & = 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 \\
13010 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13041 := 0^0 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 & = 1^1 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 \\
13011 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^0 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13042 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13012 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13043 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13013 := -1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13044 := 2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 & = 2^2 + 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 9^6 \\
13014 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13045 := 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
13015 := 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13046 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 \\
13016 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13047 := -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
13017 := 0^9 - 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 - 9^4 & 13048 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13018 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^1 - 9^4 & 13049 := -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
13019 := 0^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 - 9^4 & 13050 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^1 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
13020 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 & 13051 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^1 - 9^4 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
13021 := -1^9 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^9 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13052 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13022 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 & 13053 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13023 := 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & 13054 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13024 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13055 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13025 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^2 - 9^4 & 13056 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13026 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^3 - 9^4 & 13057 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13027 := -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 & = -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 & 13058 := 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13028 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 & 13059 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13029 := 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^3 & 13060 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13030 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & 13061 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13031 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & 13062 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
\mathbf{13063} := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13100} := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
\mathbf{13064} := 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13101} := 3^8 - 5^7 - 6^3 + 7^6 - 8^5 & = 3^8 - 5^7 - 6^3 + 7^6 - 8^5 \\
\mathbf{13065} := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13102} := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
\mathbf{13066} := 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 7^1 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 7^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13103} := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13067} := 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & \mathbf{13104} := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13068} := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13105} := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13069} := 0^8 + 2^3 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13106} := -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13070} := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^3 - 8^0 + 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13107} := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13071} := 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^4 & \mathbf{13108} := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13072} := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^3 + 8^0 + 9^5 & = -1^6 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^2 & \mathbf{13109} := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13073} := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^0 - 9^4 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13110} := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13074} := 0^3 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^3 & \mathbf{13111} := 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13075} := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^0 - 9^4 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13112} := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13076} := 0^3 - 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13113} := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13077} := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^2 & \mathbf{13114} := 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13078} := 0^3 + 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 - 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13115} := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13079} := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13116} := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13080} := 0^3 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13117} := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13081} := 0^5 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13118} := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13082} := 0^3 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13119} := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13083} := 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^4 + 8^3 + 9^5 & = 3^9 - 4^8 - 5^4 + 8^3 + 9^5 & \mathbf{13120} := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{13084} := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13121} := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13085} := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13122} := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{13086} := -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13123} := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13087} := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13124} := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13088} := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & \mathbf{13125} := -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13089} := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13126} := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{13090} := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & \mathbf{13127} := 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13091} := 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 & = 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 & \mathbf{13128} := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = -2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{13092} := 0^3 + 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^0 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13129} := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13093} := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13130} := -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13094} := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13131} := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13095} := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13132} := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
\mathbf{13096} := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13133} := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13097} := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13134} := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13098} := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13135} := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^4 \\
\mathbf{13099} := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^4 & \mathbf{13136} := 2^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5 & = 2^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 6^6 + 9^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13137 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &13174 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 &= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13138 &:= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 &= -2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 &13175 &:= 0^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 &= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
13139 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &13176 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 &= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13140 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^1 - 9^4 &13177 &:= 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 - 8^1 + 9^4 \\
13141 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &13178 &:= -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^1 - 9^4 &= -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^1 - 9^4 \\
13142 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 9^4 &13179 &:= 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 &= -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^1 - 9^4 \\
13143 &:= 0^3 - 1^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 &13180 &:= -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 &= -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13144 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 9^4 &13181 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13145 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &13182 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13146 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &13183 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13147 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &13184 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13148 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^1 - 9^4 &13185 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= -1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13149 &:= 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^2 - 9^4 &13186 &:= 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13150 &:= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 &= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 &13187 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13151 &:= 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 &13188 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13152 &:= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^1 - 9^4 &13189 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13153 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^0 - 9^4 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^4 &13190 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13154 &:= 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 5^2 - 9^4 &= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^1 - 9^4 &13191 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^4 \\
13155 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^0 - 9^4 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13192 &:= 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 &= 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
13156 &:= 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^2 - 9^4 &= 1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^2 &13193 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13157 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13194 &:= -2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13158 &:= -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13195 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13159 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13196 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13160 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^2 - 9^4 &= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 9^4 &13197 &:= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^1 - 9^4 \\
13161 &:= 0^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 - 9^2 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13198 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13162 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^2 - 9^4 &= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &13199 &:= 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13163 &:= 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 &= 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 &13200 &:= -1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 &= -1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 \\
13164 &:= 4^8 - 5^7 + 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^4 &= 4^8 - 5^7 + 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^4 &13201 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 &= -1^2 - 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
13165 &:= 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 6^2 - 9^4 &= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^1 - 9^4 &13202 &:= 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 &= 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 \\
13166 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &13203 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
13167 &:= -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &13204 &:= -0^0 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 &= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13168 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &13205 &:= 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 &= 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
13169 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13206 &:= -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 &= -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\
13170 &:= -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &= -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &13207 &:= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13171 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^4 &13208 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13172 &:= 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &= 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &13209 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 \\
13173 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 &= -1^9 - 2^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 &13210 &:= -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 &= -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13211 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & 13248 := 0^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13212 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 & 13249 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13213 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & 13250 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
13214 := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & 13251 := -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13215 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 & 13252 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 - 9^4 \\
13216 := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & 13253 := 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13217 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 & 13254 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13218 := -1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = -1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & 13255 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13219 := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & 13256 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
13220 := 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & = 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^1 & 13257 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13221 := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^0 & = -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & 13258 := 0^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
13222 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & 13259 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 \\
13223 := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^0 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 & 13260 := 0^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^8 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13224 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & 13261 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13225 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & 13262 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^1 - 4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
13226 := 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & = 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & 13263 := -4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = -4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
13227 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 & 13264 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^1 - 4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
13228 := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & 13265 := -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13229 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^5 - 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 13266 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13230 := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & 13267 := 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13231 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 13268 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13232 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 13269 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13233 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^7 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & 13270 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13234 := -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^2 + 9^4 & 13271 := 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13235 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & 13272 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13236 := -3^3 - 4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = -3^3 - 4^8 - 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & 13273 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13237 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & 13274 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = -2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13238 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & 13275 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13239 := -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 & = -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 & 13276 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13240 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & 13277 := -0^0 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13241 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 13278 := -3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13242 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 13279 := 0^0 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13243 := 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^2 - 9^4 & 13280 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13244 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 13281 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13245 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 13282 := 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13246 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & 13283 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13247 := -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 & 13284 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
13285 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 \\
13286 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
13287 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 \\
13288 := -2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13289 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13290 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13291 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13292 := -2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13293 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13294 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13295 := -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
13296 := -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
13297 := -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
13298 := 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
13299 := 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
13300 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13301 := -2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13302 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13303 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13304 := -0^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13305 := -4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13306 := 0^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13307 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13308 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13309 := 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13310 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13311 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13312 := -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
13313 := 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
13314 := 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
13315 := 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
13316 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
13317 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13318 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13319 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13320 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13321 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
= 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
= -1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
= -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
= -1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
= 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
= 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^3 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^2 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
= 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
= 1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
= 1^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
= -1^8 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
13322 := 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13323 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13324 := 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13325 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13326 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13327 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13328 := -2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13329 := -1^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
13330 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13331 := -0^0 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13332 := 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13333 := 0^0 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13334 := 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
13335 := 0^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^0 + 7^5 \\
13336 := 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
13337 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13338 := 3^8 - 4^9 + 6^3 + 8^6 + 9^4 \\
13339 := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 \\
13340 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 \\
13341 := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 \\
13342 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 \\
13343 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13344 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13345 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13346 := -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13347 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13348 := 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13349 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
13350 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13351 := 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13352 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13353 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
13354 := -2^9 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
13355 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13356 := 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^2 \\
13357 := 0^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^2 \\
13358 := 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^2 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
= 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= -1^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
= -1^1 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^1 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 \\
= 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
= 3^8 - 4^9 + 6^3 + 8^6 + 9^4 \\
= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
= -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= -2^6 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
= -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
= -2^9 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 \\
= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
= 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^1 \\
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13359 := 0^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 + 9^1 & 13396 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13360 := 0^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^0 & = -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 & 13397 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13361 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13398 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 \\
13362 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13399 := 0^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13363 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 13400 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^5 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
13364 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 7^2 - 9^4 & 13401 := -2^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13365 := 0^3 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 - 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^1 & 13402 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
13366 := -0^0 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = -1^8 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & 13403 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 \\
13367 := -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 & 13404 := -2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = -2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
13368 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & 13405 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13369 := 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 & 13406 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 - 9^0 & = 1^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
13370 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & = -1^8 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & 13407 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13371 := 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^1 - 9^4 & 13408 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 + 9^0 & = -1^7 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 \\
13372 := 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & 13409 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 & = -1^8 - 2^9 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 + 9^1 \\
13373 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13410 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
13374 := -1^5 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^5 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 & 13411 := 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
13375 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13412 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 9^4 \\
13376 := -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 13413 := -2^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13377 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13414 := -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
13378 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13415 := -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 + 9^1 & = -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 + 9^1 \\
13379 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13416 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
13380 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & 13417 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
13381 := -2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = -2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & 13418 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13382 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & 13419 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
13383 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13420 := 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^4 \\
13384 := 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 & = 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^2 & 13421 := 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13385 := 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & = 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 - 9^2 & 13422 := 0^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13386 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 & 13423 := 0^3 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13387 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^4 & 13424 := -2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13388 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & 13425 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13389 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 13426 := -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 \\
13390 := -2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 13427 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
13391 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 13428 := 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
13392 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 & 13429 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^1 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
13393 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13430 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^0 & = -2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^3 \\
13394 := -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13431 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^1 & = -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
13395 := 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^0 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & 13432 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^0 & = -1^4 - 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13433 := 0^3 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 8^1 - 9^4 & 13470 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13434 := 0^3 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 13471 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13435 := 0^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 8^1 - 9^4 & 13472 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
13436 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 13473 := -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\
13437 := 0^4 - 3^3 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13474 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13438 := 0^7 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 13475 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\
13439 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13476 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^5 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
13440 := 0^7 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 13477 := 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
13441 := 0^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 8^2 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 13478 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
13442 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 13479 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
13443 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 13480 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
13444 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^0 & = -1^6 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 13481 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
13445 := 0^3 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13482 := 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
13446 := 0^3 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^0 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13483 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
13447 := 0^3 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^1 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 8^2 - 9^4 & 13484 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
13448 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13485 := -1^2 + 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13449 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & 13486 := 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 & = 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
13450 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13487 := 1^2 + 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13451 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 - 9^4 & 13488 := -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
13452 := 0^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 - 8^2 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & 13489 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13453 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 13490 := 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
13454 := 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & 13491 := 0^4 + 2^0 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13455 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 13492 := -2^8 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13456 := 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 13493 := 0^4 + 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 \\
13457 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 13494 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
13458 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13495 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 - 9^0 & = -2^5 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
13459 := -1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 13496 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
13460 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13497 := 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 & = 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
13461 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 13498 := -2^8 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13462 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13499 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^0 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13463 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 13500 := 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
13464 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13501 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
13465 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 13502 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^5 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
13466 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 13503 := 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13467 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & 13504 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13468 := -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 7^3 - 9^4 & 13505 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 \\
13469 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 13506 := 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
13507 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^2 + 9^4 &13544 &:= 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^4 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
13508 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^0 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 &13545 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
13509 &:= 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 &= 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 &13546 &:= 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 \\
13510 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 &= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^4 &13547 &:= 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 &= 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 \\
13511 &:= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &13548 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^3 + 8^5 + 9^2 &= -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13512 &:= -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 &= -1^3 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 &13549 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 &= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 \\
13513 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= -1^1 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &13550 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13514 &:= 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &13551 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13515 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &13552 &:= -2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13516 &:= -2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= -2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 &13553 &:= 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13517 &:= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13554 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13518 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13555 &:= 0^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^0 &= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
13519 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &13556 &:= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13520 &:= -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13557 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13521 &:= -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13558 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13522 &:= 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13559 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13523 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 2^9 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 + 9^4 &13560 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^5 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
13524 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13561 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13525 &:= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13562 &:= 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13526 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 &13563 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13527 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= 1^2 + 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &13564 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 \\
13528 &:= 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^1 + 7^3 &13565 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13529 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 &13566 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13530 &:= 0^7 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 &= -1^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 &13567 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
13531 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 9^5 &= 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^1 &13568 &:= -3^8 - 4^3 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 8^6 &= -3^8 - 4^3 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 8^6 \\
13532 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 &13569 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 - 8^0 + 9^4 &= -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
13533 &:= -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 &= -2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 &13570 &:= 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^3 &= 1^2 + 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
13534 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 &13571 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
13535 &:= 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 &13572 &:= -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
13536 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 &13573 &:= -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 &= -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
13537 &:= 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^7 + 6^3 + 7^6 - 8^5 &= 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^7 + 6^3 + 7^6 - 8^5 &13574 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
13538 &:= 1^7 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 &= 1^7 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 &13575 &:= -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= -1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
13539 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 &= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 &13576 &:= -3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= -3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
13540 &:= -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 &= -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 &13577 &:= 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 \\
13541 &:= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 &= 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^4 &13578 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 \\
13542 &:= 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 &= 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^7 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^5 &13579 &:= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 &= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
13543 &:= 0^9 - 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^4 &= -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 + 9^1 &13580 &:= 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 &= 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13581 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4 & 13618 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13582 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13619 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13583 := -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13620 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 \\
13584 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13621 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^0 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13585 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^2 & 13622 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 \\
13586 := -1^4 - 3^1 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^4 - 3^1 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 13623 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 & = -1^9 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
13587 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 + 8^2 & 13624 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 \\
13588 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13625 := 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & = 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 \\
13589 := 0^4 - 3^0 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 7^2 - 8^5 & 13626 := -1^2 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13590 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13627 := 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 \\
13591 := 0^4 + 3^0 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = -2^9 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 13628 := 1^2 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13592 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13629 := -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13593 := 2^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 2^5 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & 13630 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13594 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13631 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13595 := -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13632 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13596 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13633 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13597 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^9 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 - 9^1 & 13634 := 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
13598 := -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13635 := 0^9 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
13599 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13636 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13600 := 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13637 := -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13601 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13638 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13602 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13639 := 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13603 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13640 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13604 := -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13641 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13605 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13642 := 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3 & = 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3 \\
13606 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13643 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13607 := -2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13644 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^0 - 7^3 & = 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
13608 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13645 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13609 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13646 := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
13610 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13647 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13611 := -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13648 := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
13612 := -3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^3 & 13649 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13613 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 7^1 - 8^5 & 13650 := -1^5 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
13614 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13651 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^0 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13615 := -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13652 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
13616 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13653 := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^0 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
13617 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 & 13654 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13655 := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13692 := 0^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
13656 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13693 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13657 := -2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13694 := -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13658 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13695 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13659 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13696 := -3^8 + 4^3 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 8^6 & = -3^8 + 4^3 + 6^7 + 7^4 - 8^6 \\
13660 := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & 13697 := 0^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 8^2 + 9^4 & = 1^6 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 + 8^4 \\
13661 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13698 := 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^2 & = 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
13662 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13699 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13663 := -2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13700 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
13664 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13701 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13665 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13702 := -2^8 - 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 & = -2^8 - 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
13666 := 1^5 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & 13703 := 0^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 8^2 + 9^4 \\
13667 := 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13704 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
13668 := -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13705 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13669 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = 1^5 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13706 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13670 := 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^4 & 13707 := -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13671 := -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & 13708 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13672 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & 13709 := 0^3 - 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 \\
13673 := 0^9 - 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 9^4 & = 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 + 9^1 & 13710 := 0^8 - 2^7 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 7^2 - 8^5 & = -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 7^3 \\
13674 := -1^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1 & = -1^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 - 8^1 & 13711 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13675 := -1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^5 & = -1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^5 & 13712 := -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13676 := -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 13713 := -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 & = -2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
13677 := 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^5 & = 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^5 & 13714 := -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13678 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13715 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13679 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13716 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13680 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13717 := -0^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13681 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 3^4 - 4^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 8^5 & 13718 := 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13682 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13719 := 0^0 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13683 := 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13720 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 \\
13684 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13721 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13685 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13722 := 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 - 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13686 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13723 := 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13687 := 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13724 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13688 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^3 & 13725 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 \\
13689 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13726 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 \\
13690 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13727 := 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
13691 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 13728 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13729 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & 13766 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^8 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13730 := -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 & 13767 := 1^8 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13731 := 0^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & 13768 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13732 := 0^9 - 3^6 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 9^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 & 13769 := -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13733 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^5 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 13770 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^3 \\
13734 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & 13771 := 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13735 := 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & 13772 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13736 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & 13773 := 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & = 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 \\
13737 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^3 & 13774 := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
13738 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13775 := -1^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 & = -1^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4 \\
13739 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4 & = -1^5 - 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 13776 := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
13740 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13777 := -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13741 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 13778 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
13742 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13779 := 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13743 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & 13780 := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 & = -3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\
13744 := -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13781 := 0^3 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13745 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & 13782 := 0^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
13746 := 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13783 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13747 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & 13784 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
13748 := -2^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13785 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13749 := 0^2 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13786 := -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
13750 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13787 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13751 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13788 := 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
13752 := -2^8 - 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 & = -2^8 - 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 & 13789 := 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 & = 1^9 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 \\
13753 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13790 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
13754 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 & 13791 := -2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
13755 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13792 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
13756 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & 13793 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13757 := -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & 13794 := 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^4 & = 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3 - 9^4 \\
13758 := -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 13795 := 0^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^1 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13759 := -1^8 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13796 := -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
13760 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 9^4 & 13797 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13761 := 1^8 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13798 := 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
13762 := 0^8 - 3^0 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 8^2 + 9^4 & 13799 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13763 := -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13800 := 0^5 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = -1^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 + 8^4 \\
13764 := 0^8 + 3^0 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & 13801 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13765 := 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13802 := 0^5 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^0 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
13803 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13840 := 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
13804 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^0 - 7^3 - 9^4 & = -1^8 - 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13841 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13805 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 13842 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13806 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 13843 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13807 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 5^5 + 8^4 & 13844 := 3^4 - 4^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = 3^4 - 4^8 - 5^3 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
13808 := -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13845 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13809 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 13846 := 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13810 := 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13847 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13811 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = 1^5 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 13848 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13812 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^9 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^9 - 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13849 := 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 2^5 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
13813 := 0^8 - 3^9 - 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^6 - 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4 & 13850 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13814 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & 13851 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^5 + 8^4 \\
13815 := 0^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13852 := 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13816 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^0 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13853 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 - 8^3 \\
13817 := -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13854 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13818 := -1^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = -1^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13855 := -1^8 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13819 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13856 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13820 := 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = 1^8 - 3^9 + 5^1 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13857 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^8 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13821 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13858 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13822 := 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13859 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13823 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13860 := 0^8 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13824 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13861 := -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13825 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13862 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13826 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^0 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 13863 := -2^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13827 := -2^8 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -2^8 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 13864 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13828 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13865 := -3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13829 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13866 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13830 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13867 := 1^8 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
13831 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & 13868 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13832 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^1 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 13869 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13833 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 8^4 - 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13870 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 \\
13834 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13871 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
13835 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13872 := 0^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
13836 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 13873 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
13837 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 13874 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 \\
13838 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3 & 13875 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 8^3 - 9^4 \\
13839 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 13876 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^9 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2
\end{array}$$

$13877 := -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3$	$= -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3$	$13914 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$
$13878 := -1^8 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13915 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$
$13879 := 2^4 - 4^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 8^5$	$= 2^4 - 4^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 + 8^5$	$13916 := 0^8 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$
$13880 := 1^8 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^8 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13917 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$
$13881 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4$	$13918 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$
$13882 := -1^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13919 := -1^8 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$
$13883 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$13920 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$
$13884 := 1^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13921 := 1^8 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^8 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$
$13885 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^9 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3$	$13922 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$
$13886 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 2^2 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13923 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$
$13887 := 0^8 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^9 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3$	$13924 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$
$13888 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 - 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13925 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4$
$13889 := 0^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$	$13926 := -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4$	$= -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4$
$13890 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^8 - 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13927 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4$
$13891 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$	$13928 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$
$13892 := -1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13929 := 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 8^5$	$= 2^4 - 4^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 + 8^5$
$13893 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2$	$13930 := -0^0 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$13894 := 1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13931 := -3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$13895 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^9 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3$	$13932 := 0^0 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$13896 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13933 := 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$	$= 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$
$13897 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$13934 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$13898 := 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$= 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$13935 := 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$13899 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$13936 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$13900 := -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4$	$13937 := 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
$13901 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$13938 := 0^6 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$
$13902 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^3$	$13939 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$
$13903 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$13940 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 - 9^2$
$13904 := -2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$13941 := 0^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$
$13905 := -0^0 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$13942 := -1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$
$13906 := 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$	$= 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$	$13943 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
$13907 := 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^5$	$13944 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
$13908 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2$	$13945 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$
$13909 := -1^8 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13946 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
$13910 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$13947 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$
$13911 := -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 8^4$	$= -1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 8^4$	$13948 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
$13912 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$13949 := -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$
$13913 := 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 8^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 8^4$	$13950 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$

13951 := $-0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13977 := $-1^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$
13952 := $-2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13978 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13953 := $0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13979 := $-2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13954 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	13980 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13955 := $-0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13981 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13956 := $-3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13982 := $-0^0 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13957 := $0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13983 := $4^7 - 7^4$	$= 4^7 - 7^4$
13958 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	13984 := $0^0 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13959 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13985 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13960 := $2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13986 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13961 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13987 := $2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13962 := $1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	13988 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13963 := $1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	13989 := $1^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$
13964 := $-1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$	13990 := $1^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$
13965 := $-0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13991 := $-1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$
13966 := $-2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13992 := $1^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1$
13967 := $0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13993 := $1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$
13968 := $-3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$	$= -3^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^4$	13994 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$
13969 := $-1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	13995 := $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13970 := $-1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1$	13996 := $0^3 - 3^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1$
13971 := $-1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4$	13997 := $1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1$
13972 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	13998 := $-1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
13973 := $-1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	13999 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13974 := $-1^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1$	14000 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$
13975 := $1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$		
13976 := $-1^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$		
14001 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14012 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
14002 := $1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1$	14013 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$
14003 := $-1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	14014 := $2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$
14004 := $-1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4$	14015 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$
14005 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14016 := $-3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$
14006 := $-2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14017 := $0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$
14007 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14018 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$
14008 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	14019 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$
14009 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14020 := $0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$
14010 := $3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14021 := $3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$
14011 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4$	14022 := $-3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$

14023 := $0^0 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	14060 := $0^0 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
14024 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	14061 := $-1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14025 := $2^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^4$	14062 := $-2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14026 := $2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	14063 := $0^9 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^9 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14027 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	14064 := $-2^9 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$= -2^9 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2$
14028 := $2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5$	14065 := $0^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14029 := $0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	14066 := $0^1 + 1^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$
14030 := $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4$	14067 := $1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14031 := $0^7 - 2^0 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	14068 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$
14032 := $0^8 + 3^4 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	14069 := $-2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^2$	$= -2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^2$
14033 := $0^7 + 2^0 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	14070 := $0^0 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14034 := $0^5 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	14071 := $0^3 + 2^0 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14035 := $0^7 + 3^3 - 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^8 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	14072 := $-1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$
14036 := $0^5 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	14073 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14037 := $-0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	14074 := $1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$
14038 := $2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	14075 := $0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14039 := $-0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	14076 := $1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14040 := $2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	$= 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	14077 := $-0^0 + 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14041 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4$	14078 := $2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14042 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	14079 := $0^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14043 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	14080 := $-0^0 - 1^3 - 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$
14044 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	14081 := $-1^3 - 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -1^3 - 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14045 := $2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$= 2^8 - 3^9 - 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3$	14082 := $-0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$
14046 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	14083 := $2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$
14047 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	14084 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$
14048 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	14085 := $0^3 - 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$
14049 := $0^1 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	14086 := $-2^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -2^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$
14050 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2$	14087 := $0^3 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14051 := $-0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4$	14088 := $0^1 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2$
14052 := $-1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	14089 := $-0^0 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14053 := $-3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^3$	$= -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^3$	14090 := $-4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$
14054 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4$	14091 := $0^0 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14055 := $-2^2 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -2^2 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	14092 := $2^8 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= 2^8 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5$
14056 := $2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4$	14093 := $-0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14057 := $3^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5$	$= 3^7 - 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5$	14094 := $-2^3 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4$
14058 := $-0^0 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	14095 := $2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3$	$= 2^8 - 3^9 + 5^2 + 8^5 + 9^3$
14059 := $-3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	14096 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14097 := -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 14134 := 0^2 - 2^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
14098 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14135 := 1^4 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = 1^4 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\
14099 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14136 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 \\
14100 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 14137 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14101 := 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 14138 := -1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14102 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 14139 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14103 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14140 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14104 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14141 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^1 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
14105 := 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & = 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^4 & 14142 := 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^4 \\
14106 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14143 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14107 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 14144 := -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14108 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14145 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14109 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14146 := -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14110 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14147 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14111 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14148 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14112 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14149 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14113 := -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 14150 := -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14114 := 1^8 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 14151 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14115 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14152 := 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
14116 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14153 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14117 := 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & = 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 7^5 & 14154 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14118 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14155 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14119 := 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14156 := -2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = -2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 \\
14120 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14157 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
14121 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14158 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^4 \\
14122 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 14159 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14123 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14160 := 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
14124 := 0^4 - 2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^0 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 14161 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
14125 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14162 := 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^8 + 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 \\
14126 := -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14163 := -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
14127 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14164 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 \\
14128 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 14165 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14129 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & = 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^4 & 14166 := 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14130 := 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 & = 2^9 + 3^8 - 4^2 + 8^3 + 9^4 & 14167 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14131 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14168 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14132 := 0^0 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14169 := 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14133 := 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14170 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14171 := 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 14208 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
14172 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & 14209 := 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
14173 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 14210 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^0 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 \\
14174 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 14211 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^0 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14175 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 14212 := -2^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 & = -2^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
14176 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 14213 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
14177 := -2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = -2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 & 14214 := 2^8 - 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 & = 2^8 - 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
14178 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & 14215 := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^0 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
14179 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & 14216 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 \\
14180 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^4 & 14217 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
14181 := 1^5 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^5 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 14218 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
14182 := 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 - 8^2 & 14219 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
14183 := 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & 14220 := -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 \\
14184 := 0^5 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = 1^7 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 & 14221 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 \\
14185 := 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & 14222 := 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 & = 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 \\
14186 := 0^5 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = 2^8 + 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14223 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14187 := -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14224 := -2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14188 := 0^3 - 2^9 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = -2^8 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 & 14225 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14189 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14226 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 \\
14190 := -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14227 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14191 := -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14228 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^4 \\
14192 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & 14229 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14193 := -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & = -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & 14230 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14194 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & 14231 := -2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^2 \\
14195 := -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14232 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14196 := 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14233 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
14197 := 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14234 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14198 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & 14235 := -2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14199 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14236 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14200 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & 14237 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14201 := -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14238 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14202 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 14239 := -3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14203 := 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14240 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14204 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^4 & 14241 := -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
14205 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & 14242 := -2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14206 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^6 - 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 14243 := 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 \\
14207 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 & 14244 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14245 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 14282 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14246 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & 14283 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
14247 := 0^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^5 + 9^4 & 14284 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^4 + 8^1 \\
14248 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^1 & 14285 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14249 := 0^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 14286 := -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14250 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & 14287 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14251 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 14288 := 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14252 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & 14289 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14253 := -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 14290 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = 1^8 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
14254 := -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14291 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14255 := 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 14292 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14256 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^5 - 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 14293 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14257 := 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14294 := 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14258 := -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 14295 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14259 := 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 & 14296 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
14260 := 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14297 := -1^5 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14261 := -0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14298 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
14262 := -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = -3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 14299 := 1^5 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14263 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & = 1^5 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14300 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14264 := 0^5 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^8 - 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^4 + 8^5 & 14301 := 0^5 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
14265 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14302 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14266 := 0^5 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^2 - 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 & 14303 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 \\
14267 := -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14304 := -3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14268 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 14305 := 0^0 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14269 := 1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14306 := 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14270 := -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = -1^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 14307 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14271 := 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 14308 := -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14272 := 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 14309 := 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 9^4 \\
14273 := -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14310 := -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14274 := 0^7 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 14311 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14275 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & = 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^4 & 14312 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14276 := 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & = 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^2 & 14313 := -2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14277 := -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 14314 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14278 := 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 6^6 - 8^5 & 14315 := -2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14279 := 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 14316 := 1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14280 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14317 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14281 := -2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14318 := 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14319 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14356 := -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14320 := -1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14357 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14321 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14358 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14322 := 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14359 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14323 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14360 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14324 := -1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14361 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14325 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14362 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
14326 := 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14363 := 0^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14327 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14364 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14328 := 0^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14365 := 0^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
14329 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14366 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14330 := 0^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14367 := 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
14331 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14368 := -1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14332 := -1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14369 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14333 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 3^9 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 8^3 + 9^5 & 14370 := 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14334 := 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14371 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14335 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14372 := 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14336 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14373 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14337 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14374 := 0^5 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14338 := 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14375 := 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14339 := 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 14376 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14340 := -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14377 := 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14341 := 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 & = 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 7^3 & 14378 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14342 := -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14379 := -3^3 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = -3^3 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14343 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14380 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 \\
14344 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14381 := -1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14345 := 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14382 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14346 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14383 := 1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14347 := 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14384 := 0^4 - 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^8 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^1 \\
14348 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14385 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14349 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14386 := 0^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14350 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14387 := -1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14351 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14388 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14352 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14389 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14353 := 1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14390 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14354 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^2 & 14391 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14355 := 0^5 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^4 & 14392 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^4 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14393 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14430 := 0^6 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14394 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 & 14431 := 1^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 & = 1^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 \\
14395 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14432 := 0^2 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14396 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 14433 := 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14397 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14434 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14398 := -1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 14435 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14399 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14436 := 0^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
14400 := 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 14437 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 8^4 - 9^0 & = -1^9 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^2 \\
14401 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 & 14438 := 0^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
14402 := -2^2 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = -2^2 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & 14439 := -3^9 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 8^5 + 9^3 & = -3^9 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 8^5 + 9^3 \\
14403 := 0^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^1 & 14440 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
14404 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14441 := 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
14405 := 0^6 - 3^7 + 5^0 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & 14442 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14406 := -4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = -4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & 14443 := 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14407 := 0^0 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^1 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & 14444 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14408 := -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 14445 := 1^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & = 1^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
14409 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 - 8^0 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 14446 := -1^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14410 := 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 14447 := -1^5 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
14411 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^0 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 14448 := 0^8 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14412 := 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & = 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^4 & 14449 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
14413 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 14450 := 0^8 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
14414 := 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 14451 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^5 - 8^3 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
14415 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 14452 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14416 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14453 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
14417 := -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & 14454 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^3 \\
14418 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 & 14455 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
14419 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & 14456 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
14420 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^8 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^2 & 14457 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^0 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^1 \\
14421 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14458 := 0^6 - 2^0 - 3^7 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
14422 := -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 & 14459 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
14423 := 0^4 - 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^2 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14460 := -2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
14424 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 14461 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 - 8^0 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14425 := -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & 14462 := -2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14426 := 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 7^4 & 14463 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14427 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^0 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14464 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14428 := 2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = 2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 & 14465 := -0^0 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14429 := 0^3 - 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14466 := 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14467 := 0^0 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 14504 := 1^8 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = 1^8 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
14468 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 & 14505 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
14469 := -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 14506 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14470 := 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 14507 := -0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14471 := 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 14508 := 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14472 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 14509 := 0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14473 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^3 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 14510 := 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14474 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14511 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
14475 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14512 := -0^0 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = -1^1 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
14476 := -2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14513 := -4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = -4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
14477 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14514 := 0^0 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = 1^1 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
14478 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14515 := 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
14479 := 0^5 + 3^0 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 14516 := -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14480 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14517 := 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 & = 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^4 + 6^6 + 8^5 \\
14481 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14518 := 1^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 & = 1^8 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14482 := 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & = 2^3 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^2 & 14519 := 0^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14483 := 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14520 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5 \\
14484 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 14521 := 0^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14485 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 14522 := -2^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
14486 := -1^8 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^8 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 14523 := 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
14487 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 14524 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
14488 := -0^0 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 14525 := -1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14489 := -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 14526 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14490 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14527 := 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14491 := -2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14528 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14492 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14529 := 0^2 + 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14493 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 & 14530 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14494 := -0^0 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14531 := 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14495 := -3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14532 := 0^4 + 2^0 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14496 := 0^0 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14533 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14497 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 14534 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14498 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14535 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14499 := 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14536 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14500 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 14537 := 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14501 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^4 & 14538 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14502 := 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 & 14539 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
14503 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^1 & 14540 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = -2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14541 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 14578 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
14542 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 14579 := -1^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14543 := 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & 14580 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
14544 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14581 := 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
14545 := -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14582 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
14546 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14583 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14547 := -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 14584 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14548 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14585 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14549 := -2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14586 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14550 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14587 := -2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14551 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14588 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14552 := 1^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14589 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14553 := -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & 14590 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14554 := 0^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^0 & = 2^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14591 := -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
14555 := 0^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 14592 := -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14556 := 0^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14593 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
14557 := 0^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 14594 := -1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = -1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
14558 := 0^1 + 1^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14595 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
14559 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 14596 := 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
14560 := -1^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14597 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14561 := -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 14598 := 0^4 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14562 := -1^4 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14599 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
14563 := 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 14600 := 0^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
14564 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14601 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14565 := -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 14602 := 0^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14566 := 0^4 + 2^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14603 := 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14567 := -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14604 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14568 := 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 14605 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14569 := 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14606 := -1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14570 := 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 14607 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -2^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
14571 := 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 & 14608 := 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14572 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & 14609 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
14573 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^4 & = -2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 14610 := -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14574 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14611 := 0^2 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
14575 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & 14612 := 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14576 := 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & 14613 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
14577 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^2 & 14614 := -1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

14615 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14652 := $-0^0 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
14616 := $1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	14653 := $2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
14617 := $0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14654 := $0^0 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
14618 := $0^1 - 1^3 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14655 := $1^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^1$
14619 := $0^3 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14656 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
14620 := $0^1 - 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14657 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14621 := $0^3 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -2^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	14658 := $-2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14622 := $0^1 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14659 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14623 := $-0^0 - 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	14660 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14624 := $-1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14661 := $-0^0 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14625 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14662 := $5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14626 := $1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14663 := $0^0 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14627 := $0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	14664 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14628 := $-1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14665 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14629 := $0^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14666 := $2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14630 := $1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14667 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14631 := $-2^2 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -2^2 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	14668 := $0^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6$	$= -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
14632 := $-1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14669 := $-1^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^1$
14633 := $-1^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14670 := $-1^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^1$
14634 := $-0^0 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	14671 := $1^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^1$
14635 := $-3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	14672 := $1^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^1$
14636 := $3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^4$	14673 := $-1^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6$	$= -1^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6$
14637 := $-2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	14674 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
14638 := $0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	14675 := $-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
14639 := $2^2 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	14676 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$
14640 := $1^4 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	14677 := $1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
14641 := $-0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	14678 := $-1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$
14642 := $-1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	14679 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14643 := $-2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	14680 := $1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$
14644 := $0^3 - 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	14681 := $0^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
14645 := $-2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5$	14682 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$
14646 := $0^3 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	14683 := $0^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
14647 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	14684 := $2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^4$
14648 := $1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	14685 := $0^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$
14649 := $3^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^5 - 9^3$	$= 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^5 - 9^3$	14686 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
14650 := $-2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3$	$= -2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^3$	14687 := $-1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
14651 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	14688 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14689 := 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & 14726 := 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
14690 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = 1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14727 := -2^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -2^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
14691 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 14728 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14692 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14729 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^2 \\
14693 := -2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 14730 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14694 := 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & 14731 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14695 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 14732 := -2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14696 := 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14733 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14697 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 14734 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14698 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & 14735 := -0^0 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14699 := -3^8 + 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & = -3^8 + 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 14736 := -3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14700 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^9 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14737 := 0^0 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14701 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & 14738 := -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
14702 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & 14739 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14703 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & 14740 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14704 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 14741 := -2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14705 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 14742 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14706 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & 14743 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
14707 := 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^4 & 14744 := -0^0 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14708 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14745 := -3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14709 := -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 14746 := 0^0 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14710 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14747 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
14711 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 14748 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14712 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 14749 := 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14713 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^4 & = -2^4 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 14750 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14714 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14751 := -3^7 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14715 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 14752 := -4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
14716 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14753 := 0^0 - 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^9 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
14717 := -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 14754 := 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^0 + 8^4 & = 1^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
14718 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 14755 := 1^9 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 & = 1^9 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
14719 := 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 14756 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
14720 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 6^2 + 8^4 & 14757 := -3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
14721 := 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & 14758 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = -1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
14722 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 14759 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
14723 := 0^9 - 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^4 & 14760 := 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 & = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4 \\
14724 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 14761 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
14725 := 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 14762 := 0^2 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

14763 := $-1^5 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2$	14800 := $2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$
14764 := $0^4 + 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	14801 := $2^3 + 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14765 := $1^5 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^9 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 9^2$	14802 := $0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14766 := $-0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	14803 := $-0^0 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^4 + 8^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14767 := $-2^3 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14804 := $-3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^4 + 8^3$	$= -3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^4 + 8^3$
14768 := $0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^1 + 8^4$	14805 := $-0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14769 := $0^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 - 8^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2$	14806 := $-2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^3$
14770 := $0^2 + 2^8 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 6^6 - 8^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 - 9^1$	14807 := $-2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14771 := $0^2 - 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$	14808 := $0^2 + 2^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14772 := $-0^0 + 2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14809 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14773 := $2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^6 - 3^7 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5$	14810 := $-0^0 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14774 := $-1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 - 9^1$	14811 := $3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14775 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^1 - 8^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5$	14812 := $0^0 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14776 := $-1^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^1 - 8^4$	$= -1^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^1 - 8^4$	14813 := $-1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14777 := $2^4 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 2^4 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	14814 := $-0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14778 := $-1^5 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -1^5 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14815 := $1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14779 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14816 := $0^4 - 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14780 := $-2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14817 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14781 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14818 := $0^4 + 3^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$
14782 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14819 := $-1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14783 := $-0^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14820 := $-0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^2$
14784 := $4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14821 := $1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14785 := $0^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14822 := $0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^4$
14786 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14823 := $-0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14787 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14824 := $2^4 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^4 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14788 := $2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14825 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14789 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14826 := $0^5 + 2^9 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$
14790 := $1^5 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 1^5 + 4^8 + 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14827 := $0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14791 := $2^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^4$	$= 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^4$	14828 := $1^6 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$
14792 := $1^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^1 - 8^4$	$= 1^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^1 - 8^4$	14829 := $-0^0 - 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14793 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^1 - 8^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	14830 := $-1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$
14794 := $1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 + 9^1$	14831 := $-0^0 + 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14795 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 - 9^3$	14832 := $1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$
14796 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	14833 := $0^0 + 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^3$
14797 := $2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	14834 := $0^1 - 1^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$
14798 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^2 + 8^4$	14835 := $0^6 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
14799 := $-0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	14836 := $0^1 - 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
14837 := 0^6 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -3^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^4 - 8^3 & 14874 := 2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & = 2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
14838 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 & = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 & 14875 := 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
14839 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 & 14876 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14840 := -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 14877 := 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^3 \\
14841 := 2^5 + 4^8 + 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^4 & = 2^5 + 4^8 + 5^2 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 14878 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
14842 := 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 14879 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 \\
14843 := -1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 14880 := -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14844 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14881 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 \\
14845 := 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 14882 := 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14846 := -2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & = -2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 8^2 & 14883 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^5 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\
14847 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 14884 := 0^9 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14848 := 0^6 + 3^8 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14885 := 0^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^5 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 \\
14849 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^8 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 14886 := 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14850 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14887 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14851 := -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & 14888 := 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14852 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14889 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14853 := 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & = 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & 14890 := 0^5 - 1^9 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
14854 := 2^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^2 & = 2^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 8^2 & 14891 := -3^3 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 & = -3^3 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14855 := 1^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^4 - 9^3 & = 1^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^4 - 9^3 & 14892 := 0^5 + 1^9 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14856 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 - 9^3 & = -1^7 - 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 14893 := -2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14857 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 - 9^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & 14894 := -2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14858 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14895 := 0^5 + 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14859 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14896 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14860 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 14897 := -0^0 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14861 := -1^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^4 - 9^3 & = -1^8 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^4 - 9^3 & 14898 := 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14862 := -2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -2^9 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 & 14899 := 0^0 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14863 := -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 14900 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14864 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14901 := -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -2^8 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
14865 := 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & = 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 14902 := 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14866 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14903 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^4 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
14867 := 0^2 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 14904 := 0^5 + 1^9 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14868 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^3 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14905 := -3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^5 & = -3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^5 \\
14869 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 14906 := -2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14870 := -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14907 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14871 := 0^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^3 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^4 - 9^3 & 14908 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
14872 := 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 14909 := -0^0 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14873 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^4 - 9^3 & 14910 := -3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
14911 := 0^0 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = 1^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14912 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = -1^9 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 \\
14913 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14914 := 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14915 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
14916 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 = -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
14917 := -0^0 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 = -1^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14918 := 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 = 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14919 := 0^0 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 = 1^1 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14920 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 = 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^1 - 8^4 \\
14921 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 = -1^1 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14922 := 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 = 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14923 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 = 1^1 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14924 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14925 := 2^6 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 = 2^6 - 3^7 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
14926 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 = 2^2 + 3^8 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14927 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14928 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14929 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14930 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = -1^9 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 \\
14931 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14932 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14933 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
14934 := -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 = -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
14935 := -1^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 - 9^2 = -1^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 - 9^2 \\
14936 := 0^9 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 9^3 = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
14937 := 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 = 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
14938 := 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 = 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14939 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^8 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
14940 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
14941 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
14942 := 0^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 - 9^2 = -1^9 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^3 \\
14943 := -1^5 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 = -1^5 - 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
14944 := 0^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 - 9^2 = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
14945 := 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 = 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 \\
14946 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
14947 := -2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 = -2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
14948 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14949 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14950 := 0^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 = 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^8 + 5^3 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
14951 := 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14952 := 0^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 = -1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
14953 := 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
14954 := 0^9 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
14955 := -2^6 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^2 = -2^6 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
14956 := 0^9 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
14957 := -0^0 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 = -1^1 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
14958 := 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 = 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
14959 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 = 1^1 + 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
14960 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^4 = -1^9 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
14961 := 2^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^4 = 2^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^4 \\
14962 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^2 - 8^4 = 1^9 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
14963 := 0^9 + 2^5 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^3 = -1^5 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14964 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14965 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14966 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14967 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
14968 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14969 := 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14970 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14971 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14972 := 2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 = 2^8 - 5^5 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
14973 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 6^3 + 8^4 \\
14974 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14975 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14976 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14977 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14978 := 1^6 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
14979 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^2 = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
14980 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 = -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
14981 := -1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 = -1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14982 := 2^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^2 = 2^8 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^2 \\
14983 := 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 = 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14984 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 = 1^8 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 + 8^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
14985 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -1^5 + 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14986 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
14987 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^5 + 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
14988 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
14989 &:= 0^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= -2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
14990 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
14991 &:= 0^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
14992 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
14993 &:= 0^5 + 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 &= 1^5 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15001 &:= -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= -3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
15002 &:= 0^0 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= 1^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
15003 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15004 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
15005 &:= 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
15006 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
15007 &:= -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15008 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^0 &= -1^2 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
15009 &:= 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^3 &= 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15010 &:= -1^5 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= -1^5 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15011 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15012 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15013 &:= -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^3 &= -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15014 &:= 0^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 &= 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15015 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15016 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15017 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
15018 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15019 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 &= -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
15020 &:= 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 &= 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
15021 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 &= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
15022 &:= -2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 &= -2^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
15023 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 &= 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15024 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 &= 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
15025 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15026 &:= 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 &= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^5 + 7^3 \\
15027 &:= 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 &= 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15028 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 &= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
14994 &:= 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 &= 1^2 + 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
14995 &:= 0^5 + 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
14996 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14997 &:= -1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= -1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
14998 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
14999 &:= 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 &= 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
15000 &:= -0^0 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
15029 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15030 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15031 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 9^2 &= -3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
15032 &:= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15033 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 &= -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
15034 &:= 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15035 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15036 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15037 &:= -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15038 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15039 &:= 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 &= 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15040 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15041 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15042 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15043 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15044 &:= -1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= -1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15045 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
15046 &:= 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15047 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
15048 &:= 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 &= -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15049 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^0 &= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15050 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 &= 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15051 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^0 &= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15052 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^5 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15053 &:= -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15054 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^3 \\
15055 &:= 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15056 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15057 &:= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15094 &:= -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & &= -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15058 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^5 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 & 15095 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & &= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15059 &:= -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 = -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 15096 &:= 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & &= 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15060 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^5 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 & 15097 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & &= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15061 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -2^5 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 15098 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & &= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15062 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -2^8 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6 & 15099 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15063 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15100 &:= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & &= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15064 &:= -2^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^3 = -2^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^3 & 15101 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
15065 &:= 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 = 2^8 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & 15102 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15066 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 = 1^5 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 & 15103 &:= 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15067 &:= -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 = -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 & 15104 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15068 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^3 & 15105 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15069 &:= 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 = 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 & 15106 &:= 0^2 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^1 = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
15070 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^3 & 15107 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15071 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^6 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15108 &:= -2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^4 = -2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 - 8^4 \\
15072 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15109 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
15073 &:= -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15110 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15074 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15111 &:= -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 = -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15075 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15112 &:= -2^5 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = -2^5 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15076 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^0 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15113 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15077 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15114 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^5 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15078 &:= 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^0 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15115 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15079 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15116 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^5 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15080 &:= -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15117 &:= 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^0 = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15081 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15118 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 = -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
15082 &:= 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15119 &:= -1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 = -1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15083 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15120 &:= 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^1 = -1^5 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15084 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15121 &:= 1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 = 1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15085 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 & 15122 &:= 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^1 = 1^5 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15086 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15123 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
15087 &:= 0^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 & 15124 &:= 0^2 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^1 = 1^8 - 2^2 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
15088 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = 2^9 - 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & 15125 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0 = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15089 &:= 0^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15126 &:= -1^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 = -1^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
15090 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15127 &:= 0^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0 = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15091 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15128 &:= 1^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 = 1^8 - 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
15092 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15129 &:= 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 = 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
15093 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 = 2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 - 9^2 & 15130 &:= -2^5 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 = -2^5 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
15131 := 0^8 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15168 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 \\
15132 := -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^3 & 15169 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15133 := 0^8 - 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = 1^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15170 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15134 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15171 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15135 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15172 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 & = -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 \\
15136 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15173 := -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 & = -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 \\
15137 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15174 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3 \\
15138 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15175 := 1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 & = 1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^1 \\
15139 := -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 & = -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 & 15176 := 1^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = 1^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
15140 := 0^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15177 := -2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15141 := 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 & = 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 & 15178 := 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^5 + 8^3 \\
15142 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 & = 1^4 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^3 & 15179 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15143 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15180 := -0^0 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15144 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15181 := -3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15145 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15182 := 0^0 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15146 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 15183 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15147 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 & 15184 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 3^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15148 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 9^1 & 15185 := 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^2 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15149 := -1^5 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^5 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15186 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^2 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^2 \\
15150 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^0 & = -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^5 & 15187 := -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
15151 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = 1^5 - 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15188 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^4 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15152 := 0^5 - 3^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 3^5 + 4^8 + 5^3 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 15189 := 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
15153 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15190 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^4 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15154 := 0^5 + 3^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -2^3 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15191 := 0^4 - 2^9 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 \\
15155 := -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15192 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 & = -1^5 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15156 := -1^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^1 & 15193 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15157 := -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 & 15194 := 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15158 := -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15195 := 0^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 & = -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^5 \\
15159 := 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 & 15196 := 0^1 + 1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 & = 1^4 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15160 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^1 & 15197 := 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^5 & = 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^5 \\
15161 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15198 := 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15162 := -2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15199 := -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^5 - 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
15163 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15200 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
15164 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & 15201 := 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
15165 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15202 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
15166 := -3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = -3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15203 := 0^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15167 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15204 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15205 &:= 0^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^5 = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15242 &:= 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15206 &:= -2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 = -2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 - 8^4 & 15243 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15207 &:= -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 = -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 & 15244 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15208 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 = 1^5 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 + 9^1 & 15245 &:= 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 = 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
15209 &:= 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 = 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 & 15246 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
15210 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 = -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 & 15247 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^4 - 9^2 \\
15211 &:= -1^5 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 = -1^5 - 2^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 15248 &:= -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15212 &:= 0^3 + 2^9 - 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^2 = -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 & 15249 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
15213 &:= 0^7 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 = -1^5 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 15250 &:= 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15214 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 15251 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^9 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15215 &:= 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 15252 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15216 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 15253 &:= -2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15217 &:= 0^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 = -1^3 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & 15254 &:= 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 = 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 \\
15218 &:= 0^5 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^3 & 15255 &:= 2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^2 = 2^9 + 5^7 - 6^6 - 7^5 + 9^2 \\
15219 &:= 0^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 = -1^5 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 15256 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^0 = -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15220 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15257 &:= 0^9 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^1 \\
15221 &:= -2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15258 &:= 0^7 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15222 &:= -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 = -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 & 15259 &:= -3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 = -3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
15223 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 & 15260 &:= -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 = -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15224 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 15261 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15225 &:= 0^2 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^5 & 15262 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15226 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15263 &:= 1^9 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 = 1^9 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15227 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15264 &:= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15228 &:= 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 = 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 15265 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15229 &:= -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^2 = -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^2 & 15266 &:= -2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15230 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15267 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15231 &:= 0^5 - 2^7 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 = -1^8 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2 & 15268 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15232 &:= -0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15269 &:= 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15233 &:= 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 15270 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
15234 &:= 0^0 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15271 &:= 0^5 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^0 = -1^5 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 \\
15235 &:= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 & 15272 &:= -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15236 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15273 &:= -2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 = -2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
15237 &:= 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15274 &:= -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -2^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15238 &:= 0^2 - 2^3 - 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15275 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15239 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 & 15276 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 = 1^7 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15240 &:= -1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15277 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
15241 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^5 & 15278 &:= -2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 = -2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
15279 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15316 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 = -1^7 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15280 &:= -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 = -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15317 &:= 0^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 = -1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15281 &:= 0^5 + 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15318 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 = 1^7 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15282 &:= 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^5 = -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 & 15319 &:= 0^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 = 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15283 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15320 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 = 1^7 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
15284 &:= 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^5 = 1^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 & 15321 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15285 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15322 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15286 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & 15323 &:= -1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 = -1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15287 &:= 0^5 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 15324 &:= -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 = -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 \\
15288 &:= 0^5 - 1^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = -1^7 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 & 15325 &:= -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = 1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15289 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 & 15326 &:= -3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = -3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15290 &:= 0^5 + 1^7 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = 1^7 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 & 15327 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15291 &:= -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15328 &:= -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15292 &:= 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 = 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 & 15329 &:= 0^5 - 3^4 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15293 &:= 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 = 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15330 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 = -1^2 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15294 &:= 0^9 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 = 1^9 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 15331 &:= -1^5 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 = -1^5 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15295 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^3 = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15332 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15296 &:= 0^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 + 8^0 = -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & 15333 &:= 1^5 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 = 1^5 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15297 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15334 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^5 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15298 &:= -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 = -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 & 15335 &:= -1^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 = -1^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15299 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15336 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0 = 1^5 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15300 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^1 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15337 &:= -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15301 &:= -2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15338 &:= -2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15302 &:= 0^0 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15339 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15303 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15340 &:= -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 = -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
15304 &:= 0^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^2 = -2^9 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 & 15341 &:= -0^0 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 = -1^1 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
15305 &:= -1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 = -1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 & 15342 &:= -3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 = -3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
15306 &:= 0^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 8^2 = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 15343 &:= 0^0 - 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15307 &:= 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 = 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3 & 15344 &:= 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15308 &:= -0^0 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15345 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15309 &:= -3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 15346 &:= 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^1 \\
15310 &:= 0^0 - 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2 & 15347 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15311 &:= 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15348 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15312 &:= 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2 = 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2 & 15349 &:= -2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = -2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15313 &:= 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^4 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15350 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15314 &:= -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^2 = -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^2 & 15351 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 \\
15315 &:= 0^4 - 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15352 &:= -0^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 = -1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4
\end{aligned}$$

$15353 := 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15390 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3$
$15354 := 0^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15391 := 0^2 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15355 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15392 := 0^8 + 4^0 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6$	$= 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15356 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15393 := 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15357 := 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15394 := -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15358 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15395 := 0^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15359 := -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^1$	$15396 := 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15360 := 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15397 := 0^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15361 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^1$	$15398 := 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1$
$15362 := -1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15399 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15363 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^1$	$15400 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15364 := 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15401 := 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15365 := 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15402 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15366 := 0^5 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15403 := 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15367 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15404 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15368 := 0^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15405 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15369 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15406 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15370 := 0^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15407 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15371 := 0^1 + 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15408 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15372 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15409 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15373 := -2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15410 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15374 := -1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15411 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15375 := -1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15412 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1$
$15376 := 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15413 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15377 := 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15414 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1$
$15378 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15415 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15379 := 0^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15416 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$
$15380 := 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15417 := 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15381 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15418 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$
$15382 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15419 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15383 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15420 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$
$15384 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4$	$15421 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15385 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15422 := -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15386 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15423 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15387 := -1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15424 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$
$15388 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^8 - 4^1 + 6^7 - 7^4 - 8^6$	$15425 := -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15389 := 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15426 := 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$

$15427 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15464 := 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15428 := 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$	$15465 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15429 := 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$15466 := -2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15430 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^7 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2$	$15467 := -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$	$= -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$
$15431 := -0^0 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15468 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^2$	$= 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^3 + 9^2$
$15432 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15469 := 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$
$15433 := 0^0 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15470 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$
$15434 := 0^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^2$	$= 1^7 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1$	$15471 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15435 := 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$15472 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2$	$= -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2$
$15436 := -0^0 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15473 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15437 := 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15474 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$
$15438 := 0^0 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15475 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15439 := 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15476 := 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15440 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^2$	$15477 := 0^5 - 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15441 := -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2$	$15478 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^3$
$15442 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -2^5 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15479 := 0^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15443 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15480 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$
$15444 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15481 := 0^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15445 := 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15482 := 0^1 + 1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$
$15446 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15483 := 0^4 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15447 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^2$	$= 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^1$	$15484 := -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15448 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3$	$15485 := -1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15449 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15486 := 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$
$15450 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15487 := 1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15451 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15488 := 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2$
$15452 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15489 := 0^5 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15453 := -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2$	$15490 := 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2$
$15454 := -2^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 + 8^5$	$= -2^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 + 8^5$	$15491 := 0^5 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^2$
$15455 := 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2$	$15492 := 0^2 + 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^1$	$= -1^7 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2$
$15456 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15493 := -1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15457 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$= 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15494 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^7 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2$
$15458 := 0^4 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^3$	$15495 := 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$
$15459 := -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2$	$= -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2$	$15496 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1$
$15460 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^0$	$= -2^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^2$	$15497 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15461 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$15498 := 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15462 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1$	$15499 := 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^5$	$= 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^5$
$15463 := 0^1 + 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15500 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
15501 := 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15502 := 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15503 := 0^2 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15504 := 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
15505 := -1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15506 := 2^5 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^5 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15507 := 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15508 := -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15509 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
15510 := 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15511 := 0^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 9^2 & = -1^5 - 2^4 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15512 := 0^1 - 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15513 := 0^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^1 \\
15514 := 0^1 + 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15515 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = 1^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^1 \\
15516 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15517 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15518 := -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15519 := 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15520 := 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & = 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15521 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 & = 1^5 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15522 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 - 9^0 & = -1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 \\
15523 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15524 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 + 9^0 & = 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2 \\
15525 := -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 & = -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
15526 := 0^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15527 := 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
15528 := 0^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^2 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15529 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15530 := -2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15531 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15532 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^0 & = 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
15533 := 1^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 + 9^1 & = 1^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 8^4 + 9^1 \\
15534 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^0 & = -1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2 \\
15535 := 0^1 + 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15536 := 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2 & = 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2 \\
15537 := -1^7 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^7 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
15538 := 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15539 := -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
15540 := -2^5 - 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^5 - 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15541 := 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
15542 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^9 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15543 := 0^7 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^2 & = -1^4 - 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15544 := -2^5 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -2^5 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
15545 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 & = 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^2 \\
15546 := 0^1 - 1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^4 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
15547 := 0^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1 \\
15548 := -1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 & = -1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 \\
15549 := -1^7 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^7 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^2 \\
15550 := 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 & = 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1 \\
15551 := -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 & = -1^5 - 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
15552 := -1^4 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15553 := -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15554 := 1^4 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15555 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15556 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15557 := -2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15558 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15559 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15560 := -1^4 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^4 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15561 := 0^5 - 2^0 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15562 := 1^4 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15563 := 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15564 := -1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 & = -1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
15565 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15566 := 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 & = 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1 \\
15567 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1 \\
15568 := -1^5 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -1^5 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15569 := -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 & = -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
15570 := 1^5 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^5 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15571 := -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15572 := 0^5 - 2^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^4 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 \\
15573 := 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 - 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 - 9^3 \\
15574 := 0^5 - 2^4 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 - 9^3
\end{array}$$

$15575 := 0^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 9^2$	$= -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^5$	$15612 := -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1$
$15576 := 0^4 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15613 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15577 := 0^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15614 := -1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15578 := 0^4 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15615 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15579 := 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15616 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15580 := 0^5 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^3$	$15617 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15581 := -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2$	$= -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2$	$15618 := -1^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15582 := 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^0 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15619 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15583 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15620 := 1^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15584 := -2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15621 := 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15585 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15622 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15586 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15623 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15587 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15624 := 0^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15588 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15625 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15589 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 2^0 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15626 := 0^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15590 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15627 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15591 := -1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15628 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15592 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15629 := -2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15593 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15630 := -1^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15594 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15631 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15595 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15632 := 1^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15596 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1$	$15633 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4$
$15597 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15634 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15598 := -3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15635 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15599 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15636 := 1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15600 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15637 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15601 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15638 := 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1$
$15602 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^2 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15639 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1$
$15603 := -1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15640 := 0^4 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15604 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$15641 := 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15605 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15642 := 0^4 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15606 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1$	$15643 := 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15607 := 0^5 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15644 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1$
$15608 := 0^4 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15645 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15609 := 0^5 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$15646 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15610 := 0^4 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15647 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15611 := 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1$	$15648 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^2$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
15649 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15686 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 \\
15650 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15687 := 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & = 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 \\
15651 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15688 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & = -1^4 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15652 := 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15689 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15653 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 & 15690 := 1^4 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^4 + 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15654 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & 15691 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15655 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15692 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15656 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = -2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15693 := 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15657 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15694 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15658 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15695 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15659 := -0^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15696 := -1^4 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -1^4 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15660 := 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & = 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & 15697 := 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15661 := 0^0 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 & 15698 := 1^4 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^4 + 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15662 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15699 := -1^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
15663 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 2^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15700 := -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 & = -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
15664 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15701 := 1^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & = 1^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
15665 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15702 := 1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 & = 1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1 \\
15666 := 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15703 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^2 & = 1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\
15667 := 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15704 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15668 := 0^5 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^4 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15705 := 0^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 & = -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15669 := 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & 15706 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 & = 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
15670 := 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 9^1 & 15707 := 0^7 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15671 := -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15708 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15672 := 0^4 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = -1^5 + 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15709 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15673 := 0^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15710 := 2^5 + 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 2^5 + 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15674 := 0^4 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^5 + 2^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15711 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15675 := 0^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 & = -2^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^2 & 15712 := -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -2^5 - 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
15676 := 0^5 + 2^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15713 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15677 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15714 := -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 & = -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
15678 := -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & 15715 := 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 \\
15679 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 & 15716 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^0 & = 1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2 \\
15680 := 1^4 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & = 1^4 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15717 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = -1^4 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15681 := 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & 15718 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = -1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
15682 := 1^5 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^5 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15719 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15683 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^1 & 15720 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15684 := -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 & = -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1 & 15721 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15685 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & 15722 := 0^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^2 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
15723 := -1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 15760 := 0^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
15724 := 0^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15761 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15725 := 1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 15762 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = -1^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^1 \\
15726 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = -1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 15763 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15727 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 15764 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^1 \\
15728 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = 1^8 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^2 & 15765 := -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15729 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 6^2 - 9^3 & 15766 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15730 := 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^3 & 15767 := 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15731 := 0^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = -1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & 15768 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = -2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2 \\
15732 := 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^7 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 15769 := 0^5 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15733 := 0^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 15770 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15734 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 15771 := 0^5 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15735 := 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 15772 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15736 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 15773 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
15737 := 0^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 & = -2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & 15774 := -2^5 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 & = -2^5 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15738 := -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 15775 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
15739 := 0^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 & = 3^7 - 4^6 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 15776 := -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 & = -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
15740 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & 15777 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 \\
15741 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & 15778 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15742 := 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & 15779 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
15743 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2 & 15780 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15744 := 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^3 & 15781 := -1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
15745 := 1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & 15782 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15746 := -1^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = -1^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^1 & 15783 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15747 := -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15784 := 2^4 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = 2^4 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15748 := 1^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = 1^4 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^1 & 15785 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 \\
15749 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15786 := -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 & = -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
15750 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -2^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^3 & 15787 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
15751 := -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15788 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15752 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -2^4 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^2 & 15789 := 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 & = 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 \\
15753 := 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15790 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = 2^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^2 \\
15754 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15791 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = 1^4 - 2^5 - 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
15755 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15792 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15756 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15793 := -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 \\
15757 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15794 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 \\
15758 := 0^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1 & 15795 := -1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
15759 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0 & = -2^7 - 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 15796 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1
\end{array}$$

$15797 := 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 - 7^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$15834 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$
$15798 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$15835 := 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15799 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15836 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1$
$15800 := -2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15837 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15801 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15838 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 8^1$
$15802 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$	$15839 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15803 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2$	$= -2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2$	$15840 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15804 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$	$15841 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15805 := 0^4 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15842 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15806 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2$	$= -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2$	$15843 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15807 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15844 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15808 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15845 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15809 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2$	$15846 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15810 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^2$	$15847 := 4^8 - 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^5$	$= 4^8 - 5^6 - 6^4 - 8^5$
$15811 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15848 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$
$15812 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15849 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15813 := -2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15850 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^8 + 4^1 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 8^5$
$15814 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15851 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15815 := 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$15852 := -1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^1$
$15816 := 0^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 8^2$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15853 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15817 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15854 := -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15818 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15855 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15819 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15856 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15820 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^1 - 9^3$	$15857 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15821 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 - 9^3$	$15858 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
$15822 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 8^2$	$15859 := -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
$15823 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15860 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
$15824 := -2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$15861 := -1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15825 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15862 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
$15826 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15863 := 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$15827 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^5 - 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15864 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^5 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$15828 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15865 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15829 := 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15866 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5$
$15830 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15867 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15831 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$15868 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5$
$15832 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15869 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$15833 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^3$	$15870 := -3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$

15871 := $0^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15908 := $3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$	$= 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$
15872 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	15909 := $0^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3$
15873 := $-1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15910 := $1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 8^1$
15874 := $-1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	15911 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
15875 := $1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15912 := $2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
15876 := $1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	15913 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
15877 := $2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	15914 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
15878 := $0^5 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	15915 := $1^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15879 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15916 := $0^5 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
15880 := $0^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	15917 := $-1^5 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
15881 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	15918 := $0^5 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15882 := $0^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	15919 := $1^5 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
15883 := $0^1 + 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	15920 := $0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15884 := $-0^0 - 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15921 := $0^5 + 3^4 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15885 := $-2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	15922 := $0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^0$	$= 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
15886 := $-1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15923 := $0^5 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$
15887 := $-0^0 + 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3$	15924 := $3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$
15888 := $1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15925 := $0^0 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
15889 := $0^0 + 1^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^8 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^3$	15926 := $1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^1$
15890 := $-1^5 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15927 := $1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$
15891 := $1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1$	15928 := $2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$
15892 := $-0^0 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	15929 := $-1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^1$
15893 := $-2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15930 := $-2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2$	$= -2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^2$
15894 := $0^0 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15931 := $0^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^1$
15895 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	15932 := $-2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3$	$= -2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3$
15896 := $-0^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15933 := $0^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15897 := $-4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15934 := $0^1 + 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$
15898 := $0^0 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15935 := $0^4 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15899 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15936 := $2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2$
15900 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15937 := $-1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15901 := $2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15938 := $-1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$
15902 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4$	15939 := $1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15903 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	15940 := $1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$
15904 := $-1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	$= -1^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1$	15941 := $0^0 + 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$
15905 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	15942 := $0^4 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$	$= 1^9 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^2$
15906 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1$	15943 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^1$
15907 := $0^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	15944 := $0^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^2$

$15945 := -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^2$	$15974 := 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4$
$15946 := 0^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^2$	$= -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5$	$15975 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15947 := 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^2$	$15976 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15948 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15977 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15949 := 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15978 := 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$	$= 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$
$15950 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$15979 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3$
$15951 := -1^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$15980 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 8^2$	$= 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^4 + 8^2$
$15952 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 9^2$	$= 1^5 + 2^8 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^2$	$15981 := -2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$15953 := -1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3$	$= -1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3$	$15982 := 0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$15954 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 - 7^3$	$15983 := 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^2$
$15955 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15984 := 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15956 := -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15985 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$15957 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15986 := 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$15958 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^7 - 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$15987 := 0^4 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$
$15959 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15988 := 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$	$= 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$
$15960 := -3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15989 := 0^2 - 2^7 - 3^0 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$
$15961 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15990 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$
$15962 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^8 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$15991 := -1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$
$15963 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15992 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$15964 := 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15993 := 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$
$15965 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$15994 := -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$
$15966 := 1^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$	$15995 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$
$15967 := 0^8 + 4^6 - 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= 1^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3$	$15996 := 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^1$
$15968 := -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$15997 := 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3$
$15969 := 0^8 + 4^6 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= 1^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^1$	$15998 := 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$	$= 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^3$
$15970 := 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$15999 := 0^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^3$	$= -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$15971 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$16000 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$
$15972 := -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4$	$= -1^8 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 8^4$		
$15973 := 0^5 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3$		
$16001 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^0$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$16009 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$
$16002 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$16010 := 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$
$16003 := 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$16011 := -2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$16004 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$16012 := 0^0 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$
$16005 := 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$16013 := 0^4 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^5$
$16006 := 2^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$16014 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$
$16007 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3$	$16015 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3$
$16008 := -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^1$	$16016 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
16017 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16054 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
16018 := -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = -2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & 16055 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 \\
16019 := 0^4 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^0 - 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 16056 := 0^2 + 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16020 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 & 16057 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16021 := -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16058 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16022 := -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 & = -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 & 16059 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 \\
16023 := 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16060 := 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 & = 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
16024 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 & 16061 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 \\
16025 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^6 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3 & 16062 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3 \\
16026 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 & 16063 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 8^2 & = 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
16027 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16064 := 2^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 + 8^5 & = 2^8 - 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 + 8^5 \\
16028 := 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^5 & 16065 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 \\
16029 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16066 := 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 \\
16030 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & 16067 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 \\
16031 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16068 := -2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -2^4 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
16032 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & 16069 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16033 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16070 := -2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16034 := -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16071 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16035 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16072 := 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16036 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^3 - 9^1 & 16073 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16037 := -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16074 := -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 9^1 \\
16038 := -2^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & 16075 := -1^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = -1^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
16039 := 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16076 := -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
16040 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 & 16077 := 1^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 & = 1^8 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^1 \\
16041 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16078 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^0 & = 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
16042 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^2 & 16079 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16043 := -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16080 := -2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16044 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^4 + 9^3 & 16081 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16045 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16082 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^2 \\
16046 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^5 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 - 7^3 & 16083 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16047 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16084 := 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16048 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16085 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16049 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16086 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
16050 := 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 2^4 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & 16087 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16051 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16088 := 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16052 := -2^4 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -2^4 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 & 16089 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16053 := 0^2 - 2^7 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 & 16090 := -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1
\end{array}$$

16091 := $-1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1$	16128 := $1^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3$
16092 := $1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1$	$= 1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1$	16129 := $-1^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
16093 := $1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^1$	16130 := $-1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$
16094 := $1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 9^1$	16131 := $1^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^1$
16095 := $1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	16132 := $1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$
16096 := $0^5 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^2$	16133 := $0^2 - 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$
16097 := $-2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	16134 := $0^2 - 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 8^1$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 9^1$
16098 := $0^5 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16135 := $2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^3$
16099 := $-1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	16136 := $-2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^2$	$= -2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^2$
16100 := $0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16137 := $0^2 + 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$
16101 := $0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	16138 := $2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$
16102 := $0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^0$	$= 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^2$	16139 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$
16103 := $0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3$	16140 := $0^5 - 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^1$
16104 := $-1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16141 := $-2^7 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5$
16105 := $-0^0 + 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^3$	16142 := $0^5 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
16106 := $1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16143 := $2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
16107 := $3^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 9^3$	$= 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^5 + 9^3$	16144 := $0^2 - 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$
16108 := $-0^0 - 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16145 := $0^2 + 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3$
16109 := $-1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1$	16146 := $0^2 - 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^1$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16110 := $0^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16147 := $-2^9 - 4^2 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 9^5$	$= -2^9 - 4^2 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 9^5$
16111 := $1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^1$	16148 := $0^2 + 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^1$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16112 := $0^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^3$	$= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 9^1$	16149 := $2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^2 - 9^3$
16113 := $-1^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^1$	16150 := $-1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16114 := $-1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	16151 := $-0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
16115 := $-1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3$	16152 := $1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16116 := $1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	16153 := $-0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3$
16117 := $-0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16154 := $3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3$	$= 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3$
16118 := $-2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16155 := $0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 - 9^3$
16119 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16156 := $0^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$
16120 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	16157 := $0^1 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^2$
16121 := $-0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16158 := $-1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16122 := $3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16159 := $-0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$
16123 := $0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16160 := $3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$
16124 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	16161 := $0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$
16125 := $-0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16162 := $-0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16126 := $2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16163 := $-1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$
16127 := $0^0 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^3$	16164 := $2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^4 + 7^3$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
16165 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16166 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16167 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16168 := -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
16169 := 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16170 := 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 \\
16171 := 0^0 + 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^1 & = -1^4 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
16172 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 9^0 & = 1^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^1 \\
16173 := -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16174 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^0 & = 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16175 := 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16176 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^2 \\
16177 := -1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16178 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 \\
16179 := 1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16180 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16181 := 0^7 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16182 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 9^4 \\
16183 := 0^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 9^4 \\
16184 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
16185 := -1^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16186 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
16187 := 1^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16188 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16189 := -1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16190 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16191 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16192 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16193 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 8^2 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
16194 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16195 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16196 := -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
16197 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16198 := -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
16199 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16200 := 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
16201 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16202 := 0^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 \\
16203 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
16204 := 0^7 - 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16205 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
16206 := 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16207 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
16208 := 0^7 + 3^3 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16209 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
16210 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16211 := -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
16212 := 0^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16213 := 0^7 - 2^9 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
16214 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^3 - 9^0 & = 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16215 := 0^7 - 2^9 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = -2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^2 \\
16216 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^3 + 9^0 & = -1^7 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
16217 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 9^2 & = 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 \\
16218 := -1^7 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = -1^7 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16219 := 0^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 9^2 & = 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
16220 := 1^7 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = 1^7 - 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16221 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^3 - 9^2 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
16222 := 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 & = 2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
16223 := -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
16224 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16225 := 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
16226 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 2^9 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 9^2 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16227 := 0^5 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^2 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
16228 := 0^5 + 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16229 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 - 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
16230 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^4 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^2 \\
16231 := 0^9 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^2 & = 1^4 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
16232 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 \\
16233 := 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 & = 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^2 \\
16234 := -2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2 & = -2^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
16235 := 0^5 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^0 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
16236 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16237 := 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16238 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
16239 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^4 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 5^5 - 9^4 \\
16240 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16241 := -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
16242 := -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16243 := 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
16244 := 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16245 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16246 := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16247 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16248 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^5 - 9^4 & = -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16249 := 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^6 + 5^2 + 6^5 + 8^4 \\
16250 := 0^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16251 := -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16252 := 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 9^4 & = 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^5 - 9^4 \\
16253 := 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16254 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16255 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16256 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
16257 := 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16258 := -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 & = -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
16259 := 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^2 & = 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^2 \\
16260 := -1^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 & = -1^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
16261 := -0^0 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16262 := 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16263 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16264 := -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
16265 := 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^0 & = 1^4 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
16266 := 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
16267 := 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 & = 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16268 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
16269 := 0^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^0 & = -1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
16270 := 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
16271 := 0^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^0 & = 1^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
16272 := 0^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^2 & = -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
16273 := 0^1 + 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^2 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
16274 := 1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 & = 1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 \\
16275 := 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 & = 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^3 \\
16276 := -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 \\
16277 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
16278 := 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 \\
16279 := -1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^2 \\
16280 := 1^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 & = 1^7 - 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
16281 := 1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^2 & = 1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 9^2 \\
16282 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^0 & = 1^4 - 2^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^2 \\
16283 := 0^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
16284 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3 \\
16285 := 0^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^2 \\
16286 := 0^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 - 9^2 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16287 := -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16288 := 0^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 - 9^2 & = -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^3 \\
16289 := 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16290 := -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
16291 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16292 := -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = -2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16293 := 0^0 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16294 := 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
16295 := -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16296 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16297 := 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16298 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16299 := -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16300 := 0^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = 1^7 - 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
16301 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16302 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16303 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16304 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16305 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16306 := 0^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 \\
16307 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16308 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 \\
16309 := -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16310 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16311 := 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16312 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^6 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2
\end{array}$$

$16313 := -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$16350 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$
$16314 := 1^6 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2$	$= 1^6 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2$	$16351 := 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$
$16315 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 - 6^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$16352 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$
$16316 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2$	$16353 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$
$16317 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$16354 := 0^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$16318 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16355 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$
$16319 := -2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16356 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$= -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2$
$16320 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16357 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 - 7^2$
$16321 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16358 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2$
$16322 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$16359 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$
$16323 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16360 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16324 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16361 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$
$16325 := 0^0 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16362 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16326 := 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$16363 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16327 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$16364 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= 1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1$
$16328 := -3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^3$	$= -3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^3$	$16365 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16329 := 0^0 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16366 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2$
$16330 := 1^8 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2$	$= 1^8 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 - 8^2$	$16367 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16331 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16368 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^2 + 9^3$
$16332 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16369 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16333 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$16370 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1$
$16334 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16371 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16335 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$16372 := -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16336 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16373 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16337 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^2 - 7^1$	$16374 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16338 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16375 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^4 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16339 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16376 := -1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16340 := 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$16377 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$
$16341 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^4 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16378 := 1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= 1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16342 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= -1^8 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2$	$16379 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16343 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$	$16380 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16344 := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$	$= -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2$	$16381 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16345 := 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$= 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^4 + 7^3$	$16382 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^1$
$16346 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$16383 := 0^4 + 4^7 - 7^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16347 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^2$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1$	$16384 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
$16348 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^1$	$16385 := 0^4 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1$
$16349 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$= -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1$	$16386 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
16387 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 & 16424 := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16388 := 1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16425 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 \\
16389 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16426 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
16390 := -1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16427 := 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16391 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16428 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
16392 := 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16429 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16393 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16430 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16394 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16431 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^5 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
16395 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^1 & 16432 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16396 := 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16433 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16397 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16434 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16398 := -2^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -2^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 16435 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
16399 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16436 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16400 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16437 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16401 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16438 := -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
16402 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 & 16439 := 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16403 := -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 & 16440 := 0^4 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
16404 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^2 & 16441 := -1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^2 \\
16405 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^1 & 16442 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
16406 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16443 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16407 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16444 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16408 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16445 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16409 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16446 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
16410 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = -1^6 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 & 16447 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16411 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^5 - 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^2 & 16448 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16412 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = 1^6 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 & 16449 := 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16413 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^0 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16450 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16414 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^1 & 16451 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16415 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16452 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16416 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & 16453 := 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
16417 := -2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & 16454 := -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 & = -1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
16418 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 & 16455 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16419 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16456 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^6 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
16420 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 & 16457 := -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16421 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^1 & 16458 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^8 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1 \\
16422 := 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 & = 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 & 16459 := 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 \\
16423 := -3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3 & = -3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3 & 16460 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{l}
\mathbf{16461} := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16462} := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16463} := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16464} := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16465} := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16466} := 0^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16467} := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16468} := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16469} := -2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16470} := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16471} := -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16472} := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16473} := 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16474} := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16475} := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16476} := 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16477} := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16478} := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16479} := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16480} := 0^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16481} := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16482} := 0^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16483} := 0^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16484} := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16485} := 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16486} := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16487} := -1^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16488} := 0^7 - 2^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{16489} := 1^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
\mathbf{16490} := -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16491} := -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
\mathbf{16492} := 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16493} := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 - 9^0 \\
\mathbf{16494} := -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16495} := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 + 9^0 \\
\mathbf{16496} := 0^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16497} := -0^0 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16498} := 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16499} := 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16500} := 0^4 - 1^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16501} := 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16502} := -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16503} := 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16504} := 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16505} := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16506} := -2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16507} := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16508} := -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16509} := 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16510} := 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 \\
\mathbf{16511} := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16512} := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16513} := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16514} := 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
\mathbf{16515} := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16516} := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16517} := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16518} := 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16519} := 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
\mathbf{16520} := 0^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^0 \\
\mathbf{16521} := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16522} := 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16523} := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
\mathbf{16524} := -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
\mathbf{16525} := 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16526} := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16527} := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16528} := -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16529} := 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16530} := 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16531} := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
\mathbf{16532} := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
\mathbf{16533} := -1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
\mathbf{16534} := 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 1^4 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^3 \\
= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^1 \\
= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= -2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= -1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
= 1^8 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^2 \\
= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 \\
= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 \\
= 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^2 \\
= -1^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
= -1^4 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3 \\
= 1^9 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
= -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
= -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
= 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
= 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^1 \\
= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 7^1 \\
= -1^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
= 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
= 1^1 + 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^5 \\
= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^2 \\
= 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
= -1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
= -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
= 1^4 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 \\
= 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^1 \\
= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 \\
= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 \\
= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^2 \\
= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
= 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
= 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 \\
= -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
= 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^2 \\
= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
= -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
= 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
= 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
= -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
= -1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
= 2^6 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
16535 &:= 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 &= 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 & 16572 &:= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 \\
16536 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^2 & 16573 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 &= -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16537 &:= 0^4 - 2^7 - 3^0 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= -1^4 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^1 & 16574 &:= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 \\
16538 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= -1^4 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1 & 16575 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 &= 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16539 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 &= -2^7 - 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 16576 &:= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 \\
16540 &:= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 &= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 & 16577 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 &= -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16541 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 &= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 16578 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 &= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
16542 &:= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 & 16579 &:= 0^7 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 &= 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16543 &:= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 &= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 16580 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 &= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16544 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 &= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16581 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 &= -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 \\
16545 &:= -1^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 &= -1^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 16582 &:= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 &= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16546 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 &= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16583 &:= -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 &= -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
16547 &:= 1^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 &= 1^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 16584 &:= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 &= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^2 \\
16548 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 &= -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 & 16585 &:= 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 &= 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
16549 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 &= -1^7 + 2^2 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 16586 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 &= -1^4 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^2 \\
16550 &:= 0^7 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 &= 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 & 16587 &:= 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 &= 2^9 - 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 9^3 \\
16551 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 &= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16588 &:= 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^4 + 9^3 &= 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 8^4 + 9^3 \\
16552 &:= 0^7 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 &= 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16589 &:= 0^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^0 &= -2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^3 \\
16553 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 &= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16590 &:= 0^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 8^0 &= -1^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
16554 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 &= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^1 & 16591 &:= 0^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^0 &= 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^5 + 9^2 \\
16555 &:= -1^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 &= -1^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16592 &:= 0^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^0 &= -1^9 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16556 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^0 &= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16593 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^0 &= -1^3 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
16557 &:= 0^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^0 &= 1^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16594 &:= 1^9 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 &= 1^9 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16558 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^0 &= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16595 &:= -2^8 - 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 &= -2^8 - 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
16559 &:= 0^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^0 &= -1^7 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16596 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 &= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
16560 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^0 &= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 & 16597 &:= -2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 &= -2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
16561 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 9^0 &= 1^7 + 2^2 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16598 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 &= 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
16562 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16599 &:= 0^9 - 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 &= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 \\
16563 &:= -2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= -2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16600 &:= 0^7 - 3^4 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 \\
16564 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 16601 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 8^1 &= -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
16565 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 16602 &:= 0^7 - 3^4 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= -1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16566 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= -1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 & 16603 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 &= 1^3 - 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 \\
16567 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 16604 &:= 1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 &= 1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
16568 &:= 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 & 16605 &:= 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 &= 3^6 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
16569 &:= 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 16606 &:= 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 &= 1^7 - 3^4 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
16570 &:= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 & 16607 &:= -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 &= -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
16571 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^1 &= 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 & 16608 &:= -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 &= -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3
\end{aligned}$$

$16609 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3$	$= -1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$16646 := -3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16610 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$16647 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16611 := 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^7 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$16648 := 0^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16612 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$16649 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16613 := -0^0 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16650 := 0^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16614 := -3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16651 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16615 := 0^0 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16652 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16616 := 0^7 - 2^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$16653 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16617 := 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$16654 := -2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16618 := 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16655 := 0^0 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16619 := -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$16656 := 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$16620 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$16657 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16621 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$16658 := 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16622 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^3$	$16659 := 1^4 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 - 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16623 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$16660 := 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1$
$16624 := -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$16661 := 0^7 - 3^4 - 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$
$16625 := -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3$	$= -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3$	$16662 := 0^4 - 2^7 - 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1$
$16626 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16663 := 0^7 - 3^4 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^8 - 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1$
$16627 := -2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16664 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16628 := 0^0 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16665 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 - 9^3$
$16629 := 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2$	$16666 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16630 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$16667 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16631 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$16668 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$16632 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$16669 := -2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$16633 := -2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^3$	$= -2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^3$	$16670 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$16634 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^4 - 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16671 := 0^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$
$16635 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$16672 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$16636 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$16673 := -1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16637 := -1^6 - 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 - 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$16674 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16638 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$16675 := 1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16639 := 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$16676 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16640 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^2$	$16677 := -2^7 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16641 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16678 := 0^2 - 2^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$16642 := -1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= -1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$16679 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 - 7^1 + 8^4$
$16643 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16680 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$16644 := 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$= 1^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1$	$16681 := 0^7 - 3^0 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16645 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16682 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$

$16683 := 0^7 + 3^0 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16720 := -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16684 := -1^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$16721 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16685 := 1^2 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16722 := -0^0 - 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$16686 := 1^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$16723 := -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16687 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^1$	$16724 := -0^0 + 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$16688 := 0^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^0$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$16725 := 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16689 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16726 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$
$16690 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$16727 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16691 := 1^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16728 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$
$16692 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16729 := -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16693 := 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 8^4$	$= 1^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^1 + 8^4$	$16730 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16694 := 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16731 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16695 := -1^8 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1$	$16732 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16696 := 0^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$	$16733 := -0^0 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16697 := -1^6 - 2^7 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 - 2^7 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 7^5$	$16734 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16698 := 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^1$	$16735 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16699 := -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16736 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16700 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16737 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16701 := 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$16738 := -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16702 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16739 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16703 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16740 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$
$16704 := -2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16741 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16705 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16742 := -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16706 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16743 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16707 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16744 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1$
$16708 := 0^7 - 2^6 + 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16745 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16709 := 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16746 := 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 7^1$
$16710 := 0^2 - 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16747 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16711 := 1^6 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$16748 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^7 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16712 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16749 := 1^8 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$	$= 1^8 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2$
$16713 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16750 := 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$
$16714 := 0^6 - 2^7 - 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^9 - 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1$	$16751 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16715 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16752 := 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16716 := 0^6 - 2^7 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3$	$16753 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16717 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16754 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$16718 := -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$	$= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 - 7^3$	$16755 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 6^2 + 7^5$
$16719 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^3$	$16756 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$

$16757 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^3 - 9^2$	$16794 := -0^0 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16758 := 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16795 := -2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16759 := 0^9 - 2^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$16796 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16760 := 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1$	$16797 := -1^7 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16761 := 0^9 - 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16798 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 9^1$
$16762 := 0^7 + 3^4 - 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^1$	$16799 := 1^7 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16763 := 1^7 - 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16800 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16764 := 0^7 + 3^4 + 4^0 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$16801 := -1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16765 := 0^7 - 2^4 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^3$	$16802 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16766 := 1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$= 1^9 - 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2$	$16803 := 1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16767 := 0^7 - 2^4 + 4^0 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2$	$16804 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16768 := 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^1 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$16805 := 0^1 - 1^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16769 := 0^7 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^4 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16806 := 0^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16770 := -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16807 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16771 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 - 7^3$	$= 1^7 - 2^4 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16808 := 0^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16772 := 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16809 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16773 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$16810 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16774 := -1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16811 := -1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16775 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$16812 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3$
$16776 := 1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16813 := 1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16777 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 - 7^3$	$16814 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16778 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16815 := -1^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16779 := 0^7 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16816 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^1$
$16780 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16817 := 1^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16781 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16818 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$16782 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16819 := 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$16783 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16820 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16784 := -1^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16821 := 1^7 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16785 := 1^7 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16822 := 1^7 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16786 := 1^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16823 := 0^7 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 9^2$
$16787 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$16824 := -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16788 := -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16825 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3$
$16789 := 0^7 + 2^3 - 3^0 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$16826 := -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16790 := 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16827 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16791 := 0^7 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 9^2$	$16828 := -1^7 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16792 := -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16829 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16793 := -1^7 + 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^4 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16830 := 1^7 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
16831 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16868 := 0^2 + 1^7 + 2^6 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16832 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 & 16869 := 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16833 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16870 := 0^8 + 2^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -1^7 + 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16834 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16871 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16835 := 0^7 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16872 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16836 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16873 := -2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16837 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^1 & 16874 := 0^0 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16838 := -1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16875 := -1^8 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -1^8 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
16839 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^1 & 16876 := 0^2 - 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16840 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16877 := 1^8 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
16841 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 & 16878 := -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16842 := -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16879 := 0^2 + 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^0 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16843 := -1^7 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16880 := -1^2 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
16844 := 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16881 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16845 := 0^7 + 2^6 - 5^2 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 16882 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16846 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 - 9^0 & = -1^7 - 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 16883 := 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16847 := 0^7 + 2^4 - 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 16884 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16848 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^0 & = -1^9 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & 16885 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16849 := 0^7 + 2^4 + 4^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^1 & 16886 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16850 := -0^0 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & 16887 := -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^2 & = -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^2 \\
16851 := -2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & 16888 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
16852 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & 16889 := -1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
16853 := 0^9 + 2^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = 1^7 + 2^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16890 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 \\
16854 := -1^7 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 & 16891 := 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
16855 := 0^9 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^1 & 16892 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16856 := 0^5 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16893 := 0^5 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
16857 := 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^1 & = 1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^1 & 16894 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16858 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16895 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
16859 := -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^5 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 16896 := 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^0 & = -2^3 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^2 \\
16860 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16897 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16861 := -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & 16898 := 0^6 + 2^7 - 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^5 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16862 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 16899 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16863 := 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & 16900 := 0^6 + 2^7 + 5^0 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^9 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
16864 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 - 7^2 & 16901 := -1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
16865 := -1^8 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -1^8 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 & 16902 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 7^3 + 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16866 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & 16903 := 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
16867 := 1^8 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^2 & 16904 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^1 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$16905 := -2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16942 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16906 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16943 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^5 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16907 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16944 := 0^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$16908 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16945 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16909 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16946 := 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$16910 := 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16947 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 7^5$
$16911 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16948 := -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16912 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16949 := 0^5 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3$
$16913 := -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16950 := 0^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16914 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16951 := 0^7 + 3^4 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^8 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1$
$16915 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16952 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1$
$16916 := -1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16953 := 0^7 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^1$
$16917 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$16954 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16918 := 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16955 := -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16919 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^8 + 2^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1$	$16956 := -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16920 := 0^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16957 := 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16921 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16958 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16922 := 0^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16959 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16923 := -2^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5$	$= -2^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5$	$16960 := 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16924 := -1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= -1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16961 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16925 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16962 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16926 := 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$16963 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16927 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2$	$16964 := 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16928 := -1^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16965 := 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
$16929 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16966 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16930 := 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16967 := 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5$
$16931 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$16968 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$16932 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16969 := 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16933 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 2^7 - 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$16970 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16934 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16971 := 0^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1$
$16935 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 9^1$	$16972 := 0^6 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^2$
$16936 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16973 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4$
$16937 := 2^7 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^7 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$16974 := -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$
$16938 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16975 := -1^6 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5$
$16939 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16976 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0$	$= 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$
$16940 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$16977 := 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5$
$16941 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$16978 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
16979 := -2^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 & = -2^4 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^3 \\
16980 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^3 \\
16981 := 0^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16982 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16983 := 0^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
16984 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^4 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
16985 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
16986 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16987 := 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16988 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
16989 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16990 := 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
\\
17001 := -1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17002 := 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 & = 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
17003 := 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17004 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17005 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17006 := 0^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
17007 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17008 := 0^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 & = -1^7 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17009 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = 1^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
17010 := 0^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^9 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17011 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17012 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 & = 1^9 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17013 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17014 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17015 := -1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17016 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^7 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17017 := 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17018 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^7 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17019 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17020 := -1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = -1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17021 := 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17022 := 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17023 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 2^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
17024 := -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17025 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
\\
16991 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
16992 := 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 & = 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
16993 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 \\
16994 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
16995 := 1^8 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
16996 := 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
16997 := -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
16998 := 0^8 + 2^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^3 - 9^4 \\
16999 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17000 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^2 \\
\\
17026 := -2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = -2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17027 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17028 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17029 := -1^7 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
17030 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17031 := 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17032 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17033 := 0^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17034 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17035 := 0^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17036 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17037 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17038 := -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17039 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17040 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 & = -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17041 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17042 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17043 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
17044 := 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17045 := -1^7 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^8 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
17046 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17047 := -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17048 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17049 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17050 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
17051 := 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17052 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17053 := -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17054 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17055 := -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17056 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17057 := -1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17058 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17059 := 1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17060 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^1 \\
17061 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17062 := 0^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17063 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17064 := 0^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17065 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17066 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17067 := -1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17068 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17069 := 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17070 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17071 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^0 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17072 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17073 := 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17074 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17075 := 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17076 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17077 := -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17078 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^1 \\
17079 := -1^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
17080 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17081 := -3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17082 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17083 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17084 := -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17085 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17086 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17087 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17088 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17089 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17090 := 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17091 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17092 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17093 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17094 := -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17095 := -1^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = -1^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
17096 := 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17097 := 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
17098 := -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
17099 := -0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17100 := 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17101 := 0^0 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17102 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17103 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17104 := -2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17105 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17106 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17107 := -0^0 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = -1^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17108 := 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17109 := 0^0 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17110 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17111 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17112 := 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17113 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17114 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17115 := 0^8 - 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^1 - 7^4 \\
17116 := -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
17117 := 0^8 - 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^1 \\
17118 := 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
17119 := 0^3 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^0 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
17120 := 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & = 2^8 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 \\
17121 := -1^7 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -1^7 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
17122 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^7 - 3^1 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17123 := 1^7 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
17124 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^8 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
17125 := 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17126 := 0^7 + 2^8 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17127 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
17128 := 0^7 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
17129 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 8^2 \\
17130 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17131 := -1^7 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -1^7 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
17132 := -1^8 - 2^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 2^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17133 := 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = 1^7 + 2^8 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
17134 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 1^8 - 2^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17135 := 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 & = 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 \\
17136 := -1^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17137 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
17138 := 1^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17139 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17140 := 0^8 - 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17141 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = -3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17142 := 0^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17143 := 0^1 - 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^9 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17144 := 0^8 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17145 := 0^1 + 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = 2^9 + 3^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
17146 := 0^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^8 - 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17147 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17148 := -1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17149 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17150 := 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17151 := 0^0 + 1^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17152 := -1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17153 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17154 := 1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17155 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17156 := 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 2^3 + 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17157 := 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17158 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^4 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17159 := -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17160 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17161 := 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17162 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17163 := 0^3 + 3^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -1^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17164 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17165 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17166 := 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17167 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17168 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17169 := 0^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17170 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17171 := 0^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
17172 := -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = -2^3 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17173 := 0^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^4 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17174 := -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 & = -2^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
17175 := -1^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17176 := -1^8 - 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17177 := 1^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17178 := 0^8 - 2^0 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^8 - 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17179 := -2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = -2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17180 := 0^8 + 2^0 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^8 + 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17181 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 2^0 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17182 := 1^8 + 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^8 + 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17183 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17184 := -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17185 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17186 := 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17187 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17188 := 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17189 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17190 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17191 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^2 - 9^4 \\
17192 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17193 := 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^0 + 9^3 & = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17194 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17195 := 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^0 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17196 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17197 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
17198 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17199 &:= -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 = 1^4 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 8^3 & 17236 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 = -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17200 &:= -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 = -1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 & 17237 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^3 \\
17201 &:= -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 & 17238 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17202 &:= 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 = 1^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 & 17239 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^2 \\
17203 &:= 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 9^5 = 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^7 - 7^4 - 9^5 & 17240 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^2 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17204 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 17241 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
17205 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^3 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 17242 &:= -1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = -1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
17206 &:= 0^4 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^0 + 8^3 = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 17243 &:= 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
17207 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 17244 &:= 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 \\
17208 &:= -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 = -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 17245 &:= 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^2 = 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 - 9^2 \\
17209 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 17246 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 = 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^1 \\
17210 &:= 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 = 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 17247 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 = -2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17211 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 = -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 17248 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17212 &:= -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17249 &:= -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17213 &:= 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 = 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^1 - 9^4 & 17250 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17214 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 = 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17251 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
17215 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17252 &:= 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17216 &:= 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 = 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17253 &:= 0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
17217 &:= 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17254 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17218 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17255 &:= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 9^3 = -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17219 &:= 0^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 17256 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17220 &:= 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^0 - 9^4 = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & 17257 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
17221 &:= 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 6^0 - 9^4 = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 17258 &:= -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 = -1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17222 &:= -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & 17259 &:= -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 = -2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
17223 &:= -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 = -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 17260 &:= 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 = 1^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17224 &:= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17261 &:= -2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17225 &:= 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 = 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^1 - 9^4 & 17262 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 = 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^2 - 9^4 \\
17226 &:= -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 + 9^1 = -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 + 9^1 & 17263 &:= -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17227 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17264 &:= -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 = -2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17228 &:= 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 = 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17265 &:= 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^2 = 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
17229 &:= 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17266 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^2 = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17230 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -1^1 - 2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17267 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 = -1^4 + 4^8 - 5^7 + 6^6 - 7^5 + 8^1 \\
17231 &:= -2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^7 - 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17268 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 - 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^0 = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 \\
17232 &:= -1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = -1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & 17269 &:= -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^5 = -3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17233 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17270 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17234 &:= 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 & 17271 &:= 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 = 3^5 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 7^3 + 8^4 \\
17235 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^2 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^3 & 17272 &:= 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^5 + 9^3 = -1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17273 &:= 0^3 - 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^4 - 9^1 = 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^1 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17274 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^2 - 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17275 &:= 0^3 + 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^4 - 9^1 = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17276 &:= 0^3 - 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 - 9^0 = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17277 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17278 &:= -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 = -1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^1 + 9^3 \\
17279 &:= -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^3 = -1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17280 &:= -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^3 = -1^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 6^1 + 9^3 \\
17281 &:= 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^3 = 1^7 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17282 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17283 &:= -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = -2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17284 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17285 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17286 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = -1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17287 &:= 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17288 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17289 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17290 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17291 &:= 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17292 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17293 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^0 = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
17294 &:= -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 = -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
17295 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^0 = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
17296 &:= 1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 = 1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 \\
17297 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^1 + 9^3 = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
17298 &:= 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
17299 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^2 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17300 &:= 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 = 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 - 8^2 \\
17301 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^2 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17302 &:= -1^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 = -1^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
17303 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^1 \\
17304 &:= -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3 = 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
17305 &:= 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3 = 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
17306 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3 = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
17307 &:= -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17308 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17309 &:= 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17310 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^2 \\
17311 &:= -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 = -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17312 &:= 0^2 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^1 = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17313 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 2^9 + 3^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
17314 &:= -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17315 &:= -2^7 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^7 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17316 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17317 &:= -3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 = -3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17318 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17319 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17320 &:= -2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17321 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17322 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17323 &:= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^1 = 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
17324 &:= -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17325 &:= 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 = 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
17326 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17327 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^0 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
17328 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 - 7^0 = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17329 &:= -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 = -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17330 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^0 = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17331 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^0 = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
17332 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 - 9^2 \\
17333 &:= -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17334 &:= -1^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 = -1^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
17335 &:= -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^1 = -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
17336 &:= 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
17337 &:= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^1 = 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^1 \\
17338 &:= 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
17339 &:= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17340 &:= -2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 = -2^2 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17341 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17342 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^0 = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17343 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^0 = -1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17344 &:= -4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 = -4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17345 &:= 0^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^0 = 1^1 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17346 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^0 = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
17347 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^4 + 9^0 & = -1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^4 \\
17348 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17349 := 1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^4 & = 1^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^1 + 8^4 \\
17350 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17351 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = -1^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
17352 := -3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = -3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
17353 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 1^1 - 3^8 + 5^6 + 6^5 + 8^3 \\
17354 := 0^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
17355 := -1^8 - 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^8 - 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17356 := 0^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17357 := 1^8 - 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = 1^8 - 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17358 := 0^8 - 3^0 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17359 := -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17360 := 0^8 + 3^0 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17361 := -1^8 + 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = -1^8 + 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17362 := -0^0 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17363 := 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17364 := 0^0 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17365 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17366 := 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17367 := 0^7 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17368 := 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^4 & = 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 9^4 \\
17369 := 0^7 + 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17370 := -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17371 := 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 3^3 - 4^7 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17372 := 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17373 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^8 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 + 8^2 \\
17374 := -0^0 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17375 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17376 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17377 := -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17378 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17379 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
17380 := 0^9 - 4^6 + 5^7 - 6^0 + 7^4 - 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17381 := 0^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^0 + 8^4 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
17382 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17383 := 0^2 + 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17384 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 - 9^1 \\
17385 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^2 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17386 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17387 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 6^2 + 9^3 \\
17388 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17389 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17390 := 2^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 2^8 + 3^3 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17391 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17392 := -1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17393 := 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17394 := 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17395 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
17396 := 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = 1^7 + 2^9 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17397 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17398 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 8^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17399 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17400 := 0^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 + 6^0 + 8^5 & = -1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17401 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^3 + 9^2 \\
17402 := 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17403 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17404 := 0^7 - 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17405 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17406 := 0^7 - 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 8^5 \\
17407 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^3 + 9^2 \\
17408 := -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17409 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17410 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17411 := 0^0 + 1^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
17412 := 0^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17413 := -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17414 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17415 := 0^7 - 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17416 := -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17417 := 0^7 + 2^0 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17418 := 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17419 := 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17420 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17421 &:= 0^7 - 1^9 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 9^1 = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^3 & 17458 &:= 0^7 + 3^3 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17422 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17459 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
17423 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17460 &:= 0^7 + 3^3 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17424 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17461 &:= -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 = -1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
17425 &:= 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 - 2^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17462 &:= -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17426 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^1 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17463 &:= 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 = 1^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
17427 &:= -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17464 &:= 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17428 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^2 & 17465 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 - 7^3 \\
17429 &:= 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17466 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17430 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 & 17467 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
17431 &:= 0^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17468 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17432 &:= 0^1 - 1^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & 17469 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
17433 &:= 0^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 - 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17470 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
17434 &:= 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 = 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 & 17471 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^3 = 1^8 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
17435 &:= -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17472 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17436 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^1 + 2^8 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 & 17473 &:= 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 = 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17437 &:= 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17474 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
17438 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^6 + 6^3 - 9^4 & 17475 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17439 &:= -1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17476 &:= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
17440 &:= 3^4 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^5 = 3^4 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^3 - 8^5 & 17477 &:= 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
17441 &:= 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17478 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^3 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17442 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17479 &:= 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^3 = 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^3 \\
17443 &:= 0^7 + 1^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 + 9^1 = -1^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 & 17480 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 - 8^2 + 9^3 = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
17444 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17481 &:= 0^7 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^5 = -1^5 - 2^8 - 5^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17445 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17482 &:= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^4 + 9^1 = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 7^4 + 9^1 \\
17446 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17483 &:= 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17447 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17484 &:= 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17448 &:= 0^8 - 3^0 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 & 17485 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17449 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17486 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17450 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17487 &:= -2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = -2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17451 &:= 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17488 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = 1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17452 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 2^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17489 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17453 &:= 1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 & 17490 &:= 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 7^4 + 9^2 = 1^7 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17454 &:= -1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17491 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17455 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^3 = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 17492 &:= -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = -1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17456 &:= 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & 17493 &:= -3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^4 = -3^9 - 4^7 + 6^6 + 7^3 + 9^4 \\
17457 &:= 0^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^3 = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 17494 &:= 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 = 1^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
17495 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^3 \\
17496 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17497 := 0^7 + 3^0 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17498 := -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17499 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 8^2 \\
17500 := 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17501 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17502 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17503 := 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17504 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17505 := 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17506 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17507 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17508 := 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17509 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
17510 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17511 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^5 + 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 9^2 \\
17512 := 0^5 - 2^8 - 5^2 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^1 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17513 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17514 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17515 := -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 & = -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17516 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17517 := 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17518 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17519 := 0^4 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17520 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^6 + 3^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
17521 := 0^4 - 2^8 - 4^2 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^7 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17522 := 1^6 + 3^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
17523 := 0^6 + 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 1^7 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17524 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17525 := 0^6 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^8 + 3^4 - 4^1 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 \\
17526 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17527 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^7 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17528 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17529 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^7 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
17530 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17531 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17532 := 0^3 + 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^0 - 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17533 := 0^3 + 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17534 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
17535 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
17536 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17537 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^3 \\
17538 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17539 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17540 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17541 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17542 := -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17543 := 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17544 := 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17545 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17546 := 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17547 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 & = 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^5 + 9^3 \\
17548 := -0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17549 := 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17550 := 0^0 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 - 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17551 := 0^7 + 2^8 + 3^0 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17552 := 0^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17553 := -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
17554 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17555 := -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17556 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17557 := 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17558 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17559 := 0^2 + 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17560 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17561 := 0^2 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17562 := 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^4 & = 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 8^4 \\
17563 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17564 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17565 := 0^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17566 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17567 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17568 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
17569 := -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17570 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17571 := -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17572 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17573 := 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^5 \\
17574 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17575 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17576 := 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17577 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17578 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
17579 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 & = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17580 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^2 & = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17581 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17582 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 - 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17583 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17584 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17585 := -2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17586 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17587 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17588 := -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
17589 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
17590 := 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^1 \\
17591 := -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17592 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17593 := 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^3 & = 2^9 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^3 \\
17594 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17595 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17596 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17597 := 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17598 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17599 := 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17600 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^3 \\
17601 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17602 := -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
17603 := 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17604 := 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
17605 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17606 := 2^8 - 3^2 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 & = 2^8 - 3^2 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17607 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^5 + 8^2 + 9^3 \\
17608 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17609 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
17610 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17611 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
17612 := 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
17613 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
17614 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 & = -1^1 + 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17615 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 & = 2^7 - 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17616 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^4 + 9^3 \\
17617 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17618 := 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 & = 2^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17619 := 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17620 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 - 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17621 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^3 - 7^4 \\
17622 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17623 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 8^5 \\
17624 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17625 := -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
17626 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^1 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17627 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17628 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17629 := -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^6 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17630 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17631 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17632 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17633 := 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^2 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
17634 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17635 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17636 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^1 \\
17637 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17638 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17639 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17640 := 0^6 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -1^4 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17641 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17642 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 & = 1^4 + 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17643 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 17680 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
17644 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 & 17681 &:= 0^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^6 - 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17645 &:= -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17682 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17646 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^1 + 7^5 & 17683 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^8 + 2^9 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 - 9^1 \\
17647 &:= 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17684 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17648 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 17685 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17649 &:= -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 = -2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 17686 &:= -1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17650 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 17687 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17651 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17688 &:= 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17652 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 17689 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17653 &:= -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 = -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 & 17690 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17654 &:= 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 17691 &:= 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 = 2^8 + 4^4 - 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^5 \\
17655 &:= 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 & 17692 &:= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17656 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 & 17693 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17657 &:= 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^3 = 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^3 & 17694 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17658 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^2 + 9^3 & 17695 &:= 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17659 &:= 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^3 = -1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17696 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17660 &:= 0^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^0 + 7^5 = 2^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^2 + 8^4 & 17697 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17661 &:= 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17698 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17662 &:= 0^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^0 + 7^5 = 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 17699 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17663 &:= 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 = 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^3 & 17700 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^2 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 - 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17664 &:= -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17701 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17665 &:= -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17702 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^4 + 9^2 \\
17666 &:= 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17703 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17667 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17704 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17668 &:= -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17705 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17669 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17706 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
17670 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17707 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 \\
17671 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17708 &:= 0^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = 1^6 - 2^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17672 &:= -1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17709 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17673 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17710 &:= 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^7 + 2^4 + 3^6 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17674 &:= 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17711 &:= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17675 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17712 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^1 + 9^3 \\
17676 &:= -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17713 &:= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17677 &:= 0^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^2 & 17714 &:= 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 = 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 8^6 \\
17678 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17715 &:= 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17679 &:= 0^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = 1^9 + 2^7 + 3^2 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3 & 17716 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17717 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17754 &:= 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 = -1^1 + 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^3 \\
17718 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & 17755 &:= 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^3 = 2^9 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 7^2 + 9^3 \\
17719 &:= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17756 &:= -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 = -1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17720 &:= 0^6 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^3 & 17757 &:= -1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17721 &:= -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 17758 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17722 &:= 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 17759 &:= 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17723 &:= 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17760 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17724 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^0 - 7^3 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 17761 &:= 0^8 - 2^4 - 4^2 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17725 &:= -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17762 &:= 0^8 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17726 &:= -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17763 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17727 &:= -0^0 + 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17764 &:= 0^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 7^2 \\
17728 &:= 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17765 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 = -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17729 &:= 0^1 - 1^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17766 &:= 0^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 = 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17730 &:= 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17767 &:= 0^1 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 = 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17731 &:= 0^1 + 1^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^8 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 17768 &:= -2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
17732 &:= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17769 &:= 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 = 1^8 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17733 &:= 0^0 + 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17770 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
17734 &:= 0^3 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 17771 &:= -1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17735 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^6 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17772 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 7^1 + 8^3 \\
17736 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17773 &:= 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17737 &:= -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^3 & 17774 &:= -2^2 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 = -2^2 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
17738 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17775 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 = -1^8 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17739 &:= 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17776 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17740 &:= -1^8 - 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 17777 &:= -0^0 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 = -1^1 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
17741 &:= 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 = 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3 & 17778 &:= 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 = 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
17742 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = 1^8 - 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 17779 &:= 0^0 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 = 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
17743 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 = -2^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 17780 &:= -1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17744 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 17781 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17745 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17782 &:= 1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17746 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 17783 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17747 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17784 &:= -1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17748 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^7 + 3^6 - 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 17785 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17749 &:= -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & 17786 &:= 1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17750 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = -1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17787 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17751 &:= 0^7 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 = -3^3 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 & 17788 &:= -1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 = -1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17752 &:= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 = 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17789 &:= 0^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 = -1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17753 &:= 0^7 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 = 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 7^5 & 17790 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
17791 := 0^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^3 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17792 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17793 := 0^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17794 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17795 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17796 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17797 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17798 := -1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17799 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17800 := 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17801 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17802 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17803 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17804 := 1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17805 := 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 & = 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^7 - 7^4 + 8^5 \\
17806 := 0^3 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^0 & = 1^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^1 \\
17807 := 0^3 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^1 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17808 := 0^3 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^0 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
17809 := 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^0 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17810 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
17811 := -1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17812 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -2^9 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
17813 := 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17814 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17815 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^0 & = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17816 := 0^3 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17817 := 0^3 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^1 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17818 := 0^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17819 := 0^3 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^1 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17820 := 0^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17821 := 0^3 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^1 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17822 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17823 := 0^8 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17824 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17825 := -1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17826 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
17827 := 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17828 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 4^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17829 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17830 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^8 + 2^4 + 4^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17831 := 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17832 := 0^8 - 2^3 - 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
17833 := 1^9 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 9^2 & = 1^9 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
17834 := 0^8 - 2^3 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
17835 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17836 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17837 := -0^0 - 1^8 - 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17838 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17839 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17840 := -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17841 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17842 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17843 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 2^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17844 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17845 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 2^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
17846 := 0^7 - 3^5 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17847 := 1^8 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17848 := 0^8 + 2^3 - 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17849 := -1^6 - 2^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^1 + 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^1 + 9^2 \\
17850 := 0^8 + 2^3 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 \\
17851 := 0^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 - 7^0 & = -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17852 := 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^8 + 2^4 - 4^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17853 := 0^5 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17854 := 0^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17855 := 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17856 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17857 := 0^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^0 & = -1^5 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
17858 := 0^8 + 2^4 + 4^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
17859 := 1^5 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^5 - 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
17860 := 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 \\
17861 := 0^5 - 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^9 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
17862 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1 \\
17863 := 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = 3^4 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17864 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 + 7^5 - 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17865 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & 17902 &:= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 \\
17866 &:= -2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 = -2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 17903 &:= -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 - 8^3 = -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 - 8^3 \\
17867 &:= -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17904 &:= 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 \\
17868 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17905 &:= 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 = 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^2 + 6^3 + 7^5 \\
17869 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & 17906 &:= 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^5 - 9^3 = 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^5 - 9^3 \\
17870 &:= -2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = -2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 17907 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = -1^5 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
17871 &:= 0^0 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & 17908 &:= -0^0 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = -1^1 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
17872 &:= 0^8 + 2^5 - 5^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 - 7^1 & 17909 &:= 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
17873 &:= 0^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 - 8^2 = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^1 + 8^4 & 17910 &:= 0^0 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = 1^1 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
17874 &:= 0^8 + 2^5 + 5^0 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 & 17911 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = 1^8 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 \\
17875 &:= -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5 = -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5 & 17912 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
17876 &:= 0^0 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^2 & 17913 &:= 2^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = 2^2 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 \\
17877 &:= 0^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 + 8^4 = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 17914 &:= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17878 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17915 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17879 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 - 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 = 1^8 + 2^5 + 5^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 & 17916 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -1^8 + 3^5 - 5^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
17880 &:= 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17917 &:= -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17881 &:= 0^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^0 + 6^3 + 7^5 = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 17918 &:= -3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17882 &:= -3^3 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 = -3^3 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 8^4 & 17919 &:= 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17883 &:= 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 = 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^4 + 7^3 & 17920 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17884 &:= 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 5^1 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 17921 &:= 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 \\
17885 &:= 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 = 1^3 + 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^1 + 8^4 & 17922 &:= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17886 &:= 0^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 - 8^0 = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17923 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17887 &:= -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 17924 &:= -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17888 &:= -2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = -2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & 17925 &:= -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4 \\
17889 &:= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 = -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 & 17926 &:= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 = 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17890 &:= 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^3 & 17927 &:= 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17891 &:= 0^8 - 3^5 - 5^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = 1^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 - 8^3 & 17928 &:= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 = -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17892 &:= 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^2 = -1^5 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 17929 &:= 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17893 &:= 0^8 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 = -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 17930 &:= 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^3 = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17894 &:= 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^2 = -1^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 8^1 & 17931 &:= 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^3 = 3^8 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
17895 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 17932 &:= 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^3 = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17896 &:= -2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^4 = -2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^4 & 17933 &:= -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17897 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 = -1^7 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^2 & 17934 &:= -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17898 &:= -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17935 &:= -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 = -1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 9^1 \\
17899 &:= -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 = -2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17936 &:= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 = 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^3 \\
17900 &:= 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 17937 &:= -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 = -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 \\
17901 &:= -1^7 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 7^1 - 8^4 = -1^7 + 4^8 + 5^5 - 6^6 - 7^1 - 8^4 & 17938 &:= 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^1 = 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^1
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
17939 &:= 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17971 &:= -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17940 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17972 &:= 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17941 &:= -2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17973 &:= 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17942 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17974 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -2^9 + 3^2 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
17943 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17975 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17944 &:= -0^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17976 &:= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17945 &:= 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17977 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 \\
17946 &:= 0^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17978 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 &= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17947 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17979 &:= 0^7 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 &= -1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
17948 &:= -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17980 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17949 &:= 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17981 &:= 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
17950 &:= 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17982 &:= 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^0 - 9^3 &= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 \\
17951 &:= -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 &= -1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17983 &:= -1^7 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 &= -1^7 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
17952 &:= -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= -1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 & 17984 &:= 0^6 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 - 8^0 &= -2^9 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
17953 &:= 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 &= 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 & 17985 &:= -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^3 &= 1^7 - 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
17954 &:= 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 &= 1^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 & 17986 &:= 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^3 &= 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
17955 &:= 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 & 17987 &:= 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^3 &= 1^6 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
17956 &:= 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 &= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^3 & 17988 &:= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
17957 &:= 0^7 - 2^5 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17989 &:= -1^9 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 - 9^1 &= -1^9 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 - 9^1 \\
17958 &:= 0^2 - 2^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^3 & 17990 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 \\
17959 &:= 0^7 - 2^5 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^9 + 2^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 9^1 & 17991 &:= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17960 &:= -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 &= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 & 17992 &:= 0^6 - 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
17961 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 &= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^2 & 17993 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
17962 &:= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17994 &:= 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
17963 &:= 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17995 &:= 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^0 &= -1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17964 &:= -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 &= -1^7 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17996 &:= 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
17965 &:= 0^6 - 4^8 + 5^7 + 6^5 - 7^4 + 8^0 &= 1^6 - 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 17997 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 &= 1^3 + 2^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17966 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 - 9^2 &= 1^7 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^1 & 17998 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 &= -1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17967 &:= -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 17999 &:= 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 &= 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17968 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & 18000 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 \\
17969 &:= 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 & & & \\
17970 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 &= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^3 & & & \\
18001 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 &= -1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 18006 &:= -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18002 &:= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 18007 &:= -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18003 &:= 0^9 - 3^6 + 5^7 - 6^0 - 7^3 - 9^5 &= 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 18008 &:= 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18004 &:= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 18009 &:= 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= 1^1 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18005 &:= -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= 1^6 - 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 18010 &:= 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18011 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 & = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^2 & 18048 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 \\
18012 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18049 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18013 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = 1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18050 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 \\
18014 := -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 18051 := 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18015 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18052 := -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 & = -1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
18016 := 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & 18053 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 6^3 - 7^4 \\
18017 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18054 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
18018 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & 18055 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18019 := -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18056 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
18020 := -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & 18057 := 0^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18021 := 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18058 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
18022 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^1 & 18059 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18023 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18060 := 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
18024 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & 18061 := -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18025 := -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18062 := -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
18026 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & 18063 := 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18027 := 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 - 7^0 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18064 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^9 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
18028 := 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18065 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
18029 := 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18066 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
18030 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & 18067 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
18031 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18068 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
18032 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^1 & 18069 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18033 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^0 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18070 := 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 \\
18034 := -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & = -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & 18071 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18035 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18072 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 3^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
18036 := 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & 18073 := 0^7 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^8 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^3 + 8^1 \\
18037 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^1 & = 1^7 + 2^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18074 := 0^7 + 2^9 + 3^0 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
18038 := 0^7 + 2^9 - 3^2 - 5^0 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 & 18075 := 0^7 + 2^5 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\
18039 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 & 18076 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
18040 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & 18077 := -0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
18041 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18078 := 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
18042 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & 18079 := 0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
18043 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18080 := 0^5 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 6^0 + 7^3 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 \\
18044 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 & 18081 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 \\
18045 := -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & = -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 & 18082 := 0^5 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^6 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 6^2 + 7^5 \\
18046 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^1 & 18083 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
18047 := 0^2 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18084 := -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
18085 &:= 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &18122 &:= 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 \\
18086 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &18123 &:= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 \\
18087 &:= -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &= -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &18124 &:= 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
18088 &:= 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &18125 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 \\
18089 &:= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &18126 &:= 0^4 - 3^5 + 4^8 + 5^0 - 6^6 - 8^3 &= -1^9 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^1 - 8^4 - 9^3 \\
18090 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 - 6^0 + 7^5 &= -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^1 &18127 &:= 0^8 + 2^0 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= -1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18091 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &18128 &:= 0^9 + 2^8 + 6^7 - 7^0 - 8^6 + 9^2 &= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
18092 &:= 0^3 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^5 &= -1^4 + 2^8 - 4^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &18129 &:= 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^8 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18093 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &18130 &:= -0^0 - 1^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 \\
18094 &:= 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 &= 3^8 + 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^3 + 8^4 &18131 &:= -1^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= -1^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18095 &:= -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3 &18132 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= -2^5 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^2 \\
18096 &:= -0^0 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= -1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &18133 &:= 1^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^8 - 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18097 &:= 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &18134 &:= 0^8 - 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18098 &:= 0^0 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &18135 &:= 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18099 &:= 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &18136 &:= 0^8 + 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18100 &:= 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &= 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &18137 &:= -1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= -1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18101 &:= 0^6 + 1^7 - 4^1 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 &18138 &:= -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^2 \\
18102 &:= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &= 1^4 + 2^8 + 4^1 + 6^7 + 7^2 - 8^6 &18139 &:= 1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18103 &:= -1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 - 9^2 &= -1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 - 9^2 &18140 &:= 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= -2^8 - 3^3 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 \\
18104 &:= 1^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 &= 1^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^1 + 7^5 &18141 &:= 0^7 + 2^6 - 4^0 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18105 &:= 0^6 - 1^7 + 4^1 - 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1 - 9^2 &18142 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 - 9^0 &= -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18106 &:= 0^6 - 1^7 - 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18143 &:= 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 &= 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18107 &:= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18144 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 9^0 &= 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18108 &:= 0^6 - 1^7 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18145 &:= 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 9^3 &= 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
18109 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 &= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 &18146 &:= 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 9^3 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
18110 &:= 0^6 + 1^7 + 4^0 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^2 &18147 &:= -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 \\
18111 &:= 2^7 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 &= 2^7 - 3^5 - 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 &18148 &:= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
18112 &:= 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 - 9^2 &= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18149 &:= -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^5 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^6 - 6^1 - 8^4 \\
18113 &:= -1^5 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^5 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &18150 &:= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 &= 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 \\
18114 &:= 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18151 &:= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &= 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
18115 &:= 1^5 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^5 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &18152 &:= 0^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 \\
18116 &:= 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18153 &:= 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 + 9^1 \\
18117 &:= 0^5 + 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= -1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 - 9^2 &18154 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 &= 3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18118 &:= 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^2 &18155 &:= 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 &= 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18119 &:= 0^5 + 2^7 + 4^0 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 &= 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1 - 9^2 &18156 &:= 0^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 &= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 7^4 + 9^3 \\
18120 &:= 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^3 &18157 &:= 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 &= 1^7 + 2^6 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
18121 &:= -0^0 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &= -1^1 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^2 &18158 &:= -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 &= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18159 := -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = -2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & 18196 := 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
18160 := -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 18197 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^7 + 2^6 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
18161 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 & 18198 := -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 & = -2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 \\
18162 := 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & 18199 := -2^8 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = -2^8 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 \\
18163 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^3 & = -1^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18200 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\
18164 := -0^0 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18201 := -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\
18165 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18202 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 \\
18166 := 0^0 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18203 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 - 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^7 - 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
18167 := -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = -2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 18204 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^5 + 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18168 := 0^0 - 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = 1^1 - 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 18205 := -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
18169 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = -2^7 + 3^2 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^3 & 18206 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^6 + 3^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 9^1 \\
18170 := 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 + 3^6 - 4^9 + 6^7 - 7^3 - 9^1 & 18207 := 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 \\
18171 := 0^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^7 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 18208 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
18172 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 18209 := -1^6 + 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = -1^6 + 2^7 + 4^1 - 5^2 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
18173 := 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^3 - 7^4 - 9^1 & 18210 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^1 \\
18174 := -1^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18211 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18175 := -1^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^5 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^1 + 7^4 & 18212 := 0^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = -2^9 - 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18176 := 1^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^4 & 18213 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18177 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18214 := 0^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 \\
18178 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18215 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
18179 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18216 := 0^6 + 2^7 - 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 \\
18180 := 0^5 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^3 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 18217 := 0^8 + 3^4 + 4^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18181 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 & 18218 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
18182 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 - 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^3 & 18219 := -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
18183 := -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 - 9^2 & = -1^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 - 9^2 & 18220 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
18184 := 0^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^0 + 6^4 + 7^5 & = 1^7 - 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 18221 := 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 \\
18185 := 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^0 & = -1^5 + 2^7 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & 18222 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^1 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
18186 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 18223 := 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
18187 := 0^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^0 & = -1^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 18224 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^3 \\
18188 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 3^7 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^3 & = -1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18225 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18189 := 0^5 + 2^7 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 2^6 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 18226 := 0^7 + 3^6 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 6^0 + 7^5 & = 1^6 + 3^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^3 + 9^1 \\
18190 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18227 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18191 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18228 := 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 & = 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18192 := -2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18229 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18193 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18230 := -2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = -2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18194 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^9 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & 18231 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 3^2 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18195 := 1^5 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^5 + 2^7 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 7^4 & 18232 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18233 := 0^9 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0 - 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 - 9^1 & 18270 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^3 \\
18234 := 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & = 1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 - 7^1 & 18271 := -0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18235 := 0^4 + 4^8 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 7^6 - 8^0 & = -1^5 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 & 18272 := -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18236 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & 18273 := 0^0 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18237 := 0^4 + 4^8 + 5^7 - 6^5 - 7^6 + 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18274 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
18238 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & 18275 := -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18239 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18276 := 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18240 := 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 - 9^0 & = 1^5 - 2^9 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 - 9^1 & 18277 := 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18241 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18278 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 \\
18242 := 0^6 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 + 9^0 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & 18279 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18243 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18280 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
18244 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & 18281 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
18245 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18282 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
18246 := -1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = -1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & 18283 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
18247 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18284 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18248 := 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & 18285 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18249 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & 18286 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18250 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18287 := -3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18251 := -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18288 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18252 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18289 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^9 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^3 \\
18253 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^0 & = 1^6 + 2^7 + 4^2 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 & 18290 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18254 := 0^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & 18291 := 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18255 := 2^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & = 2^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^2 - 8^6 & 18292 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
18256 := 0^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & 18293 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
18257 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^0 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & 18294 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
18258 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 & 18295 := 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
18259 := -1^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & 18296 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 \\
18260 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 & 18297 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
18261 := 1^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = 1^9 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 9^3 & 18298 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^4 + 6^7 - 7^1 - 8^6 \\
18262 := -1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 & = -1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 & 18299 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
18263 := -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & 18300 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18264 := 0^9 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^1 & 18301 := -2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18265 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & 18302 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18266 := 0^9 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^2 & 18303 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
18267 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & 18304 := -0^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18268 := -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & 18305 := 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18269 := -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & 18306 := 0^0 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18307 := -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -3^7 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & 18344 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18308 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & 18345 := -2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18309 := 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & 18346 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18310 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5 & 18347 := -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
18311 := 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18348 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 \\
18312 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18349 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
18313 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & 18350 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18314 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18351 := 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^2 & = 2^5 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^2 \\
18315 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & 18352 := -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18316 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18353 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\
18317 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18354 := -2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\
18318 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = 1^5 - 2^1 + 4^8 - 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^2 & 18355 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 \\
18319 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 & 18356 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18320 := 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & = 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 18357 := -2^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -2^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18321 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 18358 := 0^4 - 2^0 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18322 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18359 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18323 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^8 + 4^6 - 5^4 + 6^5 + 8^3 & 18360 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18324 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^0 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18361 := 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18325 := -0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^2 & 18362 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18326 := 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18363 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18327 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2 & 18364 := -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18328 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18365 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^2 \\
18329 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18366 := 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18330 := 0^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18367 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18331 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18368 := 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18332 := -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18369 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^2 \\
18333 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18370 := 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18334 := 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18371 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
18335 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18372 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18336 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 - 9^0 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18373 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
18337 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18374 := 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18338 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^0 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18375 := 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 \\
18339 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18376 := 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 9^2 \\
18340 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18377 := -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 & = -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5 \\
18341 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18378 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
18342 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^3 & 18379 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1 \\
18343 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3 & 18380 := 0^3 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^4 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 - 5^4 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

18381 := $-2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= -2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	18418 := $0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$
18382 := $2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	$= 2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	18419 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$
18383 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	18420 := $-0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$
18384 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	18421 := $2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$
18385 := $0^3 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 - 9^1$	18422 := $0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$
18386 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	18423 := $-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$
18387 := $-1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1$	18424 := $0^8 + 2^0 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$
18388 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	18425 := $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$
18389 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 - 9^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1$	18426 := $-0^0 - 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$
18390 := $0^2 + 2^8 - 3^0 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^4$	18427 := $-1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$
18391 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= -1^8 + 2^9 + 6^7 + 7^1 - 8^6 + 9^2$	18428 := $-0^0 + 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
18392 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	18429 := $1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$
18393 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	18430 := $0^0 + 1^9 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
18394 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 6^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^4 + 7^5$	18431 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^9 + 2^2 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$
18395 := $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	18432 := $-0^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
18396 := $0^3 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^2 + 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5$	18433 := $3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
18397 := $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	18434 := $0^0 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 7^5$
18398 := $0^3 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 6^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^5 + 9^4$	18435 := $-2^2 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$	$= -2^2 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$
18399 := $-0^0 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	18436 := $1^8 - 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$= 1^8 - 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$
18400 := $2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	$= 2^8 + 3^2 + 6^7 + 7^3 - 8^6$	18437 := $-1^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= -1^9 + 4^6 + 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$
18401 := $-1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	18438 := $0^8 - 4^0 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$= -1^1 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$
18402 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= 1^9 - 3^3 + 4^6 - 5^1 + 6^5 + 9^4$	18439 := $4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$	$= 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$
18403 := $1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	18440 := $0^8 + 4^0 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$= 1^1 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$
18404 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	18441 := $-1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1$
18405 := $-2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	$= -2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	18442 := $-1^8 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$= -1^8 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$
18406 := $0^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0$	$= 1^1 - 2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 8^4$	18443 := $1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1$
18407 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	18444 := $1^8 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$	$= 1^8 + 4^1 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5$
18408 := $0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 - 6^5 + 9^4$	18445 := $-2^2 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$
18409 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	18446 := $0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$
18410 := $0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^6 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^4$	18447 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 - 9^1$
18411 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	18448 := $-0^0 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$
18412 := $-3^3 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$	$= -3^3 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5$	18449 := $3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$
18413 := $-2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	18450 := $0^0 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$
18414 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	18451 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2$
18415 := $-1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^1$	18452 := $0^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2$
18416 := $-0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	18453 := $2^2 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^3$
18417 := $-3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	18454 := $0^4 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18455 := 0^7 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^3 - 8^0 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 18492 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18456 := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 18493 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18457 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 18494 := 0^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^8 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 8^2 - 9^5 \\
18458 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18495 := -0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18459 := -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18496 := -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18460 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18497 := 0^0 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18461 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18498 := 0^6 + 3^8 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 6^5 + 8^4 & = -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^1 - 7^3 \\
18462 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & = -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^6 + 6^4 - 8^5 & 18499 := 0^8 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 8^2 - 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 - 9^1 \\
18463 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18500 := -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
18464 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & 18501 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18465 := -2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & 18502 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
18466 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & 18503 := 0^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18467 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^2 & 18504 := -2^8 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 + 8^5 & = -2^8 - 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 + 8^5 \\
18468 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18505 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
18469 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 18506 := 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
18470 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 18507 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
18471 := -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18508 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18472 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18509 := -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18473 := 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18510 := 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
18474 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18511 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^2 - 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
18475 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^1 & 18512 := 1^4 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^4 - 2^9 - 4^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18476 := -1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18513 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18477 := -2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 & = -2^8 - 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^2 + 8^4 & 18514 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18478 := 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18515 := -2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = -2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18479 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18516 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18480 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18517 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
18481 := 0^8 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18518 := 0^3 + 2^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18482 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18519 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^1 + 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18483 := 0^8 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 18520 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
18484 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18521 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^2 - 9^3 & = -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^2 - 9^3 \\
18485 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^1 - 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^3 + 8^4 & 18522 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 \\
18486 := -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18523 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^1 \\
18487 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & 18524 := -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
18488 := 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18525 := 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18489 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & 18526 := 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
18490 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18527 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 \\
18491 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & 18528 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18529 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18566 := -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
18530 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 & 18567 := 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18531 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18568 := 0^6 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^3 + 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18532 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 & 18569 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18533 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18570 := 0^6 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
18534 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 & 18571 := -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18535 := 0^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18572 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
18536 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 18573 := 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18537 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^2 & 18574 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18538 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 18575 := 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & = 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18539 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^3 & 18576 := 0^0 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18540 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 18577 := 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 & = 2^9 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^3 \\
18541 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^0 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & 18578 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^2 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
18542 := -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^1 & 18579 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18543 := 0^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & 18580 := -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^2 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^2 \\
18544 := 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^1 & 18581 := 0^4 - 2^9 + 4^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18545 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 18582 := -3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^4 - 8^3 \\
18546 := -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 18583 := 0^0 - 3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 7^4 - 8^3 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
18547 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & 18584 := 0^6 + 3^7 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 6^3 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 3^7 + 4^6 - 5^3 - 6^1 + 7^5 \\
18548 := 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & = 1^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 18585 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18549 := -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^2 & 18586 := -2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18550 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 18587 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18551 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & 18588 := -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 - 9^2 \\
18552 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4 & 18589 := -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
18553 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^8 - 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 + 8^5 & 18590 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 - 9^2 \\
18554 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & 18591 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^3 - 2^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
18555 := 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & 18592 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
18556 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & 18593 := -2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
18557 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^6 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18594 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
18558 := 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & 18595 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 \\
18559 := -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & = -2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 18596 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 \\
18560 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 18597 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^4 + 9^2 \\
18561 := 0^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^2 & = -1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18598 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
18562 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^1 - 9^3 & 18599 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 & = -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 \\
18563 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^6 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18600 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 \\
18564 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^3 - 2^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & 18601 := 0^6 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 6^2 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^9 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 9^1 \\
18565 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18602 := 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^8 + 7^7 + 8^1 - 9^6 & = 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^8 + 7^7 + 8^1 - 9^6
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18603 := 0^6 + 3^4 - 4^9 + 6^7 + 7^0 + 9^3 & = 1^9 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 9^1 & 18640 := -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
18604 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 18641 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^3 & = -2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^3 \\
18605 := -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = -1^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^3 & 18642 := 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18606 := 0^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & 18643 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^0 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
18607 := 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^3 & = 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 - 5^1 - 6^6 - 8^3 & 18644 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^6 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 6^4 + 7^5 \\
18608 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 18645 := -1^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
18609 := -2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = -2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 18646 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^2 - 9^3 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^2 - 9^3 \\
18610 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 18647 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^5 - 8^4 - 9^0 & = 1^9 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
18611 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^9 - 3^1 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & 18648 := 0^3 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^0 - 9^1 & = -1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18612 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & 18649 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
18613 := -2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & 18650 := 0^3 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^1 & = 1^5 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18614 := 0^0 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & 18651 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
18615 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 & 18652 := 0^3 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 - 9^1 & = -1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18616 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 18653 := 0^8 - 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 + 8^4 & = -1^6 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
18617 := 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & 18654 := 0^3 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^0 & = 1^5 + 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18618 := -0^0 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18655 := -0^0 - 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
18619 := -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18656 := -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18620 := -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 18657 := -0^0 + 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
18621 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & 18658 := 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18622 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1 & 18659 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
18623 := -0^0 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18660 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18624 := 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18661 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
18625 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 - 9^0 & = 1^1 + 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & 18662 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18626 := 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18663 := -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18627 := 0^2 - 2^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^3 & 18664 := 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18628 := -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 9^3 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^1 & 18665 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
18629 := 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 9^3 & = 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^4 - 9^3 & 18666 := -0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18630 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18667 := -3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18631 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 & = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 9^2 & 18668 := 0^0 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18632 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18669 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
18633 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & 18670 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
18634 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & 18671 := 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18635 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & 18672 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 2^2 - 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
18636 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18673 := 0^3 - 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5 - 8^2 & = -1^4 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
18637 := -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18674 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^3 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^3 \\
18638 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18675 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
18639 := -0^0 - 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 18676 := 0^9 - 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
18677 := -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & = -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^2 & 18714 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18678 := 0^9 + 2^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^1 & 18715 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18679 := 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = 2^8 - 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 18716 := 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18680 := -4^9 + 5^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 - 9^5 & = -4^9 + 5^8 - 6^6 - 8^4 - 9^5 & 18717 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18681 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^0 - 9^3 & = -1^3 - 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18718 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18682 := -0^0 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18719 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 & = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 \\
18683 := 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & = 2^5 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18720 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18684 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18721 := 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
18685 := -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18722 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18686 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18723 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18687 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 & = -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 - 9^2 & 18724 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^2 \\
18688 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & 18725 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18689 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & 18726 := -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18690 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^1 - 9^3 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^1 - 9^3 & 18727 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = -1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18691 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & 18728 := -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = -2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18692 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 9^3 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^1 - 9^3 & 18729 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^2 + 7^4 \\
18693 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18730 := -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 & = -2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
18694 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = -2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18731 := 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18695 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18732 := 0^9 - 3^0 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
18696 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18733 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
18697 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18734 := 0^9 + 3^0 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
18698 := 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18735 := -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18699 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18736 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
18700 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4 & 18737 := 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^9 + 3^1 + 5^7 - 7^3 - 9^5 \\
18701 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18738 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
18702 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18739 := 0^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -2^6 + 3^7 + 5^2 - 6^3 + 7^5 \\
18703 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^3 & 18740 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = -2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
18704 := 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 9^3 & 18741 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
18705 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 & 18742 := -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
18706 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 7^1 - 9^3 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 7^1 - 9^3 & 18743 := 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2 & = 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2 \\
18707 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 & 18744 := 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
18708 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^1 & 18745 := -0^0 - 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
18709 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^3 & 18746 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
18710 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & 18747 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
18711 := 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & = 2^8 + 4^2 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 8^5 & 18748 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
18712 := -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & 18749 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4 \\
18713 := 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & = 2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 - 8^3 & 18750 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4
\end{array}$$

$18751 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3$	$18788 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18752 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3$	$= 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^3$	$18789 := 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18753 := -0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18790 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18754 := -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18791 := 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$
$18755 := 0^0 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18792 := 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$
$18756 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18793 := -1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$
$18757 := -0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18794 := 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1$	$= 1^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1$
$18758 := -3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18795 := 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$
$18759 := 0^0 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18796 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$
$18760 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$18797 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18761 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18798 := 0^3 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0$	$= 1^8 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1$
$18762 := 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18799 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$
$18763 := 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^3$	$= 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^3$	$18800 := -2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$= -2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$
$18764 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^4 + 9^3$	$= 1^5 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$18801 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18765 := 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$	$18802 := 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18766 := -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$	$= -1^9 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1$	$18803 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18767 := -0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18804 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$
$18768 := -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18805 := -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$
$18769 := 0^0 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18806 := -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4$
$18770 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$18807 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18771 := -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$18808 := -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18772 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1$	$18809 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18773 := -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18810 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4$
$18774 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$18811 := -0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18775 := -1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$18812 := 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18776 := -1^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1$	$= -1^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^1$	$18813 := 0^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18777 := 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1$	$18814 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4$
$18778 := -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$18815 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18779 := -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 4^7 - 5^1 + 7^4$	$18816 := 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18780 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18817 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4$
$18781 := -2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18818 := 0^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^4$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3$
$18782 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18819 := 0^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$
$18783 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18820 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3$
$18784 := -0^0 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18821 := 0^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$
$18785 := 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 4^7 + 7^4$	$18822 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$
$18786 := 0^0 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18823 := 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$
$18787 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$= -1^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4$	$18824 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$

$18825 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18862 := 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$= 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5$
$18826 := -1^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5$	$= -1^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5$	$18863 := 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 3^7 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$
$18827 := 0^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^0 - 9^3$	$= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$18864 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18828 := 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5$	$= 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5$	$18865 := -2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18829 := 0^0 + 1^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$	$18866 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18830 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$	$18867 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$
$18831 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$18868 := -0^0 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18832 := 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^2$	$18869 := 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18833 := -0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$18870 := 0^0 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18834 := -2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$= -2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$18871 := -1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$= -1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$
$18835 := 0^0 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$18872 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18836 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$18873 := 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$
$18837 := -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -2^4 + 3^7 - 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$18874 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5$
$18838 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$18875 := -2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$= -2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3$
$18839 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4$	$18876 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3$
$18840 := 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4$	$18877 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$
$18841 := -0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$18878 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0$	$= 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 8^1$
$18842 := 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$18879 := 0^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0$	$= 1^9 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1$
$18843 := 0^0 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$	$18880 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$
$18844 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$18881 := 0^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0$	$= 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$
$18845 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^1 + 7^4$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18882 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$
$18846 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2$	$18883 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^3$
$18847 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18884 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$
$18848 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^4$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2$	$18885 := 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$
$18849 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$18886 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$
$18850 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2$	$18887 := -1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$= -1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$
$18851 := 0^1 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^0 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18888 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$
$18852 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2$	$18889 := 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$
$18853 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$18890 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$= -2^3 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^2 - 8^4$
$18854 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$18891 := 0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3$
$18855 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$18892 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^2 - 9^3$
$18856 := 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4$	$18893 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3$
$18857 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$18894 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^2 - 9^3$
$18858 := 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$= 2^6 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18895 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$
$18859 := -1^9 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^1$	$= -1^9 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^1$	$18896 := -0^0 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$
$18860 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$= -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^1$	$18897 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$= -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$
$18861 := -0^0 + 4^7 - 5^6 + 6^4 + 7^5$	$= 1^9 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 - 9^1$	$18898 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$

$18899 := -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$18936 := 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$
$18900 := 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 8^1$	$18937 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 9^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$
$18901 := 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 - 5^3 + 7^5$	$18938 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$
$18902 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$18939 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$
$18903 := 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 3^5 + 4^7 - 5^3 + 7^4$	$18940 := 0^1 + 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$
$18904 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$18941 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^3$
$18905 := -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1$	$18942 := -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3$
$18906 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$18943 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^3$
$18907 := 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1$	$18944 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$
$18908 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^0$	$= 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$18945 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3$
$18909 := 0^5 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^4 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 + 9^1$	$18946 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3$
$18910 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$18947 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^3$
$18911 := 0^5 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18948 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$
$18912 := -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$= -1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$18949 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18913 := 0^1 - 1^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4$	$18950 := -2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= -2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18914 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^5 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4$	$18951 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18915 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$18952 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$
$18916 := 0^2 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$	$18953 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18917 := 0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$18954 := 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 3^9 - 9^3$
$18918 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^3$	$18955 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18919 := 0^6 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$18956 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^3$
$18920 := 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$= 2^9 + 4^6 - 5^2 + 6^5 + 9^4$	$18957 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18921 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$	$18958 := 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18922 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$	$= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$	$18959 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^3$
$18923 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^3$	$18960 := 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^3$
$18924 := -1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$18961 := 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$
$18925 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$18962 := 1^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3$
$18926 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$18963 := 1^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3$
$18927 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$18964 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^3$
$18928 := -2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2$	$= -2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2$	$18965 := -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^3$
$18929 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^2$	$18966 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$18930 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$18967 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$
$18931 := 0^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^4 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^3$	$18968 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$18932 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^3$	$18969 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$
$18933 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^3$	$18970 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$
$18934 := -1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^4 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$18971 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$
$18935 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^3$	$18972 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$

18973 := $1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	18988 := $-1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$
18974 := $0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^1 + 7^5$	18989 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$
18975 := $1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^3$	18990 := $1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$
18976 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	18991 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$
18977 := $2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	18992 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$
18978 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	18993 := $0^3 + 3^7 - 5^0 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3$
18979 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^3$	18994 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$
18980 := $0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	18995 := $0^3 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2$
18981 := $-0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	18996 := $-2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2$	$= -2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2$
18982 := $2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	18997 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2$
18983 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^3$	18998 := $-1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$
18984 := $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	18999 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4$
18985 := $-0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	19000 := $1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$
18986 := $2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$		
18987 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^3$		
19001 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4$	19023 := $-1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$
19002 := $0^7 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	19024 := $-1^9 - 2^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5$	$= -1^9 - 2^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5$
19003 := $0^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^0 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4$	19025 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^3$
19004 := $0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	19026 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
19005 := $1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4$	$= 1^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4$	19027 := $2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
19006 := $-1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	19028 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$
19007 := $-0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4$	19029 := $0^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^0 + 7^4$	$= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^1 - 9^3$
19008 := $1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5$	19030 := $1^9 + 2^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5$	$= 1^9 + 2^1 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5$
19009 := $-2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 9^2$	$= -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 9^2$	19031 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3$
19010 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19032 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$
19011 := $-2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19033 := $2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$
19012 := $0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19034 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$
19013 := $1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^3$	19035 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3$
19014 := $0^0 + 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^3$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19036 := $-2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3$
19015 := $-1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3$	$= -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3$	19037 := $-2^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^2$	$= -2^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^2$
19016 := $-1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19038 := $0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$
19017 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^0 - 9^3$	$= 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3$	19039 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^1 - 9^3$
19018 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19040 := $0^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 8^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^2 + 7^5$
19019 := $0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 - 9^3$	$= -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3$	19041 := $-1^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5$	$= -1^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5$
19020 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19042 := $0^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^1 + 7^4$
19021 := $1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3$	$= 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3$	19043 := $1^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5$	$= 1^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5$
19022 := $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5$	19044 := $0^0 + 1^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
19045 := 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 \\
19046 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^1 + 7^4 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
19047 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19048 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
19049 := 0^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19050 := 0^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
19051 := 0^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^0 + 7^4 & = 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19052 := -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19053 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19054 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19055 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19056 := 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 2^6 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19057 := 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^9 - 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19058 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19059 := 0^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19060 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
19061 := 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 & = 2^3 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^2 + 7^4 \\
19062 := -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19063 := -0^0 - 1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19064 := -1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19065 := -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
19066 := 1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19067 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19068 := -1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19069 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19070 := 1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19071 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
19072 := -1^9 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19073 := 0^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 9^2 \\
19074 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3 \\
19075 := 0^9 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19076 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^3 \\
19077 := 0^9 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^1 \\
19078 := 0^1 + 1^9 + 5^7 + 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19079 := 0^9 + 2^2 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^8 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
19080 := 1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^9 - 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19081 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = -2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19082 := -1^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19083 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
19084 := 1^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^9 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19085 := -3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19086 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^9 + 2^2 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19087 := -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
19088 := -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3 \\
19089 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
19090 := 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^3 \\
19091 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
19092 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^1 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
19093 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2 \\
19094 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^1 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
19095 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19096 := -0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 5^4 - 9^1 \\
19097 := 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19098 := 0^0 + 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19099 := 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19100 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19101 := 0^1 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19102 := 0^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 - 7^0 - 9^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 - 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19103 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19104 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
19105 := 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
19106 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 \\
19107 := 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 9^2 & = 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^4 + 9^2 \\
19108 := -0^0 - 1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19109 := -1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19110 := -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 & = -1^8 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 - 8^1 \\
19111 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19112 := -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 9^1 & = -1^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 - 9^1 \\
19113 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19114 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19115 := -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19116 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19117 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19118 := -0^0 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
19119 := 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19120 := 0^0 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19121 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19122 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19123 := 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19124 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19125 := 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 & = 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19126 := 0^9 + 2^0 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
19127 := -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 & = -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
19128 := 1^9 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^9 + 2^1 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5 \\
19129 := 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 & = 1^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^1 \\
19130 := -0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
19131 := 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 & = 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
19132 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 \\
19133 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^3 & = -1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19134 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19135 := 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19136 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^0 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19137 := 0^9 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 - 7^0 + 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19138 := 0^8 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19139 := 0^9 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^4 + 7^0 + 9^3 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^3 \\
19140 := -0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19141 := -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19142 := 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
19143 := 0^0 + 2^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19144 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 9^2 \\
19145 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19146 := 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19147 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19148 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
19149 := -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
19150 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19151 := 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 & = 2^4 + 3^7 + 4^2 + 5^3 + 7^5 \\
19152 := -0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
19153 := 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
19154 := 0^0 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
19155 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 & = -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19156 := 3^9 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5 - 9^3 & = 3^9 + 4^7 + 5^4 - 7^5 - 9^3 \\
19157 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
19158 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^5 + 4^7 + 5^3 + 7^4 \\
19159 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
19160 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19161 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
19162 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = -1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19163 := 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
19164 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19165 := 0^4 - 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
19166 := 0^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19167 := 0^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^1 \\
19168 := 0^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19169 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = 2^7 + 3^3 + 4^5 + 5^6 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
19170 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19171 := 0^1 - 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^0 & = -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 9^2 \\
19172 := 0^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19173 := 0^1 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^0 & = 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19174 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19175 := -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
19176 := 0^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19177 := 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^8 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
19178 := -0^0 - 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 3^7 + 4^8 - 6^6 - 7^4 + 8^3 \\
19179 := -1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
19180 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19181 := 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
19182 := 0^0 + 1^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19183 := -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
19184 := -0^0 + 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19185 := 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 & = 1^8 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^1 \\
19186 := -2^9 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\
19187 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
19188 := -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -2^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
19189 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = -2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 9^2 \\
19190 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19191 := -0^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = -1^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
19192 := 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
19193 := 0^0 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 & = 1^1 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 7^3 - 8^4 \\
19194 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19195 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^2 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^2 \\
19196 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19197 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^4 + 9^3 \\
19198 := 0^8 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 7^1 - 9^3 \\
19199 := 0^9 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^3 \\
19200 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 9^2 \\
19201 := -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
19202 := -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19203 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^3 \\
19204 := 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19205 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19206 := -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = -2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19207 := 0^0 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19208 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^1 - 9^3 \\
19209 := -0^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19210 := 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19211 := 0^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19212 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 5^1 - 9^3 \\
19213 := -0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19214 := 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19215 := 0^0 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^3 \\
19216 := 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 \\
19217 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^2 & = -1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
19218 := 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 7^1 - 9^3 & = 1^7 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 7^1 - 9^3 \\
19219 := 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 & = 1^2 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^1 - 9^3 \\
19220 := -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
19221 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19222 := 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1 \\
19223 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19224 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19225 := -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 & = -2^8 + 3^7 - 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3 \\
19226 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19227 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19228 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19229 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19230 := 1^5 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^1 - 9^2 & = 1^5 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^1 - 9^2 \\
19231 := 0^7 + 3^9 + 5^6 + 6^0 - 7^5 + 9^3 & = -1^8 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19232 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19233 := 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19234 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19235 := 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 9^2 & = 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^4 + 9^2 \\
19236 := -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -2^9 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 9^3 \\
19237 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19238 := 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 & = 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19239 := 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 9^4 & = 3^9 - 4^6 - 5^5 + 6^3 + 9^4 \\
19240 := 0^8 - 3^0 - 4^3 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19241 := 0^2 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = 1^8 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19242 := -0^0 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19243 := -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = -2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19244 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19245 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19246 := -0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19247 := 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19248 := 0^0 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 & = 1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^3 \\
19249 := 0^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 - 5^0 + 7^5 & = -1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19250 := -0^0 + 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19251 := 0^8 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = 1^8 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19252 := -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = -2^8 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19253 := 0^8 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = -1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19254 := -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 & = -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19255 := 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = 1^8 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19256 := -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 \\
19257 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 & = 1^4 + 3^5 + 4^8 + 5^3 - 6^6 + 8^1 \\
19258 := 0^7 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 \\
19259 := -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^4 & = -2^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 - 7^2 + 9^4 \\
19260 := 0^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 \\
19261 := 0^1 + 1^7 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
19262 := 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2 \\
19263 := -3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^4 & = -3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^4 \\
19264 := 0^0 - 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^3 + 6^6 - 9^4 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^1 + 7^5 \\
19265 := 0^7 - 3^0 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19266 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{ll}
19267 := -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = -2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19268 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19269 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^3 \\
19270 := 0^8 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 8^3 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^1 \\
19271 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = -1^8 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 8^3 + 9^2 \\
19272 := -3^8 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 8^4 & = -3^8 - 4^7 + 6^6 - 7^3 - 8^4 \\
19273 := -0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3 & = -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19274 := 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3 & = 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19275 := 0^0 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3 & = 1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^3 \\
19276 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^1 \\
19277 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19278 := -0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^3 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19279 := 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^3 & = 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^3 \\
19280 := 0^0 + 3^9 - 4^6 + 5^5 + 6^4 - 9^3 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19281 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^3 \\
19282 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^0 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19283 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 - 9^0 & = 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19284 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^0 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^2 + 7^5 \\
19285 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^0 & = 3^6 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 6^4 + 7^3 \\
19286 := -0^0 - 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^1 \\
19287 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
19288 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^1 \\
19289 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 \\
19290 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^1 \\
19291 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19292 := -0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 \\
19293 := -2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & = -2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 \\
19294 := 0^0 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 \\
19295 := 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 & = 1^8 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
19296 := 0^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^1 \\
19297 := -0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = -1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19298 := 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19299 := 0^0 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 & = 1^1 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19300 := -1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
19301 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = 1^8 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^3 \\
19302 := 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = 1^8 - 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
19303 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^3 + 7^4 \\
19304 := 0^8 - 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = 1^7 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19305 := -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
19306 := 0^8 + 4^0 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19307 := 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^1 \\
19308 := -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 & = -1^8 + 4^1 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4 \\
19309 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^3 \\
19310 := -0^0 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19311 := -3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = -3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 \\
19312 := 0^0 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19313 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = -1^8 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
19314 := -0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19315 := 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 \\
19316 := 0^0 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19317 := 0^8 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^0 - 8^3 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^1 \\
19318 := 0^4 - 2^8 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 + 8^2 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 9^2 \\
19319 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 - 9^1 \\
19320 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^1 - 9^2 \\
19321 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19322 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19323 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19324 := -1^9 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 & = -1^9 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 7^1 - 9^5 \\
19325 := -0^0 - 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19326 := -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19327 := -0^0 + 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19328 := 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19329 := -0^0 - 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^1 - 9^2 \\
19330 := -1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19331 := -0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19332 := 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19333 := 0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19334 := -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19335 := 0^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 + 9^1 \\
19336 := 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 & = 1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19337 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2 \\
19338 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2 \\
19339 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^0 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2 \\
19340 := 0^1 - 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^0 & = 1^9 + 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^1 - 9^5
\end{array}$$

19341 := $0^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 8^3 - 9^2$	19378 := $2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$
19342 := $0^1 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19379 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$
19343 := $0^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	19380 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$
19344 := $-1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^7 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	19381 := $2^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5$	$= 2^9 - 4^4 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5$
19345 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	19382 := $-1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$
19346 := $2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 - 9^2$	19383 := $-1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2$
19347 := $-0^0 - 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	19384 := $1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$
19348 := $-1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	19385 := $0^6 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2$
19349 := $-0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	19386 := $-0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2$
19350 := $1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	19387 := $2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2$
19351 := $0^0 + 1^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	$= -2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^2$	19388 := $0^0 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^2$
19352 := $-0^0 + 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3$	$= -1^7 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^1$	19389 := $0^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^0 + 9^3$	$= 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2$
19353 := $3^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3$	$= 3^9 + 4^5 - 5^4 - 9^3$	19390 := $1^4 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= 1^4 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$
19354 := $2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	19391 := $0^4 - 3^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^2 + 9^1$
19355 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^2$	19392 := $-1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	$= -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
19356 := $2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2$	19393 := $0^4 + 3^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= -1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1$
19357 := $-2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	19394 := $1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
19358 := $0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	19395 := $1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1$
19359 := $0^3 + 3^9 + 4^6 - 5^5 - 6^4 + 9^0$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^2$	19396 := $1^4 + 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= 1^4 + 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$
19360 := $0^8 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^2 + 9^3$	19397 := $-2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^3$	$= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^3$
19361 := $0^1 - 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^2$	19398 := $0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^2 + 9^3$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
19362 := $0^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	19399 := $2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$
19363 := $0^1 - 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^2 + 9^1$	19400 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 - 5^1 + 9^3$
19364 := $0^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^0$	$= 3^9 + 4^7 - 5^4 - 7^5 + 9^3$	19401 := $0^1 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 8^2 - 9^3$
19365 := $0^1 + 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 6^3 - 9^2$	19402 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0$	$= 2^8 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 8^2 - 9^3$
19366 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	19403 := $0^1 - 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 - 9^2$
19367 := $-2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= -2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	19404 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 + 9^1$
19368 := $0^0 - 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^4 + 9^2$	19405 := $2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$
19369 := $0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^8 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 8^2 + 9^1$	19406 := $0^0 + 2^9 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$
19370 := $-0^0 - 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	19407 := $0^2 + 2^4 - 3^0 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3$	$= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 9^1$
19371 := $-1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	19408 := $-0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
19372 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	19409 := $-1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$
19373 := $1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$	19410 := $-0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^5 + 5^1 + 9^3$
19374 := $-0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= -1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	19411 := $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$
19375 := $3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	19412 := $0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$
19376 := $0^0 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	$= 1^1 + 3^7 + 4^4 + 5^3 + 7^5$	19413 := $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$
19377 := $-0^0 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^9 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^2$	19414 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
19415 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & 19452 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^2 + 9^1 \\
19416 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = -1^1 - 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 19453 := -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19417 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & 19454 := -2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & = -2^7 + 4^6 - 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 \\
19418 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = -1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & 19455 := 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19419 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & 19456 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
19420 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = 1^7 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & 19457 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19421 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & 19458 := -0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19422 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^0 & = -1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & 19459 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19423 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & 19460 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = 1^2 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 - 9^1 \\
19424 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^0 & = 1^7 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & 19461 := 0^4 + 2^0 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19425 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^1 & 19462 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = 2^9 + 3^7 - 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 \\
19426 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19463 := 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^1 \\
19427 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19464 := 0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^3 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
19428 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19465 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 + 9^1 \\
19429 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19466 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^2 \\
19430 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19467 := 0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19431 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19468 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^2 \\
19432 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19469 := 0^1 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = -2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
19433 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19470 := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = -2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
19434 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19471 := -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19435 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19472 := 0^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 \\
19436 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19473 := 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 & = 3^4 + 4^8 - 6^6 + 8^3 \\
19437 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19474 := -0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 \\
19438 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19475 := -1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19439 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19476 := 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & = 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 \\
19440 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19477 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19441 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19478 := 0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 \\
19442 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & = -1^2 + 2^3 - 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19479 := -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 & = -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19443 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^1 & 19480 := 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 \\
19444 := -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & = -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 19481 := 0^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^1 \\
19445 := -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 19482 := 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^2 \\
19446 := 0^0 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 19483 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19447 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^1 & 19484 := -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19448 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^2 & 19485 := 0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19449 := -0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 19486 := 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^2 + 7^4 \\
19450 := 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 19487 := 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
19451 := 0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^2 & 19488 := -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1
\end{array}$$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
19489 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^2 & 19526 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 \\
19490 := 0^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19527 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
19491 := 0^1 - 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^0 & = 1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 6^3 - 9^1 & 19528 := -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
19492 := 0^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19529 := 0^1 - 1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 \\
19493 := 0^1 + 1^3 - 2^8 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^0 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 + 9^2 & 19530 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 \\
19494 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^4 + 2^2 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19531 := -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19495 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & = 1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 + 9^2 & 19532 := 0^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = 1^9 + 5^7 + 6^1 - 7^6 + 9^5 \\
19496 := -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & 19533 := 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19497 := -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & 19534 := -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19498 := 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1 & 19535 := 0^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 \\
19499 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & 19536 := 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19500 := -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & = -2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & 19537 := 0^4 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 \\
19501 := -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & 19538 := -0^0 + 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = -1^1 + 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
19502 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^8 + 3^7 - 5^1 + 7^5 + 8^3 & 19539 := 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
19503 := 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & 19540 := 0^0 + 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 & = 1^1 + 2^9 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5 \\
19504 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1 & = -2^7 + 4^6 + 5^2 - 6^4 + 7^5 & 19541 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 \\
19505 := 0^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^0 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & 19542 := -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = -2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
19506 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^2 + 2^4 - 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19543 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 & = -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^2 \\
19507 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & 19544 := -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
19508 := 0^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^3 + 9^2 & 19545 := -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 & = -1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19509 := 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & = 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 19546 := 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
19510 := 0^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^2 & 19547 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19511 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & 19548 := -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
19512 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^9 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 7^4 + 9^3 & 19549 := 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 & = 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^3 + 9^2 \\
19513 := 0^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 - 6^0 + 7^4 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19550 := 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
19514 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 9^1 & 19551 := 0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2 \\
19515 := -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19552 := -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & = -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 \\
19516 := 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 9^2 & 19553 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 \\
19517 := 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19554 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 \\
19518 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = 1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1 & 19555 := 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 & = 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
19519 := -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & = -1^4 + 2^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19556 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = 1^1 + 3^7 - 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5 \\
19520 := 1^9 + 5^7 - 6^1 - 7^6 + 9^5 & = 1^9 + 5^7 - 6^1 - 7^6 + 9^5 & 19557 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 - 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
19521 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & 19558 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = 2^3 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^2 + 7^4 \\
19522 := -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & = -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & 19559 := 0^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
19523 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^2 & 19560 := 0^1 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^0 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 5^3 + 9^1 \\
19524 := 0^2 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1 & 19561 := 0^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2 \\
19525 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^0 & = 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^1 + 7^4 & 19562 := -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1 & = -1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1
\end{array}$$

19563 := $0^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^0$	$= -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 5^4 - 9^3$	19600 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$
19564 := $1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19601 := $0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$
19565 := $-0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 6^1 + 9^2$	19602 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 - 9^2$
19566 := $-1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19603 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$
19567 := $-0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 6^3 + 9^2$	19604 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$
19568 := $1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19605 := $1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$
19569 := $0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= -2^4 + 3^3 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	19606 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$
19570 := $-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19607 := $-2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$
19571 := $0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 9^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19608 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$
19572 := $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19609 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$
19573 := $-0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^1$	19610 := $2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$
19574 := $2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$= 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	19611 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$
19575 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^1$	19612 := $2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2$
19576 := $1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^2$	19613 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19577 := $2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4$	$= 2^8 + 4^2 + 5^6 + 6^5 - 8^4$	19614 := $0^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^2$
19578 := $0^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 5^4 - 9^3$	$= -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^2$	19615 := $1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$
19579 := $-0^0 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^1 + 9^2$	19616 := $0^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 - 9^2$
19580 := $0^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 5^4 - 9^3$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1$	19617 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 6^1 - 9^2$
19581 := $-1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^2$	19618 := $0^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^1$
19582 := $0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^1$	19619 := $0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$
19583 := $1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 9^2$	19620 := $0^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5$
19584 := $0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 - 7^1$	19621 := $0^1 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$
19585 := $0^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 9^2$	$= -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 8^1 - 9^2$	19622 := $0^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5$
19586 := $-1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^2$	19623 := $-1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19587 := $0^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 9^2$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 6^1 - 9^2$	19624 := $0^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 + 3^7 + 4^1 + 5^4 + 7^5$
19588 := $-1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$	19625 := $0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19589 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$	19626 := $-0^0 - 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 9^2$
19590 := $1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$	19627 := $-1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19591 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$	19628 := $-0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$
19592 := $-0^0 - 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^1$	19629 := $1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19593 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	19630 := $0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 - 9^2$
19594 := $-2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	19631 := $-1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19595 := $0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	19632 := $-1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^1$
19596 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$	19633 := $0^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^0 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$
19597 := $0^7 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 - 9^2$	19634 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$
19598 := $-0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^1$	19635 := $0^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^0 - 9^2$	$= -1^8 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^1$
19599 := $-1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 9^2$	19636 := $0^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$

$19637 := 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5$	$= 2^9 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5$	$19674 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$
$19638 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$19675 := 1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$
$19639 := 0^1 - 1^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$19676 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$
$19640 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$19677 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$
$19641 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^1$	$19678 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^0$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5$
$19642 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$19679 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$
$19643 := 0^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$19680 := 0^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^1$
$19644 := 0^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^2$	$19681 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 9^0$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$
$19645 := 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$19682 := 0^3 + 3^9 - 9^0$	$= 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$
$19646 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$19683 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19647 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 6^2 + 9^1$	$19684 := 0^3 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$= -2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2$
$19648 := -0^0 - 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^2$	$19685 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19649 := -0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$19686 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1$
$19650 := -2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= -2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$19687 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19651 := 0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$19688 := 0^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^0$	$= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^7 + 4^3 + 5^4 + 7^5$
$19652 := 0^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^0$	$= 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 9^1$	$19689 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19653 := 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$19690 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^1$
$19654 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^2$	$19691 := -1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19655 := -0^0 - 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$19692 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^1$
$19656 := 0^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^2 - 9^1$	$19693 := 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19657 := 0^1 - 1^4 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$19694 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2$
$19658 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$	$19695 := -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19659 := -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^1$	$19696 := -0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2$
$19660 := 0^4 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$	$19697 := 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19661 := 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^1$	$19698 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$
$19662 := 0^0 + 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^2$	$19699 := -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19663 := -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^2$	$19700 := -0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^2 + 9^1$
$19664 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 2^9 + 3^3 + 5^7 + 7^2 - 9^5$	$19701 := 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$
$19665 := -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$19702 := 0^0 + 1^2 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^2$
$19666 := -0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^1$	$19703 := 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2$
$19667 := 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$19704 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 5^1 - 9^2$
$19668 := 0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^1$	$19705 := -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^1$
$19669 := -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$19706 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^1$
$19670 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$19707 := 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^1$
$19671 := 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$19708 := 0^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1$
$19672 := -0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$19709 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^2$
$19673 := -1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 - 9^1$	$19710 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1$

$$\begin{array}{llll}
19711 := 0^0 + 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 & = 1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^2 & 19748 := 0^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 \\
19712 := 0^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^0 & = 2^9 + 3^7 + 5^3 + 7^5 + 9^2 & 19749 := 0^1 + 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^0 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 6^1 + 9^2 \\
19713 := -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^1 & = -1^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^1 & 19750 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^0 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 \\
19714 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 - 9^0 & = -1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^1 & 19751 := -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 \\
19715 := -0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 & 19752 := 0^4 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^0 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19716 := 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2 & = 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2 & 19753 := -0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 \\
19717 := 0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 9^2 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 & 19754 := -2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2 \\
19718 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 & = 1^5 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 6^2 + 9^1 & 19755 := -0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19719 := -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 & = -1^6 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^1 & 19756 := -2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19720 := -0^0 - 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = -1^5 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^3 + 5^1 + 9^2 & 19757 := 0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19721 := -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = -1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & 19758 := 0^0 + 1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2 \\
19722 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 - 9^2 & 19759 := 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2 & = 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2 \\
19723 := 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^0 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 & 19760 := -0^0 - 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19724 := 0^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^0 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 & 19761 := -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19725 := 0^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^0 & = 1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 9^1 & 19762 := -0^0 + 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19726 := 0^5 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^1 & 19763 := 0^3 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19727 := -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3 & = -1^9 + 3^7 + 5^1 + 7^5 + 9^3 & 19764 := 0^1 - 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
19728 := 0^5 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^2 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2 & 19765 := 0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19729 := 0^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^0 - 9^2 & = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^1 & 19766 := 0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19730 := 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & = 3^6 + 4^7 + 6^3 + 7^4 & 19767 := 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19731 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^0 + 9^2 & = 1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 8^2 - 9^1 & 19768 := 0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19732 := 0^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^0 & = 1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 - 9^1 & 19769 := 0^7 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 7^3 - 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 9^2 \\
19733 := 0^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^0 + 9^2 & = -1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & 19770 := -0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 9^1 \\
19734 := 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1 & = 1^7 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1 & 19771 := -0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19735 := 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & 19772 := 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19736 := -0^0 - 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = -1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 & 19773 := 0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 \\
19737 := -1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = -1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & 19774 := 0^0 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 9^2 & = -3^5 + 4^8 + 5^4 - 6^6 + 8^3 \\
19738 := -0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 & 19775 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 \\
19739 := 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & 19776 := -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 & = -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19740 := 0^0 + 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^1 & = -2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2 & 19777 := 0^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0 & = 1^4 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 \\
19741 := 0^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^2 + 9^0 & = 1^2 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^1 & 19778 := 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 & = 1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2 \\
19742 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^0 & = 1^5 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^1 - 9^2 & 19779 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^0 + 9^2 & = 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 9^2 \\
19743 := -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 9^2 & = -1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 9^2 & 19780 := 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^2 & = 1^7 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^2 \\
19744 := 0^4 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^0 & = -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^2 - 9^1 & 19781 := 0^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^0 + 9^2 & = 1^8 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 8^1 + 9^2 \\
19745 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^0 & = 1^3 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 9^2 & 19782 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 - 9^0 & = -1^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 - 5^4 + 9^3 \\
19746 := 0^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 9^0 & = -1^5 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^2 + 9^1 & 19783 := -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 & = -1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2 \\
19747 := 0^1 - 1^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^0 & = -1^8 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 8^2 + 9^1 & 19784 := 0^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^0 & = -1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1
\end{array}$$

19785 := $1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 9^2$	19822 := $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$
19786 := $0^5 + 3^9 - 4^0 - 5^4 + 9^3$	= $1^2 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	19823 := $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 + 9^2$
19787 := $2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$	= $2^8 + 3^7 + 5^2 + 7^5 + 8^3$	19824 := $1^5 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1$	= $1^5 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^1$
19788 := $0^5 + 3^9 + 4^0 - 5^4 + 9^3$	= $2^6 + 3^9 - 4^4 + 6^3 + 9^2$	19825 := $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $-1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19789 := $3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3$	= $3^7 + 4^5 + 5^6 + 6^4 - 7^3$	19826 := $-1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^4$	= $-1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^4$
19790 := $-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2$	19827 := $0^4 - 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $1^4 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19791 := $-1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	= $-1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	19828 := $1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^4$	= $1^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^1 + 9^4$
19792 := $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^1 + 9^2$	19829 := $0^4 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $-1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19793 := $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	= $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^2 + 9^1$	19830 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$
19794 := $-1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $-1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	19831 := $1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $1^4 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19795 := $0^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 5^0 + 9^2$	= $2^9 + 4^4 + 5^7 - 7^2 - 9^5$	19832 := $1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$
19796 := $1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	19833 := $-1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 9^2$	= $-1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 9^2$
19797 := $-0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $1^2 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^1$	19834 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^0$	= $1^2 - 2^4 - 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19798 := $-1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $-1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	19835 := $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^1 + 9^2$
19799 := $-0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $-1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^2$	19836 := $0^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	= $-2^8 + 3^9 - 4^4 - 8^2 + 9^3$
19800 := $1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	19837 := $0^1 + 1^2 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	= $-1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^2$
19801 := $0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $-1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2$	19838 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^0$	= $-1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19802 := $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2$	= $1^3 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^1 + 9^2$	19839 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^0$	= $1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 6^1 + 9^2$
19803 := $0^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^0$	= $2^5 + 3^9 - 4^2 - 5^4 + 9^3$	19840 := $0^1 - 1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0$	= $1^2 - 2^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19804 := $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	= $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^1$	19841 := $0^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0$	= $-1^4 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 6^3 - 9^1$
19805 := $0^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0$	= $2^7 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 7^3 + 9^2$	19842 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $1^4 - 2^1 - 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19806 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^0$	= $1^5 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 - 9^1$	19843 := $-0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $-1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19807 := $0^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 - 9^0$	= $-1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 9^1$	19844 := $2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19808 := $0^1 - 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0$	= $1^5 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 - 5^1 + 9^2$	19845 := $0^0 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$
19809 := $0^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0$	= $1^6 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^2 + 9^1$	19846 := $0^0 + 1^1 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $1^1 - 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19810 := $0^1 + 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^0$	= $1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 - 9^1$	19847 := $-2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$	= $-2^2 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$
19811 := $-0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	19848 := $-1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $-1^2 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$
19812 := $-2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $-2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	19849 := $-0^0 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$
19813 := $0^0 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	= $1^1 - 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 9^2$	19850 := $-2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	= $-2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$
19814 := $1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $1^5 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	19851 := $4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$	= $4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$
19815 := $-0^0 - 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $-1^6 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	19852 := $0^0 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$	= $1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 - 9^1$
19816 := $-1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $-1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	19853 := $0^4 + 3^0 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	= $1^8 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 8^1 + 9^2$
19817 := $-2^7 + 3^9 + 7^3 - 9^2$	= $-2^7 + 3^9 + 7^3 - 9^2$	19854 := $-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	= $-1^4 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19818 := $1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	19855 := $-1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	= $-1^3 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$
19819 := $0^0 + 1^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $-1^6 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	19856 := $-0^0 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	= $-1^1 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19820 := $-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	= $-1^5 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^1$	19857 := $-2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	= $-2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19821 := $0^9 + 4^7 - 5^5 + 7^0 + 9^4$	= $-1^3 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 6^1 + 9^2$	19858 := $-2^8 + 3^9 + 8^3 - 9^2$	= $-2^8 + 3^9 + 8^3 - 9^2$

19859 := $0^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	19896 := $0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^2$
19860 := $0^1 + 1^3 + 2^0 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^2 + 3^1 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	19897 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^2$
19861 := $0^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	19898 := $0^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^0$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^2$
19862 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= -1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	19899 := $0^1 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^3 + 6^1 + 9^2$
19863 := $-2^5 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -2^5 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^2$	19900 := $0^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^1 + 9^2$
19864 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^1 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	19901 := $0^1 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^2 - 9^1$
19865 := $-0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	19902 := $0^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19866 := $2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	19903 := $-1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$
19867 := $0^0 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^2$	19904 := $0^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^0$	$= -1^4 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 4^2 + 7^3 - 9^1$
19868 := $-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	19905 := $1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$
19869 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 6^3 + 9^2$	19906 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 9^1$
19870 := $1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	19907 := $-1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$
19871 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^2 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^2$	19908 := $-0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^3 + 9^1$
19872 := $-2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4$	$= -2^8 - 3^2 + 4^7 - 7^3 + 8^4$	19909 := $1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$
19873 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^6 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^1 - 9^2$	19910 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^4 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19874 := $0^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 - 9^0$	$= 1^3 - 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^1$	19911 := $-1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$
19875 := $0^1 - 1^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^6 - 2^4 + 3^9 - 4^2 + 6^3 + 9^1$	19912 := $-0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 - 9^1$
19876 := $0^3 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 8^2 + 9^0$	$= -1^1 + 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	19913 := $1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$
19877 := $2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	$= 2^4 + 3^2 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$	19914 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^1$	$= -1^5 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^2 + 9^1$
19878 := $3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$	$= 3^3 + 4^8 - 5^5 - 6^6 + 8^4$	19915 := $-0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$
19879 := $0^5 + 2^8 + 3^9 - 5^3 + 8^2 + 9^0$	$= 1^4 + 2^6 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 6^3 - 9^2$	19916 := $-2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$	$= -2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$
19880 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^7 - 2^8 + 3^9 - 7^2 + 8^3 - 9^1$	19917 := $0^0 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$
19881 := $-0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	19918 := $0^0 + 1^1 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 - 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19882 := $2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	$= 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	19919 := $-0^0 - 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -1^3 - 2^6 + 3^9 + 4^4 + 6^2 + 9^1$
19883 := $0^0 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^2$	19920 := $-0^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19884 := $-1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 9^2$	$= -1^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 - 7^1 + 9^2$	19921 := $2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19885 := $-1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19922 := $0^0 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= 1^1 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19886 := $-1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	$= -1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	19923 := $1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$
19887 := $1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19924 := $0^0 + 1^2 - 2^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19888 := $-0^0 - 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	19925 := $-1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$
19889 := $-1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= -1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19926 := $-0^0 + 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^4 + 2^5 + 3^9 + 4^1 + 5^3 + 9^2$
19890 := $-0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= -1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	19927 := $1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$
19891 := $1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19928 := $-0^0 - 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19892 := $0^0 + 1^6 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^5 + 2^1 + 3^9 + 5^3 + 9^2$	19929 := $-1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$
19893 := $0^3 + 2^7 + 3^9 + 7^0 + 9^2$	$= -1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19930 := $-0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^1 - 2^2 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$
19894 := $0^6 - 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^0$	$= 1^5 - 2^1 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 5^3 + 9^2$	19931 := $1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$
19895 := $1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	$= 1^6 + 2^2 + 3^9 + 6^3 - 9^1$	19932 := $0^0 + 1^3 + 3^9 + 4^4 - 9^1$	$= -1^1 + 3^4 + 4^7 + 5^5 + 7^3$

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References

• First-Type 1.1

- [1] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Sequential Representation: Numbers from 0 to 11111 in terms of Increasing and Decreasing Orders of 1 to 9, Jan. 2014, pp.1-161, <http://arxiv.org/abs/1302.1479>; <http://bit.ly/2wnZq6g>.
- [2] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 20000, **Zenodo**, , January 18, 2019, pp. 1-224, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2543626>; <http://bit.ly/2FAhWOP>;
- [3] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 20001 to 25000, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 131, pp. 1-121, <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a131.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2qRfpGW>.
- [4] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers From 25001 to 30000, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 132, pp. 1-123, <https://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a132.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2PYrxE6>.
- [5] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Representations of Natural Numbers – The 10958 Problem, Online Link - <http://bit.ly/2AYFpoc>.

• Second-Type 1.2

- [6] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy Power Representations of Natural Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 19(2016), Art. 31, pp.1-71, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v19/v19a31.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2PFAW64>.
- [7] I.J. TANEJA, All Digits Flexible Power Representations of Natural Numbers From 11112 to 30000,**Zenodo**, January 14, 2019, pp. 1-140, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2539203>; <http://bit.ly/2VKtCn4>
- [8] I.J. TANEJA, All Digits Flexible Power Representations of Natural Numbers From 30001 to 50000, **Zenodo** , January 14, 2019, pp. 1-147, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2539412>; <http://bit.ly/2HeA7vg>.

• Third-Type 1.3

- [9] I.J. TANEJA, Single Digit Representations of Natural Numbers, Feb. 1015, pp.1-55, <http://arxiv.org/abs/1502.03501> - Also in RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Art. 15, pp.1-55, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a15.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2wnbUey>.

- [10] I.J. TANEJA, Single Digit Representations of Numbers From 1 to 5000, **Zenodo**, Open Access, <http://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.2538893>, January 14, 2019, pp. 1-345; <http://bit.ly/2TPjWpK>.
- [11] I.J. TANEJA, Single Digit Representations of Natural Numbers From 5001 to 10000, **Zenodo**, January 14, 2019, pp. 1-345, <http://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.2538897>; <http://bit.ly/2RQpXoA>.
- [12] I.J. TANEJA, Single Digit Representations of Numbers From 10001 to 15000, **Zenodo**, Open Access. January, 16, 2019, pp. 1-510, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2550414>; <http://bit.ly/2Thvgee>.

• Forth-Type 1.4

- [13] I.J. TANEJA, Single Letter Representations of Natural Numbers, Palindromic Symmetries and Number Patterns, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Art. 40, pp.1-30, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a40.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2Nvlen2>.
- [14] I.J. TANEJA, Single Letter Representations of Natural Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Art. 73, pp. 1-44, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a73.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2ojVQpb>.
- [15] I.J. TANEJA, Single Letter Fraction-Type Representations of Natural Numbers - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 149, pp. 1-136, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a149.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2BYO0Lq>.
- [16] I.J. TANEJA, Single Letter Representations of Natural Numbers From 1 to 11111, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 21(2018), Art. 123, pp.1-124, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a123.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2QB5HXt>.
- [17] I.J. TANEJA, Fraction-Type Single Letter Representations of Natural Numbers From 1 to 11111, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 21(2018), Art. 124, pp.1-193, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a124.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2zJNoFM>.

• Running Expressions 1.5

- [18] I.J. TANEJA, Running Expressions in Increasing and Decreasing Orders of Natural Numbers Separated by Equality Signs, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 18(2015), Article 27, pp.1-54. <http://rgmia.org/papers/v18/v18a27.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2okiLAH>.
- [19] I.J. TANEJA, Running Expressions with Equalities: Increasing and Decreasing Orders - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 33, pp. 1-57, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a33.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2BZFETR>.
- [20] I.J. TANEJA, Running Expressions with Equalities: Increasing and Decreasing Orders - II, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 34, pp. 1-87, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a34.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2wr7q5u>.
- [21] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci Sequence and Running Expressions with Equalities - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 20(2017), Art. 35, pp. 1-83, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a35.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2LDuSlN>.

- [22] I.J. TANEJA, Running Expressions with Triangular Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, Open Access, Dec 21, 2018, pp.1-142, <https://doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.2483327>; <http://bit.ly/2AfpCli>.

- **Work's Summary**

- [23] I.J. TANEJA, Crazy, Selfie, Fibonacci, Triangular, Amicable Types Representations of Numbers, RGMIA Research Report Collection, 21(2018), Art. 3, pp. 1-140, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v21/v21a03.pdf>; <http://bit.ly/2OKNh2S>.
-